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A new formula for evaluating the effectiveness of insecticides against cotton bollworm under Egyptian conditions, instead of the Henderson and Tilton (1955) formula

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Abstract:

Bollworms , pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saud.) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) and spiny bollworm *Earis insulana* (Bois) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae), are the main cotton insect pests in Egypt. Too many insecticides from different insecticide groups are applied against it. The protocol of estimating insecticide efficacy against it and many other insect pests depends on the formula of Henderson and Tilton (1955), which needs to have a control area (Untreated area) equals to the area of one insecticide treatment , which is four cotton feddans (Acres), to calculate the reduction percentages in bollworms infestation percent after applying each insecticide treatment. Because of this condition is impossible and is not applicable (Because the financial costs of the losses of these untreated areas are about 40 thousand Egyptian bounds), it's recommended to apply the present formula, which derived from experimental data and it does not depend on the presence of untreated area, but it depends on the initial bollworms infestation percentages before applying for the insecticide treated program, to calculate the reduction percentages in bollworms infestation percent. The application of this formula solves a lot of insecticide application problems in the estimating insecticide efficacy protocol and gives acceptable and logical data which could be beneficial when its results are applied in the cotton fields.

Introduction.

Over 1990s, the global pesticide sale remained relatively constant, between 270 to 300 billion dollars, of which 44% were herbicides, 29% were insecticides, 21% were fungicides/bactericides, and 6% the others. Over the period 2007 to 2008, herbicides ranked the first in three major categories of pesticides: insecticides, fungicides/bactericides, herbicides (Zhang *et al.*, 2011). World pesticide expenditures totaled more than \$35.8 billion in 2006 and more than \$39.4 billion in 2007.

Expenditures on herbicides accounted for the largest portion of total expenditures (Approximately 40%), followed by expenditures on insecticides, fungicides, and other pesticides, respectively. Total expenditures increased in 2007 due to increased spending on all pesticide types (Grube *et al.*, 2011). Global demand for pesticides will rise 2.9 percent annually to 2014, this study analyzes the \$45 billion world pesticide industry (Anonymous, 2010). Bakr (2013) mentioned that, efficacy of pesticides percentages can be calculated

and corrected according to Abbott (1925), Henderson and Tilton (1955), Schneider-Orelli or Sun-Shepard Püntener (1981) formulas. These formulas calculate corrected efficacy % in pesticide trials. The selection of appropriate formula is depending on two factors: 1. Trial condition (Infestation or population stability and homogeneity). 2. The handled data (Live individuals or mortality %).

Although Abbott's (1925) formula was a convenient descriptive statistic for calculating the percentage control obtained between the Core Treatment versus Control areas, modified or additional analytical procedures also were used by research teams at individual sites. Henderson and Tilton's (1955) formula provides a similar metric for measuring percentage control, but by quantifying changes in tick density between baseline and subsequent sampling times. It can be used to determine treatment effects

between any two sampling periods (Pound *et al.*, 2009).

In this study the present formula is compared to Henderson and Tilton's (1955) formula for calculating and correcting insecticides efficacy percentages against bollworms in commercial cotton fields in Egypt.

Materials and methods

This study was carried out at, Kom Isho village, Kafer Aldawar district, Bahira Governorate, , Egypt, whereas 18 commercial cotton fields were chosen 17 areas for 17 different insecticide treatments, and one as an untreated (Control) area, each area contained 4 cotton acres. Three insecticide applications (Each every 15 days) were conducted with the same insecticide, in three successive applications (29/8, 11/9, and 25/9/2012, respectively). The insecticides used, formulation, concentrations, and rates of applications are shown in Table (1).

Table (1): Applied insecticides against bollworms, formulations, concentrations, and application rates.

Application #	Insecticide (Trade name)	Insecticide (Common name)	Con. % and formulation	Application rate / Acre
I- Organophosphorus				
1	Helpan	Chlorpyrifos	48% - Ec	1 L
2	Dorsell	Chlorpyrifos	48% - Ec	1 L
3	Chlorzid	Chlorpyrifos	48% - Ec	1 L
4	Pesteban	Chlorpyrifos	48% - Ec	1 L
5	Pyrofos	Chlorpyrifos	48% - Ec	1 L
6	Chlofet	Chlorpyrifos	48% - Ec	1 L
7	Silian	Profenofos	72% - Ec	750 ml
8	Teliton	Profenofos	72% - Ec	750 ml
II- Pyrethroids				
9	Lampada Star	Lambdacyhalothrin	5% - Ec	375 ml
10	Kafrothrin	Deltamethrin	2.5% - Ec	750 ml
11	Lamdathrin	Lambdacyhalothrin	5% - Ec	375 ml
12	Decies	Deltamethrin	2.5% - Ec	350 ml
13	Agristar	Lambdacyhalothrin	5% - Ec	375 ml
14	Pylarmada	Lambdacyhalothrin	5% - Ec	750 ml
15	Demand	Deltamethrin	2.5% - Ec	400 ml
16	Alfazed	Alpha cypermthrin	10% - Ec	250 ml
III - Carbamates.				
17	Newmell	Methomyl	90 % - SP	300 gm

Seventy two (72) green cotton boll samples (14 -21 day old, four randomized samples from each treatment, each contained 100 green boll) were weekly collected from the 18 cotton fields in six successive investigations , beginning from 29/8/2012 , and up to 3/10/2012, transferred to the laboratory, whereas Henderson and Tilton’s (1955) formula:

subjected to investigations, calculating and recording boll infestation percentages.

Two formulas were used to calculate the reduction in boll infestation percentages caused by different insecticide application, these formulas are:

$$\text{Reduction \%} = \left(1 - \frac{(\text{B.I. \% in Co. before treatment}) \times (\text{B.I. \% in T after treatment})}{(\text{B.I. \% in Co. after treatment}) \times (\text{B.I. \% in T before treatment})} \right) \times 100$$

Where : B.I. % = boll infestation % , T = treated , Co. = control

The present formula :

$$\text{Reduction \%} = \left(\frac{(\text{B.I. \% in T. before treatment}) - (\text{B.I. \% in T. after treatment})}{(\text{B.I. \% in T. after treatment})} \right) \times 100$$

Where : B.I. % = boll infestation % , T. = treated .

Results and discussion

Data showed in Table (2) summarized the weekly averages of boll infestation percentages pre and post the above mentioned insecticide

treatments. These data include the bollworm infestation percentages recorded from the untreated area (Control).

Table (2) : Averages of weekly bollworms infestation % .

Treatment #	Averages of weekly bollworms infestation %					
	Pre Treatment	Post Treatment				
	1	2	3	4	5	6
1	16	7	7	3	5.5	6.25
2	12	5.5	6.5	1.75	6.75	11.75
3	15	3.5	3.5	1.5	6.25	4.25
4	14.5	5	5.5	2.25	4.75	3.25
5	32	11.5	11.5	1.75	3.5	4.5
6	30.5	4.5	4.5	2.5	5.5	6.75
7	26.5	4.5	4.5	0.75	4.75	8
8	26	4	4	0.75	10.25	2.25
9	17.5	5.5	5.5	0.75	2.75	3.25
10	17.5	3	3	2.25	4	0.75
11	25	5.5	5.5	1.5	1.25	1.75
12	22	7	7	1	1.5	1.5
13	12	4.5	4.5	2	2	3
14	12.5	2	2	2.5	1.75	2.25
15	9	15.5	17	1	1.75	0.75
16	14	6	5	1.25	1.5	1
17	8.5	4.5	5	0.75	1.5	1.5
18	16	4	4	0.25	0.75	0.25

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Data in Table (3) showed the negative bollworms reduction percentages obtained after applying Henderson and Tilton's (1955) formula in calculating the reduction percentages

of bollworms infestation percentages (Table 2) after the application of the above mentioned insecticide applications .

Table (3) : Reduction percentages in boll infestation % according to Henderson and Tilton's (1955) formula .

Treatment #	Weekly bollworm investigations					Average boll infestation Red. %
	1	2	3	4	5	
1	-174.0	-99.0	-684.7	-60.1	-339.9	-271.5
2	-182.3	-117.2	-429.8	-127.6	-521.2	-275.6
3	-92.3	-99.0	-684.7	-137.9	-203.0	-243.4
4	-136.9	-109.0	-653.5	-69.4	-204.3	-234.6
5	-142.8	-99.0	-242.5	-65.7	-384.7	-186.9
6	-58.0	-99.0	-887.9	-72.3	-367.2	-296.9
7	-66.9	-99.0	-265.7	-210.1	-504.3	-229.2
8	-60.5	-99.0	-299.0	-454.6	-64.9	-195.6
9	-124.7	-99.0	-217.2	-121.2	-353.5	-183.1
10	-67.6	-99.0	-1,199.0	-58.3	-55.3	-295.8
11	-87.0	-99.0	-435.4	-26.8	-419.0	-213.4
12	-126.3	-99.0	-227.6	-49.0	-299.0	-160.2
13	-149.0	-99.0	-710.1	-32.3	-449.0	-287.9
14	-63.0	-99.0	-1,999.0	-22.3	-384.7	-513.6
15	-687.9	-108.7	-93.1	-57.3	-127.6	-214.9
16	-170.4	-82.3	-399.0	-39.0	-199.0	-178.0
17	-210.8	-110.1	-239.0	-65.7	-299.0	-184.9

Data in Table (4) showed the positive bollworms reduction percentages obtained after applying the present formula in calculating the reduction percentages of bollworms infestation percentages (Table 2) after the application of the above mentioned insecticide applications .

crop and against any pest rather than using Henderson and Tilton's (1955) formula, which uses in calculating the reduction in insect population (Not infestation %) .

This paper does not discuss the efficacy of different insecticides applied against bollworms, but it discusses the viability of using the formula here instead of Henderson and Tilton's (1955) formula in these different cases :

2. In a case of the absence of untreated area (Control).

3. In a case of a farmer applied insecticide to the untreated area for a commercial reasons (To gain more benefits) , so fare the infestation in the untreated (Control) is equal or smaller than in the treated areas, because this'll cause a negative reduction % not positive ones .

1. In calculating the reduction in infestation % after any treatment (Herbicide, insecticide, bactericide fungicide or any other pesticide), in any

4. In a case of getting illogical data from the untreated area or data loss for any reason or another.

Table (4) : Reduction percentages in boll infestation % according to the present formula .

Treatment #	weekly reduction in bollworm infestation %					Average boll infestation Red. %
	1	2	3	4	5	
1	56.3	56.3	81.3	65.6	60.9	64.1
2	54.2	45.8	85.4	43.8	2.1	46.3
3	76.7	76.7	90.0	58.3	71.7	74.7
4	65.5	62.1	84.5	67.2	77.6	71.4
5	64.1	64.1	94.5	89.1	85.9	79.5
6	85.2	85.2	91.8	82.0	77.9	84.4
7	83.0	83.0	97.2	82.1	69.8	83.0
8	84.6	84.6	97.1	60.6	91.3	83.7
9	68.6	68.6	95.7	84.3	81.4	79.7
10	82.9	82.9	87.1	77.1	95.7	85.1
11	78.0	78.0	94.0	95.0	93.0	87.6
12	68.2	68.2	95.5	93.2	93.2	83.6
13	62.5	62.5	83.3	83.3	75.0	73.3
14	84.0	84.0	80.0	86.0	82.0	83.2
15	-72.2	-88.9	88.9	80.6	91.7	20.0
16	57.1	64.3	91.1	89.3	92.9	78.9
17	47.1	41.2	91.2	82.4	82.4	68.8

The present formula is very simple, easy to be calculated and applicable that any farmer who cultivated any crop and has applied any control action (Biologically, physically, or chemically " as a part of integrated pest management (IPM)) can apply it to know the efficacy of this control action in his own farm however it's a small or large one . By this way farmers can manage their control action easily and scientists and experts can get more reliable data successfully. The

References

Abbott, W.S. (1925): A method of computing the effectiveness of an insecticide. J. Econ. Entomol.; 18 : 265-267.

Anonymous (2010) : World Pesticides to 2014 - Market Research, Market Share, Market Size, Sales, Demand Forecast,

most valuable advantage of the formula here is that: it does not have any financial costs , while the application of all other formulas causes financial losses and costs for a very simple reason, The present formula does not need any untreated areas (Control), and does not need any control samples, it depends on the data of the pre treatment to compare with that of the post treatment to calculate the reduction percentage for any control action under any conditions .

Market Leaders, Company Profiles, Industry Trends. <http://www.freedoniagroup.com/World-Pesticides.html>.

Bakr, E. (2013) : Ldp line software . <http://www.ehabsoft.com/ldpline/onlinecontrol.htm#SunShepard>

- Grube, A.; Donaldson, D. ; Kiely, T. and La, Wu (2011):**Pesticides Industry, Sales and Usage 2006 and 2007 Market Estimates. EPA, Biological and Economic Analysis Division, Office of Pesticide Programs, Office of Chemical Safety and Pollution Prevention, U.S. Environmental Protection Agency ,Washington, DC 20460.pp33. http://www.epa.gov/opp00001/pestsales/07pestsales/market_estimates2007.pdf
- Henderson, C.F. and Tilton, E. W. (1955):** Tests with acaricides against the brow wheat mite, J. Econ. Entomol., 48:157-161.
- Pound, J. M.; Miller, J. A.; George, J.E.; Fish, D. ; Carroll, J. F.; Schulze, T. L. ; Daniels, T. J. Falco, R. C.; Stafford, K. C. and Mather, T. N. (2009):** The United States Department of Agriculture's Northeast. Area-Wide Tick Control Project: Summary and Conclusions. Vector-borne and Zoonotic Diseases, 9(4): 439- 448 . <http://naldc.nal.usda.gov/download/35190/pdf>
- Půntener, W. (1981):** Manual for field trials in plant protection second edition. Agricultural Division, Ciba-Ciegy Limited.
- Zhang, W.; FuBin, J. and Jian Feng, O. (2011) :** Global pesticide consumption and pollution: with China as a focus. Proceedings of the International Academy of Ecology and Environmental Sciences, 1(2):125-144. [http://www.iaees.org/publications/journals/piaees/articles/2011-1\(2\)/Global-pesticide-consumption-pollution.pdf](http://www.iaees.org/publications/journals/piaees/articles/2011-1(2)/Global-pesticide-consumption-pollution.pdf).

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**Influence of two new insecticides on toxicity, physiological and biological aspects of
Spodoptera littoralis (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae)**

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Abstract:

The Egyptian cotton leafworm *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisduval) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae), is a one of the major insects of cotton and other crops within its African tropical and subtropical countries. It has developed resistance to many conventional and nonconventional insecticides. The present investigation aimed to throw light on the efficiency of two novel insecticides, chlorfenapyr and metaflumizone on to lethal, biochemical parameters, and physiological aspects effects of chlorfenapyr and metaflumizone were determined by a leaf dipping technique bioassays to different two larval instars (2nd and 4th) *S. littoralis*. The 2nd instar larvae were more susceptible than the older 4th instars. Based on the LC₅₀ values Chlorvenapyr is the most toxic to *S. littoralis* than the metaflumizone. The toxicity of chlorfenapyr was 1.55 fold with 2nd than 4th instar also, the toxicity of metaflumizone was 4.91 fold with 2nd than 4th instar. Biochemical studies indicated that treatment of 4th instar larvae with LC₅₀ of testing insecticides. Both of them reduced total carbohydrate contents. The total lipids decrease with metaflumizone but there was no significance with chlorfenapyr, the free amino acid was significantly lower with chlorfenapyr and metaflumizone. Both of them had no significant effect on Glutathione S-transferase (GST) activity in the larval homogenate. The histological examination of the mid gut of 4th instar larvae of *S. littoralis* showed that all tested insecticides, lead to several damages occurred in all the cell layers in the midgut. Shrinkage of the epithelial layer cells was observed after the treatment with chlorfenapyr and the cytoplasm was vacuolated, and some of them lost their nuclei or appeared pyknotic. Changes were most noticeable in the columnar, regenerative, and caliciform cells. Larval treated by metaflumizone had a circular muscle layer and a longitudinal muscle layer seems to become thicker than normal and basement membrane partially separated, and lysis in the epithelial cells.

Introduction

Insects are one of the major menaces to agriculture, causing between 20 to 40 percent of global crop

production loss annually. Each year, invasive insects cost the global economy around US\$70 billion (FAO, 2019). The challenges of insect attacks

on crops have been noticed to be increased with climate change and global warming (IPPC, 2021). The Egyptian cotton leafworm *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisduval) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) is one of the most devastating agricultural lepidopteran insects within its subtropical and tropical countries. *S. littoralis* cover more than 40 plant families, including about 90 host plant species of economic importance (Ghoneim, 2020). These caterpillars are very polyphagous, infesting decorative, industrial, and vegetable yields, resulting in hazardous economic losses (El-Sayed *et al.* , 2020).

The extensive use of conventional pesticides requires the application of several insecticides to control this pest; depending on extending and preserving the insecticide efficacy which is based on rotating numerous insecticides has resulted in several issues, including environmental pollution, the extinction of natural enemies, beneficial insect populations, and insect resistant to the certain insecticides (Mosallanejad and Smagghe, 2009). The control of this pest is focused on searching for new strategies with biological and ecological characteristics. One of these strategies, the use of new insecticides such as chlorfenapyr and metaflumizone insecticide. chlorfenapyr, which is one of the pyrrole insecticides classes, the biological action based on its transformation to another chemical. Oxidative removal of the N-methoxymethyl group of chlorfenapyr by mixed-function oxidases forming a toxic compound identified as CL 303268, which uncouples oxidative phosphorylation in the mitochondria, which cause disruption of the production of ATP and loss of energy, causing cell dysfunction cellular death, and ultimately organism mortality

(EPA, 2001). This compound has low mammalian toxicity, also it is categorized according to WHO as a slightly hazardous insecticide because of it has a new mode of action (Tomlin, 2000). Metaflumizone classified in the new class of semicarbazone insecticides. Which is procured from pyrazoline (Takagi *et al.*, 2007). Acts as a sodium channel blocker by binding selectively to the slow-deactivated status of the sodium channel, it produces a relaxed (Khakame *et al.*, 2013 and Hatem *et al.*, 2017).

Many studies were managed to define the basic metaflumizone toxicity and there are cross-resistance between indoxacarb and metaflumizone, both of them sodium channel blocker (Shen *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, this study makes a major contribution to research on the effects of chlorfenapyr and metaflumizone on *S. littoralis* larvae. (a) Lethal effects of both insecticides, (b) The lethal effects of chlorfenapyr and metaflumizone as a biological control agent on some biochemical parameters such as carbohydrates, total lipids, free amino acids, and GST enzyme activity in 4th larval instars of *S. littoralis*, and (c) Histological changes of the treated midgut of 4th larvae were also determinate.

Materials and methods

1. Insects:

A laboratory colony of *S. littoralis* continuously was reared reared in the laboratory in the plant protection Research Institute. Newly hatched larvae were transferred to clean glass jars covered with muslin held in position with rubber bands. They were fed on fresh castor bean leaves, (*Ricinus communis* L.). Moths were fed on a 10% sugar solution soaked a piece of cotton tissue, *Nerium Oleander* L. as an oviposition site. The insects were maintained at $25 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $65 \pm 5\%$ RH. and a photoperiod of 16:8 hrs. (L: D). Rearing of insects was conducted

following the technique described by EL-Defrawi *et al.* (1964). As larva reached the 2nd and 4th instars, they were used in the experiments described below.

2. Leaf dip bioassay:

To assess the activity of different concentrations of chlorfenapyr and metaflumizone was prepared in water. The larvae used in the experiments were freshly 2nd and 4th instar larvae by using the leaf dipping bioassay technique. Fresh castor bean leaves were immersed for 1 minute in each concentration. Then let to dry at laboratory temperature. Each concentration was replicated three times and each replicate contained 30 larvae. Castor bean leaves treated with distilled water were fed to control larvae. Mortality was recorded after five days of treatment. mortality percentage was corrected using (Abbott's formula, 1925). The adjusted mortality percentage of each compound was calculated statistically using (Finney, 1971) from which the corresponding concentration probit lines (Ld-P lines) 50% and 95% mortality, slope values of tested compounds were also determined.

3. Biochemical studies:

3.1. Preparation of insects for analysis:

Preparation of sample biochemical analysis, the 4th instar larvae of *s. littoralis* after five days of all LC₅₀ treatments and control by (Amin, 1998). The starved larvae were placed in clean glass jars. The starved larvae were homogenized in distilled water (50 mg/1ml) at 8000 r.p.m. supernatants, When kept at 5°C until analysis, enzyme extracts can be stored for at least one week without losing significant activity.

3.2. Free amino acids:

Total amino acids were measured using the ninhydrin reagent in a colorimetric manner, as reported by

Lee and Takahashi (1966). A 1 ml sample is added to a 1.9 ml ninhydrin-citrate buffer-glycerol combination, which includes 0.5 ml of 1 percent ninhydrin solution in 0.5 M citrate buffer (pH 5.5); 0.2 ml of 0.5 M citrate buffer (pH 5.5); and 1.2 ml glycerol. The mixture was cooked for 10 minutes in a boiling water bath before cooling in a tap water bath. At 570 nm, the developed colour was measured. The amino acids were measured in µg alanine each body weight.

3.3. Total carbohydrates:

The phenol-sulphuric acid reaction was used to determine total carbohydrates in the acid extract of the sample (Dubois *et al.*, 1956 and Crompton and Birt, 1967). Homogenization of the sample (1 gm) in 0.3N HClO₄ (5 ml) at 0 °C for 1 minute, for another 10 minutes, the homogenate was maintained on ice. Insoluble debris was removed by centrifugation at 2000 rpm for 3 minutes, then redispersion and centrifugation twice in ice-cold HClO₄ (5ml). The acid extract was made up of the three supernatant. In a colorimetric tube, 100 microliters of acid extract were added to 0.5 ml of phenol (20 percent w/v). Then, with shaking, 5 mL of strong sulfuric acid was added. The total carbohydrate content is calculated as g glucose per g of fresh weight.

3.4. Total lipids:

Total lipids were determined using the phosphovanillin reagent (Knight *et al.*, 1972), which was created by dissolving 0.6 gm pure vanillin in 10 ml ethanol and diluting to 100 ml with distilled water. After that, 400 mL of concentrated phosphoric acid was added. 250 l of the sample was mixed with 5 ml of concentrated sulphuric acid in a test tube and heated in a boiling water bath for 10 minutes. The digest was added to the phosphovanillin reagent after cooling to room temperature (6 ml). The produced

colour was measured at 525 nm against the reagent blank after 45 minutes. The optical density of the samples was compared to a reference standard, and the findings were reported in mg lipids/ml hemolymph.

3.5. Glutathione S-transferase (GST) activity :

Glutathione S-transferase (GST) catalyses the conjugation of reduced glutathione (GSH) with 1-chloro 2,4-dinitrobenzene (CDNB) via the -SH group of glutathione. The conjugate, S-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)-L-glutathione, was identified using the technique described by Habig *et al.* (1974). 1 ml potassium salt of phosphate buffer (pH 6.5), 100 μ l GSH, and 200 μ l larval homogenate made up the reaction mixture. The reaction began with the addition of 25 μ l of CDNB solution as the substrate. Both GSH and CDNB concentrations were changed to 5m M and 1m M, respectively. For 5 minutes, using a molar extinction coefficient of 9.6/mM/cm, the increase in absorbance at 340 nm was measured against a blank containing everything but the enzyme to estimate the nanomole substrate conjugated/min/larva.

4. Histopathological studies:

The effect of LC_{50s} of chlorfenapyr and metaflumizone on the histological structure of the mid-gut of the 4th instar *S. littoralis* larvae was determined. After 5 days of treatment, 10 larvae of each treated and control group were dissected under a binocular microscope. The separated mid-gut was transferred into alcoholic Bouin's solution was used as a fixative, for dehydration and removal of the yellow color of Bouin's solution the larvae were rinsed in a series of ethanol solutions. They were transferred first into 50% ethyl alcohol for 2 hrs at 40 °C (Two changes) then left for 24 hrs. Then the larvae passed through a series of alcoholic treatments each for 2 hrs at

room temperature starting with 80% , followed by 90%, 96%, and ending with 100%. After dehydration, the larvae were placed in a solution of amy1 acetate and colloidal to clear the tissues. Treated with soft wax stated by placing them in vials containing equal portions of fresh amy1 acetate solution and soft paraffin wax and leaving them for 24 hrs. at 50 °C. Serial longitudinal sections at 6 microns were made by microtome and mounted on clean slides using Mayer's albumin. Sections were mounted on glass slides and stained with haematoxyline and counterstained in alcoholic Eosin and prepared for observation and photomicroscope (Humason and Freeman, 1979).

5. Statistical analysis:

The findings of biochemical measurements were aggregated from triplicate determinations in all studies with three replicates (Insect homogenates). Using Costat (2007) statistical software, the findings were evaluated using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) (Cohort software, Berkeley). The Tukey's HSD test was used to compare means when the ANOVA data were significant < (P 0.05).

Results and discussion

1. Leaf dip bioassay:

The bioassay to the toxicity of chlorfenapyr and metaflumizone on 2nd and 4th instars *S. littoralis* larvae demonstrated that 2nd instar larvae were more susceptible than the 4th instar. As evidenced by Table (1) LC₅₀ and LC₉₅ values were 35.90 and 148.14 ppm for 2nd instar larvae and 55.62 and 621.01 ppm for 4th instar larvae, respectively. The slope values were 4.21±0.38 and 4.92±0.53 and 2.77±0.36 and 3.31±0.32 in treating 2nd instar larvae, there was higher homogeneity than in treating 4th instar larvae for the corresponding instar larvae. Based on the LC₅₀ values chlorvenapyr is the most toxic to *S. littoralis* than the

metaflumizone. The toxicity of chlorfenapyr was 1.55 fold with 2nd than 4th instar also, the toxicity of metaflumizone was 4.91 fold with 2nd than 4th instar. This result

correspondingly, chlorpyrifos and spinosad insecticides were acting as the same effect on *Prodenia litura* (F.) (Lepidoptera : Noctuidae) treated larvae (Singh and Sohi, 2008).

Table (1): Relative toxicity of chlorfenapyr and metaflumizone against *Spodoptera littoralis* 2nd and 4th instar larvae on the basis of LC₅₀ values.

Insecticides	larval instars	LC ₅₀ (%) ^a (ppm)	95% Confidence limits (%)		Slope ^b b ± S. E	X ^c	Relative Potency ^d
			Lower	Upper			
Chlorfenapyr	2 nd	35.90	33.19	38.75	4.21±0.38	4.39	1.55
	4 th	55.62	49.76	65.02	2.77±0.36	6.44	1
Metaflumizone	2 nd	148.14	138.19	156.96	4.92±0.53	5.86	4.91
	4 th	621.01	566.75	692.21	3.31±0.32	4.79	1

2. Biochemical studies:

The results of biochemical analysis of *S. littoralis* 4th instar larvae treated with LC₅₀ of chlorfenapyr and metaflumizone compared were shown in (Table 2). There was a significant difference between chlorfenapyr and metaflumizone and control in total carbohydrate contents, both of them reduced total carbohydrate contents. Also, the total lipids decrease with metaflumizone it was (4.05±0.15 mg/g.b.wt) but there was no significant difference between chlorfenapyr and untreated (5.9±0.13 and 5.7±0.26 mg/g.b.wt, respectively). In addition, the free amino acid was significantly lower in a chlorfenapyr and metaflumizone treated larvae compared with control (1.71±0.052, 1.92±0.025, and 2.22±0.102 mg alanine/g. b. wt., respectively).

Chlorfenapyr decreased the carbohydrate and free amino acid contents significantly compared with the control. All macronutrients include carbohydrates, proteins, and lipids that supply energy for insects to maintain their vital processes, these macronutrients can be affected by exhibits factors such as insecticides. These study findings suggest that chlorfenapyr can influence carbohydrate reduction, which can be explained by the high quantity of energy required for all body processes.

This defect could be caused by chlorfenapyr's action, which is an uncoupler of oxidative phosphorylation in the mitochondria. As a result, ATP generation is disrupted, and energy is lost (Zhao *et al.*, 2018). Trehalose is an insect's major blood sugar that can successfully prevent protein denaturation and function loss in stress conditions (Jain and Roy, 2009).

Data obtained in the present work disclosed a significant reduction in the carbohydrate, Total lipids, and free amino acid contents of *S. littoralis* 4th instar larvae treated with LC₅₀ of metaflumizone. This finding was also reported by Hatem *et al.* (2017), metaflumizone caused a reduction in total carbohydrates and total protein in treating *S. littoralis* larvae. Antifeedant impact of the investigated substances was demonstrated by a considerable decrease in free amino acids and carbohydrate, indicating that the treated larvae with tested compounds which were unable to digest the diet and the reduction in lipids may be due to the larvae use it as an energy in case of starvation due to temporary stop feeding as a result of treatment (Abd-El-Aziz *et al.*, 2020; Abd-El-Aziz and Salama, 2020). No significant differences in the activities of GST in larvae exposed to LC₅₀ of both insecticides compared with control. Metaflumizone, like indoxacarb, is a

voltage-dependent sodium channel blocker that preferentially targets voltage-gated sodium channels in the slow inactivated state by binding to or near the local aesthetic receptor within the sodium channel pore (Tian *et al.*, 2014).

Our results were in agreement with Zhao *et al.* (2018), after exposing *Bradysia odoriphaga* Yang et Zhang (Diptera: Sciaridae) larvae with chlorfenapyr for 24 hrs., the activities of GST were assessed. The LC₂₀ and LC₅₀ GST activities were not significantly different from the control. GST activities were not significantly different between susceptible and resistant *Tetranychus urticae* Koch (Acari: Tetranychidae) strains to chlorfenapyr (Van Leeuwen *et al.*,

2006). The GST had no obvious effect on metaflumizone in resistant and susceptible strains of *Plutella xylostella* (L.) (Lepidoptera: Plutellidae) and *Spodoptera exigua* (Hübner) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) (Shen *et al.*, 2020 and Tian *et al.*, 2014). On the other hand, many results reflect the important role of GST in the metaflumizone accordance with Hatem *et al.* (2017) and Yalcin *et al.* (2015), which confirmed an increased enzyme activity due to metaflumizone treatment. These results are useful for formulating chlorfenapyr and metaflumizone insecticides management strategies to control *S. littoralis* in the field.

Table (2): Amounts of total carbohydrates, yotal lipids, free amino acids, and the activity of GST enzyme in *S. littoralis* 4th instar larvae treated with LC₅₀ of chlorfenapyr and metaflumizone compared with untreated control larvae (Mean ± SE).

Insecticides	Total carbohydrates (mg/g.b. wt)	Total lipids (mg/g.b. wt)	Free amino acids (mg alanine/g.b. wt)	GST (mmole sub. Conj./min/g.b. wt)
Chlorfenapyr	23.13±0.58b	5.9 ±0.31a	1.71±0.052a	21.23±0.14a
Metaflumizone	25.55±0.45b	4.05 ±0.15b	1.92±0.025a	21.2±0.10a
Control	33.63±1.06a	5.7 ±0.26a	2.22±0.102b	22.13±0.57a

3. Histopathological studies:

Histological studies of the mid-gut of the treated larvae with LC₅₀ show that the insect muscles were affected by

the tested compound. Normal structural features of the mid-gut of the 4th larval instar of *S. littoralis* are illustrated in Figure (1).

Figuer (1): Transverse section of control mid-gut of the 4th instar larva of *Spodoptera littoralis* cm = circular muscle; E= epithelial layer; L= lumen; lm = longitudinal muscle; vs = vesicles (Scale bar = 200µm).

The mid-gut epithelium is a simple epithelium composed of three main cell types, columnar epithelial cells, regenerative cells, and goblet cells supported by a basement membrane which is surrounded from inside to the outside by a circular muscle layer and a longitudinal muscle layer. Larvae treated with chlorfenapyr showed induced several irreversible histopathological changes in the mid-

gut of larvae the epithelial cells' cytoplasm was vacuolated, and some of them lost their nuclei or appeared pyknotic. Changes were most noticeable in the columnar, regenerative, and caliciform cells. These cells' apical surfaces were damaged.

The empty apical vesicles indicate that certain epithelial cells have lost their ability to secrete. Shrinkage of the epithelial layer cells was observed after the treatment with chlorfenapyr (Figure 2).

Figure (2): Transverse section in the mid-gut of 4th larval instar of *Spodoptera littoralis*, treated with LC₅₀ of Chlorfenapyr fc= cells with pyknotic nuclei.

The changes histopathological were observed in the mid-gut of 4th larval instar of *S. littoralis*, treated by metaflumizone. The circular muscle layer and a longitudinal muscle layer

seem to become thicker than normal and the basement membrane is partially separated. Lysis in the epithelial cells (Figure 3).

Figure (3): Transverse section in the mid-gut of 4th larval instar of *Spodoptera littoralis*, treated with LC₅₀ of metaflumizone.

Similar observations were mentioned by many authors, Youssef (2006) found pyriproxyfen and abamectin caused defects in columnar epithelium-cells and stretching the lead to peritrophic membrane tearing. Saleh *et al.* (2021) found lufenuron, diflubenzuron, emamectin benzoate

Chlorantraniliprole, methoxyfenozid, and spinosad destruction of both goblet and columnar cells in the mid-gut. The basement membrane was separated from the epithelial layer, which was disordered and accompanied by an increased vacuolization. Basement and peritrophic membranes are separated (Hanan *et al.*, 2020). The midgut of *S. littoralis* was treated with *Hyptis brevipes* dichloromethane extract, which caused the peritrophic membrane to be detached and the midgut lumen was packed with pycknotic-nuclei-epithelial cells. Extensive destruction of

and indoxacarb on the 2nd and 4th larval instar of the *S. littoralis* larvae exhibit destruction of the mid-gut muscle layers, disorganization in the epithelial cells, separation of the peritrophic membrane, and occurrence of visualizations and detachment of the basement membrane.

the epithelium with cells lacking nuclei in the midgut (Sakr, 2014).

Histomorphological disturbances in the mid-gut of 4th instar larvae *S. littoralis* treated with the tested compounds were vacuolation, lysis, and necrosis of the epithelial cells and destruction of epithelial cells and their boundaries. The present histopathological destruction caused by the investigated chlorfenapyr and metaflumizone insecticides may suggest that any of these insecticides are capable of causing a disturbance in the function and gradual death of an insect when entering into tissues in adequate amounts.

Abd-El-Aziz, H.S. and Salama, M.A.

(2020): Physiological studies of some insecticides on *Spodoptera littoralis* larvae. Egyptian Academic Journal of

References

Abbott, W. S. (1925): A method of computing the effectiveness of an insecticide. J. Econ. Entomol., 18:265-267.

- Biological Sciences, An Entomology, 13(2):333-344.
- Abd-El-Aziz, H.S.; Hassan, A.T. and Sabagh, M.M.E. (2020):** Field evaluation and some physiological studies of certain insecticides against black cutworm, *Agrotis ipsilon* (Hufn.) larvae. International Journal of Entomology Research, 5(6):160-167.
- Amin, T.R. (1998):** Biochemical and physiological studies of some insect growth regulators on the cotton leafworm, *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisd.). Ph.D. Thesis, Faculty of Science, Cairo University.
- Costat (2007):** Cost Software Package, co-hort Software Inc. Berkeley CA, USA, Release 5.5.
- Crompton, M. and Birt, L.M. (1967):** Changes in the amounts of carbohydrates, phosphagen, and related compounds during the metamorphosis of the blowfly, *Lucilia cuprina*. J. Insect Physiol., 13:1575-1595.
- Dubois, M.; Gilles, K. A.; Hamilton, J. K.; Rebers , P. A. and Smith, F. (1956):** Colorimetric method for determination of sugars and related substances. Analyst. Chem., 28:350-356.
- EL-Defrawi, M.; Topozada, A.; Mansour, N. and Zeid, M. (1964):** Toxicological studies on the Egyptian cotton leaf worm, *Prodenia litura* 1-Suceptibility of different larval instars to insecticides. J. Econ. Entomol., 57: 591-593.
- El-Sayed, A.S.; Moustafa, A.H.; Hussein, H.A.; El-Sheikh, A.A.; El-Shafey, S.N.; Fathy, N.A. and Enan, G.A. (2020):** Potential insecticidal activity of *Sarocladium strictum*, an endophyte of *Cynanchum acutum*, against *Spodoptera littoralis*, a polyphagous insect pest. Biocatalysis and Agricultural Biotechnology, 24: p.101524.
- EPA (2001):** Chlorfenapyr insecticide-matricide environmental fate and ecological effects assessments and characterization for a section 3 for use on cotton. <http://www.epa.gov/opprd001/c hlorfenapyr/toc.htm>.
- FAO (2019):** New standards to curb the global spread of plant pests and diseases. <http://www.fao.org/news/story/en/item/1187738/icode/>
- Finney, D. J. (1971):** Probit analysis. A Statistical Treatment of the Sigmoid Response Curve. 7th Ed., Cambridge Univ. Press, England.
- Ghoneim, K., (2020):** Impairing Effectiveness of Nerolidol, a Sesquiterpene Compound, on Adult Performance and Reproductive Potential of Egyptian Cotton Leafworm, *Spodoptera littoralis* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae). Egyptian Academic Journal of Biological Sciences. A, Entomology, 13(2):97-120.
- Habig, W. H.; Pabst, M. J. and Jakoby, W. B. (1974):** Glutathione S-transferase. the first enzymatic step in mercapturic acid formation. J. Biol. Chem., 249:7130-7139.
- Hanan, S. A. E. A.; Heba, M. S. E. and Mohamed, A. S. S. (2020):** Contact and feeding effects of chlorantraniliprole, methoxyfenozid and spinosad on some histological changes in cotton leaf worm *Spodoptera littoralis* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae). Egyptian Journal of Plant Protection Research Institute, 3(2): 731-742.

- Hatem, E.; Sorour, A. and Hassan, T. (2017):** Biochemical parameters, toxicity, development and reproductive effects of two novel insecticides on *Spodoptera littoralis* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae). Egypt. Acad. J. Biolog. Sci., 9 (3):135-147.
- Humason, G. L. and Freeman, W. H. (1979):** Animal tissue Technique. 4th edition San Francisco, USA.
- IPPC Secretariat, (2021):** Scientific review of the impact of climate change on plant pests – A global challenge to prevent and mitigate plant pest risks in agriculture, forestry and ecosystems. Rome. FAO on behalf of the IPPC Secretariat. <https://doi.org/10.4060/cb4769en>
- Jain, N.K. and Roy, I. (2009):** Effect of trehalose on protein structure. Protein Science, 18(1):24-36.
- Khakame, S.K.; Wang, X. and Wu, Y. (2013):** Baseline toxicity of metaflumizone and lack of cross resistance between indoxacarb and metaflumizone in diamondback moth (Lepidoptera: Plutellidae). Journal of economic entomology, 106 (3):1423-1429.
- Knight, J.A.; Anderson, S. and Rawle, J.M. (1972):** Chemical basis of the sulfo-phospho-vanillin reaction for estimating total serum lipids. Clin. Chem., (18):199-202.
- Lee, Y.P. and Takahashi, T. (1966):** An improved colorimetric determination of amino acids with the use of ninhydrin. Analytical Biochemistry, 14(1):71-77.
- Mosallanejad, H. and Smagghe, G. (2009):** Biochemical mechanisms of methoxyfenozide resistance in the cotton leafworm *Spodoptera littoralis*. Pest Management Science: formerly Pesticide Science, 65(7):732-736.
- Sakr, H. H. (2014):** Effect of *Hyptis brevipes* dichloromethane extract on feeding and histological structure of the midgut and malpighian tubules of *Spodoptera littoralis* larvae (Lepidoptera: Agrotidae). Sci. J. Fac. Menoufia Univ., 16: 1-19.
- Saleh, H. A.; El-Rahman, A.; Soheir, F.; El-Gably, A. R.; Yacoub, S. S. and Khorchid, A. M. (2021):** Biological and histological effects of certain insecticides on *Spodoptera littoralis* (Bosid). Journal of Plant Protection and Pathology, 12 (2): 111-115.
- Shen, J.; Li, Z.; Li, D.; Wang, R.; Zhang, S.; You, H. and Li, J. (2020):** Biochemical mechanisms, cross-resistance and stability of resistance to metaflumizone in *Plutella xylostella*. Insects, 11 (5): 311.
- Singh, I. and Sohi, A. S. (2008):** Sublethal influences of insecticides on *Spodoptera littoralis* (Fabricius). J. Insect. Sci. (Ludhiana), 21(1): 50-55.
- Takagi, K.; Hamaguchi, H.; Nishimatsu, T. and Konno, T. (2007):** Discovery of metaflumizone, a novel semicarbazone insecticide. Veterinary parasitology, 150(3):177-181.
- Tian, X.; Sun, X. and Su, J. (2014):** Biochemical mechanisms for metaflumizone resistance in beet armyworm, *Spodoptera exigua*. Pesticide Biochemistry and Physiology, 113: 8-14.
- Tomlin, C.D. (2000):** A World Compendium. In The Pesticide

- Manual. Edited by: 12th. British Crop Protection Council, London, UK.
- Van Leeuwen, T.; Van Pottelberge, S. and Tirry, L. (2006):** Biochemical analysis of a chlorfenapyr-selected resistant strain of *Tetranychus urticae* Koch. Pest Management Science, 62(5): 425-433.
- Yalcin, M.; Mermer, S.; Kozac, L. D. and Turgut, C. (2015):** Insecticide Resistance in Two Populations of *Tuta Absoluta* (Meyrick, 1917) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) from Turkey. Turk. Ent. Derg., 39(2):137-145.
- Youssef, L. A. (2006):** Some physiological and histopathological effects of two pesticides against the cotton leaf worm, *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisd.). Arab Universities Journal of Agricultural Sciences, 14(2): 803-812.
- Zhao, Y.; Wang, Q.; Ding, J.; Wang, Y.; Zhang, Z.; Liu, F. and Mu, W. (2018):** Sublethal effects of chlorfenapyr on the life table parameters, nutritional physiology and enzymatic properties of *Bradysia odoriphaga* (Diptera: Sciaridae). Pesticide Biochemistry and Physiology, (148): 93-102.

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Effect of mixing some microbial control agents with pollen grain suspension to control two early date palm pests and fruit setting

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Abstract:

Date palm crop (*Phoenix dactylifera*) is the backbone of the agricultural economy in the New Valley Governorate, which cultivated more than two and half million date palm trees especially the semi-dry varieties. Field trials were conducted to investigate the efficacy of mixing some microbial control agents, *Bacillus thuringiensis* sub sp. *Kurstaki*, *Metarhizium anisopliae* (Sorok) and *Beauveria bassiana* (Bals.) with pollen grain suspension to combat the greater date moth, *Arenipses sabella* (Hampson) (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) and the lesser date moth, *Batrachedra amydraula* (Meyrick) (Lepidoptera: Batrachedridae) which considered as an early date palm pests as well as the fruit set. The highest reduction in the fruit infestation with no significant differences (94.26 and 96.04 and 94.14 and 96.45%) was obtained with *M. anisopliae* and *B. thuringiensis* during 2020 and 2021 seasons, respectively. Meanwhile, the low effects against *A. sabella* (51.48 and 53.55%) were recorded in the case of the treatment with *B. bassiana*. The maximum reduction against *B. amydraula* infestations (88.36 and 87.88%) followed by (80.39 and 80.43%) and (72.78 and 71.89%) was obtained when pollen was mixed with, *B. thuringiensis*, *B. bassiana* and *M. anisopliae* during the two successive seasons, respectively. Regarding the effect of mixing the microbial control agents with the pollen suspension on the initial fruit set and fruit retention ratios, no side effect was observed, and a good result was obtained if compared to the control. This means that, the materials carrying microbial agents did not affect the vitality of pollen grains and stigma receptivity. These results encourage the mixing of biological compounds with pollen grain suspension during mechanical pollination of date palms in order to maximize the economic return.

Introduction

Recently, the Arab Republic of Egypt has tended to expand the cultivation of date palms, especially in

the New Valley Governorate. This expansion requires conducting all agricultural operations using all modern methods in order to save time, effort

and money. The greater date moth and the lesser date moth are considered the early date palm pests under this region conditions (Gameel and Sayed, 2009; Gameel *et al.*, 2014; Sayed *et al.*, 2014 and Mansour *et al.*, 2019).

Regarding the greater date moth, spathes, bunches, fruit stalks and fruits were attacked in March and April. When the larvae infested at the later stage of growth, bunch bases broken and caused extreme damage to fruits and affected its quality. This usually happens during August such bunches are heavy enough and then these infested bunches were unable to bear their weight (Saleh, 1974; Ali *et al.*, 1988 and Abdel-Rahman *et al.*, 2007).

Gameel (2017) recorded that, the greater date moth, *Arenipses sabella* (Hampson) (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) is considered a key insect pest on the date palm under El-Kharga Oasis conditions. The main date palm cultivar (Saidy) suffered from the greater date moth, *A. sabella* attacks, over 80% of the inspected date palm were found infested with the pest. The general average of the cut bunch bases was 9.58% (This value expresses the economic loss in the crop for the Saidy variety in the El-Kharga Oasis). Different larval instars of *A. sabella* were observed in full activity status in the frond bases during mid January. Unopened spadix of the date palm males recorded the earliest infestation during the last week of January. Also, Gameel *et al.* (2017) found that, the direct date fruit losses ranged between (20.87 and 26.23 %) on Saidy and (47.21 and 44.62%) on Tamr (Dray date) in El-Dakhla Oasis.

The lesser date moth *Batrachedra amydraula* (Meyrick) (Lepidoptera: Batrachedridae) is an early pest on date fruit in the Oases of the New Valley (Saleh, 1974; Temerak *et al.*, 2007; Gameel *et al.*, 2014 and Sayed *et al.*, 2014).The lesser date

moth, is a pest of date fruits. The larvae of the first generation feed on the small fruits after fruit set. The larvae enter from the top between the three carpels inside the young fruit. Each larva has its independent entry pore in the fruit and may attack from three to four fruits during its lifetime. Usually, each larva eats more than a third of the fruit and it may sometimes feed on the entire content and consume seed in varieties in which this is tender, leaving only the outer fruit skin. These infested fruits wither and are suspended from the stalks by the threads secreted by the larvae or they fall onto the ground. The larvae of the second and third generations enter inside the fruits near the calyx or through the calyx and they feed on the placenta, fruit flesh and the fruit kernel. After some time, these fruits become reddish in color. Hence, the name Homera is given to the insect, which means red in Arabic. The damaged fruits begin to drop from bunches. The infestation of the dropped fruits can be differentiated by the pore present on each infested fruit filled with the faeces of the larvae and by the presence of the silk weaving secreted by the larvae (Venezian and Blumberg, 1982 and Kinawy, 2012).

Microbial control agents such as *B. thuringiensis*, *B. bassiana* and *M. anisopliae* and other species were evaluated against many date palm pests. Hussein *et al.* (2020) found that the mortality percent of adult females of the dust mite, *Oligonychus afrasiaticus* (McGregor) were 73.3, 88, 92 and 92%, respectively, after seven days of treatment with *B. bassiana*, *Metarhizium acridum*, *Lecanicillium muscarium* and *Isaria fumosorosea*, respectively. Under El-Kharga Oasis conditions, Temerak *et al.* (2007) recorded that, the infestation reduction ratios with the lesser date moth were 89.3, 88.6 and 87.2% after the treatment with *Paecilomyces farcinus*, *M.*

anisopliae (Bioranza product) and *Bacillus thuringiensis* subsp *aegypti* (Agerin product), respectively.

Aziz *et al.* (2014) evaluated the pathogenicity of *B. bassiana* on *B. amydracula* under laboratory conditions and found that, a significant and high mortality rate on the eggs, first and fifth instars of the Homera larvae which reaches 100%, 96.19% and 91.20% after 7 days of treatment. However, mortality rates were found to be decreased to 88.97% for fifth instars after 10 days of treatment, while results showed parasitism potentially reaches 94.50% in pupae and 90.22% in adults.

Artificial pollination is a necessary method for commercial date production (Nixon, 1951 and Ream and Furr, 1970). Pollen grain germination is closely related with both the environmental conditions and stigma receptivity. Pollination of 60-80% of the female flowers is considered satisfactory and will usually lead to a good fruit set. The pollination efficiency is affected by several factors and consequently fruit set is highly dependent on these factors.

The pollination time, flowering period of male palm, the type of pollen, its viability and amount and the female flower receptivity are the main factors to take into account (Brown and Perkins, 1969 and El-Salhy *et al.*, 1997). Several studies have been conducted to increase the efficiency of the pollination process in date palm by mixing the pollen suspension with different materials. Moreover, using of pollen grains mixed with pure water as a carrier was successful in the pollination of the Fard date palm cultivar and it was recommended to use 0.5g/liter of water in the pollination of it (Al-Sabahi *et al.*, 2006).

Also, it was recommended to use 0.5 g of pollen grains/Liter of water concentration to pollinate Jabree and 0.1 g/liter for Helaly Oman (Alabri *et*

al., 2006). Pollination by spraying pollens water suspension mixed with different carriers had an announced effect on yield and fruit quality in various date palm cvs rather than pollination with the traditional method (El-Salhy *et al.*, 2010 and Ahmed, 2014).

In order to face the increasing expansion of date palm cultivation in that province to save some agricultural operations, this study was conducted to evaluate the effect of mixing some biocides with pollen grain suspension to control two early date palm pests (*A. sabella* and *B. amydracula*) and fruit set.

Materials and methods

This study was conducted in a date palm orchard situated at El-Kharga Oasis, New Valley Governorate, Egypt, during 2020 and 2021 seasons, on 18 years old Saily date palm cultivar (As a semi dry date palm). Sixteen date palms that are uniform in vigor and in good physical condition were selected. The number of spathes per palm were adjusted to ten by removing excess earliest, latest and smallest clusters for achieving this work.

The biocides products were:

1. Protecto 9.4% WP, *Bacillus thuringiensis* subsp *Kurstaki* (32000 Inter. Units) at the rate of 125 gm / 100 L.
2. Bioranza (0.29%) (A natural metabolite of the Deuteromycete, *Metarhizium anisopliae* Sorok) at the rate of 200 ml/100 L.
3. Biovar 10 % (A natural metabolite of the Deuteromycete, *Beauveria bassiana* (Bals.) at the rate of 200gm / 100 L.

All compounds locally produced by Insect Pathogen Unit, Plant Protection Research Institute, ARC, MOA, Egypt. Pollination was uniformed in respect of source and method to avoid residues of metaxenia. Each bioproduct was mixed individually with 5 gm pollen grains/L

water and applied one time/season during the second half of March. Pollination treatment sprays were applied at the third day of spathe cracking. The combination was applied by using small hand sprayer (1/2 liter capacity) at the amount of 50 ml/bunch. The comparison palm was treated with pollen suspension only. The experiment was set up in a complete randomized block design with four replications. One date palm tree was considered as one replicate. Samples size was 10 strands / one date palm taken at random from each replicate.

Inspection times were conducted at two weeks interval from the mid of April until beginning of July during the two successive seasons (2020, 2021). In each strand, the infested fruits with the greater and lesser date moths, the naturally fallen fruits, initial fruit sit, and fruit retention were examined (El-Salhy *et al.*, 2010; Ahmed, 2014 and Sayed *et al.*, 2014).The initial fruit set (I.F.S.) was counted using 10 strands per spathe after 4 weeks from pollination and the percentage these values was calculated using the following equation:

$$\text{Initial fruit set (\%)} = \frac{\text{Av. number of set fruit per strand}}{\text{Av. number of set fruit} + \text{Av. number of flower scars}} \times 100$$

Fruit retention: In the first week of July, the previous 10 strands were inspected and counted then the percentage of retention fruits was calculated.

Data were statistically analyzed by F-test and the means were compared according to Duncan's Multiple Range Test (Snedecor and Cochran, 1971).

Results and discussion

Data in Tables (1 and 2) indicated that, all tested microbial control agents (*B. thuringiensis*, *M. anisopliae* and *B. bassiana*) when

mixed with pollen grain suspension induced a remarkable reduction on the infestation rates with *A. sabella* and *B. amydraula* with different levels during 2020 and 2021 seasons.

Concerning to the greater date moth, data in Table (1) indicated that, the period of infestation with the pest extended from the second half of April until the first of May. After then, the infestation was decline to zero until the end of inspection time (Beginning of July) of the two successive seasons.

Table (1) : Reduction% of *A. sabella* infestation after the treatment with a mixture of microbial control agents and the pollen suspension, during 2020 and 2021 seasons.

Inspection date and treatments	2020					
	16/4		1/5		Mean*	
	Infestation %	Reduction %	Infestation %	Reduction %	Infestation %	Reduction %
<i>Beauveria bassiana</i>	5.86	50.43	6.56	52.53	6.21 b	51.48b
<i>Metarhizium anisopliae</i>	0.68	94.25	0.79	94.26	0.74c	94.26 a
<i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i>	0.50	95.77	0.51	96.31	0.51 c	96.04a
Control	11.82		13.82		12.82 a	
2021						
<i>Beauveria bassiana</i>	6.04	50.25	6.27	56.87	6.16 b	53.55 b
<i>Metarhizium anisopliae</i>	0.72	94.07	0.84	94.22	0.78 c	94.14a
<i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i>	0.56	95.38	0.36	97.52	0.46c	96.45a
Control	12.14		14.54		13.34 a	

*Means followed by the same letter in each column are not significantly different at 0.05 level of probability

The results indicate that the low effects against *A. sabella* 51.48 and 53.55 % were recorded in case of the treatment with *B. bassiana* during 2020 and 2021 seasons, respectively. The highest reduction in the fruit infestation with no significant differences (94.26 and 96.04 and 94.14 and 96.45 %) were obtained with *M. anisopliae* and *B. thuringiensis* during 2020 and 2021 seasons, respectively.

Regarding the infestation with the lesser date moth, as shown in Table (2), the infestation time extended from the second half of April to the beginning of June. After then, the infestation was decline to zero until the end of inspection time (Beginning of July) of the two successive seasons.

Table (2) : Reduction% of *B. amydraula* infestation after the treatment with a mixture of microbial control agents and the pollen suspension during 2020 and 2021 seasons.

2020								
Inspection date and treatments	16/4		1/5		1/6		Mean*	
	Infestation %	Reduction %						
<i>Beauveria bassiana</i>	1.38	83.82	1.57	83.24	0.78	43.88	1.24 bc	80.39 b
<i>Metarhizium anisopliae</i>	2.22	73.97	2.73	70.86	0.30	78.41	1.75 b	72.78 c
<i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i>	0.84	90.51	0.99	89.43	0.43	69.06	0.75 c	88.36 a
Control	8.53		9.37		1.39		6.43 a	
2021								
<i>Beauveria bassiana</i>	1.48	82.94	1.48	84.13	0.83	37.12	1.26 bc	80.43 b
<i>Metarhizium anisopliae</i>	2.35	72.92	2.83	69.66	0.25	81.06	1.81 b	71.89 c
<i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i>	0.87	89.98	1.01	89.17	0.46	65.15	0.78 c	87.88 a
Control	8.68		9.33		3.33		6.44 a	

*Means followed by the same letter in each column are not significantly different at 0.05 level of probability

When the pollen grain suspension was mixed with the biological control agents such as *B. thuringiensis*, *B. bassiana* and *M. anisopliae* do not induce any negative effect on the initial fruit set and fruit set ratios if compared to the control as shown in Table (3)

In 2020, higher initial fruit set (84.37 and 82.89 %) was obtained after the treatment with *M. anisopliae* and *B. thuringiensis*, respectively. The low

In 2020, the maximum average level of infestation reduction (88.36%) was recorded when the pollen grain mixed with *B. thuringiensis* followed by (80.39%) in case of *B. bassiana*. Meanwhile, the low average effect (72.78%) was obtained when the bunches treatment with *M. anisopliae*.

The same trend of results was obtained during 2021 season, where the combination of *B. thuringiensis* with the pollen grain suspension induced the high average rate of the infestation reduction (87.88%) followed by (80.43 and 71.89%) in the case of *B. bassiana* and *M. anisopliae*, respectively.

initial fruit set (78.23 %) was obtained after the treatment with *B. bassiana*. During 2021 season, the maximum initial fruit set 87.46 %, followed by 83.19 and 78.80% was recorded in case of *B. thuringiensis*, *M. anisopliae* and *B. bassiana*, respectively. Regarding to, the effect of mixing some microbial control agents with pollen grain suspension on the fruit retention ratio, all tested compounds induced a positive significant effect if compared with

control which recorded for 66.79 and 62.45% in 2020 and 2021 respectively. The percentage of fruit set was (80.87 and 84.55%), (82.91 and 81.20%) and (74.31 and 76.55%) when treated with

B. thuringiensis, *M. anisopliae* and *B. bassiana* in 2020 and 2021, respectively.

Table (3) : Percentage of the fruit set after the treatment with a mixture of microbial control agents and the pollen suspension during 2020 and 2021 seasons.

Season	2020		2021	
	Initial fruit set	Fruit retention	Initial fruit set	Fruit retention
<i>Beauveria bassiana</i>	78.23 b	74.31b	78.80 c	76.55c
<i>Metarhizium anisopliae</i>	84.37 a	82.91a	83.19 b	81.20b
<i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i>	82.89 a	80.87a	87.46 a	84.55a
Control	66.79 c	66.79c	65.56 d	62.45d

*Means followed by the same letter in each column are not significantly different at 0.05 level of probability.

Finally, it can be observed that, the infestation rate with *A. sabella* is twice the rate of infestation with *B. amydracula*. This is consistent with what Gameel *et al.* (2014) and Gameel (2017) emphasized in previous studies in the same province that the greater date moth is the main pest in the New Valley. It is clear that the process of mixing pollen grains with the tested biological compounds has achieved several successes such as: (1) *B. thuringiensis* (Protecto product), *M. anisopliae* (Bioranza product) and *B. bassiana* (Biovar product) when mixed with pollen grain suspension induced a significant reduction on the infestation rates with *A. sabella* and *B. amydracula*. More than 90% reduction in the infestation with *A. sabella* was obtained when date palm bunches treated with a mixing pollen grains and *B. thuringiensis* or *M. anisopliae*. Poor results were recorded in case of *B. bassiana*. Regarding the lesser date moth, all treatments gave satisfactory results, ranging between 70 and 88%. It can be arranged in descending order as follows: *B. thuringiensis*, *B. bassiana* and *M. anisopliae*. Nearly the same trend of results was obtained by Temerak *et al.* (2007) who found that, the infestation reduction ratios with the lesser date moth were 88.6 and 87.2% after the treatment with *M. anisopliae* (Bioranza product) and *B. thuringiensis*

subsp *aegypti* (Agerin product), respectively. Aziz *et al.* (2014) evaluated the pathogenicity of *B. bassiana* to *B. amydracula* under laboratory conditions and found that, high mortality rates in the eggs, first and fifth instars of the *B. amydracula* larvae reached to 100%, 96.19% and 91.20% after 7 days of treatment. (2) No side effect was observed on the initial fruit set and fruit set ratios and a good result were obtained if compared to the control. This means that, the materials carrying microbial agents did not affect the vitality of pollen grain and stigma receptivity. (3) Mixing pollen grains with various carriers and nutrient minerals were beneficial in establishing mechanical pollination and obtaining an economical yield with good fruit quality. Also, it is responsible for enhancing pollination efficiency (Furr and Hewitt, 1964; Khalil and Al-Shawaan, 1982; El-Mardi *et al.*, 1995; Hussein and Hassan, 2001; Ragab *et al.*, 2004; Ashour *et al.*, 2004 and El-Salhy *et al.*, 2007). Previous studies showed that pollination by spraying pollens water suspension mixed with different carriers had an announced effect on yield and fruit quality in various date palm cvs rather than pollination with the traditional method (El-Salhy *et al.*, 2010 and Ahmed, 2014). In conclusion, it can be recommended that, during the date palm pollination process that used a mixing pollen grains (5 gm/L water) and the recommended dose of *B. thuringiensis* or

M. anisopliae to combat *A. sabella* and *B. thuringiensis* or *B. bassiana* to control *B. amydraula* during the second half of March

References

- Abdel-Rahman, G.A. ; Fouda, M. A.; Mahmoud, H. I.; El-Agamy, E. A.; Imam, A.I. and Mansour, A. N. (2007):** Observations on the greater date moth (*Arenipses sabella*) in Baharia Oasis–Egypt. Egyptian J. Agric. Res., 85:73-83.
- Ahmed, E. F. S.(2014):** Increasing pollination efficiency in Saidy date palms by using starch carrier along with pollens suspension Proceeding of the Fifth International Date palm Conference , Abu Dhabi, UAE March 16 – 18, ISBN978-9948-22-868-4 , 237-243.
- Alabri, N.; Al-Busaidi, K. and Alhemaimee, S. (2006):** Effect of pollen grains suspension on fruit set and physicochemical characteristics of two date palm (*Phoenix dactylifera*) cultivar Qnt .Conf. on Date Palm Production and Processing Technology May 9-11 Muscat , Oman. p19.
- Ali, M. A.; Abdel-Salam, A. L.; Metwally, M. M. and Hussain, A. E. (1988):** Response of different date varieties to infestation with certain lepidopterous pests with to cleaning process as a measure for reducing pest infestation. Proc. XVIII Int. Congress of Entomology, Vancouver, Canada.
- Al-Sabahi, S.; Al-Busaidi, K.; Al-Amr, S.E. and Al-Abri, S. (2006):** Effect of pollen grains suspension on fruit set and yield of date palm (*Phoenix dactylifera*) cultivar Fard. Qnt. Conf. on Date Palm Production and Processing Technology May 9-11 Muscat, Oman. p18.
- Ashour, N.E.; Hassan, H.S.A. and Mostafa, E.A.M.(2004):** Yield and fruit quality of Zaghoul and Samany date palm (*Phoenix dactylifera* L.) as affected by pollination methods Annals Agric. Sci. Ain Sham Univ., Cairo, 49 : 631-642.
- during mechanical pollination of date palms in order to save money, effort and time.
- Aziz, F.M.; Al-janabi, S.D.S. and Na'ama, R. A. (2014):** Laboratory studies on the effects of the entomopathogenic fungus *Beauveria bassiana* (Bals.) Vuill, on the Homaira insect, *Batrachedra amydraula* (Lepidoptera : Cosmopterygidae). Iraqi Journal of Science, 55:643-648.
- Brown, G.K. and Perkins, R. M. (1969):** Pollen application to date palm in California. Proc. 4th Int . Agric Aviat. Congr. (Kingston) Ontario, Canada, 540-545.
- El-Mardi, O.M.; Labiad, S.N.; Consolation, E. and Abdel-Basit, K.M.(1995):** Effect of pollination methods and pollen dilution on some chemical constituents of Fard dates at different stages of fruit development. Emr. J. Agric. Sci., 7: 1-19.
- El-Salhy, A.; Abdalla, A.Y. and Mostafa, R.A. (1997):** Evaluation of some date palm male seedlings in pollination of Zaghoul and Samany date palms under Assiut conditions. Assiut J. Agric. Sci., 28: 79-89.
- El-Salhy, A.; Marzouk, H.M.; Abdel-Galil, H.A. and Mahmoud, A.E.(2007):** Effect of some pollination treatments on yield and fruit quality of some date palm cultivars. The 4th Symposium on date palm in Saudi Arabia, King Faisal Univ., Al-Hassa, 5-8 May.
- El-Salhy, A.M; El-Bana, A.A.; Abdel-Galil, H.A. and Ahmed, E.F.S. (2010):** Effect of pollen grains suspensions spraying on yield and fruit quality of Saidy date palm cultivar Proceeding of the Fourth International Date palm Conference ,Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates , 15-17 March. Acta Horticulturæ, 882 : 329-336.
- Furr, J.R. and Hewitt, A.A. (1964):**Thinning trials on" Madjool" dates, pollen dilution and

- chemicals. Date growers Inst. Rep., 41:17-18.
- Gameel, S. M. M. (2017):**The Economic importance of the greater date moth, *Arenipses sabella* Hampson (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae). Egypt Acad. J. Biolog. Sci., 10:41-49.
- Gameel, S. M. M. and Sayed, A. A. (2009):** Control of the greater date moth, *arenipses sabella* Hmpson (Pyralidae: Lepidoptera) at The New Valley-Egypt. Egypt. J. Agric. Res., 87:1323-1328.
- Gameel, S. M. M.; Abd-Ella, A. A. and Tolba, E. F. (2017):** Date palm host preference of the greater date moth, *Arenipses sabella* Hampson (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) at New Valley Governorate-Egypt. Egypt. Acad. J. Biolog. Sci.,10:221-230.
- Gameel, S.M.M.; Ewais, M.A. and Sayed, A.A. (2014):** Using of *Trichogramma evanescens* West. (Hymenoptera: Trichogrammatidae) for controlling *Arenipses sabella* Hmpson and *Batrachedra amydraula* Meyrick in the date palm fields at the New Valley-Egypt. Egypt. Acad. J. Biolog. Sci., 6:35-41.
- Hussein, F.H. and Hassan, A.S. (2001):** Effect of hand and mechanical pollination on fruit set, yield and fruit quality of dry dates CV. "Gondeila" under conditions of Aswan Governorate, Egypt. Zagazig J.Agric. Res., 28: 1035-1049.
- Hussein, H.M ; Al-Dahwy, S.S.J. and Ruman, O.K. (2020) :** Efficiency evaluation of some entomopathogenic fungi on dust mite *Oligonychus afrasiaticus* (Mcgregor) (Acari:Tetranychidae). Plant Archives, 20 : 225-228.
- Khalil, A.R. and Al-Shawaan, A.M. (1982):** Wheat flour and sugar solution media as carrier for date palm pollen grains. King Faisal Univ. Saudi Arabia 2nd Conf. on date Palm , 120-125.
- Kinawy, M. (2012):** Date palm pests in Oman. Mazoon Printing Press, Registration No:273/2012. pp.406.
- Mansour, A. N.; Abdel- Rahman, A. G.; Kobisi, A.A. and Imam, I.A. (2019):** Distribution of the greater date moth, *Arenipses sabella* Hmps. (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) in the Egyptian western desert Oases. Egyptian J. Desert Res., 69:1-14.
- Nixon, R.W.(1951):** Fruit thinning experiments with the "Medjool" and "Barhee" varieties of dates Annals of Date Growers Inst. Rept., 8:14-17.
- Ragab, M.A.; Gobara, A.A. and Mohamed, A.Y.(2004):** Effect of some pollen carriers on yield and fruit quality of Sewy date palms. J. Agric. Sci. Mansoura Univ., 29: 2501-5208.
- Ream, C.L. and Furr, J.R. (1970):** Fruit set of dates as affected by pollen viability and dust or water on stigmas. Date Grower's Inst. Rep., 47: 11.
- Saleh, M.R.A. (1974):** Ecological, biological and control studies on pests infesting date-bunches in the New Valley. Ph.D. Thesis. Fac. of Agric., Ain Shams University.
- Sayed, A.A.; Temerak, S.A; Gameel, S.M.M. and Moussa, A. (2014):** Alternate two different modes of actions of green chemicals to combat *Batrachedra amydraula* Meyrick and *Cadra cautella* Walk on date palm fruit, Egypt. Journal of Agricultural Science and Technology., 529-534.
- Snedecor, G. W. and Cochran, W. G. (1971):** Statistical methods. Iowa state Univ. Press, Ames, Iowa. USA.
- Temerak, S. A.; Sayed, A. A.; Bekheit, H. K. and Gameel, S. M. M. (2007):** Actinomycete natural metabolites to combat *Batrachedra amydraula* Meyrick and *Cadra* spp at Kharga Oasis, New Valley, Egypt. Egypt. J. Agric. Res., 85: 9-17.
- Venezian, A. and Blumberg, D. (1982):** Penology, damage and control of the lesser date moth *Batrachedra amydraula*, in date palms in Israel. Alon Hanotea., 36: 785-788.

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Relationship between the quantity of pollen grains as used in the pollination process and the infestation with *Arenipses sabella* (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) and *Batrachedra amydraula* (Lepidoptera: Batrachedridae)

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Abstract:

Many of the interrelationships between date palm and its pests have not been determined yet, especially in the case of the greater date moth, *Arenipses sabella* (Hampson) (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) and lesser date moth, *Batrachedra amydraula* (Meyrick) (Lepidoptera: Batrachedridae). So, this work aimed to investigate the effect of quantity of pollen grain as used in pollination process on the infestation with two early date palm pests, *A. sabella* and *B. amydraula* which are considered a key insect pest causing enormous damages to the crop. Hand pollination was achieved by using 7, 14, 21 and 28 fresh pollens strands per spathe. The obtained results indicated that, there is no significant effect in the initial fruit set as the pollen grains concentration is increasing. The greater date moth has a specific trend, where, the infestation rate increases severely when 28 fresh pollens strands per spathe was applied. On the other hand, the lesser date moth did not have a specific and clear trend, although the lowest rate of infestation was observed when the pollination was carried with 7 fresh pollens strands per spathe. The reduction in the fruit retention percentages with the increase in the number of pollen grains strands attributed to the relationship between the number of pollen grains strands as used in the pollination process and the infestation with two early date palm pests especially *A. sabella*. Perhaps, an increase in the amount of pollen is likely to have an attractive effect on both insects, especially the greater date moth.

Introduction

Date palm had great economic importance and agricultural uses throughout human history. Many arthropod species were recorded as a key pest attacking date palm successively during the grown season.

For the success of the integrated management of date palm, it is necessary to study the interrelationships between the pests that cause economic damage and the plant host. Wakil *et al.* (2015) emphasized that, future research, attracts for several important

pests of date palm need to be identified, especially for the rhinoceros beetle, *Oryctes agamemnon* (Burmeister) (Coleoptera: Scarabaeidae), the greater date moth, *Arenipses sabella* (Hampson) (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae), and the date stone beetle, *Coccotrypes dactyliperda* F. (Coleoptera: Curculionidae), that can cause significant crop damages.

A. sabella and lesser date moth *Batrachedra amydraula* (Meyrick) (Lepidoptera: Batrachedridae) are considered as an early date palm pest under New Valley region-Egypt as recorded by Gameel (2017) who found that, different larval instars of *A. sabella* were observed in full activity status in the frond bases during mid January. Unopened spadix of the date palm males recorded the earliest infestation during the last week of January. Over 80% of the inspected date palm were found infested with the pest. The general average of the cut bunch bases was about 10% (This value expresses the economic loss in the crop for the Saily variety in the El-Kharga Oasis). Also, Gameel *et al.* (2017) recorded that, the direct date fruit losses ranged between (25 %) on Saily and (45%) on Tamr (Dry date) in El-Dakhla Oasis. First damage is seen in March when young larvae are found eating the tips of unopened spathes. When the spathes open, the larvae enter and may strip the flowers and young fruits from whole strands. Their depredations are marked by a coarse silken tunnel, which becomes littered with grass and plant fragments, and which may be 3.5 cm long when the larva is full-grown (Wiltshire, 1957 and Hussain, 1963).

Concerning to the lesser date moth which attacks date fruits and causes several damages to dates, thus reducing the crop yield. The damage is

caused by the larvae which bore deep tunnels into the fruit ultimately the fruit dries and drops. Infestation can be easily recognized by turning brown and remaining attached to the fruit stalks by a silken thread. Infestation may cause more than 40% loss of fruits (Saleh, 1974; Venezian and Blumberg, 1982; Temerak *et al.*, 2007; Kinawy, 2012; Gameel *et al.*, 2014 and Sayed *et al.*, 2014).

Several efforts have been accomplished to improve date palm production through facing production problems and improving agricultural practices as the efficiency of the pollination process. Therefore, it is required to ensure good fruit production through understanding some horticultural practices that affect tree growth and productivity. Pollination is one of the major practices in this concern (Ream and Furr, 1970; Shaheen, 1986; Gasim, 1993 and Kotb, 1993). Hand pollination is considered the common and traditional way for date production and is necessary for successful fruit set and fruiting (Nixon, 1951 and Ream and Furr, 1970). It is executed by inserting the male strands into the female flower cluster (Dawson, 1956; Ahmed, 1959; Goor, 1967; Sial, 1980; Kataab, 1985 and Hamood *et al.*, 1986).

Traditional pollination with seven strands/ spathe which the recommended method (Ahmed *et al.*, 2016). But farmers applied high rates of strands for each spathe to conduct the pollination process. So, this study aims to find out is there a relationship between the amount of pollen used in the pollination and insect infestations.

Materials and methods

This study was conducted during 2020 and 2021 seasons in a date palm orchard situated at El-Kharga

Oasis, New Valley Governorate on 16 years old Saidy (As a semi dry date palm cv). These palms were produced through conventional propagation by offshoots as well as characterized by regular bearing. Also, they are uniform in vigour, healthy and good physical conditions. All selected palms (16 palms) received the common and usual horticultural practices that already applied in the orchard except those dealing with hand pollination. Bunches/leaf was adjusted to 1:6 according to Ahmed (2002). Hand pollination of all the selected palms was achieved by inserting fresh male strands into the center of one female spathe using the same source of pollens to avoid residues of metaxenia according to (Al-Tahir and Asif, 1983 and Hussein *et al.*, 1985). The pollen grains viability was tested before carrying out pollination with acetocarmine staining. One drop of 1.0% acetocarmine was dispersed. Pollens were microscopically examined colorless or unstained pollen grains were considered

non viable, according to Moreira and Gurgel (1941) and Furr and Enriquez (1966).

Hand pollination with 7, 14, 21 and 28 fresh pollens strands per one spathe was applied and carried out three days after female spathe cracking. Each treatment was replicated four times (one palm per each). The experiment was set up in a complete randomized block design with four replications.

Inspection times were conducted at two weeks interval from the mid of April until beginning of July. Ten fruit strands were randomly marked on each palm. In each strand, the infested fruits with the greater and lesser date moths, the naturally fallen fruits, initial fruit sit, and fruit retention were examined (El-Salhy *et al.*, 2010; Ahmed, 2014 and Sayed *et al.*, 2014).

1. Initial fruit set (I.F.S) percentage:

It was determined after 4 weeks from pollination time for ten fruit strands. Then the (I.F.S) was calculated according to the following equation:

$$\text{Initial fruit set (\%)} = \frac{\text{Av. number of set fruit per strand}}{\text{Av. number of set fruit} + \text{Av. number of flower scars}} \times 100$$

2. Fruit retention:

In the first week of July, the previous 10 strands were inspected and counted then the percentage of retention fruits was calculated. Data were statistically analyzed by F-test and the means were compared according to Duncan's Multiple Range Test (Snedecor and Cochran, 1971).

Results and discussion

The relationship between pollination with four rates of pollen grain (7, 14, 21 and 28 fresh pollens strands per bunch) and the infestation levels with *A. sabella* and *B. amydraula* during 2020, and 2021 seasons was indicated in Table (1). The highest rates of infestation with the greater date moth

(10.22 and 11.27%) were obtained when (28 fresh pollens strands per bunch) applied during 2020 and 2021, respectively. There are insignificant differences between the infestation rates when 7, 14 and 21 fresh pollens strands per bunch were applied during the two successive seasons. Regarding the lesser date moth during the first season, the maximum rates of infestation (2.68 %) followed by (2.00%) were obtained with 14 and 21 fresh pollens strands per bunch treatment during 2020, respectively. The pest induced the minimum rate of damage (1.23%) when 7 fresh pollens strands per bunch was applied. In 2021 season, the high rates of infestation with

B. amydraula (2.78 and 2.61%) were obtained when (14 and 21 fresh pollens strands per bunch) applied, respectively. Meanwhile, the minimum rate of damage (1.34%) when 7 fresh pollens strands per bunch was applied. The effect of the pollination levels on

the fruit set and fruit retention percentages in 2020, and 2021 seasons was indicated in Table (2).

Table (1): Infestation (%) with *Arenipses sabella* and *Batrachedra amydraula* after the treatment with different quantities of pollen grain in Saida date palm cultivar.

Treatment	<i>Arenipses sabella</i> infestation%		<i>Batrachedra amydraula</i> infestation%	
	2020	2021	2020	2021
Hand pollination with 7 fresh pollens strands (T ₁)	1.25 b	1.24 b	1.23d	1.34 b
Hand pollination with 14 fresh pollens strands (T ₂)	1.18 b	1.22 b	2.68 a	2.78 a
Hand pollination with 21 fresh pollens strands (T ₃)	1.28 b	1.300 b	2.00 b	2.61 a
Hand pollination with 28 fresh pollens strands (T ₄)	10.22 a	11.27 a	1.56 c	1.69 ab

*Means followed by the same letter in each column are not significantly different at 0.05 level of probability.

Table (2) : Effect of different quantities of pollen grain on initial fruit set and fruit retention (%) of Saida date palm cultivar during 2020 and 2021 seasons.

Characteristics	Initial fruit set (IFS) %		Fruit retention %	
	2020	2021	2020	2021
Hand pollination with 7 fresh pollens strands (T ₁)	87.30a	84.72a	85.59a	83.64a
Hand pollination with 14 fresh pollens strands (T ₂)	88.77a	86.00a	82.50b	81.78a
Hand pollination with 21 fresh pollens strands (T ₃)	87.53a	85.41a	80.00b	78.79a
Hand pollination with 28 fresh pollens strands (T ₄)	86.22a	84.33a	75.29c	73.05b

*Means followed by the same letter in each column are not significantly different at 0.05 level of probability

Concerning to the initial fruit set ratio, the obtained results in 2020 indicated that, there are insignificant differences between the values with different treatments (7, 14, 21 and 28 fresh pollens strands per bunch) which recorded (87.30, 88.77, 87.53 and 86.22%), respectively. Nearly the same trend of results was recorded during 2021season. Regarding fruit retention percentage, there are significant differences in different levels of treatments during 2020 season. The maximum rate of fruit retention (85.59%) recorded when 7 fresh pollens strands per bunch was applied.

Meanwhile, the minimum rate of fruit retention (75.29%) recorded when 28 fresh pollens strands per bunch was applied. In 2021 season, the high values of the fruit retention(83.64, 81.78 and 78.79%) were recorded after the treatment with 7, 14 and 21 fresh pollens strands per bunch, respectively. On the other hand, the low value of the fruit retention(73.05%)was recorded with 28 fresh pollens strands per bunch.

It is clear that, during 2020 and 2021, the high values of fruit retention (85.59 and 83.64%) were obtained after the treatment with 7 fresh pollens strands per bunch, respectively.

Meanwhile the lowest fruit retention percentage values (75.29 and 73.05%) were recorded after 28 fresh pollens strands per bunch were applied, respectively.

Finally, it can be concluded that: **a.** *A. sabella* caused the most damage if compared with the rate of infestation with *B. amydraula*. This is consistent with what Gameel *et al.*, 2014 and Gameel, 2017 emphasized in previous studies in the same province that the greater date moth is the main pest in the New Valley. **b.** The greater date moth has a specific trend, where, the infestation rate increases severely when 28 was applied. On the other hand, the lesser date moth did not have a specific and clear trend, although the lowest rate of infestation was observed when the pollination was carried with 7 fresh pollens strands per spathe. **c.** Concerning to the initial fruit set ratio, the obtained results indicated that, there are insignificant differences between the values with different treatments (7, 14, 21 and 28 fresh pollens strands per bunch). **d.** The reduction in the fruit retention percentages with the increase in the number of pollen grains strands attributed to the relationship between the number of pollen grains strands as used in the pollination process and the infestation with two early date palm pests especially *A. sabella*. Perhaps, an increase in the amount of pollen is likely to have an attractive effect on both insects, especially the greater date moth. Levi-Zada *et al.* (2014) mentioned that, copulation in the laboratory was observed only in the presence of date palm tissue, thus suggesting that sexual communication and mating of GDM moths probably occurs in the crown of date palms. Also, Wakil *et al.* (2015) emphasized that, future research, attracts for several important pests of the date palm need to be identified, especially for the rhinoceros beetle, *Oryctes agamemnon*

(Burmeister), the greater date moth, *A. sabella*, and the date stone beetle, *Coccotrypes dactyliperda* F., that can cause significant crop damages. **e.** It can be emphasized that, the greater date moth has become one of the most important pests on the date palm, and it needs the cooperation of researchers to conduct more investigations ecological and biological studies to understand the behavior of this insect.

References

- Ahmed, E. F. S. (2014):** Increasing pollination efficiency in Saily date palms by using starch carrier along with pollens suspension. Proceeding of the Fifth International Date palm Conference, Abu Dhabi, UAE March 16 – 18, ISBN978-9948-22-868-4 p. 237-243.
- Ahmed, E.F.S. (2002):** The productive capacity of Sewy date palms grown under New Valley conditions in response to leaves/bunch ratio. M.Sc. Thesis Fac. Agric. Minia University .
- Ahmed, E.F.S.; Saied, H.H.M. and El-Sharabasy, S.F.A. (2016):** Pistil receptivity of Saily date palms grown under new valley conditions when pollinated with pollen suspension. J. Plant Production, Mansoura Univ., 7(11): 1179-1182.
- Ahmed, M.S. (1959):** Date palm pollination in the East. First FAO International technical meeting on date production and processing. Tripoli, Libya, Back Ground paper No. (11+12).
- Al-Tahir, O.A. and Asif, M.I. (1983):** Study of variations in date pollen material. In Proceedings of the First Symposium on the date palm in Saudi Arabia. Al-Hassa, Saudi Arabia, King Faisal University, pp. 62-66.

- Dawson, V.H.W. (1956):** An account of the date palm by Francesco Redi, A.D. 1666. Trop. Agric. 33: 207-213.
- El-Salhy, A.M.; El-Bana, A.A.; Abdel-Galil, H.A. and Ahmed, E.F.S. (2010):** Effect of pollen grains suspensions spraying on yield and fruit quality of Sady date palm cultivar Proceeding of the Fourth International Date palm Conference, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates, 15-17 March Acta Horticulturae, 882: 329-336.
- Furr, J.R. and Enriquez V.M. (1966):** Germination of date pollen in culture media. Rept. Ann. Date Grs, Inst., 45: 24-27.
- Gameel, S.M.M.; Abd-Ella, A. A. and Tolba, E. F. (2017):** Date palm host preference of the greater date moth, *Arenipses sabella* Hampson (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) at New Valley Governorate- Egypt. Egypt. Acad. J. Biolog. Sci., 10:221-230.
- Gameel, S.M.M. (2017):** The economic importance of the greater date moth, *Arenipses sabella* Hampson (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae). Egypt. Acad. J. Biolog. Sci., 10: 41-49.
- Gameel, S.M.M.; Ewais, M.A. and Sayed, A.A. (2014):** Using of *Trichogramma evanescens* West. (Hymenoptera: Trichogrammatidae) for controlling *Arenipses sabella* Hampson and *Batrachedra amydraula* Meyrick in the date palm fields at the New Valley- Egypt. Egypt. Acad. J. Biolog. Sci., 6: 35-41.
- Gasim, A.A. (1993):** Effect of pollen quantity of fruit-setting, yield and some physical fruit properties of some date palm. Third Symp. on Date Palm in Saudi Arabia. King Faisal Univ., Al-Hassa, Saudi Arabia, January, Abstract No. B28, p. 91.
- Goor, A. (1967):** The history of the date through the ages in the holy land. Economic Botany, 21: 320-340.
- Hamood, H.H.; Mawlood, E.A. and Al-Khafaji, M.A. (1986):** The effect of mechanical pollination on fruit set, yield and fruit characteristics of date palm (*Phoenix dactylifera* L.) Zahdi cultivar. Date Palm, 4: 175-184.
- Hussain, A.A. (1963):** Biology and control of the dubas bug *Ommatissus binotatus lybicus* de berg. (Homoptera, Tropiduchidae), infesting date palms in Iraq. Bull. Entomol. Res., 53: 737-745.
- Hussein, F.; Badr, S.M. and Al-Aller, S.S. (1985):** Effect of different pollination methods on quality and quantity of date palm (*Phoenix dactylifera* L.) fruit. J. Agric. Water Resources Res., 4: 265-282.
- Kataab, H.A. (1985):** Date palm in old Egypt. Agric. J., 40: 33-35.
- Kinawy, M. (2012):** Date palm pests in Oman. Mazoon Printing Press, Registration No:273/2012. 406 pp.
- Kotb, A. (1993):** Studies on pollination, fertilization and the effect of some hormonal treatments on three date cultivars. Third Symp. on Date Palm in Saudi Arabia Faisal Univ., Al-Hassa. Saudi Arabia. January, 1993. Abstract No. B30. pp.91-92.
- Levi-Zada, A.; David, M.; Fefer, D.; Seplyarsky, V.; Sadowsky, A.; Dobrinin, S.; Ticuchinski, T.; Harari, D.; Blumberg, D. and Dunkelblum, E. (2014):**

- Circadian release of male-specific components of the greater date moth, *Aphomia (Arenipses) sabella*, using sequential SPME/GC/MS analysis. J. Chem. Ecol., 40:236-243.
- Moreira, S. and Gurgel, J.A. (1941):** Pollen fertility and its correlation with number of seeds in species and forms of the genus citrus progornita, Sao Paul, L. 669-711 (Plant Breeding Abst. 14: 976).
- Nixon, R.W.(1951):** Fruit thinning experiments with the "Medjool" and "Barhee" varieties of dates. Annals of Date Growers Inst. Rept., 8:14-17.
- Ream, C.L. and Furr, J.R. (1970):** Fruit set of dates as affected by pollen viability and dust or water on stigmas. Date Grower's Inst. Rep., 47: 11.
- Saleh, M.R.A. (1974):** Ecological, biological and control studies on pests infesting date-bunches in the New Valley. Ph.D. Thesis. Fac. of Agric., Ain Shams University.
- Sayed, A. A.; Temerak, S.A; Gameel, S.M.M. and Moussa, A. (2014):** Alternate two different modes of actions of green chemicals to combat *Batrachedra amydraula* Meyrick and *Cadra cautella* Walk on date palm fruit, Egypt. Journal of Agricultural Science and Technology, 529-534.
- Shaheen, M.R. (1986):** Pistil receptivity in three cultivars of date palm (*Phoenix dactylifera* L.). Proc. 1st Hort. Sci. Conf. Tanta Univ., Egypt, September, H: 489-499.
- Sial, F.S. (1980):** Development of a pneumatic date pollinator. ASAE paper No. 80-1506, Am. Soc. Agric. Eng. Winter Meeting, Chicago.
- Snedecor, G.W. and Cochran, W.G. (1971):** Statistical methods. Iowa state Univ. Press, Ames, Iowa. USA.
- Temerak, S. A.; Sayed, A. A.; Bekheit, H. K. and Gameel, S. M. M. (2007):** Actinomycete natural metabolites to combat *Batrachedra amydraula* Meyrick and *Cadra* spp. at Kharga Oasis, New Valley, Egypt. Egypt. J. Agric. Res., 85: 9-17.
- Venezian, A. and Blumberg, D. (1982):** Penology, damage and control of the lesser date moth *Batrachedra amydraula*, in date palms in Israel. Alon Hanotea., 36: 785-788.
- Wakil, W.; Miller, T.A. and Faleiro, J.R. (2015):** Sustainable pest management in date palm: Current status and emerging challenges: Sustainability in Plant and Crop Protection. In: Soroker, V.; Harari, A. and Faleiro, J.R. The role of semiochemicals in date pest management ISBN 978-3-319-24395-5 426pp.
- Wiltshire, E. P. (1957):** The lepidoptera of Iraq. ed. 2, 162 pp. Nicholas & Kaye Ltd. London.

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**Application timing and efficacy of some insecticides against the grapevine mealybug
Planococcus ficus (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae) infested grapes in Egypt**

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Abstract:

Mealybugs are the most important pests of cultivated crops in Egypt. Their damage on vineyards has dramatically increased during the past two decades. The grapevine mealybug, *Planococcus ficus* (Signoret) (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae) is a primary pest of vineyards in Egypt. In this study, the effect of eight insecticides was evaluated against nymphs and adults of grapevine *P. ficus* during sunset and sunrise applications in 2019 and 2020 in Egypt. During the 2019 season, four weeks, the highest efficacy against the nymph mealybugs was achieved by the used mineral oil (Kz oil) and buprofezin with a 92% and 90% population reduction, respectively. The best effects after the sunset application were achieved with Kz oil and buprofezin after four weeks (95% and 92%). The results obtained from 2020 confirmed that during the sunrise application, the highest reductions in the adult populations were achieved by mineral oils (96%) and buprofezin (93.2%) after four weeks. Four weeks after the sunset application, the mineral oil had the highest effective against the adult mealybugs (92%) followed by spirotetramat (89%). In contrast, *Verticillium lecanii* showed the least effective against the adults, four weeks after the sunset application of 73%. The results provide an appropriate framework for insecticides, application and timing of control process against vineyard mealybug infestations in Egypt.

Introduction

Grapes in the world are one of the favorite fruits and have become one of the biggest fruits in production in 2019 the total production of grapes all over the world was around 77 million tons with a harvested area of 6.9 million hectares according to FAOSTAT (2019). Table grapes are one of the most important fruits produced in Egypt, second only to citrus in terms of production quantities. Grape cultivation is spread geographically from Alexandria in the north to Aswan in the

south, which – combined with the production of early and late ripening grapes – enables the prolonged availability of fresh table grapes in the market from May to November. In 2020, commercial table grape production in Egypt is forecast to reach 1.42 million tons with a harvested area of 77895 hectares, while exports are estimated to reach 170,000 tons in 2020. The European Union remains the major importer of Egyptian table grapes. In Egypt, most of the grape area has been occupied by two main

cultivars; *Thompson seedless* and *Romi Ahmar* as well as a small area cultivated with some local cultivars. After 1981 some new table grape cultivars were introduced and planted in different growing regions, both in Delta and desert areas. These cultivars were found to be different in their morphological characteristics and fruit quality.

Scale insects (Hemiptera: Coccoidea) are among the most important pests of cultivated crops worldwide (Mansour *et al.*, 2017; Daane *et al.*, 2012; Franco *et al.*, 2009 and Sforza *et al.*, 2005). Within this large group of insects, mealybugs (Pseudococcidae) constitute the second most species-rich family following the armored scales (Diaspididae) with more than 2000 described species to date (García *et al.*, 2016). Twelve scale insects are found in Egypt. Mealybugs are small, soft-bodied insects, usually covered with a white mealy wax, which feeds on plant phloem and excrete honeydew (Williams and Watson, 1988). Most of the species are polyphagous infesting foliage, stems, or fruits. Their main damage is caused by ingestion of plant sap leading to plant vigor reduction, dropped the leaves, spottily yellowing, deformation of the shoot and twig, development of blisters like galls, loss of fruits, decreasing the normal tree physiological activities (Hassan *et al.*, 2012). The vine mealybug, *Planococcus ficus* Signoret (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae) is the key economic scale insect occurring in vineyards worldwide, including the Mediterranean basin, which represents its native range (Mansour *et al.*, 2017; Franco *et al.*, 2009; da Silva *et al.*, 2014; Gülec *et al.*, 2007; Reineke and Thiéry, 2016 and Walton *et al.*, 2009).

Historically, using pesticides is the main controlling method for mealybugs including potassium cyanide, sodium cyanide, and sulfur fumigation (Essig, 1914) permitting the

chlorinated hydrocarbons and organophosphates used at 1940s to the 1990s interval (Charles, 1985 and Frick, 1952). These chemicals were effective at low rates as 48 gm active ingredient/ha of ethyl parathion provided

Pseudococcus maritimus (Ehrhorn) (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae) control (Frick, 1952). Eventually, however, most of these pesticides became less effective (Flaherty *et al.*, 1982) or ultimately banned from use because of concerns about non-target biota. Many organophosphates are still effectively using (Walton *et al.*, 2009 and Sazo *et al.*, 2008).

New chemicals with more novel modes of action have also been gaining in popularity, including neonicotinoids, insect growth regulators, botanicals, and biosynthesis inhibitors (Daane *et al.*, 2006; Lo and Walker, 2010 and Sunitha *et al.*, 2009). Many of these compounds are controversial due to significantly sub-lethal effects on non-target organisms (Henry *et al.*, 2012). A major difference between the older and newer pesticides is the importance of coverage of the mealybug population, especially under the bark and for some species on the vine roots. Many of the older foliar sprays did not effectively contact and kill mealybugs in these more protected locations. Some of the newer pesticides have systemic properties and can be applied either through the irrigation system or as a foliar spray. For organic or sustainable farming programs, neem, light mineral oils, lime-sulfur, citrus products, and fatty acid soaps have been used. Few studies of these products have provided mixed results (Srinivas *et al.*, 2007).

Therefore, in the present study, we evaluated eight insecticides with different modes of action against the grapevine mealybug *P. ficus* and determine the effect of all treatments

after sunset and sunrise application to stand at the optimal time for their treatment applications to achieve the highest population reductions of mealybugs.

Materials and methods

1. Experimental design:

Field experiments were carried out to evaluate the efficacy of certain treatments against the grapevine mealybug, *P. ficus* on grapes grown at El-Noubaria, El-Beheira Governorate, Egypt in 2019 and 2020. Eight commercial formulated insecticides (Table 1) were used based on the Egyptian Ministry of Agriculture recommends for each insecticide to control sucking insects under field conditions.

The trial was laid out in a randomized complete block design in three replicates and control was concurrently conducted. For each replicate (3 trees) a spray was applied with a CP₃ knapsack sprayer (Cooper

Pegler Co. Ltd., Northumberland, England). As soon as these steps were carried out, the insecticides were applied at the used rates (Table 1). Insecticides were sprayed in the early morning (A sunrise application) and repeated before the night (Sunset application) in another treatments, the environmental conditions minimize the potential risk of spray drift and evaporation. The numbers of live mealybugs under the bark were counted on all trees in the plot before spraying and 1, 2, 3, and 4 weeks after application and the percentage population reduction in nymphs and adults separately was calculated (Henderson and Tilton, 1955) according to this formula:

$$\text{Reduction \%} = 100 [1 - (T_2 / T_1 * C_1 / C_2)]$$

T₂ Population in Treatment after spray

T₁ Population in Treatment before spray

C₁ Population in control before spray

C₂ Population in control after spray

Table (1): The tested insecticides; shown as their basic information.

Common name	Trade name	Chemical classes	Formulation	Basic manufacture	Applic at-ion rate	Target pest
Sulfoxaflor	Closer	Sulfoximines	240 SC	Dow Agro Sciences, LLC, Indianapolis, IN	100 mL/ Fed.	Aphid, Whitefly, Leafhopper, Mite, Mealybugs
Abamectin + Thiamethoxam	Agri-flex	Avermectins + neonicotinoids	18.56% SC	Syngenta Crop Protection, LLC, Greensboro, NC	240 mL/ Fed.	Tomato leaf miner, Red spider mite, Aphid, Armored scale, Psyllid
Spirotetramat	Movento	Tetramic acid derivative (Ketoenole)	10% SC	Bayer Crop Science LP, Research TrianglePark, NC	75 mL/ 100 L	Aphid, Red spider mite, Whitefly, Some scales, Mealybugs
Thiamethoxam	Actara	Neonicotinoids	25% WG	Syngenta Crop Protection, LLC, Greensboro, NC	25 g/ 100 L	Aphid, Termite, Boll worm, Redpalm weevil, Leaf miner, Thrips, Leaf hoppers
Imidacloprid	Best	Neonicotinoids	25% WP	Bayer Crop Science LP, Research TrianglePark, NC	75 g/ 100 L	Aphid, Whitefly, Some scales, Mealybugs, Red spider mite, Fruit fly, Root-knot nematode, Thrips.
Buprofezin	Applaud	Buprofezin	25% SC	Dow AgroSciences, LLC, Indianapolis, IN	600 mL/ Fed.	Fruit fly, Mealybug, Whitefly, Thrips, Aphid, Leaf hoppers.
<i>Verticillium lecanii</i>	Bio-catch	Fungal agent	WP(1x108 CFU's/gm)	T. Stanes Company limited	3 L./ha	Whiteflies, Aphids, Thrips, Mealy bugs
Mineral oils	Kz oils	Mineral oil	95 %	KafrEl-Zayat Pesticides and Chemicals Co.	1.5L/ 100 L	Aphid, Red spider mite, Whitefly, Some scales, Mealybugs

2. Statistical analysis:

The plot system was designed in a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with eight treatments compared to control and three replicates were used. The analysis was performed using the Costat program, version 6.311 (CoHort Software, Monterey, CA, USA) at a 0.05 probability level.

Results and discussion

The present study investigated the impact of insecticides applied as a foliar treatment against the nymph and adult of Grapevine mealybug, *P. ficus* Signoret during 2019 and 2020 seasons. In the past decade, the economic losses resulting from vineyard mealybug infestations have increased (Rajagopal *et al.*, 1997).

Mealybugs are phloem, vine's roots, trunk, canes, leaves, and fruit clusters sucking out plant fluids. Population size depends on the number of annual generations, female fecundity, preferred feeding locations, and temperature tolerances (Charles, 1982). Mealybugs accumulate on the lower surface of leaves and in the grape clusters, especially in late summer and early fall, where they select their favorite place to feed on the plant juice and secrete honeydew.

Due to this accumulation of mealybugs, the black sooty mold fungus develops on the honeydew excretions (Charles, 1982). For table grape growers, any live or dead mealybugs and the honeydew or sooty molds will cause cosmetic damage to the grape cluster and reduce its marketability (Tsai *et al.*, 2011). We undertook this study to develop suitable management programs to suppress the pest population below the critical economic limit that affect the yield of the vineyard.

1. Efficacy on the grapevine mealybug in 2019:

The grapevine mealybug, *P. ficus* was affected differently with the

tested insecticides. Significant differences were found between the insecticides in their effects against the populations of nymphs during the sunrise application (Tables 2 and 3). After one week, these tests revealed that the most striking reduction in the populations of nymphs was achieved by Kz oil as a mineral oil (75.64%) followed by buprofezin (70.70%), abamectin+thiamethoxam (70.13%), spirotetramat (69.91%), thiamethoxam (68.25%), sulfoxaflor (68.23%), imidacloprid (65.26%) and *V. lecanii* (26.23%), respectively.

After four weeks, the used mineral oil (Kz oil) and buprofezin achieved the highest mean reduction percentages of the treated population exhibiting 92.09% and 99.58% reduction, respectively. The least effective insecticide against the nymphs was *V. lecanii* as it caused 58.98% reduction in the treated population. During the sunset application, the highest population reduction of the nymphs after four weeks was achieved by the used mineral oil (Kz oil), which caused 95.44% reduction in the treated nymph population.

For adult populations, the used mineral oil showed a lower effect when applied after the sunrise than that obtained when applied after the sunset (Tables 4 and 5), suggesting that sunset is the optimal time for controlling the mealy bug adults by its foliar application. In case of the application after the sunrise, the used mineral oil achieved the highest population reduction after four weeks (89.88%) among all the other treatments.

Similarly, after the sunset application the adult population was highly reduced when treated with the used mineral oil and spirotetramat as they exhibited a reduction percent of 92.46% and 89.25%, respectively (Table 5). The least effective treatments during the sunset application were *V.*

lecanii with 57.02% reduction and imidacloprid with 69.98% reduction, respectively in the treated adult population. The adult population reduction effects after the sunset application were achieved differently according to the tested insecticide as they were arranged in descending order as the following: the used mineral oil (Kz oil), spirotetramat, abamectin+thiamethoxam, sulfoxaflor, buprofezin thiamethoxam, imidacloprid and *V. lecanii* as they respectively reduced the treated population with 84.51%, 82.18%, 81.61%, 79.78%, 77.55%, 73.89%, 69.98% and 57.02% reduction in the same array (Table 5).

2. Efficacy on the grapevine mealybug in 2020:

The insecticidal activity results obtained in 2020 against the grapevine mealybug were highly similar to our 2019 findings. The data confirm that the time of application has a significant effect on the reduction of the treated mealybugs population already one-week after application.

After the sunset application, the reduction percent of the treated nymph population was differed according to the applied insecticide. The highest reduction percentage was achieved by the used mineral oil (Kz oil) as it caused 87.37% average reduction percent of the treated population and abamectin+thiamethoxam with 85.76% average population reduction of the treated nymphs. Sulfoxaflor, spirotetramat and buprofezin were near to the mixture of abamectin+thiamethoxam in their effect with non-significant difference as they exhibited 83.77%, 84.69% and 82.36% reduction of the treated population, respectively. While imidacloprid and *V. lecanii* were less effective with 76.14 and 60.43% reduction percent, respectively.

During the sunrise application, it was found that after one week, the

reduction in nymphs population was distributed as the used mineral oil was the highest effective with 75.99% reduction, followed by abamectin+thiamethoxam with 73.55% reduction, spirotetramat (72.76%), sulfoxaflor (71.93%), thiamethoxam (70.68%), buprofezin (69.79%), imidacloprid (66.44%) and *V. lecanii* (64.82%) in descending order of activity (Tables 6 and 7).

After two weeks of application, the highest reduction during the sunrise application was achieved by abamectin+thiamethoxam (86.12%) and sulfoxaflor (85.32%) with non-significance between them. The residual effects among the tested insecticides four weeks after the application were the highest in case of the used mineral oil (Kz oil) with 99.08% reduction in the treated nymphs population. This effect was changed according to the tested insecticide as the obtained reduction in the treated nymph population was 96.83%, 94.89%, 93.91%, 91.51%, 92.23%, 78.66% and 66.06% by buprofezin, thiamethoxam, abamectin+thiamethoxam, sulfoxaflor, spirotetramat, imidacloprid and *V. lecanii* in the same arrangement (Tables 6 and 7).

Against the adult females, one week after the sunset application, the highest reduction effect (73.57%) and (71.74%) with non-significance difference between them were due to application of the mineral oil (Kz oil) and the abamectin+thiamethoxam mixture, respectively (Tables 8 and 9). In contrast, the lowest reductions in the adult population were 24.22% and 59.12% are obtained by treatment with *V. lecanii* and imidacloprid insecticides, respectively after one week of sunrise application.

Four weeks after the sunset application, our results showed that the highest effects were achieved by the used mineral oil (92.46%) and

spirotetramat (89.25%) with non significance between them, whereas the least effective insecticide against the adults was *V. lecanii* with 73.02% reduction and imidacloprid with 73.28% reduction in the treated adult population.

From the obtained findings, the results confirm the usefulness of insecticides as a tool to reduce grapevine mealybug nymphs and adults. The data furthermore confirms that the highest reduction against adults was found after four weeks by mineral oil for both the sunrise and sunset application, while *V. lecanii* proved to be the least effective. Overall, we found that the sunset application of the used insecticides was better than the sunrise application for controlling the *P. ficus* population.

This phenomenon is more likely referred to a more effective mode of action of these insecticides during this period on the insects due to the climatic conditions or insect foraging behavior or activity, which makes them more susceptible to the insecticides (Piechowicz and Grodzicki, 2014).

The obtained results agreed with other studies, which found that mineral oils are the most important insecticides for controlling the mealybugs as it blocks the spiracles and trachea through which insects breathe (Helmy *et al.*, 2012). The mineral oil reduced populations of the soft scale insect *Pulvinaria psidii* Maskell (Hemiptera: Coccidae) infesting guava trees by more than 90% after 60 days of treatment (Helmy *et al.*, 2012).

The mineral oils were effective, economically safe, and the pests did not get developing resistance to them (Aly *et al.*, 1984). Similarly, Helmy *et al.*(2012) found that the recommended spray gave satisfactory control of *Leucaspis riccae* Targ (Hemiptera : Diaspididae) and had a moderate effect on *Euphyllura straminea* Loginova

(Hemiptera: Aphalaridae), whereas super misrona (1.5%) had a superior effect (93%) and (88%), respectively, followed by Kz oil and super royal oil.

El-Sahn *et al.* (2007) reported that the mayonnaise oil (Alboleum) achieved the highest population reduction against *Saissetia coffeae* (Walker) (Hemiptera: Coccidae) infesting *Cycas revolute* Thunb (Cycadaceae) till 25 days after spraying. Orange, sesame and jasmine oils were tested against two species of mealybugs, *Icerya seychellarum* (Wes twood) (Hemiptera: Monophelibidae) and *Ferrisia virgata* Cockerell (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae) in guava trees with different concentration, the author found that after application the adults decreased in numbers, also nymphs were recorded as more sensitive than adults (Mohamed and Bakry, 2019).

Synergistic effects have also been investigated with a combination of spirotetramate (12%) + imidacloprid (36 %) 480 SC, spirotetramate 150 OD, imidacloprid 200 SL, thiodicarb 75 WP and profenophos 50 EC tested against the mealybug, *Phenacoccus solenopsis* Tinsley (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae) on Bt cotton during 2007 and 2008 and the results indicated that application of spirotetramate (12%) + imidacloprid (36 %) 480 SC @ 625 ml/ ha was the most effective in control all mealybug tested (El-Sahn *et al.*, 2007).

In contrary study, buprofezin was found to be the most effective insecticide for the control of mealybug on cotton with more than 95% reduction in the pest population 3 days after spraying followed by carbaryl and chloropyriphos (Mohamed and Bakry, 2019).

Laboratory studies on the effect of pesticides against mealybugs give similar results to our field experiment results. The diafenthiuron,

imidacloprid, carbosulfan, methamidophos, acetamiprid and thiamethoxams found to be extremely toxic to *Chrysoperla carnea* (Stephens) (Neuroptera: Chrysopidae) larvae with over 90% mortality after 48 hrs of applying. No successful pupation was recorded after treatment with acetamiprid, whereas successful pupation rate was highest in the buprofezin treated larvae (72%) (Nasreen *et al.*, 2007).

The toxicity of imidacloprid and diafenthiuron to eggs, larvae and adults of *C. carnea* were investigated under laboratory conditions while, the imidacloprid at 0.28 ml/l recommended dose recorded 15% egg mortality and larval mortality by 27% and 33 % after ingestion and contact, respectively, and 50% adult mortality. Whereas, the egg mortality was about 15.38 %, larval mortality of 23.33 % and adult mortality of 26.67% was caused by diafenthiuron (Preetha *et al.*, 2009).

Our work has led us to conclude that the time of application of insecticides has a significant impact on the effective control of the grapevine mealybug, *P. ficus* and the sunset application give the best overall results. The results of this study found that the time of application with a range of different insecticides, applied as foliar treatments, reduced the nymphs and adults of grapevine mealybug, *P. ficus* during the two seasons of 2019 and 2020. We have devised a strategy which increased the effect of insecticides

against *P. ficus*. The sunset application provides a powerful tool for controlling the nymph of the mealybug, *P. ficus*. In addition, the evidence from this study suggests significant differences between all insecticides against *P. ficus* with the most effective being mineral oils four weeks after application.

These different effects may be due to the different mode of action of the tested insecticides as sulfoxaflor (Closer) is nicotinic acetylcholine receptor (nAChR) agonist (Henry *et al.*, 2012), abamectin + thiamethoxam (Agri-flex) affect as GABA and glutamate-gated chloride channel (GluCl) allosteric modulators, nicotinic acetylcholine receptor (nAChR) agonist (Srinivas *et al.*, 2007), while spirotetramat (Movento) works as lipid biosynthesis inhibitor (Growth inhibitor) (Ben-Dov, 1994), imidacloprid (Best) nicotinic acetylcholine receptor (nAChR) agonist (Henderson and Tilton, 1955), buprofezin (Applaud) chitin synthesis disruptor, the *V. lecanii* (Bio-catch) spore of the fungus, when it comes in contact with the cuticle (Skin) of the target pest insect, germinates and grows directly through the spiracle in the cuticle into the inner body of the host, whenever, mineral oils (Kz oils) It makes a thin film around the insect that prevents it from breathing and its ability to excrete waste.

Table (2): Effect of different foliar applied insecticides on the nymph population of grapevine mealybug, *Planococcus ficus* in 2019; shown as mean numbers.

Time of application	Interval (week)	Mean nymphal population numbers/3 plants after different periods of spray								Mean no. of interval days	
		Control	Sulfoxaflor	Abamectin +Thiamethoxam	Spirotetramat	Thiamethoxam	Imidacloprid	Buprofezin	<i>V. lecanii</i>		Kz oil
Sunrise	1	118 b	37.33 gh	32.33 h-k	33.33 g-j	34.66 ghi	39.33 g	34 g-j	79.66 c	27.33 jk	48.44 a
	2	121.33 ab	18.33 mno	17.66 m-p	20.33 lmn	26.0 kl	30.33 ijk	26.33 kl	66 d	17.33 m-p	38.18 b
	3	120.33 ab	11.66 opq	10.33 pq	15.33 m-q	17.0 m-p	27.33 jk	15.66 m-q	58.0e	12 opq	31.96c
	4	124.33 a	13.66 m-q	13 m-q	17.66 m-p	20.66 lm	30.33 ijk	12.66 n-q	46.66 f	9.33 q	32.03 c
	Average	121 a	20.25 ef	18.33 fg	21.66 e	24.58 d	31.83 c	22.16 e	62.58 b	16.5 g	
Sunset	1	117.66 a	31.66 fg	27.66 gh	32.33 fg	36.33 ef	37.66 de	31.66 fg	61 b	27 gh	44.77 a
	2	116 a	15.33 kl	12 klm	12.33 klm	20.66 ij	24.33 hi	21 ij	52.66 c	14 klm	32.03 b
	3	115.66 a	11.33 k-n	7.33mn	11.33 k-n	13.66 klm	16.66 jk	10.66 k-n	41.33 d	8.66 lmn	26.29 c
	4	118 a	12.66 klm	10 k-n	9.33 lmn	13.66 klm	21.33 ij	8.66 lmn	28 gh	5 n	25.18 c
	Average	116.83 a	17.75 e	14.25 f	16.33 e	21.08 d	25 c	18 e	45.75 b	13.66 f	

Average, general mean number of insects; Sulfoxa., Sulfoxaflor; Abamec., Abamectin; Thiameth., Thiamethoxam; Spirot., Spirotetramat; Imidac., Imidacloprid; Buprof., Buprofezin; *V. lecanii*, *Verticillium lecanii*; Mean, Mean no. of interval days. Means followed with the same letter (s) are not significantly different from each other at P= 0.05

Table (3): Effect of different foliar applied insecticides on the nymph population of grapevine mealy-bug, *Planococcus ficus* in 2019; shown as reduction%.

Time of application	Interval (week)	Mean population of the reduction percentage of nymphal stage after different period of spray [†]								Mean no. of interval days
		Sulfoxaflor	Abamectin +Thiamethoxam	Spirotetramat	Thiamethoxam	Imidacloprid	Buprofezin	<i>V. lecanii</i>	Kz oil	
Sunrise	1	68.23 hi	70.13 ghi	69.91 ghi	68.25 hi	65.26 i	70.70 f-i	26.32 m	75.64 e-h	64.31 c
	2	84.84 a-d	84.48 a-d	82.18 b-e	77.40 d-g	73.99 fgh	77.93 def	40.61 l	84.94 a-d	75.80 b
	3	90.29 abc	90.68 ab	86.43 abc	84.81a-d	76.29 efg	86.75 abc	47.35 k	89.55 abc	81.52 a
	4	88.98 abc	88.68 abc	84.87a-d	82.05 cde	74.59 fgh	89.65 abc	58.98 j	92.09 a	82.49 a
	Average	83.08 ab	83.50 ab	80.85 b	78.13c	72.54 d	81.26 b	43.31 e	85.56 a	
Sunset	1	71.18 f-i	72.49 f-i	69.79 g-j	67.81 ij	64.20 j	69.13 hij	47.70 l	75.13 e-h	67.18 c
	2	85.93 bc	87.79 abc	88.39abc	80.40 de	76.68 ef	79.32 de	54.12 k	87.02 bc	79.96 b
	3	89.43 abc	92.68 ab	89.25abc	87.76 abc	83.88 cd	89.43 abc	63.90 j	91.91 ab	86.03 a
	4	88.54 abc	90.07 abc	91.36 abc	87.88 abc	79.80 de	91.58 abc	75.98 efg	95.44 a	87.58 a
	Average	83.77 bc	85.76 ab	84.69 abc	80.97 d	76.14 e	82.36 cd	60.43 f	87.37 a	

Means followed with the same letter (s) are not significantly different from each other at P=0.05. The percentage of the reduction after different periods of spraying.

Table (4): Effect of different foliar applied insecticides on the adult population of grapevine mealybug, *Planococcus ficus* in 2019; shown as mean numbers.

Time of application	Interval (week)	Mean population of adult stage /3 plants after different periods of spray										Mean no. of interval days
		Control	Sulfoxaflor	Abamectin +Thiamethoxam	Spirotetramat	Thiamethoxam	Imidacloprid	Buprofezin	V. <i>lecanii</i>	Kz oil		
Sunrise	1	53.33 a	16.33 f-i	16.33 f-i	16 f-j	18.66 efg	22.66 e	20.33 efg	38.33 b	15 g-j	24.11 a	
	2	55 a	8.66 lm	9 klm	10.66 i-m	14.66 g-k	20.66 ef	15.33 f-j	33.33 c	9.33 klm	19.62 b	
	3	56 a	7.33 lm	6.66 lm	9 klm	11.33 h-m	14.66 g-k	10.33 j-m	29.66 d	7.66 lm	16.96 c	
	4	53.3 a	8.33 lm	8.33 lm	10.33 j-m	11.66 h-l	16.66 fgh	7.66 lm	23.33 e	5.33 m	16.11 c	
	Average	54.41 a	10.16 e	10.08 e	11.5 e	14.08 d	18.66 c	13.41 d	31.16 b	9.33 e		
Sunset	1	55.66 a	16 ef	15.66 ef	16 ef	17.66 de	21.33 cd	17.33 de	28.33 b	14.66 efg	22.51 a	
	2	55 a	9.66 g-j	9.66 g-j	7.33 ijk	14.33 e-h	17.33 de	11.33 f-i	26.66 b	10 g-j	17.92 b	
	3	58 a	7.66 ijk	7 ijk	7 ijk	11 f-i	14 e-h	9.33 h-k	21.66 c	5.66 jk	15.70 c	
	4	57.66 a	9.33 h-k	8.66 ijk	8.66 ijk	11.33 f-i	15.33 ef	10 g-j	14.66 efg	4.33 k	15.55 c	
	Average	56.58 a	10.66 ef	10.25 ef	9.75 f	13.58 d	22.83 b	12 e	22.83 b	8.66 f		

Means followed with the same letter (s) are not significantly different from each other at P=0.05.

Table (5): Effect of different foliar applied insecticides on the adult population of grapevine mealybug, *Planococcus ficus* Signoret in 2019; shown as reduction%.

Time of application	Interval (week)	Mean population of the reduction percentage of nymphal stage after different period of spray										Mean no. of interval days
		Sulfoxaflor	Abamectin +Thiamethoxam	Spirotetramat	Thiamethoxam	Imidacloprid	Buprofezin	V. <i>lecanii</i>	Kz oils			
Sunrise	1	67.40 cd	69.42 cd	67.77 cd	64.42 de	55.64 ef	62.61 de	22.18 i	71.59 bcd	60.13 c		
	2	83.38 ab	83.85 ab	79.11 abc	72.74 bcd	60.81 def	72.75 bcd	34.44 h	82.42 ab	71.19 b		
	3	86.10 a	88.25 a	82.78 ab	79.16 abc	72.38 bcd	81.85 ab	42.48 g	85.80 a	77.35 a		
	4	83.47 ab	84.47 ab	79.19 abc	77.87 abc	67.31 cd	85.91 a	52.59 f	89.88 a	77.59 a		
	Average	80.09 abc	81.50 ab	77.21 bcd	73.55 d	64.04 e	75.78 cd	37.92 f	82.42 a			
Sunset	1	69.35 i-l	71.74 h-k	68.07 jkl	65.60 kl	61.96 l	67.15 jkl	45.91 m	73.57 f-k	65.42 c		
	2	81.29 b-g	82.31 b-g	85.01 a-e	71.69 h-k	68.74 jkl	78.14 d-i	48.62 m	81.78 b-g	74.70 b		
	3	85.75 a-e	87.81 a-d	86.37 a-d	79.56 d-h	75.94 e-j	83.08 b-f	60.54 l	90.26 ab	81.16 a		
	4	82.72 b-g	84.59 a-e	89.25 abc	78.71 d-i	73.28 f-k	81.85 b-g	73.02 g-k	92.46 a	81.98 a		
	Average	79.78 bc	81.61 ab	82.18 ab	73.89 d	69.98 e	77.55 c	57.02 f	84.51 a			

Means followed with the same letter (s) are not significantly different from each other at P=0.05.

Table (6): Effect of different foliar applied insecticides on the nymph population of grapevine mealybug, *Planococcus ficus* in 2020; shown as mean numbers. Mean population of nymph stage/3 plants after different periods of spray

Time of application	Interval (week)	Mean population of nymph stage/3 plants after different periods of spray								Mean no. of interval days	
		Control	Sulfoxaflor	Abamectin +Thiamethoxa m	Spirotetramat	Thiamethoxam	Imidacloprid	Buprofezin	V. <i>lecanii</i>		Mineral oils
Sunrise	1	66.66 b	17 gh	17 gh	17 gh	17 gh	20 fg	20 fg	43 c	16 gh	25.96 a
	2	67.33 b	9 j-m	9 j-m	9.66 jkl	11.33 jkl	14.33 hi	13.66 hi	38 d	9.66 jkl	20.22 b
	3	72 a	5.33 l-o	4.66 m-p	6.33 l-o	7.66 k-n	13 hij	7 lmn	31 e	4.33 nop	16.81 c
	4	73.33 a	5.66 l-o	4.33 nop	5.33 l-o	3.33 nop	14 hi	2.33 op	22 f	0.66 p	14.55 d
Sunset	Average	69.83 a	9.25 def	8.75 ef	9.58 de	9.83 de	15.33 c	10.75 d	33.5 b	7.66 f	
	1	87.33 b	22.66 ghi	20 ij	24.33 fg	23.66 fgh	26.66 f	24.33 fg	42 c	20.66 hij	32.40 a
	2	87.33 b	10.66 no	9 opq	8.66 o-r	14.66 lm	18.33 jk	13.33 mn	35 d	10 op	23 b
	3	89.66 b	6.66 p-s	5 rs	8 o-s	8.66 o-r	13 mn	6.33 p-s	31.33 e	4.66 s	19.25 c
Sunset	4	92 a	6.66 p-s	5.66 qrs	6.66 p-s	9.66 op	16.66 kl	5.33 qrs	22.66 ghi	2.0 t	18.59 c
	Average	89.08 a	11.66 e	9.91 f	11.91 e	14.16 d	18.66 c	12.33 e	32.75 b	9.33 f	

Means followed with the same letter (s) are not significantly different from each other at P= 0.05.

Table (7): Effect of different foliar applied insecticides on the nymph population of grapevine mealy-bug, *Planococcus ficus* Signoret in 2020; shown as reduction%.

Time of application	Interval (week)	Mean population of the reduction percentage of nymphal stage after different period of spray								Mean no. of interval days
		Sulfoxaflor	Abamectin +Thiamethoxam	Spirotetramat	Thiamethoxam	Imidacloprid	Buprofezin	V. <i>lecanii</i>	Kz oil	
Sunrise	1	71.93 lm	73.55 jkl	72.76 kl	70.68 lmn	66.44 mn	69.79 lmn	64.82 n	75.99 i-l	70.75 d
	2	85.32 d-g	86.12 d-g	84.60 e-h	81.64 f-i	76.05 ijkl	79.61 g-j	36.62 p	85.60 d-g	76.95 c
	3	91.88 bcd	93.30 abc	90.52 b-e	87.83 c-f	79.67 g-j	90.25 b-e	51.60 o	93.99 abc	84.88 b
	4	91.51 b-e	93.91 abc	92.23 bcd	94.89 abc	78.66 h-k	96.83 ab	66.06 mn	99.08 a	89.15 a
Sunset	Average	85.16 b	86.72 ab	85.03 b	83.76 b	75.20 c	84.12 b	54.78 d	88.67 a	
	1	71.18 f-i	72.49 f-i	69.79 g-j	67.81 ij	64.20 j	69.13 hij	47.70 l	75.13 e-h	67.18 c
	2	85.93 bc	87.79 abc	88.39 abc	80.40 de	76.68 ef	79.32 de	54.12 k	87.02 bc	79.96 b
	3	89.43 abc	92.68 ab	89.25 abc	87.76 abc	83.88 cd	89.43 abc	63.90 j	91.91 ab	86.03 a
Sunset	4	88.54 abc	90.07 abc	91.36 abc	87.88 abc	79.80 de	91.58 abc	75.98 efg	95.44 a	87.58 a
	Average	83.77 bc	85.76 ab	84.69 abc	80.97 d	76.14 e	82.36 cd	60.43 f	87.37 a	

Means followed with the same letter (s) are not significantly different from each other at P= 0.05.

Table (8): Effect of different foliar applied insecticides on the adult population of grapevine mealybug, *Planococcus ficus* in 2020; shown as mean numbers.

Time of application	Interval (week)	Mean population of adult stage/3 plants after different periods of spray										Mean no. of interval of days
		Control	Sulfoxaflor	Abamectin+Thiamethoxam	Spirotetramat	Thiamethoxam	Imidacloprid	Buprofezin	<i>V. lecanii</i>	Kz oil		
Sunrise	1	28.66 b	8.66 fgh	7.33 f-i	7 g-j	9 fg	10 ef	10 ef	18 c	7.33 f-i	11.77 a	
	2	28.66 b	4.33 j-n	3.66 k-n	4 k-n	7.66 fgh	9 fg	6.33 g-k	13.66 d	4.66 i-m	9.11 b	
	3	29 b	3.33 lmn	2.33 mn	3 lmn	6 h-l	6 h-l	4.33 j-n	12 de	3 lmn	7.66 c	
	4	32.66 a	4 klm	3 lmn	3.66 k-n	3 lmn	8fgh	2.33 mn	10 ef	1.33 n	7.55 c	
Sunset	Average	29.75 a	5.08 ef	4.08 f	4.41 f	6.41 d	8.25 c	5.75 de	13.41 b	4.08 f		
	1	40.33 b	11.33 gh	11 hi	11.66 gh	12.33 fgh	14.66 ef	14 efg	22 c	10 h-k	16.37 a	
	2	40 b	5.66 l-p	5 m-p	4.33 nop	14.66 ef	11.66 gh	8 j-m	18.66 d	6.33 l-o	12.70 b	
	3	41.66 ab	4.33 nop	3.66 op	4.33 nop	6.66 l-o	8.33 i-l	5.33 l-p	15.33 e	3.33 op	10.33 c	
	4	43.33 a	5.33 l-p	4.33 nop	4.66 nop	7.66 k-n	10 h-k	4.66 nop	10.66 hij	2.33 p	10.33 c	
Average	41.33 a	6.66 e	6 e	6.25 e	10.33 c	11.16 c	8 d	16.66 b	5.5 e			

Means followed with the same letter (s) are not significantly different from each other at P= 0.05.

Table (9): Effect of different foliar applied insecticides on the adult population of grapevine mealybug, *Planococcus ficus* in 2020; shown as reduction %.

Time of application	Interval (week)	Mean population of the reduction percentage of nymphal stage after different period of spray									
		Sulfoxaflor	Abamectin +Thiamethoxam	Spirotetramat	Thiamethoxam	Imidacloprid	Buprofezin	<i>V. lecanii</i>	Kz oil	Mean no. of interval days	
Sunrise	1	69.08 fgh	71.28 fgh	70.56 fgh	67.51 ghi	59.12 i	63.77 hi	24.22 l	73.09 fgh	62.33 d	
	2	84.49 a-e	85.49 a-e	83.41 b-e	72.44 fgh	63.29 hi	77.08 defg	42.27 k	82.81 b-e	73.91 c	
	3	88.24 abc	90.75 ab	87.69 a-d	78.71 c-f	75.81 efg	84.51 a-e	49.93 j	89.24 abc	80.61 b	
	4	87.49 a-d	89.12 abc	85.77 a-e	90.61 ab	71.36 fgh	92.62 ab	62.55 hi	95.81 a	84.42 a	
Sunset	Average	82.32 ab	84.16 a	81.86 ab	77.32 c	67.40 d	79.50 bc	44.74 e	85.24 a		
	1	69.35 i-l	71.74 h-k	68.073 jkl	65.60 kl	61.96 l	67.15 jkl	45.91 m	73.57 f-k	65.42 c	
	2	81.29 b-g	82.31 b-g	85.01 a-e	71.69 h-k	68.74 jkl	78.14 d-i	48.62 m	81.78 b-g	74.70 b	
	3	85.75 a-e	87.81 a-d	86.37 a-d	79.56 c-h	75.94 e-j	83.08 b-f	60.54 l	90.26 ab	81.16 a	
	4	82.72 b-g	84.59 a-e	89.25 abc	78.71 d-i	73.28 f-k	81.85 b-g	73.02 g-k	92.46 a	81.98 a	
Average	79.78 bc	81.61 ab	82.16 ab	73.89 d	69.98 e	77.55 c	57.02 f	84.51 a			

Means followed with the same letter (s) are not significantly different from each other at P= 0.05.

References

- Aly, A.G.; El Attal, Z. M. and Helmy, I. (1984):** Efficiency of some local spray oils as summer-applications against *Pulvinaria psidii* on guava trees [Egypt]. In Proceedings of the General Conference of Agricultural Research Centre. Giza (Egypt), 9-11.
- Ben-Dov, Y. (1994):** A systematic catalogue of the mealybugs of the world (Insecta: Homoptera: Coccoidea: Pseudococcidae and Putoidea) with data on geographical distribution, host plants, biology and economic importance; Intercept Limited, 1994, pp 686; ISBN 1898298076.
- Charles, J. G. (1982):** Economic damage and preliminary economic thresholds for mealybugs (*Pseudococcus longispinus* TT.) in Auckland vineyards. New Zeal. J. Agric. Res., 25: 415–420.
- Charles, J. G. (1985):** *Diadiplosis koebelei* Koebele (Diptera: Cecidomyiidae), a predator of *Pseudococcus longispinus* TT. (Homoptera: Pseudococcidae), newly recorded from New Zealand. New Zeal. J. Zool., 12: 331–333.
- da Silva, V. C. P.; Bertin, A.; Blin, A.; Germain, J. F.; Bernardi, D.; Rignol, G.; Botton, M. and Malausa, T. (2014):** Molecular and morphological identification of mealybug species (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae) in Brazilian vineyards. PLoS One, 9 (10): 32-67.
- Daane, K. M.; Almeida, R. P. P.; Bell, V. A.; Walker, J. T. S.; Botton, M.; Fallahzadeh, M.; Mani, M.; Miano, J. L.; Sforza, R. and Walton, V. M. (2012):** Biology and management of mealybugs in vineyards. In *Arthropod Management in Vineyards*, Springer, 271–307.
- Daane, K.; Bentley, W.; Walton, V.; Malakar-Kuenen, R.; Millar, J.; Ingels, C.; Weber, E. and Gispert, C. (2006):** New controls investigated for vine mealybug. Calif. Agric., 60: 31–38.
- El-Sahn, O. M. N.; Hemeida, I. A.; Elshabrawy, H. A. and Helmy, E.I.M. (2007):** Studies on *Parlatoria pergandii* Comstock and *Saissetia coffeae* (Walker) infesting certain ornamental plants, Ph D., Faculty of Agriculture, Cairo University.
- Essig, E.O. (1914):** The mealybugs of California. Mon. Bull. Calif. State Comm. Hort., 3: 18–143.
- FAOSTAT (Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations) (2019):** <http://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data>. Accessed 12 Jan.
- Flaherty, D.; Peacock, W.; Bettiga, L. and Leavitt, G. (1982):** Chemicals losing effect against grape mealybug. Calif. Agric., 36: 15–16.
- Franco, J. C.; Zada, A. and Mendel, Z. (2009):** Novel approaches for the management of mealybug pests. In *Biorational control of arthropod pests*; Springer: pp. 233–278.
- Frick, K. E. (1952):** The value of some organic phosphate insecticides in control of grape mealybug. J. Econ. Entomol., 45: 340–341.
- García, M. M.; Denno, B.D.; Miller, D.R.; Miller, G.L.; Ben-Dov, Y. and Hardy, N.B. (2016):** Scale Net: a literature-based model of scale insect biology and systematics. Database.
- Güleç, G. ; Kilincer, N. ; Kaydan, M. B. and Ülgentürk, S. (2007):** Some biological interactions between the parasitoid *Anagyrus*

- pseudococci* (Girault) (Hymenoptera: Encyrtidae) and its host *Planococcus ficus* (Signoret) (Hemiptera: Coccoidea: Pseudococcidae). Journal of Pest Science, 80(1):43-49.
- Hassan, N. A.; Radwan, S.G. and El-Sahn, O.M.N. (2012):** Common scale insects (Hemiptera: Coccoidea) in Egypt. Egypt. Acad. J. Biol. Sci., 5: 153–160.
- Helmy, E. I.; Kwaiz, F. A. and El-Sahn, O.M.N. (2012).** The usage of mineral oils to control insects. Egypt. Acad. J. Biol. Sci. Entomol., 5: 167–174.
- Henderson, C.F. and Tilton, E.W. (1955):** Tests with acaricides against the brown wheat mite. J. Econ. Entomol., 48: 157–161.
- Henry, M.; Beguin, M.; Requier, F.; Rollin, O.; Odoux, J. F.; Aupinel, P.; Aptel, J.; Tchamitchian, S. and Decourtye, A. (2012):** A common pesticide decreases foraging success and survival in honey bees. Science, 80 (336): 348–350.
- Lo, P. L. and Walker, J. T. S. (2010):** Good results from a soil-applied insecticide against mealybugs. NZ Winegrower, 14: 125–127.
- Mansour, R.; Grissa-Lebdi, K.; Suma, P.; Mazzeo, G. and Russo, A. (2017):** Key scale insects (Hemiptera: Coccoidea) of high economic importance in a Mediterranean area: host plants, bio-ecological characteristics, natural enemies and pest management strategies—a review. Plant Prot. Sci., 53: 1–14.
- Mohamed, L.H.Y. and Bakry, M.M.S. (2019):** Insecticidal efficiency of some insect growth regulators (IGRs) and plant oils against the seychellarum mealybug, *Icerya seychellarum* and the striped mealy bug, *Ferrisia virgata* infesting guava trees. Curr. Invest. Agric. Curr. Res., 3: 930–936.
- Nasreen, A.; Ashfaq, M.; Mustafa, G. and Khan, R.R. (2007):** Mortality rates of five commercial insecticides on *Chrysoperla carnea* (Stephens)(Chrysopidae: Neuroptera). Pak. J. Agric. Sci., 44 (2): 266- 271.
- Piechowicz, B. and Grodzicki, P. (2014):** Circadian changes in susceptibility of various species of Gryllidae to insecticides, depending on time of intoxication and size of tested group. Pol. J. Environ. Stud., 23: 1861.
- Preetha, G.; Johnson, S.; Manoharan, T.; Chandrasekaran, S. and Kuttalam, S. (2009):** Toxicity of imidacloprid and diafenthiuron to *Chrysoperla carnea* (Stephens) (Neuroptera: Chrysopidae) in the laboratory conditions. J. plant Prot. Res., 49 (3): 290 - 296.
- Rajagopal, B.K.; Viraktamath, C.A. and Nache Gowda, V. (1997):** Incidence of ant associated mealy bug, *Xenococcus annandalei* (Homoptera: Pseudococcidae) on grapes in South India. Entomon-Trivandrum, 22: 165–166.
- Reineke, A. and Thiéry, D. (2016):** Grapevine insect pests and their natural enemies in the age of global warming. J. Pest Sci., 89: 313–328.
- Sazo, L.; Araya, J. E. and de la Cerda, J. (2008):** Effect of a silicate adjuvant and insecticides in the control of mealybug of grapevines, *Pseudococcus viburni* (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae). Cien. Inv. Agr., 35 (2): 215-222.

- Sforza, R.; Kirk, A. and Jones, W.A. (2005):** Results of foreign exploration for natural enemies of *Planococcus ficus* (Hom.: Pseudococcidae), a new invasive mealybug in California vineyards. In Proceedings of the AFPP-7EME Conference International Sur Les Ravageurs en Agriculture, pp. 26–27.
- Srinivas, T.; Prasad, K.S.; Shekhar, M.A. and Manjunath, D. (2007):** Evaluation on neem based formulations vis-a-vis dichlorvos against *Maconellicoccus hirsutus*. Uttar Pradesh J. Zool.:13–20.
- Sunitha, N.D.; Jagginavar, S.B. and Biradar, A.P. (2009):** Bio efficacy botanicals and newer insecticides against grape vine mealy bug, *Maconellicoccus hirsutus* (Green). Karnataka J. Agric. Sci., 22: 710–711.
- Tsai, C. W.; Bosco, D.; Daane, K.M. and Almeida, R.P.P. (2011):** Effect of host plant tissue on the vector transmission of Grapevine leafroll-associated virus 3. *J. Econ. Entomol.*, **104**: 1480–1485.
- Walton, V. M.; Krüger, K.; Saccaggi, D. L.; Millar, I.M. and Michaud, J. P. (2009):** A survey of scale insects (Sternorrhyncha: Coccoidea) occurring on table grapes in South Africa. *J. Insect Sci.*, **9** (47): 1-6.
- Williams, D.J. and Watson, G.W. (1988):** Scale insects of the tropical South Pacific region. Part 2. Mealybugs (Pseudococcidae).; CAB International, pp 260.

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Preparation of some safe synthetic botanical materials as fumigant tablets as alternatives for hazard phostoxin for controlling cowpea beetle *Callosobruchus maculatus* (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) infesting leguminaceous seeds

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Abstract:

Although phostoxin fumigant tablets are considered the best material for controlling cowpea beetle for their ease of use and the most successful material against this pest it has undesirable and hazardous effects against man, beneficial animals and insects, this research was completed for preparation of the two safe botanical materials, thymol and camphor as fumigant tablets and evaluation their effect against cowpea beetle as a solution of damage effect of phostoxin. Both botanical materials were prepared as pure and mixed with the anti-releasing agent, talc or bee wax at ratios 80:20 and 65:35 (botanical: anti-releasing agent) as fumigant tablet which their diameter was 13 mm and 0.3 mm height. The initial effect was determined by exposure cowpea beetles *Callosobruchus maculatus* (Fabricius) (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) adults, three days and determination % mortality and the residual effect was examined after 1, 2 and 3 months only for the lowest concentration which succeeded in initial effect, i.e. which after three days of exposure, adults died in 100 percent. Results obtained indicated that camphor was very highly effective than thymol in initial effect since it gave 100 % mortality at 0.03 gm/120 ml (wt./v.) while thymol gave 100 % mortality rate at 0.4 gm/120 ml (wt./v.). Results of residual effect indicated that the succeeded concentration in initial effect gave 100 % mortality in their residual effect up to three months storage. Results indicated also that treatment with botanical tablets protected cowpea seeds germination which was very high than untreated infested seeds since the larvae burrow in seeds and destroy endosperms then reduce germination. For economic consideration, it could be recommended camphor at 0.03 gm/120 ml for controlling cowpea beetle infesting leguminaceous seeds.

Introduction

Stored grain insects are a worldwide concern because they decrease grain quantity and quality. Their harm to stored grains and their products may be 5–10% in the temperate environment and 20–30% in

a tropical environment (Haque *et al.*, 2000). While tropical areas, insect pests cause the loss of stored food grains also semitropical settings (Tripathi *et al.*, 2001). As a result, there is a requirement for a variety of acceptable pesticides or repellents for use on food

grains. In general, synthetic pesticides and fumigation are the primary ways of pest management in stored products. Cowpea *Vigna unguiculata* (L.) is among the most well-known cost-effective legume seeds, having a high protein, vitamin, and mineral content (Singh *et al.*, 2003).

Cowpea beetle *Callosobruchus maculatus* (Fabricius) (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) is regarded as one among the most popular damaging brushed species of various legumes, including cowpea, in the world's tropic and subtropical areas (Babarinde *et al.*, 2016). Inside the seeds, the larval and pupal stages grow. The larvae burrow into the seed, destroying the endosperm (Adenekan *et al.*, 2018). It destroys 25% of seeds, reducing germination by up to 13% and lowering the market value after six months of storage (Haile, 2006). Phostoxin fumigant tablets are used at a large scale for controlling leguminous beetles, stored grain insects as it easy for application and very effective against this pest.

Unfortunately, phostoxin is very toxic to man, therefore efforts should be directed towards finding more safe materials to be used instead of phostoxin for controlling cowpea beetle. Previous researches indicated that both thymol and camphor have fumigant effect against stored grain insects (Rozman *et al.* (2006), Negahban *et al.* (2007), Abdelgaleil *et al.* (2009), Chu *et al.* (2010), Liska *et al.* (2010), Hossain *et al.* (2014) and Wahba *et al.* (2018).

The goal of this research is the preparation of those safe botanical materials thymol and camphor alone or mixed with anti-releasing agents (Bee wax and talc) as fumigant tablets as alternatives to hazard phostoxin for controlling cowpea beetle.

Materials and methods

1. Botanical materials:

1.1. Thymol (99%)

- IUPAC name: 2-Isopropyl-5-methylphenol

Thymol (2-isopropyl-5-methylphenol) is a natural monoterpene phenol derivative of cymene, C₁₀H₁₄O. The melting point is 51°C boiling point is 232 °C and solubility in water (Insoluble in water). Produced by: Alpha Chemika, India. Supplied by El-Goumouria Co. for Trading Medicines, Chemicals and Medical Appliances Importation Department 32 El Sawah Str., Cairo, Egypt.

1.2. Camphor (99%):

- IUPAC name: (1, 7, 7-Tri methyl bicycle [2.2.1] heptan-2-one). Camphor is a waxy, white or transparent solid with a strong, aromatic odor. It is a terpenoid with the chemical formula C₁₀H₁₆O. Melting point is 175-181°C and Boiling point is 204°C. Produced by: S.D. (Fine.Chem. limited), India. Supplied by: El-Goumouria Co. for trading Medicines, Chemicals and Medical Appliances Importation Department 32 El Sawah Str., Cairo, Egypt.

1.3. Anti-releasing agent:

1.3.1. Talc powder: (Magnesium meta silicate): it was supplied by El-Nasr Co. for Phosphate, Cairo, Egypt. Talc is a mineral composed of hydrated magnesium silicate with the chemical formula H₂Mg₃ (SiO₃)₄ or Mg₃Si₄O₁₀ (OH)₂.

1.3.2. Bee wax: It was supplied from Bee Pest's Research Department, Plant Protection Research Institute.

2. Cowpea beetle culture:

The rearing technique for stock culture and experimental insects was, according to Kalifa and Badawy (1961), preparing and conditioning of seeds was, according to Selim (1963) and Abdel-Kawy (1979). For starting a culture of testing, insect, adult cowpea beetle, *Callosobruchus maculatus* reared on cowpea seeds in a glass jar (Each of approximately 500 ml) and each jar was covered with

muslin cloths and fixed with rubber bands. Approximately 500 adults were placed in jars containing seeds for egg-laying and then housed in an incubator at $30\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $65\pm 5\%$ RH. to create an initial population of insect adults that were all the same age. All insects were removed from the media after three days, and the jars were returned to controlled conditions.

The seeds were regularly observed for lay eggs and subsequent adult emergence. Hatched eggs were known by the presence of larval frass which causes the egg to turn milky–white as larvae tunnel into the seeds for larvae and pupae age calculated. The insect was reared in the Department of Stored Products and Grains Pests of the Plant Protection Research Institute of the Agricultural Research Centre in Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

3. Preparation of thymol and camphor as fumigant tablets:

Each botanical material was used alone (100%) and mixed with bee wax and talc as an anti-releasing agent at two concentrations 80% and 65% active ingredient. Active ingredient alone or mixed with an anti-releasing agent more melted using heat, mixed well then poured in circle plastic vessel has 13 mm diameter and 0.3 cm high, after $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. formed tablets were turned off from the plastic vessel and stored in plastic sheet up to biological tests. Five different fumigant tablets were prepared for each botanical material:

3.1. Botanical alone (100%).

3.2. Botanical+ wax (80%).

3.3. Botanical+ wax (65%).

3.4. Botanical+ talc (80%).

3.5. Botanical+ talc (65%).

4. Initial the efficacy of the prepared fumigant tablets against cowpea beetle adults:

To study the initial effect of the tested materials, 20g of cowpea seeds were translated to small container 120 ml capacity seeds and immediately

infested with 20 adult insects of *C. maculatus* then different weights of the prepared fumigant tablets were added. Three replicates for each weight compared with untreated. The jars were covered with caps, dead and alive adults were counted after 3 days of exposure and mortality percentages were calculated according to (Abbott, 1925).

5. Determination of the insecticidal effect against immature stages of cowpea beetle:

The effect of treating immature stages of the cowpea beetle with fumigant tablets on adult emerging was carried out according to Shemais *et al.* (2002) by placing adults on cowpea seeds for one day to lay eggs. Fumigant tablets were added after 1 day of laying eggs for 3 days to study the latent effect on the egg stage also, fumigant tablets were added after 12 (As a larva) and 24 days (As pupa) from laying of the eggs for 7 days to study the latent effect on larvae and pupae, both of hatching egg and emerged adults were counted.

6. Determination of the residual effect of the prepared fumigant tablets of cowpea beetle:

It was determined for cowpea seeds stored with different weights of tablets after 1, 2 and 3 months of treatments by the same test mentioned materials according (Abdelfattah and Zein, 2019).

7. Determination of the residual effect on the viability of cowpea seeds (Germination test):

The germination test was carried out under laboratory conditions to evaluate the effect of thymol and camphor on cowpea seeds after 1, 2 and 3 months of storage. 20 seeds were randomly picked from treated and untreated groups and placed on a surface layer of cotton wool in a petri dish (6×1 cm) which was wetted careful with tap water. Seeds were set up in a three-replicate, entirely random design. After 7 days later the germination

percentage was calculated (AL-Akhdar *et al.*, 2019).

Results and discussion

1. Initial effect on adults:

Results in Table (1) about the initial effect of treatment with fumigant tablets of thymol for 3 days on cowpea adults indicated that concentration 0.4 gm gave 100% for all thymol tablets while at 0.3 gm, a mixture of thymol with talc showed the highest toxic effect than a mixture with wax, therefore mixing thymol with talc is preferred than mixing with wax. On the other

hand, results presented in Table (2) about the effect of camphor fumigant tablets against cowpea beetle adults, indicated that all tested concentrations up to 0.03 gm for all camphor mixture succeeded in their initial toxicity since they gave 100% mortality. As general results of Tables (1 and 2), it could be said that camphor fumigant tablets are more active than thymol.

Table (1): Initial toxicity of fumigation with different concentration of thymol prepared as fumigant tablets against adult of *Callosobruchus maculatus*.

Treatment	% mortality					
	1 gm	0.5 gm	0.4 gm	0.3gm	0.2gm	0.1 gm
Wax 80%	100	100	100	77.5	95	65
Wax 65%	100	100	100	87.5	41.5	40
Talc 80%	100	100	100	100	95	65
Talc 65%	100	100	100	95	65	45
Pure	100	100	100	100	100	100
Control	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0

Table (2): Initial toxicity of fumigation with different concentration of camphor prepared as fumigant tablets against adult of *Callosobruchus maculatus*.

Treatment	% mortality					
	0.25gm	0.12 gm	0.06 gm	0.03 gm	0.02 gm	0.01 gm
Wax 80%	100	100	100	100	75	0.0
Wax 65%	100	100	100	100	25	0.0
Talc 80%	100	100	100	100	100	0.0
Talc 65%	100	100	100	100	17.5	0.0
Pure	100	100	100	100	100	25
Control	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0

2. Latent effect against immature stages:

2.1. First experiment:

The lowest concentrations which gave 100% mortality against adults were tested against immature stages eggs, larvae and pupae by the methods mentioned before. Results in the Table (3) indicated that all tested materials succeeded against the egg stage since no adults emerged in egg treatments except in camphor wax 65% and camphor talc 65%, but all treatments failed against larvae and

pupae stages since they did not prevent an adult emergency, therefore the second experiment was carried at more higher concentrations 1g thymol and 0.25g for camphor.

2.2. Second experiment:

Results in Table (4) about the latent effect of cowpea beetle egg with fumigant tablets for 3 days with thymol at 1 gm and camphor at 0.25 gm /120 ml, results obtained indicated that no adult emerged in all treating with thymol and camphor.

Table (3): The effect of treatments against immature stages of cowpea beetle fumigated until adult emerged.

Treatment		Egg		Larva		Pupa	
		Emerged adult no	Reduction%	Emerged adult no	Reduction %	Emerged adult no	Reduction %
Thymol	Wax 80% 0.4 g	0.0	100	46.5	43.6	65	21.2
	Wax 65% 0.4 g	0.0	100	43.5	47.3	82	0.6
	Talc 80% 0.3 g	0.0	100	49	40.6	82	0.6
	Talc 65% 0.4 g	0.0	100	63.5	23	54	34.5
	Pure 0.1	0.0	100	64	22.4	80.5	2.4
Camphor	Wax 80% 0.03 g	0.0	100	14	83.5	22.5	72.7
	Wax 65% 0.03 g	7.0	77.8	23.5	71.5	41	50.3
	Talc 80% 0.02 g	0.0	100	11	86.6	44	46.6
	Talc 65% 0.04 g	0.3	99	46	44.2	13	84.2
	Pure 0.02 g	0.0	100	4	95	15	82
Control		31.5		82.5	43.6	82.5	

Table (4): Latent effect of treatment of *Callosobruchus maculatus* eggs with fumigation tablets for 3 days.

Treatment		Mean No. of eggs	Hatched %	Pupation %	Adult emergence %	Reduction %
Thymol 1 gm /120 ml	Wax 80%	111.33	7.41	0	0	100
	Wax 65%	98.67	2.1	0	0	100
	Talc 80%	106.67	7.27	0	0	100
	Talc 65%	88	3.68	0.75	0	100
	Pure	106.33	13.33	0.31	0	100
Champhor 0.25 gm /120 ml	Wax 80%	158.33	18.45	5.89	0	100
	Wax 65%	125	10.25	5.06	0	100
	Talc 80%	89.33	25.46	2.98	0	100
	Talc 65%	125	7.64	2.66	0	100
	Pure	113	1.29	0	0	100
Control		115.33	100	87.58	79.63	20.37

As shown in Table (5) about the treatment of cowpea beetle larva and pupa with fumigant tablets for 7 days with thymol at 1 gm and camphor at 0.25 gm., results obtained indicated that no adult emerged in case of treating

larva with thymol and camphor, while in case of pupa treatment all concentration except mixing thymol with wax 80% and camphor with talc 65% gave 100% reduction in an adult emergency.

Table (5): Latent effect of thymol and camphor prepared as fumigant tablets against larva and pupa stages of *Callosobruchus maculatus* for 7 days.

Treatment		Larva		Pupa	
		% adult emergence	Reduction %	% adult emergence	Reduction %
Thymol 1 gm /120 ml	Wax 80%	0	100	50	50
	Wax 65%	0	100	0	100
	Talc 80%	0	100	0	100
	Talc 65%	0	100	0	100
	Pure	0	100	0	100
Champhor 0.25 gm/120 ml	Wax 80%	0	100	0	100
	Wax 65%	0	100	0	100
	Talc` 80%	0	100	0	100
	Talc 65%	0	100	12	88
	Pure	0	100	0	100
Control		100		100	

3. Residual effect of botanical materials against cowpea beetle:

This test was carried out by concentrations that only succeeded in initial effecting against adults and immature stages to determine its ability to protect cowpea seeds from *C. maculatus*

for long periods. As shown in Table (6) all tested concentrations of thymol or camphor fumigant tablets gave complete protection of cowpea seeds up to 3 months of a treatment since they gave 100% mortality against adults.

Table (6): Residual effect of thymol and camphor prepared as fumigant tablets against adults of *Callosobruchus maculatus* on cowpea seeds.

Treatment		1 month (%)	2 months (%)	3 months (%)
Thymol 1gm / 120 ml	Wax 80%	100	100	100
	Wax 65%	100	100	100
	Talc 80%	100	100	100
	Talc 65%	100	100	100
	Pure	100	100	100
Champhor 0.25 gm / 120 ml	Wax 80%	100	100	100
	Wax 65%	100	100	100
	Talc` 80%	100	100	100
	Talc 65%	100	100	100
	Pure	100	100	100
Control		0	0	0

Results obtained well agree with Rozman *et al.* (2006) about the fumigant effect of camphor against rusty grain beetle and *S. oryzae*, also with Abdelgaleil *et al.* (2009) against rice weevil *S.oryzae*, Chu *et al.* (2010) about camphor maize weevil and Hossain *et al.* (2014) about camphor

against *S. oryzae*. The results are compiled also with Wahba *et al.* (2018) about the fumigation effect of thymol against the cowpea beetle.

4. Residual effect on cowpea seeds:

Results in the Table (7) about the effect of all treatments on cowpea germination in case botanical materials

were very high than untreated infested control seeds since larvae burrow into the seed and destroy its endosperm then reducing germination. Germination in case camphor was more than thymol, camphor + talc showed the highest

value followed by camphor + wax, while thymol + wax (80:20) showed the lowest value of germination followed by thymol + wax (65:35) while in case of thymol + talc showed the highest value of all thymol treatments.

Table (7): Residual effect of botanical materials on cowpea seeds germination percentage.

Treatment		1 month (%)	2 months (%)	3 months (%)
Thymol 1 gm / 120 ml	Wax 80%	46.66	46.66	31
	Wax 65%	76.66	76.66	66.5
	Talc 80%	93.3	93.3	88.5
	Talc 65%	95	95	90
	Pure	53.3	53.3	40
Champhor 0.25 gm / 120 ml	Wax 80%	96.7	96.7	95
	Wax 65%	97.66	97.66	95
	Talc 80%	100	100	96
	Talc 65%	100	100	97
	Pure	100	100	96.7
Infested Control		38	33.3	0
Uninfested Control		100	100	100

5. Mode of action:

The mode of action of the tested materials may be due to one or more of the following: -Respiration effect as mentioned by De-Oliveira *et al.* (1997) and Lee *et al.* (2001 b). -Fumigation effect as mentioned by Lee *et al.* (2001a), Negahban *et al.* (2007) and Jayakumar *et al.* (2017). -Inhibition of acetyl cholinesterase as mentioned by Lee *et al.* (2001a). -Repellent effect as mentioned by Nerio *et al.* (2010).

It could be concluded that both thymol and camphor prepared as fumigant tablets were active against cowpea beetle and showed complete protective effect up to 3 months after treatment, the study proved also that camphor was more active than thymol on the other hand the anti-releasing agent talc was better than wax.

As a general recommendation, it could be recommended with camphor prepared as fumigant tablet at 0.25gm/120 ml as an alternative to the danger phostoxin for controlling cowpea beetle, also more experiments at large scale with this recommended

concentration and lower concentration should be carried out.

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References

- Abbott, W.S. (1925):** A method of computing the effectiveness of an insecticide, *J. Econ., Entomol.*, 18:265-270.
- Abdelfattah, N.A.H. and Zein, D. M. (2019):** Biological studies and toxicity experiments of AEROSIL 200 nanoparticles on adults and larvae of some stored grain insects. *International Journal of Entomology Research*, 4 (1) : 103-108.

- Abdelgaleil, S.A.M; Mohamed, M.I.E.; Badawy, M.E.I. and Elarami, S.A.A. (2009):** Fumigant and contact toxicities of monoterpenes to *Sitophilus oryzae* (L.) and *Tribolium castaneum* (Herbst) and their inhibitory effects on acetylcholinesterase activity. J. Chem. Ecol., 35: 518–525.
- Abdel-Kawy, F.K. (1979):** Studies on the effect of gamma irradiation on the different development stages of the khapre, beetle, *Trogoderma granarium*. M.SC.Thesis, Fac. Agric., Ain Shams University .
- Adenekan, M.O.; Ajetunmobi, O.T.; Okpeze, V.E. and Aniche, D.C. (2018):** Residual effect of different temperature regimes on the developmental stages of F1 progeny of *Callosobruchus maculatus*(F)(Coleoptera: Bruchidea) on cowpea seeds. Int. J. Agric. Innov. Res., 6(6): 2319-1473.
- Al-Akhdar, H. H. ; Zinhoum, R. A. and Abdelfattah, N. A. H. (2019):** Microwave energy as an alternative control method for stored grain pests Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst., 2 (4):612 – 621.
- Babarinde, S.A.; Akinyemi, A.O.; Odewole, A.F.; Yisa, S.; Oke, O.O. and Adeyemo, A.O. (2016):** Phytochemical composition and insecticidal properties of mechanically extracted castor, seed oil against cowpea seed bruchid (*Callosobruchus maculatus* Fabricius) infesting Bambara groundnut. Elixir Inter. J. 92, 39086-39092.
- Chu, S.S.; Liu, Q.R. and Liu, Z.L. (2010):** Insecticidal activity and chemical composition of the essential oil of *Artemisia vestita* from China against *Sitophilus zeamais*. Biochemical Systematics and Ecology, 38:489–492.
- De-Oliveira, A.C.; Ribeiro-Pinto, L.F. and Paumgarten, J.R. (1997):** In vitro inhibition of CYP2B1 monooxygenase by myrcene and other monoterpenoid compounds. Toxicol. Lett., 92:39–46.
- Haile, A. (2006):** On-farm storage studies on sorghum and chickpea in Eritrea. African J. Biotec., 5(17), 1537-1544.
- Haque, M.A.; Nakakita, H.; Ikenaga, H. and Sota, N., (2000).** Development-inhibiting activity of some tropical plants against *Sitophilus zeamais* Motschulsky (Coleoptera: Curculionidae). J. Stored Prod. Res. 36, 281–287.
- Hossain, F.; Lacroix, M.; Salmieri, S.; Khanh, V. and Follett, P.A. (2014):** Basil oil fumigation increases radiation sensitivity in adult *Sitophilus oryzae* (Coleoptera: Curculionidae). J. Stored Prod. Res., 59:108-112.
- Jayakumar, M.; Seenivasan, S.P.; Rehman, F. and Ignacimuthu, S. (2017):** Fumigant effect of some essential oils against pulse beetle, *Callosobruchus maculatus* (Fab.) (Coleoptera: Bruchidae). African Entomology, 25 (1): 193–199.
- Kalifa, A. and Badawy, A. (1961):** Preference of *Trogoderma granarium granarium* everts, *Trogoderma granium afrumpriesener* and *Trogoderma irroratum*reitter and the effect of diet on their biology (coleoptera: dermesitdae). Soc. Ent.d, Egypt Bu1.45:251-261.
- Lee, B.H.; Choi, W.S.; Lee, S.E. and Park, B.S. (2001a):** Fumigant toxicity of essential oils and their constituent compounds towards the rice weevil, *Sitophilus oryzae* (L.). Crop Prot., 20: 317–320.
- Lee, S.E.; Lee, B.H.; Choi, W.S.; Park, B.S.; Kim, J.G. and Campbell, B.C. (2001b):** Fumigant toxicity of volatile natural products from Korean spices and medicinal plants towards the rice weevil, *Sitophilus oryzae* (L.). Pest. Manag. Sci., 57: 548–553.

- Liska, A.; Rozman, V.; Kalinovic, I.; Ivezic, M. and Balicevic, R. (2010):** Contact and fumigant activity of 1,8-cineole, eugenol and camphor against *Tribolium castaneum* (Herbst). 10th International Working Conference on Stored Product Protection. Julius-Kühn-Archiv, 425.
- Negahban, M.; Moharramipour, S. and Sefidkon, F. (2007):** Fumigant toxicity of essential oil from *Artemisia sieberi* Besser against three stored-product insects. J. Stored Prod. Res., 43: 123–128.
- Nerio, L.S.; Verbel, J.O. and Stashenko, E. (2010):** Repellent activity of essential oils: A review. Bioresource Technology, 101: 372–378.
- Rozman, V.; Kalinovic, I. and Liska, A. (2006):** Bioactivity of 1,8-cineole, camphor and carvacrol against rusty grain beetle (*Cryptolestes ferrugineus* Steph.) on stored wheat. Proceedings of the 9th International Working Conference on Stored Product Protection, 15–18, Campinas, Sao Paulo, Brazil. ABRAPOS, Brazil, 687–694.
- Selim, A.A. (1963):** A comparative study on the effect of certain insecticides on cereals and certain grain pests. M.Sc. Thesis, Fac. Agric., Ain Shams University.
- Shemais, S. A.; Kassis, S.R. and Ahmed, S. M.S. (2002):** Effectiveness of jojoba oil for the protection of wheat grains against the rice weevil, *Sitophilus oryzae* L. and the granary weevil, *Sitophilus granaries* L. adults (Curculionidae: Coleoptera). 2nd International Conference Plant Protect. Res. Institute, Cairo, Egypt, 21-24.
- Singh, B.B.; Ajeigbe, H.A; Tarawali, S.A.; Fernandez-Rivera, S. and Abubakar, M. (2003):** Improving the production and utilization of cowpea as food and fodder. Field Crops Res., 84(1):169-177.
- Tripathi, A.K.; Prajapati, V.; Aggarwal, K.K. and Kumar, S. (2001):** Toxicity, Feeding deterrence and effect of activity of 1,8 cineole from *Artemisia annua* on progeny production of *Tribolium castaneum* (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae). J. Econ. Entomol., 94, 979–983.
- Wahba, T.F.; Mackled, M.; Selim, S. and. El-Zemity, S.R. (2018):** Toxicity and reproduction inhibitory effects of some monoterpenes against the cowpea weevil *Callosobruchus maculatus* F. (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae: Bruchinae). Middle East J. Appl. Sci., 8(4): 1061-1070.

Reproductive injury convinced by zinc oxide nanoparticles and *Senecio glaucus* plant actions via oxidative damage, hormonal disturbance, and histopathological change with the hopeful prophylactic effect of gallic acid in male rats

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Abstract:

This study intended to estimate the lethal effects of either alone or combined treatments of zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO NPs) and mureer or *Senecio glaucus* L. plant (SP) on testis via oxidative, biochemical, and histological studies, and to assess the promising protective effect of gallic acid (GA) in rats. Rats were allocated into eight groups with orally treated for 30 days as follows: Control, GA (100mg/kg), ZnO NPs (150mg/kg), SP (400mg/kg), GA+ZnO NPs (100,150mg/kg), GA+SP (100,400mg/kg), ZnO NPs+SP (150,400mg/kg), and GA+ZnO NPs+SP (100,150,400mg/kg). Our data said that ZnO NPs and SP reduced testosterone concentration and raised some parameters, such as (Acidic phosphatase and lactate dehydrogenase activities). They also declined glutathione-S-transferase activity and elevated malondialdehyde levels. Moreover, they caused testicular necrosis and sloughing in its tubules. Our data also detected that the toxic effect of combined treatment was harder than the effect of alone one. Inversely, GA amended testicular damage. Lastly, this study endorsed that the alone or mixed usages of ZnO NPs and SP may be used as alternative insecticides in a pest control program of the agricultural applications and GA may be used as a protective source against ecological testicular-toxins.

Introduction

Rodents are one of the greatest risks pests in Egypt. They persuade harmful impacts on cultivated crops and protected harvests. The recurrent use of chemical rodenticides in pest control programs may be reflected as having a negative effect on the environment. Hence, it must be used unconventional insecticides to control pests, such as nanoparticles and natural plants that act safer than on living organisms. Nanotechnology has newly displayed an inventive science, which could be exploited in many mandatory

applications in varied fields, including agriculture, medicine, electricity, and industry (Thiruvengadam *et al.*, 2018 and Saratale *et al.*, 2018). Generally, the nanostructures have strange physiognomies with a small-scale size of only around (1–100 nm) and a wide surface area to interact with any outward surface. Hence, nanoparticles (NPs) have already become fleeting within intracellular membranes and plentiful biological barriers disturbing the biomolecules in the cellular membranes (Jesus *et al.*, 2019). With a full application of NPs, nanotoxicology

has concerned a significant devoutness in environmental science. Due to the easiness permitting of NPs through the blood-testis barrier, they convinced testicular function moans (Stanton, 2016). Many academics have shown that NPs effectively stimulated compensations in the male reproductive system, resulting in the reduction of testosterone (TST) synthesis, impaired spermatogenesis, decreased libido, and eventually infertility. These changes may take a cytotoxic route via oxidative damage, necrosis, apoptosis, and proliferation of testicular cells (Brohi *et al.*, 2017 and Wang *et al.*, 2018).

Amongst the used eminent NPs, zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO NPs) are the further most efficient NPs, which are entered in various profitable materials, such as sensors, sunscreens, batteries, food storing, ceramics, electronics, insecticides, and drug delivery. Therefore, they can urge many deleterious effects in diverse organs, especially in the testis organ (Singh, 2019). Due to their rapid distribution, slow or ineffective elimination, their dissolution, and possible long-time tissue accumulation, they can persuade zinc homeostasis imbalance results in a range of remedial signs, such as testicular atrophy, cerebral as well as immune dysfunctions, and reducing drug removal capability of the body (Grüingreiff *et al.*, 2016).

Consuming natural plants is extensively used in an unconventional fashion of insecticidal sources that deed as slighter negative effects and a biodegradable manner in the environment. Amongst the well-known native plants, Mureer or *Senecio glaucus* subsp. *coronopifolius* (Maire) C. Alexander L. (SP) reveals as one member of (Asteraceae family, *Senecio* species) found in the deserts all over the world.

Unfortunately, they caused risky problems in animals, which

negatively produced enzymatic disturbances, hematoma, diarrhea, pulmonary difficulties, cardiac abnormalities, and hepatic degeneration (Ren *et al.*, 2016). No experimental studies have explored the effect of SP in testis rats; yet, numerous studies have reported there were disparaging influences of *Senecio* plants in many surviving cells (Tundis *et al.*, 2011 and Mendonça *et al.*, 2019). From ancient criticism, there are many phytochemical compounds, such as saponins, flavonoids, alkaloids, phenolic compounds, coumarin, and others accumulated in intracellular tissues, which are responsible for tissue damage (Parra *et al.*, 2017).

In particular, the testis is a principal organ that is responsible for the spermatogenesis process, which produced spermatozoa in the seminiferous tubules. It is more sensitive to exposure to noxious compounds (Staub and Johnson, 2018). From a consideration, male infertility persuades a result of a disturbance in the spermatogenesis process, which is based on a reduction in sperm count, oxidative stress inspiration, and disturbance of sex hormones. Among the conjoint biomarkers for evaluation of testis damage, TST hormone is the main androgen secreted hormone in the blood. It is secreted from the Leydig cells of the testis. Furthermore, it is responsible for the progress of secondary male sex characteristics and its capability of fertilization (Nassar and Leslie, 2021).

Even if the TST hormone may be found in three primary forms: unbound or free, TST, tightly bound TST, and supported TST. Only free and weakly bound TST can bind to the androgen receptor (Rhoden and Morgentaler, 2004). It is most organs exposed to oxidative stress (OS) that is the main cause for the generation of programmed cell death, which is an

abnormal imbalance between oxidants and antioxidants in cellular membranes, leading to lipid peroxidation (LP), DNA damage, and protein interruption in intracellular tissue. The antioxidant defense mechanism encompasses enzymatic and non-enzymatic systems, such as glutathione-S-transferase (GST) protected the cells from reactive oxygen species production (ROS) action (Preiser, 2012).

Afterward, it is compulsory to examine more tangible approaches against persuaded complications while conserving or augmenting its useful effects. Amid these valuable approaches, the use of antioxidants, such as gallic acid (GA). GA, (3,4,5 trihydroxy benzoic acid), is a polyphenol natural product found in roses, oak, grapes, mango, cashew nut, hazelnut, walnut, raspberry, lemon, spinach, gallnut, and green tea. It is speedily absorbed through the gastrointestinal tract into the bloodstream passing through a wide variety of metabolic processes, which is concomitant with its antioxidant effects. Numerous studies have revealed that it has many important activities, including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-diabetic, and anti-cancer activities. It has the ability to cell recovery from inflammation (Khan *et al.*, 2018 and Singla *et al.*, 2020). In order to explain the correlation between the structure of GA and protective capability, it has a benzene ring with hydroxyl and carboxyl groups that can evade ROS. Additionally, it can interrelate with ions to lessen the potentials of free radical production. Overall, the hydroxyl group of its structure can pass through the liposome membrane to retort with 1,1-diphenyl-2-picryl-hydrazyl (DPPH) free radical and stimulate repression of LP in testicular cells (Kilic *et al.*, 2019).

As an ultimate point, the purpose of the current study was

designed to examine the deadly effects of either alone or joined treatments of ZnO NPs and SP through scrutinizing biochemical, oxidative, and histopathological investigations on testis tissue. Moreover, this study scrutinized to appraise the imaginable ameliorative effect of GA against reproductive toxicity fortified by ZnO NPs and SP in male rats.

Materials and methods

Zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO NPs) (<50 nm) (BET), gallic acid (GA), and sodium carboxymethyl cellulose (Na-CMC) salt were purchased from (Sigma Aldrich, St. Louis, Missouri, USA). 70% of ethanol solvent was obtained from (EL-Naser Company, Egypt). Malondialdehyde and glutathione-S-transferase kits were coming from (Biodiagnostic Company, Egypt). A testosterone kit also was bought from (Ezo Company, Asia). LDH kit was credited from (Egyptian Company for Biotechnology, S.A.E, Egypt). Other chemicals and reagents were secondhand from high-quality kinds of biochemical analysis.

1. The characterization and preparation of ZnO NPs nanoparticles:

The description of ZnO NPs can be measured to ascertain their size and morphology using the transmission electron microscopy (TEM) (JEOL-JEM-1230, National Research Center) equipped with a digital CCD camera at 100 kV. ZnO NPs suspension was equipped by using 0.5% Na-CMC sonicated for 20 min. in a bath sonicator and vortexed for 1min before every administration in Plant Protection Research Institute, El-Sharkia.

2. Preparation of ethanolic extract of mureer plant:

The whole portions of the renewed plant of mureer were harvested in April from Cairo- Ismailia Road, Egypt with Taxon identifier (183639) on NCBI (National Center for

Biotechnology Information) database that was nominated by Dr. Abdel-Halim Abdel-Mogaly, Botanist, Herbarium of Horticultural Research Institute, Egypt. After grinding dried plant parts (leaves, stems, roots, and flowers) in the air, the achieved powder was used to prepare the ethanolic extract by the maceration method for 72 h. At the end of the maceration period, the liquid part was filtered with a Whatman paper and gotten out of the excess solvent at 60 °C through a rotary evaporator. Then, it was entirely dehydrated in an aired oven at 45 °C. The crude extract was retained at -20 °C for the experiment (Bahrin *et al.*, 2018).

2.1. Estimation of phytochemical components of plant:

The primary phytochemical screening test was carried out the entire plant for the recognition of various constituents using typical methods, such as saponins, alkaloids, flavonoids, and phenolic compounds that were measured as the approaches, Hiai *et al.*, 1976; Yubin *et al.*, 2014; Zhishen *et al.*, 1999 and Chun *et al.*, 2003, respectively.

2.2. Calculation of median lethal dose (LD₅₀) of ethanolic plant extract:

It was performed according to Karber (1931). It was used an oral single dose of (2500, 5000, 10000, 2000, 40000, and 80000 mg/kg) of an ethanolic extract of the plant to determine LD₅₀ from this equation: $LD_{50} = LD_{100} - \frac{\sum(Dd \times Md)}{n}$, **n**=Total number of animals in a group, **Dd**=The difference between two successive doses of administering extract, **Md**=The average number of dead animals in two successive doses, and **LD₁₀₀** = The lethal dose causing 100% death of all tested animals.

3. Experimental protocol:

An experimental trial was conducted on forty male *Wistar* albino rats (*Rattus norvegicus*). They were weighed (180-220 g) and had 7 weeks

age-old. It was made according to the approval of the Animal Ethics Committee of Zagazig University under “Principles of Laboratory Animal Care”. The rats were housed in cages in a persistent temperature (23±2 °C), humidity (60±10%), and a light/dark (12 hrs.: 12 hrs.) cycle. After a week of acclimation, the rats were allocated into eight groups containing 5 rats in each one as follows: **a.** Control group: rats were received (0.5% Na–CMC with 5 ml/kg, b.wt) as a vehicle (Dhiyaaldeen *et al.*, 2014). **b.** GA-treated group: rats were received (100 mg/kg, b.wt.) of GA (Mansouri *et al.*, 2013) dangling in 0.5% Na-CMC (Sen *et al.*, 2013). **c.** ZnO NPs-treated group: rats were received (150 mg/kg, b.wt) of ZnO NPs, which was adjoined in 0.5% Na-CMC (Srivastav *et al.*, 2016). **d.** SP-treated group: rats were received (400 mg/kg, b.wt) of SP chosen through LD₅₀ experiment in this study. **e.** GA+ZnO NPs-treated group: rats were received (100 and 150 mg/kg, b.wt), respectively. **6)** GA+SP-treated group: rats were received (100 and 400 mg/kg, b.wt), respectively. **f.** ZnO NPs+SP-treated group: rats were received (150 and 400 mg/kg, b.wt), respectively. **8)** GA+ZnO NPs+SP-treated group: rats were received (100, 150 and 400 mg/kg, b.wt), respectively. GA was managed at the pretreatment of other substances. The administration of all poisonous and ameliorating agents was set for one month by gavage administration and suspended in 0.5% Na-CMC at volume (5 ml/kg) (Plate 1).

After this period, the rats were assassinated by cervical dislocation. The serum was collected for total lipid analysis and testis tissue was sensibly dissected that was divided into two parts as follows: a small portion of testis tissue was homogenized and centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 min to do biochemical and antioxidant studies. Another part was stored at 10% neutral

buffered formalin for histological studies.

4. Estimation of biochemical parameters:

4.1. Biochemical analyses:

4.1.1. Estimation of testicular testosterone concentration (TST) bioassay:

The TST ELISA kit could be a competitive ELISA (Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay) that was designed for the accurate and quantitative method. It was purchased from Ezo Company according to the procedures of Abraham (1981). A Supernatant of testicular homogenate was reacted with TST-HRP conjugate in the wells, where TST in the sample competed with the added TST-HRP antibody binding. After incubation, the wells were washed to remove unbound material and TMB substrate was then added catalyzed by HRP to produce a blue color. The reaction was ended with the addition of a stop solution, which was stopped the development of color and produced a color change from blue to yellow. The intensity of the signal was inversely proportional to the amount of TST in the sample and the intensity was measured at 450 nm.

4.1.2. Estimation of testicular acidic phosphatase activity (ACP) bioassay:

Testicular ACP activity was evaluated according to Kind and King (1954) method that phenyl phosphate phenol was reacted with sample acidic phosphatase in the presence of pH 4.9. Then, the liberated phenol was colorimetrically measured in the presence of 4-aminophenazone and potassium ferricyanide to appear a defined color at 510 nm.

4.1.3. Estimation of testicular lactate dehydrogenase activity (LDH) bioassay:

Testicular LDH activity catalyzes the change of lactate to pyruvate. The enzyme was assessed according to Zimmerman and Hennery

(1979). 20 µl of testicular homogenate was added to 1ml of working solution, mixed, and read at an initial absorbance after 30 sec. Then, it must be read again after 1, 2, and 3 min. It was estimated the difference absorbance per min.

5. Estimation of prooxidant/antioxidant status biomarkers:

5.1. Estimation of testicular malondialdehyde (MDA) level:

The MDA level of the testicular homogenate was determined according to the method of Ohkawa *et al.* (1979), which was based on thiobarbituric acid (TBA). It reacted with MDA content in a sample at an acidic medium and a boiling water bath for 30 min to make TBA reactive product. The absorbance of the obtained pink product can be measured at 534 nm.

5.2. Estimation of testicular glutathione-S-transferase (GST) activity:

GST activity of the testicular homogenate was estimated according to the method of Habig *et al.* (1974) using 1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene as an electrophilic substrate that joined to GSH to the participation of the enzyme, created a colored GSH-substrate complex, and detected at 340 nm. The proportion of the increase was directly proportional to the GST activity in the sample.

6. Histopathological studies:

Testis specimens were fixed using 10% neutral buffered formaldehyde. After proper fixation, the specimens were dehydrated in ascending grades of ethyl alcohol, cleared in xylol, impregnated, and embedded in paraffin wax. 5-µm thick sections were cut using a rotatory microtome. Testis sections were stained with routine hematoxylin and eosin (H&E.) stain for studying the general histological structure of the testis (Bancroft and Layton, 2012).

7. Statistical analysis:

The quantitative variables were estimated by applying the statistical software package SPSS (IBM Corp. SPSS, 2011). They were described as a mean±standard deviation (Mean±SD) using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post hoc test for the comparison between several groups. The level of significance was documented at $P < 0.05$.

Results and discussion

The existing study targeted to investigate the toxic impacts of either alone or united actions of ZnO NPs and SP on testes and to assess the cautious effect of GA against their noxious effects in male rats.

1. The size and shape of ZnO NPs estimation:

Our results showed that the size and morphology of ZnO NPs were estimated using TEM that seemed as 43 ± 1 nm and the morphology of particles was noticed as spherical crystals (Figure 1).

2. Phytochemical constituent screening of SP:

Moreover, our data presented that SP enclosed an extraordinary amount of saponins, mediocre amount

of phenolic compounds, and small amount of flavonoid and alkaloid compounds, (Table 1) that were the main cause for convincing its hurtful influences of plant extract on testis tissue and persuaded tissue damage when gathered.

3. Toxicity trial of ethanolic extract of SP (LD₅₀):

Table (2) displayed that LD₅₀ of SP in rats was obtained (60.000 mg/kg), so our study selected a defined dose (400 mg/kg) or (1/150 LD₅₀) used in it and made our investigations in rats. It did not give any mortality for 24 hrs.

4. Estimation of biochemical parameters:

Table (3) exhibited that either alone or combined treatments of ZnO NPs and SP may be persuaded reproductive-toxicity and the pretreatment of GA caused a testicular-protective effect through the studying of testicular function biomarkers: testicular ACP activity (U/g tissue), testicular TST concentration (ng/g protein), and testicular LDH activity (U/mg protein).

Figure (1): Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) image of ZnO NPs showing the morphology and size of the particles in Milli-Q water. Particles were scanned by TEM at 120kV.

Table (1): Phytochemical constituents of *Senecio glaucus* plant (SP).

Analysis	Quantity
Saponins	+++
Alkaloids	+
Total phenolic	++
Total flavonoids	+

+++ : high amount, ++:medium, +: low.

Table (2): Determination of median lethal dose (LD₅₀) of ethanolic extract of *Senecio glaucus* plant (SP) in rats.

Groups	Doses (mg/kg)	Number of animals (N)	Dead animals	Md (Mortality difference)	Dd (Dead difference)
1	0	4	0	0	0
2	2.500	4	0	0	2.500
2	5.000	4	0	0	2.500
4	10.000	4	0	0	5.000
5	20.000	4	0	0	10.000
6	40.000	4	0	0	20.000
7	80.000	4	4	2	40.000
Sum					∑ 80.000

$$LD_{50} = D_{100} - \sum \frac{Md \times Dd}{N} = 80.000 - \frac{80.000}{4} = 60.000 \text{ mg/kg.}$$

Table (3): Influence of Zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO NPs), *Senecio glaucus* L. plant (SP), and gallic acid (GA) on the biochemical parameters [testicular acidic phosphatase activity (ACP) (U/g tissue), testicular lactate dehydrogenase activity (LDH) (U/mg protein), and testicular testosterone concentration (TST) (ng/g protein)].

Groups	ACP (U/g tissue)	LDH (U/mg protein)	TST (ng/g protein)
Control	30.152±1.52	1162.89±1.93	50.33±1.73
GA	25.71±1.31 ^{***g}	1154.24±1.57 ^{***g}	62.55±1.28 ^{***g}
ZnO NPs	95.45±1.29 ^{***a}	1531.72±1.53 ^{***a}	37.71±1.88 ^{***a}
SP	46.31±1.05 ^{***}	1263.19±2.87 ^{***}	31.57±0.89 ^{***}
GA+ZnO NPs	61.93±1.47 ^{***d}	1512.98±1.97 ^{***d}	41.58±1.02 ^{***d}
GA+SP	42.34±1.19 ^{***e}	1255.49±2.09 ^{***e}	36.52±0.78 ^{***e}
ZnO NPs+SP	151.09±0.85 ^{***b,c}	1763.93±2.56 ^{***b,c}	15.77±1.22 ^{***b,c}
GA+ Zn NPs+SP	126.25±0.95 ^{***f}	1722.95±1.47 ^{***f}	23.06±1.12 ^{***f}

Values were given as mean±SD, (n=5 rats per group). Statistical analysis was done by using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post hoc test for multiple comparisons between groups. Compared to the control group, highly significant: *** (P < 0.001) and n.s. (P is non-significant). a,b,c,d,e,f,g letters represent the relations between treated groups at P < 0.05: [^aZnO NPs relative to SP, ^bZnO NPs+SP relative to ZnO NPs, ^cZnO NPs+SP relative to SP, ^dGA+ZnO NPs relative to ZnO NPs, ^eGA+SP relative to SP, ^fGA+ZnO NPs+SP relative to ZnO NPs+SP, ^gGA relative to control].

On a hand, it was evident from the data, testicular ACP activity and testicular LDH activity were significantly increased in either alone or combined treatments of ZnO NPs and SP compared to the control group (P≤0.001). Correspondingly, there was an improvement in GA-treated group in the values of ACP and LDH activities compared to the control group due to its antioxidant activity. On the other hand, the pretreatment of GA to ZnO NPs and SP significantly reduced in these

parameters relative to either alone or combined treatments of ZnO NPs and SP as follows: (GA+ZnO NPs-treated group relative to ZnO NPs-treated group, GA+SP-treated group relative to SP-treated group, and GA+ZnO NPs+SP-treated group relative to ZnO NPs+SP-treated group) (P≤0.001).

Furthermore, our data also reported that the testicular TST concentration was significantly decreased in either alone or collective treatments of ZnO NPs and SP

compared to the control group ($P \leq 0.001$). Likewise, there was an enhancement in GA-treated group in the value of TST concentration relative to the control group due to its special endocrine excitation characters. In addition, the alterations in all tested parameters of the combined treatment of ZnO NPs and SP were stronger than the alterations in the alone treatment of them. Moreover, the changes in these parameters of ZnO NPs-treated group were severer than the changes in SP-treated group.

In contrast, the pretreatment of GA to ZnO NPs and SP significantly increased in the TST concentration relative to either alone or combined treatments of ZnO NPs and SP as follows: (GA+ZnO NPs-treated group relative to ZnO NPs-treated group, GA+SP-treated group relative to SP-treated group, and GA+ZnO NPs+SP-treated group relative to ZnO NPs+SP-treated group) ($P \leq 0.001$).

5. Estimation of testicular antioxidant/oxidative status biomarkers:

Table (4): Influence of Zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO NPs), *Senecio glaucus* L. plant (SP), and Gallic acid (GA) on testicular oxidative biomarkers [malondialdehyde (MDA) (nmol/g tissue) and Glutathione-S-transferases (GST) (U/g protein)].

Groups	MDA (nmol/g tissue)	GST (U/g protein)
Control	41.69±1.43	1.25±0.07
GA	39.10±1.18 ^{n.s. g}	1.47±0.16 ^{n.s. g}
ZnO NPs	101.13±0.91 ^{*** a}	0.36±0.06 ^{*** a}
SP	51.64±0.79 ^{***}	0.41±0.05 ^{***}
GA+ZnO NPs	81.48±0.77 ^{***d}	0.64±0.04 ^{*** d}
GA+SP	40.99±1.29 ^{*** e}	0.60±0.03 ^{***e}
ZnO NPs+SP	103.26±1.76 ^{*** b,c}	0.26±0.04 ^{*** b,c}
GA+Zn NPs+SP	91.31±1.11 ^{***f}	0.50±0.08 ^{*** f}

Values were given as mean±SD, (n=5 rats per group). Statistical analysis was done by using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post hoc test for multiple comparisons between groups. Compared to the control group, highly significant: ^{***}($P < 0.001$) and ^{n.s.}(P is non-significant). a,b,c,d,e,f,g letters represent the relations between treated groups at $P < 0.05$: [^a ZnO NPs relative to SP,^bZnO NPs+SP relative to ZnO NPs,^cZnO NPs+SP relative to SP,^d GA+ZnO NPs relative to ZnO NPs, ^eGA+SP relative to SP, ^fGA+ZnO NPs+SP relative to ZnO NPs+SP, ^gGA relative to control].

Indifference, the pretreatment of GA to both compounds caused a significant reduction in MDA level, but it induced a significant rise in GST

Table (4) presented that either alone or combined treatments of ZnO NPs and SP could persuade OS *in vivo* and provoke the antioxidant outcome of GA against oxidative damage that was discussing the effect of MDA level (nmol/g tissue) and GST activity (U/g protein) in testicular tissue. Our records observed that they caused a significant increase in MDA level; however, they induced a significant decrease in GST activity compared to the control group ($P < 0.001$). Moreover, there was no significant change between the control and GA-treated groups in both parameters. Furthermore, the shifts in these biomarkers of the combined treatment of ZnO NPs and SP (ZnO NPs+SP-treated group) were more powerful than the shifts in the alone treatment of them (ZnO NPs-treated group and SP-treated group). Moreover, the deviations in these biomarkers of ZnO NPs-treated group were more sturdily than the deviations in SP-treated group.

activity relative to either alone or combined treatments of ZnO NPs and SP as follows: (GA+ZnO NPs-treated group relative to ZnO NPs-treated

group, GA+SP-treated group relative to SP-treated group, and GA+ZnO NPs+SP-treated group relative to ZnO NPs+SP-treated group) ($P \leq 0.001$).

Inclusively, our data observed that the deadly impacts of mixed treatment of ZnO NPs and SP were more strappingly than the alone treatment on the level of the biochemical and antioxidant/oxidant status parameters. Correspondingly, our records showed that GA might be acting as an anti-testicular toxic and antioxidant agent against testicular toxicity induced by both compounds.

6. Histopathological studies:

Figure (2:a-h) illustrated that the histological investigation of testis tissue in treated groups. Our data showed that the testicular toxic effect of ZnO NPs and SP and the preventive effect of GA against them. Microscopically, there was a normal histological structure of testis tissue comprising from spermatogonia in the control group, including spermatocyte cells surrounded by spermatocyte membrane, which secreted spermatozoa and Leydig cells in interstitial areas, (Figure 2:a). Additionally, a healthy structure of testicular tissue appeared in GA-treated group similar to the control group (Figure 2:b). Meticulously, on a hand, the sloughing in the seminiferous

tubules, the appearance of necrotic cells, the degeneration of germinal epithelium, the widening in the interstitial tissues and vacuolization in the germ cells occurred in ZnO NPs-treated group, (Figure 2:c). Correspondingly, a slight sloughing of seminiferous tubules from the basement membrane and an appearance of a small hemorrhage region transpired in SP-treated group, (Figure 2:d).

On the other hand, a mild sloughing of seminiferous tubules, a moderate degeneration in some tubules, and an appearance of vacuolization in the germ cell existed in GA+ZnO NPs-treated group, (Figure 2:e). Interestingly, GA+SP-treated group seemed to have any change in testis tissue close to the control group, (Figure 2:f). The combined group of ZnO NPs and SP persuaded extensive necrosis in the spermatogenic cells, a reduction in the germinal cells, interstitial capillary congestion, a thickening of the wall of blood vessels, and a sloughing in the seminiferous tubules, (Figure 2:g). However, the pretreatment of GA to them in GA+ZnO NPs+SP-treated group caused a simple sloughing in tubules, (Figure 2:h).

Figure 2(a): Control group showing the normal histological structure of testis tissue: spermatocyte cells (Sp), spermatocyte membrane (SM), spermatozoa (SZ), and Leydig cells (LC) (H&E., $\times 200$).

Figure 2(b): GA-treated group showing a healthy normal structure of testicular tissue similar to the control group: spermatocytes (Sp), spermatocyte membrane (SM), spermatozoa (SZ), and Leydig cells (LC) (H&E.,×200).

Figure 2(c): ZnO NPs-treated group showing an appearance of necrotic cells (NC), degeneration of germinal epithelium with sloughing of seminiferous tubules from basement membranes (ST), widening of interstitial tissue (star), and appearance of vacuoles (V) (H&E.,×200).

Figure 2(d): SP-treated group showing slight sloughing of seminiferous tubules from basement membranes (ST) and small hemorrhage area (H) (H&E.,×200).

Figure 2(e): GA+ZnO-NPs-treated group showing a mild sloughing of seminiferous tubules organizations (ST), moderate degeneration in some tubules (D), and an appearance of vacuolization (star) (H&E.,×200).

Figure 2(f): GA+SP-treated group showing a closely similar normal structure of testis tissue (H&E.,×200).

Figure 2(g): ZnONPs+SP-treated group showing extensive necrosis of spermatogenic cells (NC), reduction in germinal cells along with interstitial capillary hemorrhage (H), widening of interstitial tissue with thickening of the wall of blood vessels (B), and sloughing of seminiferous tubules (ST) (H&E.,×200).

Figure 2(h): GA+ZnO NPs+SP-treated group showing close to the normal structure of testis (arrow) (H&E.,×200).

Figure 2(a-h): Photomicrograph of influence of Zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO NPs), Mureer or *Senecio glaucus* L. plant (SP), and gallic acid (GA) on the histopathological studies of testis tissue in treated groups.

In order to evaluate testicular toxicity, TST hormone is the main biomarker, which must be measured. It may be found as a free form or binding to a carrier molecule (albumin or globulin) that protected the integrity of the testis. Moreover, this protein controls TST secretion, which is the conversion of TST to active metabolites stimulating the binding of luteinizing hormone (LH) to its receptors to initiate the intracellular signaling pathway. Thus, this is responsible for the production of TST from the Leydig cells. Total TST is the best biomarker for testis integrity estimation (Kelly and Jones, 2013). In light of such results, the repetition in TST synthesis leads to a loss of the ability of fertility and sperm production. Furthermore, the deficit in TST level inhibits germ cell production from the transitory meiotic stage of division (Holdcraft and Braun, 2004).

Generally, the sperm supply and androgen metabolic enzymes have become the principal functions of testis relevant to the spermatogenesis process, but testicular damage is caused by secreting LDH enzymes outside the tissue and produced the deficiency in TST exudation. Hence, it has already produced hypogonadism parameters, such as prolonged sexual development and shrinking testes that are allied to a drop in the energy content and increased body fat accumulation inside them (Strauss *et al.*, 2009).

Nevertheless, the existing information regarding about ACP enzyme is a very vital enzyme that is responsible for hydrolyzing phosphoric esters of various phosphate-containing compounds at acid pH. It is involved in several metabolic processes, such as production, transport, and utilization of inorganic phosphate that is the principle of cell growth and differentiation. It is found in the lysosome of the Leydig

cells, which performs the synthesis of proteins carried by sex hormones. Unfortunately, ACP enzyme is released in large amounts into semen when there is reproductive harmfulness, such as prostate cancer. It caused thickening of the basement membrane of seminiferous tubules, tubular atrophy, and arrest of cell maturation (Akimoto *et al.*, 1997). Apart from the previous approaches and explanations, ACP activity and TST concentration are the chief biomarkers for a guesstimate of the reproductive toxicity of any toxic material antagonizing to the androgen receptor that can change the glycosylation of gonadotropins leading to the turbulences in the levels (Sikka and Naz, 1999).

Our results were in the same line with, Hong *et al.* (2016) who reported that NPs treatment caused a reduction in TST level, damaged spermatogenesis, and induced infertility in mice. In addition, they were in harmony with Zhang *et al.*, (2020) who showed that NPs management persuaded an inhibition in TST production, DNA damage, and stimulated levels of mRNA expression of apoptotic genes in genital cells. Thus, they impaired the quality of sperm parameters, including a reduction in sperm count, motility, and vitality. Our observations were in agreement with Sharafutdinova *et al.* (2018) who presented that titanium dioxide nanoparticles instigated many morphological changes in spermatocyte constituents and sperm numbers. Furthermore, our results about the toxic effect of plant extract were according with, Lienou *et al.* (2012) who described that *Senecio* plant caused peritubular testicular fibrosis, reduced sperm number, disrupted regulation of LH, depressed TST synthesis, destruction of prenatal follicles, increased atresia, and reduced number of primordial follicles in female rats.

Likewise, Diallo *et al.* (2015) revealed that feeding on a hydroalcoholic extract of *Ageratum conyzoides* plant (Asteraceae) induced many physiological disorders in the gentile cells of rats.

When testes may suffer dramatically from OS due to induction of LP and caused leakage of LDH from the mitochondrial membrane altering both spermatogenic and steroidogenic functions. These events instigated a lack of blood supply in testis (Aitken and Roman, 2008). OS can be modulated a steroidogenic capacity of Leydig cells disrupting the ability of germinal epithelium to distinguish spermatozoa, which may be arisen infertility (Hales *et al.*, 2005). Generally, MDA is the product of LP that impairs antioxidant capacity in testicular tissue. Furthermore, zinc balance disturbance causes a reduction in the sulfhydryl groups of cysteine residues, leading to a conformational modification in the protein assembly causing GST activity disorder (Ho *et al.*, 2003).

From the aforementioned report, ROS are the main cause for the induction of inflammation and necrosis associated with NF- κ B pathway activation that caused the production of the inflammatory cascade. Moreover, testicular damage can drop the expression of connexin43 protein because of apoptosis in Sertoli and spermatogenic cells, which may be a reason for a reduction in the height of epithelial cells and tubules diameter. Thus, this process has already caused the breakdown of DNA, chromatin condensation, and protein destruction involving histological alterations (Jiménez-Lamana *et al.*, 2014). Finally, of this part, Lone *et al.*, (2014) explained the negative impact of plant extract in the testis due to the accumulation of chemical constituents

of the *Senecio* plant, which is responsible for its cytotoxicity effect.

In contrast, to explain the positive role of GA in this study, antioxidants alleviated prostate and testicular injuries because of suppressing the inflammatory and apoptotic mechanisms promoting normal spermatogenesis (Shahin and Mohamed, 2017). Confirming our results, the histological structure of the testis was recovered, which was evidence of the protective effect of GA against either alone or mixed treatments of ZnO NPs and SP. It restores testicular degeneration, atrophy, and tubular disarrangement. The antioxidant power is dependent on the potential phenolic compound, which can prevent OS-mediated testicular damage by the capture of ROS. Furthermore, GA has the capability to stimulate the hypothalamic-pituitary-gonadal axis that improves the testicular function for the production of sperms (Mazloom *et al.*, 2017).

Moreover, the optimistic effect of GA may be attributed to its

proficiency in the generation of intracellular free zinc ions by persuading the secretion of metallothionein enzyme to incite nuclear factor-erythroid2-related factor2 (Nrf2) transcription factor that is responsible for stimulating the synthetic pathway of glutathione (Cortese *et al.*, 2008).

Our findings were in the same line with, Oyagbemi *et al.* (2016) who showed that GA significantly balanced TST concentration and induced an improvement in the testicular atrophy disturbed by cyclophosphamide treatment in rats. Moreover, our outcomes were parallel to, Mehraban *et al.* (2020) who revealed that GA attenuated the disturbance in DNA sperm, marked testicular atrophy, and caused a significant decline in MDA levels after cyclophosphamide administration (Plate 1).

Plate (1): Graphic abstract

References:

- Abraham, G.E. (1981):** In clinical endocrinology, Marcel Dekker, Inc., N.Y.
- Aitken, R.J. and Roman, S.D. (2008):** Antioxidant systems and oxidative stress in the testes. *Journal of Oxidative medicine and cellular longevity*, 1(1):15-24.
- Akimoto, S.; Furuya, Y.; Akakura, K.; Shimazaki, J. and Ito, H. (1997):** Relationship between prostate-specific antigen, clinical stage, and degree of bone metastasis in patients with prostate cancer: comparison with prostatic acid phosphatase and alkaline phosphatase. *International Journal of Urology*, 4(6):572-575.
- Bahrin, N.; Muhammad, N.; Abdullah, N.; Talip, B.H.A.; Jusoh, S. and Theng, S.W. (2018):** The effect of processing temperature on antioxidant activity of *Ficus carica*. *Journal of Science and Technology*, 10:99-103.
- Bancroft, J.D. and Layton, C. (2012):** The hematoxylin and eosin. *Bancroft's Theory and Practice of histological techniques*, Expert Consult: Online and print, 7th Eds. pp.173, Elsevier: Amsterdam, Netherlands.
- Brohi, R.D.; Wang, L.; Talpur, H.S.; Wu, D.; Khan, F.A.; Bhattarai, D.; Rehman, Z.U.; Farmanullah, F. and Huo, L.J. (2017):** Toxicity of nanoparticles on the reproductive system in animal models: a review. *Journal of Frontiers in Pharmacology*, 8:606-628.
- Chun, O.K.; Kim, D.O. and Lee, C.Y. (2003):** Superoxide radical scavenging activity of the major polyphenols in fresh plums. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 51(27):8067-8072.
- Cortese, M.M.; Suschek, C.V.; Wetzel, W.; Kröncke, K.D. and Kolb-Bachofen, V. (2008):** Zinc protects endothelial cells from hydrogen peroxide via Nrf2-dependent stimulation of glutathione biosynthesis. *Journal of Free Radical Biology and Medicine*, 44(12):2002-2012.
- Dhiyaaldeen, S.M.; Amin, Z.A.; Darvish, P.H.; Mustafa, I.F.; Jamil, M.M.; Rouhollahi, E. and Abdulla, M.A. (2014):** Protective effects of (1-(4-hydroxyl-phenyl)-3-m-tolyl-propenone chalcone in indomethacin- induced gastric erosive damage in rats. *Journal of BMC Veterinary Research*, 10:961-975.
- Diallo, A.; Batomayena, B.; Povi, L.; Eklu-Gadegbeku, K.; Aklikokou, K.; Creppy, E. and Gbeassor, M. (2015):** Fetal toxicity of hydroalcoholic extract of *Ageratum conyzoides* L. leaves (Asteraceae) in rats. *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 7(8):264-266.
- Grüngreiff, K.; Reinhold, D. and Wedemeyer, H. (2016):** The role of zinc in liver cirrhosis. *Journal of Annals of Hepatology*, 15(1):7-16.
- Habig, W.H.; Pabst, M.J. and Jakoby, W.B. (1974):** Glutathione-S-transferases. The first enzymatic step in mercapturic acid formation. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 249(22):7130-7139.
- Hales, D.B.; Allen, J.A.; Shankara, T.; Janus, P.; Buck, S.; Diemer, T. and Hales, K.H. (2005):** Mitochondrial function

- in Leydig cell steroidogenesis. Journal of Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences, 1061:120-134.
- Hiai, S.; Oura, H. and Nakajima, T. (1976):** Color reaction of some saponinins and saponins with vanillin and sulfuric acid. Journal of Planta Medica, 29(2): 116–122.
- Ho, E.; Courtemanche, C. and Ames, B.N. (2003):** Zinc deficiency induces oxidative DNA damage and increases p53 expression in human lung fibroblasts. Journal of Nutrition, 133(8): 2543–2548.
- Holdcraft, R.W. and Braun, R.E. (2004):** Androgen receptor function is required in Sertoli cells for the terminal differentiation of haploid spermatids. Journal of Development, 131(2): 459-467.
- Hong, F.; Zhao, X.; Chen, M.; Zhou, Y.; Ze, Y.; Wang, L.; Wang, Y.; Ge, Y.; Zhang, Q. and Ye, L. (2016):** TiO₂ nanoparticles-induced apoptosis of primary cultured Sertoli cells of mice. Journal of Biomedical Materials Research Part A, 104(1): 124-135.
- IBM Corp. SPSS (2011):** IBM SPSS (Statistical package for the social sciences) Statistics for Windows, Version 20.0. Armonk, NY IBM Corp.
- Jesus, S.; Schmutz, M.; Som, C.; Borchard, G.; Wick, P. and Borges, O. (2019):** Hazard assessment of polymeric nanobiomaterials for drug delivery: what can we learn from literature so far. Journal of Frontiers in Bioengineering and Biotechnology, 7: 261-298.
- Jiménez-Lamana, J.; Laborda, F.; Bolea, E.; Abad-Álvaro, I.; Castillo, J.R.; Bianga, J.; He, M.; Bierla, K.; Mounicou, S.; Ouerdane, L.; Gaillet, S.; Rouanet, J.M. and Szpunar, J. (2014):** An insight into silver nanoparticles bioavailability in rats. Journal of Metallomics, 6(12):2242-2249.
- Karber, G. (1931):** Beitrag zur kollektiven behandlung pharmakologischer reihenversuche. Archiv for Experimentelle Pathologie und Pharmakologie Journal, 162:480-483.
- Kelly, D.M. and Jones, T.H. (2013):** Testosterone: a metabolic hormone in health and disease. Journal of Endocrinology, 217(3):R25-R45.
- Khan, B.A.; Mahmood, T.; Menea, F.; Shahzad, Y.; Yousaf, A.M.; Hussain, T. and Ray, S.D. (2018):** New perspectives on the efficacy of gallic acid in cosmetics & nanocosmeceuticals. Journal of Current Pharmaceutical Design, 24(43): 5181-5187.
- Kilic, K.; Sakat, M.S.; Akdemir, F.N.E.; Yildirim, S.; Saglam, Y.S. and Askin, S. (2019):** Protective effect of gallic acid against cisplatin-induced ototoxicity in rats. Brazilian Journal of Otorhinolaryngology, 85(3):267-274.
- Kind, P.R.N. and King, E.J. (1954):** Estimation of plasma phosphatase by determination of hydrolysed phenol with amino-antipyrine. Journal of Clinical Pathology, 7(4):322-326.
- Lienou, L.L.; Telefo, B.P.; Bale, B.; Tagne, D.; Yemele, R.S.; Goka, S.C.; Lemfack, C. M.; Mouokeu, C. and Moundipa, P.F. (2012):** Effect of the aqueous extract of *Senecio*

- biafrae* (Oliv. & Hiern) J. Moore on sexual maturation of immature female rat. Journal of Archive of BMC Complementary and Alternative Medicine, 12:36-45.
- Lone, S.H.; Bhat, K.A.; Bhat, H.M.; Majeed, R.; Anand, R.; Hamid, A. and Khuroo, M.A. (2014):** Essential oil composition of *Senecio graciliflorus* DC: Comparative analysis of different parts and evaluation of antioxidant and cytotoxic activities. Journal of Phytomedicine, 21(6):919–925.
- Mansouri, M.T.; Farbood, Y.; Sameri, M.A.; Sarkaki, A.; Naghizadeh, B. and Rafeirad, M. (2013):** Neuroprotective effects of oral gallic acid against oxidative stress induced by 6-hydroxydopamine in rats. Journal of Food Chemistry, 138(2-3):1028-1033.
- Mazloom, B.F.; Edalatmanesh, M.A. and Hosseiniord, E. (2017):** The effect of gallic acid on pituitary-ovary axis and oxidative stress in rat model of polycystic ovary syndrome. Journal of Report of Health Care, 3(1):41- 47
- Mehraban, Z.; Ghaffari, N.M.; Golmohammadi, M.G.; Sagha, M.; Ziai, S.A.; Abdollahifar, M.A. and Nazarian, H. (2020):** Protective effect of gallic acid on testicular tissue, sperm parameters, and DNA fragmentation against toxicity induced by cyclophosphamide in adult NMRI mice. Journal of Urology, 17(1): 78-85.
- Mendonça, S.S.; Domingues, R.; Baldo G.E.; Azevedo, D.S.P.; Marques, C.K.; Pelegrine, M.A. and Botelho, V.M.I. (2019):** *In vitro* ovicidal effect of a *Senecio brasiliensis* extract and its fractions on *Haemonchus contortus*. Journal of BMC Veterinary Research, 15(1): 99-108.
- Nassar, G.N. and Leslie, S.W. (2021):** Physiology, Testosterone. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK526128/>.
- Ohkawa, H.; Ohishi, N. and Yagi, K. (1979):** Assay for lipid peroxides in animal tissues by thiobarbituric acid reaction. Journal of Analytical Biochemistry, 95(2):351–358.
- Oyagbemi, A.A.; Omobowale, T.O.; Saba, A.B.; Adedara, I.A.; Olowu, E.R.; Akinrinde, A.S. and Dada, R.O. (2016):** Gallic acid protects against cyclophosphamide-induced toxicity in testis and epididymis of rats. Journal of Andrologia, 48(4):393-401.
- Parra, C.; Soto, E.; León, G.; Salas, C.O.; Heinrich, M. and Echiburú-Chau, C. (2017):** Nutritional composition, antioxidant activity and isolation of scopoletin from *Senecio nutans*: support of ancestral and new uses. Journal of Natural Product Research, 32(6):719-722.
- Preiser, J.C. (2012):** Oxidative stress. Journal of Parenteral and Enteral Nutrition, 36(2):147-154.
- Ren, C.; Tong, T.J.; Hong, Y. and Yang, Q.E. (2016):** *Senecio changii* (Asteraceae: Senecioneae), a New Species from Sichuan, China. Journal of PLoS One, 11(4): e0151423-e151438.
- Rhoden, E.L. and Morgentaler, A. (2004):** Risks of testosterone-

- replacement therapy and recommendations for monitoring. *The New England Journal of Medicine*, 50(5): 482-492.
- Saratale, R.G.; Saratale, G.D.; Shin, H.S.; Jacob, J.M.; Pugazhendhi, A.; Bhisare, M. and Kumar, G. (2018):** New insights on the green synthesis of metallic nanoparticles using plant and waste biomaterials: current knowledge, their agricultural and environmental applications. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research International*, 25(11):10164-10183.
- Sen, S.; Asokkumar, K.; Umamaheswari, M.; Sivashanmugam, A.T. and Subhadradevi, V. (2013):** Antiulcerogenic effect of gallic Acid in rats and its effect on oxidant and antioxidant parameters in stomach tissue. *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 75(2):149-155.
- Shahin, N.N. and Mohamed, M.M. (2017):** Nano-sized titanium dioxide toxicity in rat prostate and testis: Possible ameliorative effect of morin. *Journal of Toxicology and Applied Pharmacology*, 334:129–141.
- Sharafutdinova, L.A.;Fedorova, A.M.; Bashkatov, S.A.; Sinel'nikov, K.N. and Valiullin, V.V. (2018):** Structural and functional analysis of the spermatogenic epithelium in rats exposed to titanium dioxide nanoparticles. *Journal of Bulletin of Experimental Biology and Medicine*, 166(2):279-282.
- Sikka, S.C. and Naz, R.K. (1999):** Endocrine disruptors and male infertility. In: Naz RK (Ed) *Endocrine disruptors: effects on male and female reproductive systems*. CRC Press, Boca Raton, Florida, pp. 225–246.
- Singh, S. (2019):** Zinc oxide nanoparticles impacts: cytotoxicity, genotoxicity, developmental toxicity, and neurotoxicity. *Journal of Toxicology Mechanisms and Methods*, 29(4): 300-311.
- Singla, E.; Dharwal, V. and Naura, A.S. (2020):** Gallic acid protects against the COPD-linked lung inflammation and emphysema in mice. *Journal of Inflammation Research*, 69(4):423-434.
- Srivastav, A.K.; Kumar, M.; Ansari, N.G.; Jain, A.K.; Shankar, J.; Arjaria; N.; Jagdale, P. and Singh, D. (2016):** A comprehensive toxicity study of zinc oxide nanoparticles versus their bulk in *Wistar* rats: Toxicity study of zinc oxide nanoparticles. *Journal of Human and Experimental Toxicology*, 35(12):1286-1304.
- Stanton, P. G. (2016):** Regulation of the blood-testis barrier. *Journal of Seminars in Cell and Developmental Biology*, 59:166-173.
- Staub, C. and Johnson, L. (2018):** Review: Spermatogenesis in the bull. *Journal of Animal*. 12 (s1):s27-s35.
- Strauss, L.; Kallio, J.; Desai, N.; Pakarinen, P.; Miettinen, T.; Gylling, H.; Albrecht, M.; Mäkelä, S.; Mayerhofer, A. and Poutanen, M. (2009):** Increased exposure to estrogens disturbs maturation, steroidogenesis, and cholesterol homeostasis via estrogen receptor alpha in adult mouse Leydig cells. *Journal of*

- Endocrinology, 150 (6): 2865-2872.
- Thiruvengadam, M.; Rajakumar, G. and Chung, I.M. (2018):** Nanotechnology: current uses and future applications in the food industry. *Journal of 3 Biotech*, 8(1):74-87.
- Tundis, R.; Menichini, F.; Loizzo M.R.; Bonesi, M.; Solimene, U. and Menichini, F. (2011):** Studies on the potential antioxidant properties of *Senecio stabianus Lacaita* (Asteraceae), and its inhibitory activity against carbohydrate-hydrolysing enzymes. *Journal of Natural Product Research*, 26(5):393-404.
- Wang, R.; Song, B.; Wu, J.; Zhang, Y.; Chen, A. and Shao, L. (2018):** Potential adverse effects of nanoparticles on the reproductive system. *International Journal of Nanomedicine*, 13: 8487-8506.
- Yubin, J.I.; Miao, Y.; Bing, W. and Yao, Z. (2014):** The extraction, separation, and purification of alkaloids in the natural medicine. *Journal of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Research*, 6(1):338-345.
- Zhang, X.; Yue, Z.; Zhang, H.; Liu, L. and Zhou, X. (2020):** Repeated administrations of Mn₃O₄ nanoparticles cause testis damage and fertility decrease through PPAR-signaling pathway. *Journal of Nanotoxicology*, 14(3):326-340.
- Zhishen, J.; Mengcheng, T. and Jianming, W. (1999):** The determination of flavonoid contents in mulberry and their scavenging effects on superoxide radicals. *Journal of Food Chemistry*, 64(4):555-559.
- Zimmerman, H.J. and Henery, J.B. (1979):** Clinical enzymology. In: *Clinical diagnosis and management by laboratory methods*, 16th, J.B. Henery, editor, Saunders, Philadelphia, pp.365-368.

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Effect of the vegetation density of some ornamental plants on the abundance and the diversity of spiders

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Abstract:

Diversity and spider community inhabiting foliage of two different categories of ornamental plants (Flowers and shrubs) was carried out in the Orman Garden. Collecting spiders by foliage beating on sweep nets, numbers of collecting spiders were pooled and analyzed for species diversity for the two categories using Shannon-Wiener and Simpson Indices and Sørensen Quotient of Similarity. Vegetation type influenced spider abundance; the flowers category received 130 individuals representing 10 families, 19 genera and 21 species; the most common species were *Thomisus spinifer* of the family Thomisidae, while the shrub category received 127 individuals representing 6 families, 13 genera and 13 species; the most frequent species were *Pulchellodromus glaucinus* of the family Philodromidae. The relative abundance of guilds (Based on numbers of individuals) varied greatly, which may reflect the availability of spiders within different hosts.

Introduction

The Orman Garden is a flat area covered with a great variety of ornamental plants, flowers, shrubs, trees and palm trees, flowering all year rounds and it provides water channels filled with water for long periods, therefore, this area is an excellent field for surviving many living organisms. The plant structural, the architectural arrangement of biomass in vegetation and in space has been recognized as one of the main factors that determine the diversity and abundance of plant dwelling spiders (Gunnarsson, 1990 and Halaj *et al.*, 1998). A positive influence between plant architecture and spider abundance was demonstrated through the incidence of structural complexity, such as foliage density in big sage, *Artemisia* sp.

(Hatley and McMahon, 1980), leaf surface area in different species of *Eucalyptus* (Evans, 1997) and density of needles in spruce *Picea abies* (Gunnarsson, 1990). Halaj *et al.* (2000) suggested that differences in the spider fauna in different plant species indicate the existence of spider associations for specific characteristics of the habitat.

It is clear from previous studies, that the difference in the density of vegetation, the surface or size of leaves or leaflets, the lack of increase of branches and their interlacing and the height and lower length of the plant, all affect the presence of spiders that use the plant as a shelter (Ghallab, 2013).

The objective of the work is to throw light on spider taxonomy, diversity and their distribution in different species of two ornamental

categories (Six species of flower plants and four species of shrubs). The diversity analysis was based on Shannon-Wiener and Simpson "S" Indices quantify the community structures of spiders among the two categories mentioned before and to determine their similarities of spider composition.

Materials and methods

1. Study site, plant selected and sampling of spiders:

Orman Garden provides an excellent field for surviving many living organisms due to the presence of different ornamental plants all over the year. The flower category selected is of low elevation ranging between 0.75–1.5 m. Six species were selected included *Dimorphotheca pulvialis* L., *Salvia splendens* L., *Helichrysum bracteatum* (Vent.), *Tagetes erecta* L., *Chrysanthemum coronarium* L. and *Crinum asiaticum* L. While the shrubs selected are of high elevation ranging between 1-2.5m. They were *Acalypha macrophylla* Müll, *A. marginata* Müll, *A. hoffmanii* Müll and *Plumbago auriculata* Lam.

Spiders living on foliage were collected by shaking plants on the sweeping net with a mesh bag and each specimen was kept singly in a glass vial to prevent cannibalism. Samples were collected every two weeks from the previously mentioned hosts in the period between January and July 2020. All specimens were preserved in 70% ethyl alcohol and some droplets of glycerine and examined under a stereo-zoom microscope in the laboratory.

2. Identification of spiders:

The scientific names of the adult spiders' and their classification follows different specialized description keys and catalogues provided by Kaston (1978), Levi (2002), Oger (2002) and Proszynski (2003).

3. Data analysis:

3.1. The Shannon-Wiener "H" and Simpson "S" Indices:

The Shannon Index indicates the community stability under the balance of nature, while Simpson Index "S" is a measure of dominance (Nestle *et al.*, 1993). The typical values of Shannon diversity index generally range from 1 to 3 thus showing moderate species diversity with which values below 1 indicates low diversity and values more than 3 indicates high diversity. The two indices were calculated as described by Ludwig and Reynolds (1988).

Shannon Index $H' = -\sum (n_i/n) \ln (n_i/n)$

Simpson Index $S = \sum (n_i/n)^2$

Where n_i is the number of individuals belonging to the i^{th} of "S" taxa in the sample and "n" is the total number of individuals in the sample."

While the species evenness "e" is a measure that indicate how evenly the total number of individuals (Abundance) is apportioned among species; i.e., the ratio of the actual H' value to the maximum value and thus it ranges from (0 to 1), the closer to one the more homogeneous population.

Evenness "e" = $H' / H' \text{ max.}$ or $H' / \log(s)$ where "s" is the number of species.

3.2. Sørensen quotient of similarity (QS):

It was used to compare the community of spiders in vegetation of the two categories (Flowers and shrubs) and determine their similarity. Sørensen's quotient (Sørensen, 1948) was applied to the number of species and individuals of the two categories of the plant and ranges from (0-1).

Sørensen's formula "QS" = $2C / A + B$.

Where A and B are the number of species in samples A and B, respectively, and C is the number of species shared by the two samples.

3.3. Guild composition:

Spiders collected were divided into six guilds according to spider's web-building and prey-catching behaviors as described in the classification system proposed by Uetz *et al.* (1999).

Results and discussion

1. Species richness of true spiders inhabiting flowers category:

Over the seven months of study the true spiders were collected from 6 different types of flowers, Table (1) recorded a total of 130 individuals representing 10 families, 19 genera and 21 species. When ranked by abundance Figure (1), the most common families Thomisidae (38.5%), Salticidae (16.2%) and Theridiidae (15.4%) accounted for 70 % of all spiders sampled; the next two families, Philodromidae (11.5%) and Cheiracanthiidae (10.8%) contained another 22.3% and the least common five families Dictynidae, Araneidae, Linyphiidae, Oxyopidae and Uloboridae comprising only 7.7%.

The most frequently encountered individuals were *Thomisus spinifer* (44 individuals) belonging to family Thomisidae then

Cheiracanthium isiacum (14), *Pulchellodromus glaucinus* (12), *Thyene imperialis* (12), *Kochiura aulica* (12) and *Theridion melanostictum* (8) of families Cheiracanthidae, Philodromidae, Salticidae, and Theridiidae, respectively.

As for preference of the plant structure and the spider abundance which showed in Figures (1 and 2), it is not yet known why the spider prefers the plant where it is endemic (By excluding the presence of pests), but it is hypothetical possibilities. The *Helichrysum* and *Chrysanthemum* flowers appeared to be a suitable dweller for foliage spiders, they recorded the highest collection of spiders of 33 and 29 individual respectively of the total 130 individuals included the most abundant species, *Thomisus spinifer* is very common in the garden for the abundance of flowers. This species belongs to the family Thomisidae, distributed different vegetation, *Helichrysum* 75.8%, *Dimorphotheca*(50%), *Tagetes* (42.8%) *Salvia* and *Chrysanthemum* 25 and 24.1% respectively, while it was absent in crinum plant.

Table (1): Spiders inhabiting flowers between January to the end of July 2020.

Family names and species	A	%	B	%	C	%	D	%	E	%	F	%	Total	%
Philodromidae														
<i>Pulchellodromus glaucinus</i> (Simon)	3	15	2	8.7	4	12.1	-	0	1	13.8	2	18.2	15	11.5
<i>Thanatus</i> sp.	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	-	-	-	-	-
Salticidae														
<i>Thyene imperialis</i>	-	-	6	-	1	-	1	-	2	-	2	-	-	-
<i>Plexippus paykulli</i>	-	0	1	34.8	-	6.1	-	7.1	-	6.9	3	72.7	21	16.2
<i>Alfraftacilla spiniger</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Hasarius adansoni</i>	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	-
<i>Heliophanus</i> sp.	-	-	1	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-
Cheiracanthidae														
<i>Cheiracanthium istiacum</i> O.P.	-	0	7	30.4	1	3.03	3	21.4	3	10.3	-	-	14	10.8
Oxyopidae														
<i>Oxyopes bilineatus</i> O.P.	1	5	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	-	1	0.8
Theridiidae														
<i>Theridion melanosictum</i> O.P.	5	25	-	4.4	-	3.03	1	21.4	2	34.5	-	-	20	15.4
<i>Kochiura aulica</i> Koch	-	-	1	-	1	-	2	-	8	-	-	-	-	-
Araneidae														
<i>Neoscona</i> sp.	1	5	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	3.5	-	-	2	1.5
<i>Araneus</i> sp.	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	--	-	-
Thomisidae														
<i>Thomisus spinifer</i> O.P.	9	50	2	8.7	25	75.8	3	42.8	5	24.1	-	0	50	38.5
<i>Thomisus onustus</i> Walckenaer	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	-	2	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Thomisus</i> sp.??	1	-	-	-	-	-	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Dictynidae														
<i>Nigma</i> sp.	-	0	1	4.4	-	0	-	7.1	2	6.9	-	-	4	3.1
<i>Dictyna</i> sp.	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Linyphiidae														
<i>Sengletus extricatus</i> O.P.	-	0	1	8.7	0	-	0	-	-	-	-	-	2	1.5
<i>Gnathanarium</i> sp.	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Uloboridae														
<i>Uloborus</i> sp.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	9.1	1	0.8
Total of alive individuals	20		23		33		14		29		11		130	

A: Dimorphotheca, B: Salvia, C: Helichrysum, D: Tagetes, E: Chrysanthemum, F: Crinum

The height of the two plants (Up to one meter) and the structure of leaves and dense vegetation might be a reason for spiders' abundance. This observation in accordance with that of (Corcuera *et al.*, 2008), they indicate the high numbers of *P. viridans* correlated with a plant height of the shrub *Croton ciliatoglanduliferus*. Moreover, leaves of *Chrysanthemum* with glandular trichomes attracts different arthropods which represent available prey for spiders, this result agreed with (Vasconcelos-Neto *et al.*, 2006).

In contrary, *Tagetes* and *Crinum* flowers recorded 14 and 11 individuals, respectively. Spiders distributed in *Tagetes* were *Cheiracanthium* and *K. aulica* (21.4 and 14.3%), respectively, followed by *T. spinifer* in their abundance. While *Crinum* plant recorded 4 species of Salticidae of 72.2 %. The low elevation of these two plants as well as the lack of poor branches, probably might be a reason to distribute species of Salticidae which were abundant in microhabitat and leaf litter beneath these two plants.

2. Species richness of true spiders inhabiting the shrubs category:

According to the true spiders collected from 4 species of shrubs Table (2), a total of 127 individuals representing 6 families, 13 genera and 13 species were obtained. When ranked by abundance Figure (3) the most common family was Salticidae (35.4%), followed by Philodromidae (20.5%) then Cheiracanthidae (17.3%), those families accounted 73 % of all spiders sampled; the next two families, Thomisidae and Theridiidae contained another (24.4%) and the least common family was Araneidae comprising (2.4%).

The most frequently encountered individuals were *Pulchellodromus glaucinus* (24

individuals) of family Philodromidae, followed by *Cheiracanthium isiacum* and *Plexippus paykuli* (22 and 21 individuals, families Cheiracanthidae and Salticidae, respectively), then *Thomisus spinifer* and *Thyene imperialis* (17 and 16) individuals, families Thomisidae and Salticidae, respectively) then *Theridion melanostictum* (10 individuals) belonging to Theridiidae .

As for preference of the shrub structure and the spider abundance which showed in Figures (3 and 4). The three common species selected of *Acalypha* were of dense vegetation as well as broad leaves, the abundance of spiders in the three plants species was close, recorded 28, 27 and 25 for species *macrophylla*, *marginata* and *hoffmanii*, respectively. The *A. macrophylla* had 10 sp. three of them were common in the four shrubs, they were *Pulchellodromus* (24 individuals of total 26) followed by *Cheiracanthium* (22) then *Thyene* (16). The shrub, *A. marginata* recorded the most common abundance of Salticid spiders, which was *Plexippus paykullii*, (66.7%); while the 3rd shrub *A. hoffmanii* comprised 7 species two of them were common, *Cheiracanthium* (40%) and *Plexippus paykullii* (36%).

The 4th shrub, *Plumbago* distinguished by loose branchlets with small leaves. It invaded by 47 individuals, including 8 species of 6 families; the most abundant species was *Pulchellodromus glaucinus* (14 individuals). This result is in conformity with that of (Ghallab, 2013) which proved that foliage runner spiders were the dominant on *Lantana* shrubs which had few branches, and De Souza and Martins (2005) who proved that foliage-runners constituted the dominant spiders on *Desmanthus virgatus* and *Banksia gardneri*, which have few branches; and they suggest that branch architecture is the most important factor determining the abundance of plant-dwelling spiders in the study area independently of branch biomass, leaf surface area or texture; in addition, Evans (1997) found that social crab spiders preferred *Eucalyptus* species with smaller leaves.

Table (2): Spiders inhabiting shrubs between January to the end of July 2020.

Family names and species	A. <i>macrophylla</i>	%	A. <i>marginata</i>	%	A. <i>hoffmanii</i>	%	<i>P. auriculata</i>	%	Grand total	%
Philodromidae										
<i>Putcheilodromus glaucinus</i>	6	28.6	2	7.4	2	8	14	29.8	26	20.5
<i>Philodromus blankei</i>	1		-		-		-			
<i>Thanatus sp.</i>	1		-		-		-			
Salticidae										
<i>Thyene imperialis</i>	4		5	66.7	1	36	6	21.3	45	35.4
<i>Plexippus paykullii</i>	1	28.6	12		8		-			
<i>Bianor</i>	3		-		-		-			
<i>Heliophanus sp.</i>	-		1		-		4			
Cheiracanthiidae										
<i>Cheiracanthium isiacum</i> O.P.	5	17.8	6	22.2	10	40	1	2.1	22	17.3
Theridiidae										
<i>Theridion melanosictum</i> O.P.	2	14.3	-	0	2	12	6	14.9	14	11
<i>Kochiura aulica</i> Koch	2		-		1		1			
Araneidae										
<i>Neoscona sp.</i>	-	0	-	0	1	4	-	4.3	3	2.4
<i>Araneus sp.</i>	-		-		-		2			
Thomisidae										
<i>Thomisus spinifer</i> O.P.	3	10.7	1	3.7	0	0	13	27.7	17	13.4
Total of alive individuals	28		27		25		47		127	

3. Foraging guild of analysis:

The analysis of functional groups (Foraging guild) of the collected spiders composed of six functional groups based on their foraging behavior

in the field (Uetz *et al.*, 1999), they are stalkers, ambushers, foliage runners, orb web, space weavers and wandering sheets Figures (5 and 6).

In the floral, plants (Table 1 and Figure 5), the ambushers and space weavers were the dominant feeding guilds on flora. The ambushers (Thomisidae (38.5%) and Philodromidae (11.5%)), comprised 50 % of the total spider collected; Thomisidae recorded the high frequency in *Helichrysum* (75.8%) followed by *Dimorphotheca* and *Tagetes* 50 and 42.8 %, respectively. This observation is in accordance with (Nentwig, 1993 and De Souza and M6dena (2004) who indicated that the high frequency of ambushers was

expected in flowering branches, because spiders from this guild belong to the Thomisidae family, typical of inflorescences. While Philodromidae recorded the high frequency in *Crinum* (18.2%) followed by *Dimorphotheca* (15%). The space weavers (Thrediidae and Dictynidae) comprised 18.5 % of the total spider collected of high frequency in *Tagetes* 34.5% then *Dimorphotheca* 25%.

According to shrub category (Table 2 and Figure 6), the stalkers (Salticidae) was predominant (35.4%) of the total spider collected; recorded

the high frequency in *A. marginate* (66.7) and *A. hoffmanii* 36%; this result was in accordance with Labanon *et al.* (2020) where they proved in their studies that Salticids or jumping spiders can be abundantly found in all ecosystems with a broad range of microhabitats from beneath leaf litter to the forest canopy. The Salticidae followed by the Philodromidae (20.5) and Thomisidae (13.4) which constitute together, the ambushers, of total frequency (33.9); both families have recorded the high frequency in *P. auriculate* (29.8 and 27.7%, respectively) then *A. macrophylla* (28.6 and 10.7%, respectively).

Orb weaver guild was the least frequent in both flora and shrubs categories, recording 2.3 and 2.4 %, respectively, (Figures 5 and 6), space weavers was absent in shrubs and comprised 1.5% in flora. The foliage

Table (3): Biodiversity of spider species in the different flowers.

Type of Index	Spider diversity in flowers					
	<i>Dimorphotheca</i>	<i>Salvia</i>	<i>Helichrysum</i>	<i>Tagetes</i>	<i>Chrysanthemum</i>	<i>Crinum</i>
Shannon–Wiener (H')	1.3	1.6	0.8	1.4	1.7	0.7
Species evenness	1	1.2	0.5	1.2	1.1	0.7
Simpson Index (S)	0.34	0.24	0.59	0.22	0.21	0.57

5. Biodiversity of spider species in the different flowers:

Table (3) showed the comparison of the biodiversity of spider species in the different structures of flowers. The biodiversity index calculation (H') indicated that the bigger number is more diverse, where the values (1.7 and 1.6) which recorded in the flowers *Chrysanthemum* and *Salvia*, respectively, were the most diverse and both recorded 10 species belonging to 7 families and evenness 1.1 and 1.2, respectively. Next comes plants *Tagetes* and *Dimorphotheca* of values 1.4 and 1.3, respectively, they included 6 and 7 species belonged both to 5 families, while the species evenness was 1.2 and 1, respectively.

running spiders (Cheiracanthidae) depend on vegetation for finding food; they recorded 10.8 and 17.3% in flora and shrubs, respectively.

The flora recorded the highest species richness (21 species) while shrubs recorded (13 species). The guild composition in the different species of flora and shrubs were definitely different which indicates the high difference between their habitats. This result may be the best indicator that some factor is interfering in the spider community.

4. Spider’s diversity:

By using Shannon-Wiener Index, we can describe the diversity of the spider communities in different flower plant (Spider dwellers) (Table 3).

The lowest spider diverse was observed in *Helichrysum* and *Crinum* flowers of values 0.8 and 0.7 and both of 6 species belonged to 5 and 3 families and species evenness were 0.5 and 0.7, respectively.

According to Simpson Index, which is a measure of dominance, it was found that *Helichrysum* included the highest number of dominant species recorded the value (0.59) which was 75.8% of the species *Thomisus spinifer* (Table 1).

6. Biodiversity of spider species in the different shrubs:

Table (4) showed the comparison of the biodiversity of spider species in the structures of four different species of shrubs. *Acalypha macrophylla* and *Plumbago auriculata*

were the most plants that dwelled by spiders, the values of diversity recorded the biggest values, 1.5 for both shrubs which indicates the most diverse; the *A. macrophylla* comprised 10 species belongs to 5 families where *Plumbago* includes 8 species of 6 families; while the species evenness was 1 and 0.9, respectively. The lowest spider diverse was observed in *A. marginata* of value 0.9 and species evenness was 0.6

comprised 6 species belong to 4 families.

According to Simpson Index, *A. marginata* shrub included the highest number of dominant species (0.5), it was for members of Salticidae and Cheiracanthidae 66.7% and 22.2%, respectively.

Table (4): Biodiversity of spider species in the different shrubs.

Type of Index	Spider diversity in shrubs			
	<i>A. macrophylla</i>	<i>A. marginata</i>	<i>A. hoffmanii</i>	<i>P. auriculata</i>
Shannon–Wiener (H')	1.5	0.9	1.3	1.5
Species evenness	1	0.6	0.9	0.9
Simpson Index (S)	0.22	0.5	0.3	0.2

7. Faunal similarity of spiders:

In relation to the flowers, the *Helichrysum* plant was the most highly collected spider recording a total of 33 individuals belonging to five families, while the number of spider species was (6) followed by *Chrysanthemum* and *Salvia* of 29 and 23 individuals, respectively, belonging both to seven families and 10 species, then the remaining plants *Dimorphotheca* and *Crinum*, recorded 20 and 11 individuals, belonging to 5 and 3 families, respectively and 6 species both. The total species of flower plants were 21 species. According to the shrubs, the *Plumbago* was the most highly collected spider recording a total of 47 individuals belonging to 6 families 8 species followed by *A. macrophylla* and *A. marginata* of 28 and 27 individuals belonging to 5 and 4 families and 10 and 6 species, respectively, the last shrub was *A. hoffmanii* recorded 25 individuals, belonging to 5 families and 7 species. The total species of shrub plants was 13 species, the number of common species by the two communities flowers and shrubs was 11. To allow a comparison

of similarity between the habitats of the flowers and the shrubs, the Sørensen's quotient of similarity (QS) was calculated. It is concluded that the two communities were semi-similar as they recorded 65% of similarity.

This research is one of series research that have been studied on the diversity of spider fauna in the Orman Botanical Garden. The objective was to make initial observations of how habitat structure influence foliage spiders by determined the association between selected habitat of several hosts plants to the abundance and diversity of spider fauna. It is concluded that, habitat structure and species richness caused by the dependence of spiders on the vegetation of their habitat due to a way of life and foraging, and these factors predict the abundance and diversity of spiders which plays a significant role in shaping these communities. Ried and Miller (1989) suggested that diversity increased in presence of a greater varieties of habitat types, while Uetz (1991) and Labanon and Nuñez (2020) proposed the complex structure of shrubs can support a more diverse spider community, as the vegetation

matures, becoming denser and more stratified, more spider species become available, thus further supporting the hypothesis that structural complexity of plants influences spider species richness. While the view of Wise (1993) is the environmental structure may or may not impact spider composition. In terms of microhabitat preference, spiders generally do not have a strong association with the plants on which they live, however, spiders are known to be selective of their microhabitats and foraging sites, increasing their survivorship and reproductive success (Labanon and Nuñezza, 2020).

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References

- Corcuera, P.; Jimenez, M. L. and Valverde, P.L. (2008):** Does the microarchitecture of Mexican dry forest foliage influence spider distribution?. *Journal of Arachnology* , 36(3): 552-556.
- De Souza, A.L.T. and Martins, R.P. (2005):** Foliage density of branches and distribution of plant-dwelling spiders. *Biotropica: The Journal of Biology and Conservation*, 37(3):416-420.
- De Souza, A.L.T. and Módena, Es. (2004):** Distribution of spiders on different types of inflorescences in the Brazilian Pantanal. *The Journal of Arachnology*, 32(2): 345-348.
- Evans, T. A. (1997):** Distribution of social crab spiders in eucalypt forests. *Aust. J. Ecol.*, 22: 107–111.
- Ghallab, M. M. (2013):** Preliminary study of the spiders inhabiting ornamental plants in Orman Garden. *Serket* , 13(1/2), pp. 8.
- Gunnarsson, B. (1990):** Vegetation structure and the abundance and size distribution of spruce-living spiders. *J. Anim. Ecol.*, 59:743-752.
- Halaj, J.; Ross, D.W. and Moldenke, A.R. (1998):** Habitat structure and prey availability as predictors of the abundance and community organization of spiders in western Oregon forest canopies. *J. Arachnol.*, 26: 203– 220.
- Halaj, J.; Ross, D.W. and Moldenke, A.R. (2000):** Importance of habitat structure to the arthropod food-web in Douglas-fir canopies. *Oikos*, 90: 139–152.
- Hatley, C. L. and MacMahon, J. A. (1980):** Spider community organization: Seasonal variation and the role of vegetation architecture. *Environ. Entomol.*, 9: 632–639.
- Kaston, B.J. (1978):** How to know spiders, 272 pp, 3rd edit. Wm. C Brown company Publishers.
- Labanon, K.K. O. and Nuñezza, O. M. (2020):** Species Diversity of Salticid Spiders (Araneae: Salticidae) according to Elevation and Vegetation Type in Western Mindanao State University. *Experimental Forest Area, Upper La Paz, Zamboanga City, Philippines*, *Bull. Env. Pharmacol. Life Sci.*, 9(5):53-64
- Levi, H.W. (2002):** Keys to the genera of araneid orb weavers (Araneae, Araneidae) of the Americas. *Journal of Arachnology*, 30 (3): 527-562.
- Ludwig, J.A. and Reynolds, J.F. (1988):** *Statistical Ecology: A primer on methods in*

- computing. New-York, John Wiley & Sons, pp.337.
- Nentwig, W. (1993):** Spiders of Panama. Biogeography, investigation, phenology, check list, key and bibliography of a tropical spider fauna. Fauna and Flora Handbook no. 12. Gainesville, USA: Sandhill Crane Press, pp. 247.
- Nestle, D. ; Dickschen, F. and Altieri, M.A. (1993):** Diversity patterns of soil macro-Coleoptera in Mexican shaded and unshaded coffee agro-ecosystems in indication of habitat perturbation . Biodiversity and Conservation , 2 : 70 – 78.
- Oger, P. (2002):** Les Araignées de Belgique et de France on line at <http://arachno.piwigo.com/index.php?categories>
Press, Cambridge, England.
- Proszynski, J. (2003):** Salticidae genera of levant (Israel and Neighboring Countries) <http://salticidae.org/salticid/diagnost/keys-sal/levant.htm>
- Ried, W.V. and Miller, K. R. (1989):** Keeping options alive: A scientific basis for conserving biodiversity. Washington D.C., World Resources Institute.
- Sørensen, T. (1948):** A method of establishing groups of equal amplitude in plant sociology based on similarity of species and its application to analyses of the vegetation on Danish commons. Biologiske Skrifter/Kongelige Danske Videnskabernes Selskab, 5:1-34.
- Uetz, G. W. (1991):** Habitat structure and spider foraging. { In: Bell, S. S., Mc Coy, E. D. and Mushinsky, H. R. (eds), Habitat structure: the physical arrangement of objects in space. Chapman and Hall : 325-348.
- Uetz, G. W.; Halaj, J. and Cady, A. B. (1999):** Guild structure of spiders in major crops. Journal of Arachnology, 27: 270-280.
- Vasconcelos-Neto, J.; Romero, G.Q. and Santos A.J. (2006):** Association of spiders in the genus Peuceelia (Oxyopidae) with plant bearing glandular hairs. Biotropica, 39: 221-226.
- Wise, D. H. (1993):** Spiders in ecological webs, 328 p. Cambridge University

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**Pheromone traps for the assessment of insecticides efficiency and monitoring
insecticides resistance in insect field strains**

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Abstract:

Up to date insecticides are the backbone of agricultural industry (Agricultural Mass Production) and for public health protection purposes. Annually, trillions of US \$ are lost as a result of insect infestations and damages in different agric. Crops around the world , even under the heavy use of insecticidal applications because of the control failure of many inefficient insecticides , that is happen because many insect field strains have developed resistance against these compounds. For the purposes of assaying insecticides efficiency and resistance in insect field strains, it's required to apply huge amounts of insecticides in many sequential treatments, investigate huge amounts of agric. crop fields, collect huge amounts of crop samples (Vegetation and / or fruit parts), rather than environmental pollution, human health hazards, using application equipments which require a lot amounts of effort, time and money. It's recommended here to use pheromone traps technique for the assessment of insecticides efficiency, monitoring insecticides resistance in insect field strains instead of the insecticides conventional applications to overcome all the above mentioned problems and to apply an advanced insecticides resistance management throughout an integrated pest management (IPM) with a very simple, easy, quick, and efficient technique.

Introduction

Formulated pesticides are used in a large scale through the world as a major mean for pest management and control. Although pesticides provide numerous benefits in terms of increased agricultural production and improve its quality, but their efficacy may be not often good because of the development of insecticide resistance in many pest species. Resistance to one or more pesticides has been documented in more than 447 species of insects and mites (Roush and McKenzie, 1987). Pesticide resistance is an increasingly urgent worldwide problem. Resistance

in vectors of human disease, particularly malaria-transmitting mosquitoes, is a serious threat to public health in many nations. Agricultural productivity is jeopardized because widespread resistance in crop and livestock pests. Serious resistance problem is also evident in pests of the urban environment, most notably cockroaches.

Resistance to insecticides is one of the most serious problems facing agriculture today. Many previous studies revealed the high resistance of pink bollworm to insecticides in the cotton fields. In Egypt, several

pyrethroids and organophosphorus have been widely used against cotton pests. However, although pyrethroid and organophosphorus insecticides were the most efficient and widely used against bollworms but the onset of resistance development to these compounds in bollworms have been recently documented (Georghiou, 1983; Haynes *et al.*, 1987; Miller, 1990 and Shekeban, 2000). The major economic losses due to the pesticide resistance in the USA were: \$1.5 billion (Pimentel, 2005). The price of insecticide resistance in lost yields and higher insect control costs is staggering - in some years more than 1 billion \$ in cotton for the budworm/bollworm complex alone. In IPM, pheromones are considered to be an essential component because they are used for detecting the economic threshold levels of pest populations and for mating disruption as a direct pest suppression measure. Pheromones of major pests have been found to be effective, economic and eco-friendly in agro-ecosystems in which cotton is cultivated (Tamhankar *et al.*, 2000). For resistance management tactics to be effective, resistance must be detected in its early stage (Roush and Miller, 1986) and early detection necessitates using one or more techniques that being accurate, easy, rapid and inexpensive, which would aid production, consultants and extension personal in making informed decisions on adequate control measures (Mink and Boethel, 1992). Firstly, the traditional approach uses complete dose-response tests with 4-5 doses that produce 10-90% mortality. Resistance is expressed in terms of the ratio of LD₅₀ or LC₅₀ of the resistant strain to that of the susceptible strain. Alternatively, an approach called the discriminating or diagnostic dose test was used where one dose is often investigated and the mortality of the

susceptible test strains is compared (Pasquier and Charmillot, 2003).

Another approach is the attracticide method which was developed in summer of 1985 as a rapid test to determined resistance in pink bollworm adult in cotton fields. The attracticide method was full implementation in 1986 and 1987 as an effective method to monitor insecticide resistance to pink bollworm to a wide range of insecticides (Miller, 1986 and Haynes *et al* ,1986 c and 1987). Detection of changes in response is needed, especially in the early stages of resistance development. Monitoring insecticide resistance in field population moth is in great importance in resistance management programs (Tabashnik and Cushing, 1987). In Egypt, very few dose mortality studies using attrcticides resistance monitoring technique were carried out (Al-Beltagy *et al.*, 1993). Therefore, it is important to study efficacy of insecticides against insect field strains in Nile Basin countries to establish a program for controlling and reducing the resistance level of these pest to insecticides. Such a program could be efficiently used to reduce number of insecticide sprays; cost of insecticides and increases the crop production per unit.

This review is concentrated on the use of attracticide resistance monitoring technique against different insect field strains and its modified procedure.

1. Attracticide resistance monitoring technique (ARMT) review:

Henneberry and Clayton (1982) conducted studies to determine the relationship between catches of male insects in pheromone-baited traps and crop infestation. Numbers of male moths of the pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae), caught daily in cotton fields at the University of Arizona Cotton Research Center,

Phoenix, Arizona, in gossypure-baited traps were variable. However, average catches of male moths for 3–7 days between boll-sampling periods were strongly correlated with oviposition on cotton bolls, percentages of infested bolls and numbers of larvae per boll. Average weekly numbers of moths emerging from infested cotton were also strongly correlated with the number of males caught. The number of females emerging was strongly correlated with oviposition on cotton bolls. Insecticide applications of carbaryl and fenvalerate reduced catches of male moths of pink bollworm in gossypure-baited traps compared with catches in traps in untreated fields (Average 56%). However, 13–48 male moths/trap per night were caught in the treated fields after applications. Thus, scheduling treatments on the basis of male moth trap catches, except for the initial treatment, was not feasible. Small field sizes, moth immigration and/or continuing emergence from the infested cotton in the fields may have obscured the impact of the insecticide treatments on adult moth populations.

Riedl *et al.* (1985) developed a procedure to screen field population of codling moth, *Cydia pomonella* (L) (Lepidoptera: Tortricidae), directly for resistance to azinphos-methyl or other toxicants. Male moths were collected in the field with pheromone traps and assayed with azinphos-methyl by topical application to the insects directly on the adhesive coated-trap surface. The LC₅₀ of moths trapped during the spring flight was somewhat higher (0.22 µg / moth) than during the summer (0.08 – 0.16 µg / moth). The longevity of moths and their toxicological response was not affected by the polybutene adhesive which was applied as a thin uniform film to the trap surface. Susceptibility to azinphos-methyl increased considerably with age in both sexes and was not correlated

with loss in body weight. Haynes *et al.* (1986 a) reported that the effectiveness of combinations of insecticides with pheromones (attracticides) for control of the pink bollworm (PBW) *P. gossypiella* may depend on, among other factors, males freely contacting attracticide source, insecticide-induced mortality, and sublethal interference with the male locating sequence in poisoned males. In flight-tunnel tests, males readily, contacted pheromone sources containing permethrin, fenvalerate, or cypermethrin and suffered mortality. Moreover, after 24 hr survivors were less likely to complete the normal behavioral sequence involved in sex pheromone-mediated mate location. The latter sublethal effects may contribute substantially to the effectiveness of the attracticide technique at the doses of insecticides used in the field. Cypermethrin induced lethal and sublethal effects at a lower concentration than other insecticides tested. Chlordimeform appears to be a poor candidate for attracticide formulations because males avoided contact with this insecticide. Recovery from sublethal effects of cypermethrin occurred after 48 hrs. and represents potential limitations to sublethal modification of behavior for population control.

Haynes *et al.* (1986 b) tested the use of yellow sticky cards to monitor resistance by incorporating various dosages of a selected insecticide into the sticky material on the cards and then seeing if reproducible dose–mortality relationships could be generated from adults flies caught on the cards. The technique was tested with laboratory strains to select the appropriate sticky material, suitable thickness and best time for evaluation of mortality. They found that, the yellow sticky cards are effective when used in monitoring populations of many insect species, and

in monitoring resistance levels to insecticides. Haynes *et al.* (1986 c) described a novel pheromone-baited sticky trap laced with insecticides proved to be a simple and effective means of monitoring insecticide resistance in pink bollworm moth. Adult males from field treated frequently with pyrethroid insecticides showed up to 20-fold resistance to permethrin and up to 14.5-fold resistance to fenvalerate. Information from the resistance-monitoring traps could be used to time the rotation of other chemicals. Miller (1986) reported that a population of tobacco budworm *Heliothis virescens* (Fabricius) from the West Texas cotton fields was found to have a 15-20 fold resistance to pyrethroid insecticides. A new method of measuring resistance in the field, the attracticide method was perfected for adults pink bollworm, *P. gossypiella*. In the attracticide method adult moths collect themselves, sex themselves and dose themselves. The field worker then collects the traps and counts mortality after two days without handling the moths themselves.

Haynes *et al.* (1987) reported that a rapid technique using sex pheromone and insecticide-laced traps was developed for measuring insecticide resistance in pink bollworm moth. This method was developed in the laboratory by allowing males to fly up wind to a sex-pheromone source in a wind tunnel and then trapping them on sticky cards inserted into standard delta traps (delta traps are used for trapping and monitoring Lepidopteran pests or other good-flyer insect pests. They can be used to monitor in orchards, large row crop plantations, small vegetable plots, indoors, etc. Dimensions 12 x 10 x 18 cm. In orange, yellow, or white). Using this technique, populations of adult male *P. gossypiella* trapped in the field were shown to be more resistant to permethrin and fenvalerate in field

frequently treated with pyrethroids than in fields with little or no exposure to these insecticides. The new method eliminates handling of insects that is involved in other methods of assessing toxicity and is compatible with the current practice of monitoring populations with pheromone traps. Schouest and Miller (1988) measured toxicities of fenvalerate and permethrin on a laboratory strain of adult male of pink bollworm by attracticide bioassay. Delta trap was used with a sticky adhesive-coated cards insert containing the insecticide concentration placed in the trap bottom. A rubber septum with 1 mg gossyplure acted as a pheromone source. The caught moths were placed in constant temperature chambers. Data from the attracticide bioassay fit the probit model well and gave a precise estimate of a discriminating dose. Tabashnik *et al.* (1988) monitored resistance in diamondback moth larvae by testing pheromone-attracted males. Three populations were tested for mortality and knockdown responses to fenvalerate, DDT, permethrin and diazinon. Males and females responded similarly. Adult mortality and knockdown were correlated with larval LC_{50} 's across insecticide – population combinations, but adults from one population with DDT-resistant larvae were not resistant to DDT. Brewer and Trumble (1989) developed a technique for monitoring insecticide resistance in field populations of beet armyworm *Spodoptera exigua* (Hubner), and compared with conventional topical bioassay. Insecticides were incorporated into the adhesive of a pheromone trap thereby combining insect collection with insecticide application. This attractant trap technique (ATT) provided stable LC_{50} 's with low control mortality when traps were incubated at 21 °C for 30-36 hrs. after insects were captured. LC_{50} 's of a laboratory colony tested with

fenvalerate, permethrin and methomyl were 95.6, 142 and 11.5 $\mu\text{g/g}$ of adhesive, respectively. Slopes of probit regression for males were similar for topical and ATT bioassay indicating a parallel response of the insect to the two methods. Resistance ratios at LC_{50} from (ATT) ranged from 3 to 7.3 for fenvalerate, 1.5 to 2.5 for permethrin and 7.1 to 33 for methomyl.

Campanhola and Plapp (1989) conducted tests to detect reasons for the loss of pyrethroid resistance which occurs in laboratory and field strains of the tobacco budworm in the absence of continuous exposure to pyrethroid insecticides. Attracticide pheromone traps were used in these tests. Larvae of a resistant strain (ICI) maintained in the laboratory developed more slowly than larvae of susceptible laboratory strain. The ICI females were less fertile and produced fewer eggs per individual than susceptible females. In addition, ICI females produced significantly less pheromone and attracted fewer males than did susceptible females. Susceptible males were more attracted to pheromone traps than resistant males. Knight and Hull (1989) investigated the use of sex pheromone traps to monitor the susceptibility of adult male tufted apple bud moths to azinophosmethyl in laboratory experiments and field trials in a number of apple orchards in South Central Pennsylvania and West Virginia. Two techniques were compared: the topical treatment of males caught on the trap's sticky surface and the incorporation of the insecticide directly into the adhesive. Compared with the laboratory strain, LD_{50} 's populations from apple orchards were 2 to 8 times greater in the topical application bioassays and 6 to 18 times greater in the adhesive incorporation assay. Sanderson *et al.* (1989) used yellow sticky cards with thin layers of insecticide – sticker mixture as a bioassay to determine insecticide

resistance in adult *Liriomyza trifolii*, (Burgess) (Diptera: Agromyzidae), mortality was used to estimate the degree of resistance of a given population to insecticides. Duration of exposure to insecticide before mortality evaluation was standardized at 24 hrs. Control mortality increased with increasing amounts of sticker on the cards and with increasing adult age. Males were slightly more susceptible to permethrin and chlorpyrifos insecticides than females. The sticky card bioassay a simple procedure that is accurate repeatable and usable for field or greenhouse populations. Brewer *et al.* (1990) used a field bioassay that measure adult male susceptibility to document resistance to fenvalerate, permethrin and methomyl in beet armyworm *S. exiqua*. Susceptibility of adult males to these insecticides was monitored in field with technical insecticide mixed into the adhesive of pheromone traps. At the LC_{50} , the highest levels of resistance were typically found at many sites. Geographic and temporal variability in resistance followed this trend: overall variation among regions > variation among sampling dated at the same site within a region \geq variation among sites in a region within three consecutive days. Knight *et al.* (1990) used sex pheromone traps coated with concentrations of azinophosmethyl impregnated adhesive to test levels of resistance in adult populations of male tufted apple bud moth from apple orchards in seven Eastern States. The results suggest that the level of resistance found within an orchard may be influenced the intensity of fruit production within a region. Level of resistance to azinophosmethyl was positively correlated with current seasonal carbamate use and was not significantly correlated with current use of azinophosmethyl or other organophosphates. Levels of resistance

and fruit injury were both significantly correlated with population densities. Miller (1990) determined the toxicity of carbamate, organophosphorus and pyrethroids insecticides by the attracticide method to field populations of pink bollworm in cotton growing areas of Texas, Arizona, California, Mexico and China. A gradual increase in tolerance to pyrethroid was correlated with high use of these insecticides. A resistance management program for insecticides used in control of pink bollworm is now a possibility and will require considerable cooperation at the grower level. Rummel (1990) reported that during recent years the use of pheromone traps has enabled significant advances to be made in survey, detection and sampling techniques for the boll weevil, pink bollworm, bollworm *Heliothis zea* (Boddie) and tobacco budworm *H. virescens* (F) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae).

Daly (1992) determined the dose response in different age classes of adults of *H. armigera* (H) by exposing moths to a discriminating dose of fenvalerate using an adult vial test and reported a decline in survival with age so that by 8d after exclusion 60-70% of resistant females and 97% resistant males died at the discriminating dose compared with < 5% of freshly emerged moths. Prabhaker *et al.* (1992) detected resistance in field populations of sweet potato whitefly, efficiently and sensitively using a resistance monitoring technique with yellow sticky cards sprayed with insecticides. Thirty-two populations exhibited various levels of resistance to sulprofos (Resistance ratio [RR] ranging from 19 to 104 and for cypermethrin (RR ranging from 14 to 82) indicating that insecticide resistance is widespread in the Imperial Valley of California. The advantages of this new method for monitoring resistance are discussed in relation to conventional leaf bioassay.

Sanderson and Roush (1992) investigated the use of insect trap coated with insecticides mixed with a polybutene adhesive as a resistance monitoring technique for greenhouse whitefly. The technique provided accurate estimates of the mortality response of whiteflies after 24h, with minimal control mortality. The technique was used to estimate diagnostic concentration (LC₉₉ of a susceptible strain) and then they were tested against the susceptible and resistant strains. Bush *et al.* (1993) performed a sticky-card bioassay on adult males captured with traps that revealed an 8 fold resistance to parathion in a population of codling moth *C. pomonella*. Parathion resistance in this population was confirmed with a sticky-card bioassay where adult males were exposed to a diagnostic concentration of 120 µg (a.i) parathion per gram adhesive (The estimated LC₉₅ for adult males from susceptible populations). Reduced nonspecific esterase activity detected in adult males captured from the mechanism of codling moth, *C. pomonella* resistance to parathion may be a modified esterase with lower specificity for naphthyl acetate substrates.

Horowitz *et al.* (1993) assayed the efficacy of the insecticide resistance management strategy, a long-term monitoring program in *H. armigera* was undertaken to test the response of this pest to various insecticides. The monitoring technique was based on the exposure of pheromone trap-caught males to groups of insecticides. The diagnostic concentration, established on LC₈₀₋₉₀ of a susceptible *H. armigera* field population were 0.57 µg endosulfan, 0.74 µg cypermethrin, 0.38 µg methomyl and 2.0 µg methidathion per scintillation vials. In general, the results indicate that the susceptibility of *H. armigera* to the test compounds was

not appreciably altered from 1987 to 1991, although fluctuations during the season were observed, in most cases, the resistance levels to the test compounds fluctuated in a typical V-shaped curve during the season. The susceptibility of *H. armigera* to the various insecticides observed during the course of this study is consistent with proposition that the insecticide resistance management (IRM) strategy can be correlated with successful management of resistance in this pest. Qureshi *et al.* (1993) used the male moth catches in gossypure-baited traps to predict larval infestation of pink bollworm, *P. gossypiella*, in cotton fields during 1988 and 1989. The mean moth catches per trap per night were positively correlated with percentage larval infestation. The moth counts in traps and larval infestation in green bolls increased with advance in reproductive stage of the cotton plants. A mean trap catch of 9–12 pink bollworm moths per night was associated with economically damaging infestation. It is, therefore, inferred that insecticidal sprays may be scheduled when 9–12 moths are captured per trap per night. Varela *et al.* (1993) surveyed variation in response to insecticide in codling moth in California, Oregon, Utah and Washington using pheromone traps by two techniques (Topical application and direct incorporation of insecticide into the trap adhesive). LC₇₅ from a susceptible population was as a standard dose and 20 apple and pear orchards were monitored for resistance to azinphos-methyl by the topical application. In laboratory tests, female moths were monitored as susceptible as male moths in bioassays with treated adhesive. Anonymous (1995) used an attracticide resistance monitoring technique with a set of key techniques system of integrated management against several damage by the cotton bollworm, *H. armigera* in Xin Xiang,

China Demonstration Area, Henan, in the central Yellow River Valley cotton region in 1992 and 1993. Outbreaks of *H. armigera* were effectively controlled and good harvests were obtained using these techniques. These included improved medium term predication techniques, setting up action thresholds, measures to use and conserve natural enemies, systematic monitoring and management of insecticide resistance using pest resistance cotton germplasm and trapping adult noctuids.

Downham *et al.* (1995) described a series of trials examining the feasibility of an attracticide technique for control of *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisduval). Those trials were assessed by monitoring pheromone trap catches. Similar levels of mating and trap-catch suppression were observed in the two treatments. It was concluded that the mating suppression observed in attracticide plots was due principally to disruption of chemical communication between the sexes, not to male mortality arising from contact with the insecticide sources. Al-Beltagy *et al.* (1996) used pheromone delta sticky traps as an attracticide tolerance monitoring technique in two different locations having two different control strategies for the pink bollworm; one depending on insecticides and the other on pheromone disruption. The field recommended dose as its double and half rates of insecticides dursban and sumicidin were applied to the pheromone delta traps with pheromone sources for the pink bollworm, spiny bollworm. Pheromone tarps as an attracticide tolerance monitoring technique proved to be effective, simple and quick for assaying the moth field strains of Lepidoptera for insecticide resistance. Shekeban (2000) compare the efficiency of the attracticide resistance monitoring technique with different conventional bioassay

techniques and vial technique. Al-Beltagy *et al.* (2001) used attracticide resistance monitoring technique for measuring insecticide resistance in pink bollworm (PBW) male moths, *P. gossypiella* (S). This technique eliminates handling of insect and is compatible with current practice of monitoring populations with pheromone traps. Results showed that, PBW developed resistance to all insecticides tested with R.R. of 19 and 12.7 folds for chlorpyrifos, 14.1 and 34.7 folds for deltamethrin, 14.1 and 38.5 folds for emperin and 22.6 and 56 folds for thiodicarb, respectively. This technique used to estimate discriminating concentration for tested insecticides. El-Bassiony (2001) used the attracticide resistance monitoring technique to study pyrethroids resistance under two different pink bollworm control strategies (pheromone disruption technique and insecticides program . El-Armi (2008) used the attracticide resistance monitoring technique to study the development of insecticides resistance against pink bollworm in two different geographical strains.

2. Pheromone traps uses:

2.1. For assaying and monitoring insect pests population density and dynamics all the year round (Al-Beltagy *et al.*, 1991). **2.2.** For assaying insect pests geographical distribution throughout its regional and seasonal abundance (Brania and Al-Beltagy, 1996). **2.3.** For insect pests mass trapping technique as a pest control tool (Hamid and Al-Beltagy,1995). **2.4.** For assaying insecticides resistance development in insect pests field strains (Al-Beltagy *et al.*, 1996 ; Al-Beltagy *et al.*, 2000 and Al-Beltagy *et al.*, 2010). **2.5.** For measuring the successful of a pheromone disruption technique applied against any insect pest (Al-Beltagy *et al.*, 2001a and 2001b). **2.6.** For triggering biological and / or

chemical control action (Al-Beltagy, 1999). **2.7.** For assaying the efficiency of different insecticides before any insecticide treatment (Al-Beltagy *et al.*, 2011).

3. Procedure :

3.1. Attracticide resistance monitoring technique (ARMT) :

A novel resistance monitoring method was created and perfected for pink bollworm by Miller (1986) and Haynes *et al.* (1986 a and 1987) and was modified by Al-Beltagy *et al.*(1996) and Shekeban (2000) under the Egyptian conditions. This method employs pheromone baited delta traps (Figure 1) that are usually used for assessment of populations of male moths. The conventional yellow paper delta traps supplied by the Ministry of Agriculture in Egypt are used for the population assessment in different cotton fields all over the country.

3.2. Laboratory bioassays:

For ARMT laboratory bioassays, serial concentrations of each tested formulated pyrethroid and organophosphorous are diluted in acetone and mixed with sticky material. Condensed petroleum glue, as a trapped sticker, produced by Agrycins Corp., England, and supplied by Ministry of Agriculture, are used. Two grams of the sticky adhesive and different insecticide concentrations for pyrethroids ranged from 0.05 to 20 ppm and for OP's ranged from 1 to 240 ppm. Each concentration for each insecticide is replicated three times on separate sheet card. Control without insecticide is included. Male moths are transferred from the rearing facility to the bioassay laboratory. Ten male moths are captured and stuck to the yellow sticky card which is treated before with the insecticide concentration as mentioned. The insert cards are kept under constant conditions of $21 \pm 3^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $95 \pm 5\%$ R.H. Adult mortalities are recorded at 6 and 12 h-periods. Mortality is subjected

for probit analysis to estimate LC_{50} , LC_{95} and slope. Resistance ratios (R.R.) at LC_{50} (or LC_{95}) are calculated by dividing each value for field strain, of each species, by corresponding value of laboratory reference strain.

3.3. Preparation of insecticide-pheromone-baited sticky trap:

For preparation of pheromone-baited sticky trap laced with an insecticide the following technique is used: serial concentrations of each tested pyrethroid and organophosphorous formulations are diluted in acetone and mixed with sticky material. Condensed petroleum glue, as a trapped sticker, produced by Agrycins Corp., England, and supplied by Ministry of Agriculture, is used. Two grams of the sticky adhesive and an insecticide concentration are scaped on the trap insect sheet cards (Inserts) using putty knife starting with the lowest concentration and ending to the highest one, every time the putty knife is washed with kerosene and dried. Six diluted concentrations from each insecticide are used, with relative folds of the field recommended rate (F). 0.125 F, 0.25 F, 0.5 F, 1 F, 1.5 F and 2 F. These inserts (cards) are secured with paper for attracticide resistance monitoring technique (ARMT) field bioassays, the traps are baited with an appropriate commercially available pheromone lures (Figure 2) supplied by the Ministry of Agriculture in Egypt, for trapping techniques.

3.4. Field experiments:

The field experiments are carried out twice during the growing seasons: 1) at the early-season when plant buds emerged, and 2) at the late-season when the fruits are up to the maturity as following steps: - Traps are hung on stakes higher 20-30 cm above the canopy of the plants and distributed by a rate of one trap / five feddans. - The dosed insert cards and control cards are placed into the delta traps with a

pheromone source, randomly. All cards are inserted before sunset.

- Traps are left overnight and collect quickly in the following morning. - All insert cards are collected at dawn with trapped adult male moths (Figure 3) and checked for mortality %, this termed the zero time mortality %, then placed each insert card into the holding container (Figure 4) . - The cards are collected at dawn to avoid the heat of the day, the trapped moths will not be well if they were allowed to warm up in the morning sun. - Cards are kept away of the sun in the shadow until they delivered from the field to their storage sites.- It is very important to store the insert cards in the holding containers in a constant temperature 21 ± 3 °C for 12 hours. After 6 hr and 12 hr cards are removed from container and mortality are recorded. - The adults are scored as alive if any movement is recorded (i.e., leg, abdomen, wing even the antenna). The insects are recorded as died if they do not move at all. - Each dose and control are replicated three times.- When all doses and cards are accounted and all insects are checked for mortality, these data together with the mortality of controls for each insecticide are analyzed by probit analysis computer program (Finney, 1971) to determine slope, LC_{50} and LC_{95} values. Resistance ratios (RR) at LC_{50} or LC_{95} are calculated by dividing LC_{50} for field strain, of each species, by LC_{50} of laboratory (Reference) strain. Abbott's formula (Abbott, 1925) is used to correct mortality according to mortality control traps.

4. Biochemical confirmations :

Biochemical studies (Enzymes and /or proteins) are conducted for the confirmation of insecticides resistance development in insect pest field strains data that are recorded by the pheromone traps technique, throughout enzymes activity determinations and total protein electrophoretic assays (Al-Beltagy,

1993, Albeltagy *et al.*, 2001a and Albeltagy *et al.*, 2001 b).

5. The recommendation:

Many advantages have been indicated for the use of the attracticide resistance monitoring technique (ARMT), some of these advantages – as a tool for indicating the efficacy of different insecticides are :- **5.1.** It is easy, whereas no need to complicate equipment or high technology tools, but only use some delta pheromone traps. **5.2.** It is speed, whereas it is applied by sunset and get data by next morning sunrise, just after about 12 hours of applications. **5.3.** It is effective, whereas it is applied in a very short

period (As mentioned above), so there is no interference of any changeable environmental conditions . **5.4.** It is applied directly against the field insect population strains, whereas no need for the mass rearing techniques and facilities. **5.5.** It is very accurate – for the above mentioned advantages – compared to the conventional insecticide bioassay techniques which depend on the application against insect colonies that are got from rearing facilities for a few generations which cause that these strains may be very closed to the susceptible strains.

Figure (1): Yellow paper delta pheromone traps over cotton plants.

Figure (2) : Rubber septum pheromone sources.

Figure (3): Adult moths stuck to sticky sheet.

Figure (4): Adult moths holding container.

References

- Abbott, W.S. (1925):** A method of computing the effectiveness of an insecticide. *J. Econ. Entomol.*, 18 : 265-267.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M. ; El-Mourshedy, and Mourad, A.K. (1996):** Pheromone traps for monitoring insecticide tolerance in three different lepidopterous insects: an effective tool for insecticide resistance management. *Egypt. J. Agric. Res.*, 74 (1): 29-37.
- Al-Beltagy, A. M.; Radwan, H. S. ; El-Bermawy, Z. A. ; Nassar, M. E. ; Yousef, A. G. and Shekeban, M. M. (2001):** Attracticide resistance monitoring technique for assaying insecticide resistance in pink bollworm male moths, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (S) field populations. *Egypt. J. Agric. Res.*, 79 (3): 949-963.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M. ; Shawir, M. S. ; Osman, K.A. ; Abo El-Saad, M.M. and Mourad, M. A. (1993):** Biochemical technique for measuring susceptibility of pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* to certain insecticides. *Alex. J. Agric. Res.*, 38 (3): 393-411.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M.; Radwan, H.S. ; Abo El-Ghar, G.E. ; Ammar, I.M. ; Eisa, A.A. ; Shekiban, M.M. and El Bassiony, M.M. (2001a):** Biochemical impact of pyrethroid resistance management in bollworms field populations with Gossyplure disruption technique .1- in

- relation to total protein electrophoretic analysis. J. Adv. Agric. Res. , 6(4) : 1029 –1041 .
- Al-Beltagy, A.M.; Radwan, H.S. ; Abo El-Ghar, G.E. ; Ammar, I.M. ; Eisa, A.A. ; Shekiban, M.M. and El Bassiony, M.M. (2001b) .** Biochemical impact of pyrethroid resistance management in bollworms field populations with Gossyplure disruption technique .2- in relation to AchE and total esterases activity determination. J. Adv. Agric. Res. , 6(4) : 1043 – 1055 .
- Al-Beltagy, A.M.; Shaker, N.; Taman, F.A. and El-Khishen, S.A. (1991):** The influence of pheromone traps on the infestation percentages and population density of bollworms in Alexandria and Al-Behera Governorates. Proc. of the 4th Arab Congress of Plant Prot., Cairo, 1-5 Dec., 7 (3): 477-487.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M.; Shawir, M.S.; Othman, E.A.; Abo-Elsaad, M.M. and Mourad, M.A. (1993):** Biochemical techniques for measuring susceptibility of pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* to certain insecticides., Alex. J. Agric. Res., 38 (3): 393-411.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M.; Shekeban, M. M.K. ; Abo El-Amayem, M.M.; Kassem, S. M. I. ; Mancee, A.H. and EL-Arami, S.A. (2010 :** Monitoring for Pyrethroid resistance in pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) field strains . Pest Management Newsletter , 19(2) : 46-52 .
- Al-Beltagy, A.M; Abo El-Amayem, M.M.; Kassem, S. M. I.; Mancee, A.H.; Shekeban, M. M.K. and EL-Arami, S.A. (2011):** Assaying insecticidal efficacy of some formulated organophosphorus insecticides against pink bollworm male moth field strains using the attracticide efficacy monitoring technique. Resistant Pest Management Newsletter, 21 (2): 7-13.
- Al-Beltagy; A.M (1999):** Plant and insect triggers for sequential use of gossyplure and insecticides for pink bollworm control actions . Egypt J. Agric. Res., 77(4) : 1633 – 1643 .
- Anonymous (1995):** A study of the key technique system of integrated management against severe damage by the cotton bollworm. CAB Abstracts; record 9 of 19.
- Brania , H. A. A. and Al-Beltagy, A.M. (1996):** Regional and seasonal variations of pink bollworm trap catches and boll infestation relationships. Alex. J. Agric. Res., 41 (3): 77-84.
- Brewer, M.J. ; Trumble, J.T.; Rodrigues, B.A. and Chaney, W.E. (1990):** Beet armyworm adult and larval susceptibility to three insecticides in managed habitats and relationship to laboratory selection for resistance. J. Econ. Entomol., 83(6):2136-2146.
- Brewer, M.J. and Trumble, J.T. (1989):** Field monitoring for insecticide resistance in beet armyworm. J. Econ. Entomol., 82(6): 1525-1526.
- Bush, M.R.; Abd El-Aal, Y.A.I. and Rock, G. C. (1993):** Parathion resistance and esterase activity in codling moth (Lepidoptera: Tortricidae) from North Carolina J. Econ. Entomol., 86(3):660-666.
- Campanhola, C. and Plapp, Jr F.W. (1989):** Pyrethroid resistance in the tobacco budworm

- (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) insecticide bioassay and field monitoring. J. Econ. Entomol., 82(1):22 -28.
- Daly, J.C. (1992):** Decline in survival with age of resistance adult *Helicoverpa armigera* (Lepidoptera : Noctuidae) at a discriminating dose of the pyrethroid fenvalerate. J. Econ. Entomol., 83(3):705 -709.
- Downham, M.C.A. ; Mc Veigh, L.J. and Moawad, G.M. (1995):** Field investigation of an attracticide control technique using the sex pheromone of the Egyptian cotton leafworm *Spodoptera littoralis* (Lepidoptera : Noctuidae). Bull. Entomol. Res., 85: 463-472.
- El-Armi, S. A. A. (2008):** Insecticides efficacy of some insecticide formulations under certain environmental conditions. Ph. D. Thesis, Pesticides Chemisry, Fac. Of Agric., Alexandria University.
- El-Bassiony M. M. (2001):** Studies on the management of pyrethroid resistance in bollworm populations in cotton fields. Ph. D.Thesis, Pesticides Department, Menoufiya University.
- Finney, D. J. (1971):** Probit analysis. A Statistical Treatment of the Sigmoid Response Cure. 7th Ed., Cambridge Univ. Press, England.
- Georghiou, G.P. (1983):** Management of resistance in arthropods pp. 769-792. In G.P. Georghiou and T. Satto (eds), pest resistance to pesticides. Plenum, New York.
- Hamid, A.M. and Al-Beltagy, A.M. (1995):** Mass-trapping technique for pink bollworm control. Proc. of 1st Int. Conf. of Pest Control, Mansoura, Egypt, 3-5 Sept: 189-195.
- Haynes, K.F. ; Li, W.G. and Baker , T.C. (1986 a):** Control of pink bollworm moth (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) with insecticides and pheromones (Attracticide): lethal and sublethal effects. J. Econ. Entomol., 79 (2): 1466-1471.
- Haynes, K.F. ; Miller, T.A. ; Staten, R.T. ; Li, W.G. and Baker, T.C. (1987):** Pheromone traps for monitoring insecticide resistance in the pink bollworm moth (Lepidoptera : Gelechiidae) : New tool for resistance management. Environ.Entomol., 16:84-89.
- Haynes, K.F. ; Miller, T.A. ; Staten, R.T. ; Li, W.G. and Baker, T.C. (1986 c):** Monitoring insecticide resistance with insect pheromone. Experientia., 42:1293-1295.
- Haynes, K.F.; Parrella , M.P.; Tumble, J.T. and Miller, T.A. (1986 b):** Monitoring insecticide resistance with yellow sticky cards. California Agric., 11-12.
- Henneberry, T.J. and Clayton, T. E. (1982):** Pink bollworm of cotton (*Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders)): male moth catches in gossyplure-baited traps and relationships to oviposition, boll infestation and moth emergence. Crop Protection., 1(4):497-504.
- Horowitz, A.R. ; Seligman, I. M. ; Forere, G. ; Bar, D. and Ishaaya, I. (1993):** Preventive insecticide resistance strategy in (*Helicoverpa armigera*) *Heliothis armigera* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) in Israel cotton. J. Econ. Entomol., 86 (2) : 205-212.
- Knight, A. L ; Hull, L.A. ; Rajotte, E. ; Hogmire, H. ; Horton, D. ;**

- Polk, D. ; Walgenbach, J.; Weires, R. and Wnalon, J. (1990):** Monitoring azinphos-methyl resistance in adult male *Platynota idaeusalis*. (Lepidoptera : Tortricidae) in apple from Georgia to New York. J. Econ. Entomol., 83(2):329-334.
- Knight, A. L. and Hull, L. A. (1989):** Sex pheromone traps to monitor azinphosmethyl resistance in tufted apple bud moth (Lepidoptera: Tortricidae). J. Econ. Entomol., 82(4): 1019-1026 .
- Miller, T.A. (1986):** Status of resistance in the cotton insect complex. Beltwide Cotton Production Research Conf., 162-165.
- Miller, T.A. (1990):** Resistance monitoring of pink bollworm California Department of Food and Agriculture (CDFA), pink bollworm final report , 146-147.
- Mink, J.S. and Boethel, D.J. (1992):** Development of a diagnostic technique for monitoring permethrin resistance in soybean looper larvae (Lepidoptera : Noctuidae). J.Econ. Entomol., 85(4):10565-10620.
- Pasquier, D. and Charmillot, P.J. (2003):** Effectiveness of twelve insecticides applied topically to diapausing larvae of the codling moth, *Cydia pomonella* L. Pest. Manag. Sci., 60 (3):305–308.
- Pimentel, D. (2005):** Environmental and economic costs of the application of pesticides primarily in the United States. Environ. Develop. and Sustain., 7 (2): 229-252.
- Prabhaker, N. ; Toscano, N.C. ; Perring, T.M. ; Nuessley, G. ; Kido, K. and Youngman, R.R. (1992):** Resistance monitoring of the sweet potato whitefly in the imperial valley of California. J. Econ. Entomol., 85 (4):1063-1068.
- Qureshi, Z. A. ; Ahmad, N. and Hussain, T. (1993):** Pheromone trap catches as a means of predicting damage by pink bollworm larvae in cotton. Crop. Protection, 12(8): 597-600.
- Riedl, H. ; Seaman, A. and Henrie, F. (1985):** Monitoring susceptibility to azinphos-methyl in field population of the codling moth (Lepidoptera: Tortricidae) with pheromone traps. J. Econ. Entomol., 78 (1) : 692-699.
- Roush, R. T. and McKenzie, J. A. (1987):** Ecological genetics of insecticide and acaricide resistance. Ann.Rev. Entomol., 32: 361-380.
- Roush, R.T. and Miller, G.L. (1986):** Considerations for design of insecticide. J. Econ. Entomol., 87 (2): 184-192.
- Rummel, D.R. (1990): **Pheromone in pest detection and pest management, CDFa, pink bollworm final report., 145-146.**
- Sanderson, J.P. and Roush, R.T. (1992):** Monitoring insecticide resistance in green house whitefly with yellow sticky cards. J. Econ. Entomol., 85(3):634-642.
- Sanderson, J.P. ; M.P. Parrella and J.T. Trumble (1989).** Monitoring insecticide resistance in *Liriomyza trifolii* (Diptera : Agromyzidae) with yellow sticky cards. J. Econ. Entomol., 82(4):1011-1018.
- Schouest, L.P. Jr. and Miller, T.A. (1988):** Factors influencing pyrethroid toxicity in pink bollworm (Lepidoptera :

- Gelechiidae) : Implications for resistance management. J. Econ. Entomol., 81(2):431-436.
- Shekeban, M. M. K. (2000):** Studies on insecticide resistance in certain major cotton insects Department of Pesticides, Faculty of Agriculture, Menoufiya University.
- Tabashnik, B.E. ; Rethwisch, M.D. and Johnson, M.W. (1988):** Variation in adults mortality and knockdown caused by insecticides among populations of diamondback moth (Lepidoptera : Plutellidae). J.Econ. Entomol., 81(2):437-441.
- Tabashnik, B.E. and Cushing, N.L. (1987):** Leaf residues topical bioassay for assessing insecticide resistance in the diamondback moth. FAO plant Prot. Bull., 35:11-14.
- Tamhankar, A.J. ; Gahukar, R.T. and Rajendran, T.P. (2000):** Pheromones in the management of major lepidopterous and coleopterous pests of cotton. Integr. Pest. Manag. Rev., 5 (1) :11-23.
- Varela, L.G.; Wекter, S.C.; Jones, V.P.; Brunner, J.F. and Riedl, H. (1993):.** Monitoring and characterization of insecticide resistance in codling moth (Lepidoptera : Tortricidae) in four Western States. J. Econ. Entomol., 86 (1): 1-10.

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Study on the comparative efficacy of different insecticides for management of onion thrips *Thrips tabaci* (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) and its yield in Afghanistan

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Abstract:

This study was conducted to determine the effects of different insecticide applications on onion thrips *Thrips tabaci* (Lindeman) (Thysanoptera: Thripidae), management, and onion yield in two different locations. The study was carried out at the research farm of Agriculture faculties of, Kabul and Nangarhar Universities, during 2019. The experiment was laid out in Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) using carbaryl WP 950 g/ hectare, lambda-cyhalothrin EC 900 ml/ hectare, cypermethrin EC 900 ml/ hectare, emamectin benzoate EC 900 ml/hectare, acetameprid SL 950 g/hectare and chlorpyrifos SL 900 g/hectare. Twenty four hours prior to insecticide application, the experimental plots were first recorded in the presence of thrips population and at 24 hours, 3 days, and 7 days post application. The results showed that acetamiprid SL was the most effective insecticide to reduce the onion thrips population and increase the yield followed by chlorpyrifos SL and carbaryl WP, while emamectin benzoate EC was the least effective. The same trend of the effectiveness of insecticides was observed in both experimental sites. Our study showed that the efficacy of acetameprid SL, chlorpyrifos SL and carbaryl WP were significantly higher in comparing to emamectin benzoate EC, lambda-cyhalothrin EC and cypermethrin EC respectively.

Introduction

Onion, *Allium cepa* (L.) is one of the most important products all around the world. It is an important condiment and vegetable for Afghans. The green leaves and bulbs are eaten either raw or used in the preparation of several recipes. In the Afghan food market, onion has a high value among other vegetables (Minoia *et al.*, 2015). It is widely grown in most European, American, Asian and some African countries (Duchovskiene, 2006; Gholami *et al.*, 2015 and Shang *et al.*, 2016).

Several pests attack the onion plant, but onion thrips *Thrips tabaci* (Lindeman) (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) is considered one of the very important pests (Ananthkrishnan, 1993; Ashghar *et al.*, 2018 and Azazy *et al.*, 2018). The onion thrips is a polyphagous insect that is widespread on all continents and is recognized as a harmful economic pest of field and greenhouse crops all around the world (Fernandes *et al.*, 2015; El-Naggar and Zidan, 2013 and Bielza *et al.*, 2009).

Dry and hot weather can increase

the population of onion thrips and the severity of damage to onions. The reason for this is probably due to a combination of factors, such as lower generation time and reduced rainfall and plant pathogen mortality (Badillo-Vargas *et al.*, 2015; Demirozer *et al.*, 2012 and Broughton *et al.*, 2011). Heavy rains have been shown to wash onion thrips from plants (De Brujin *et al.*, 2006) . Additionally, water stress may impact the nutritional quality of onion plants and also increase the attractiveness of the plants to thrips (Cannon *et al.*, 2007; Din *et al.*, 2016 ; Jacobson *et al.*, 2016 and Brunner *et al.*, 2004). The larval stages of the onion thrips can transmit virus diseases such as Tomato spotted wilt virus (TSWV), Iris yellow spot virus (IYV) that is caused by the tospovirus (El-Wakeil *et al.* , 2010; Gill *et al.*, 2015 and Fernandes *et al.*, 2015) . Iris yellow spot virus (IYSV) has emerged in recent years as high priority, invasive or potential threats to sustainable onion production (Nault and Shelton , 2010 ; Jacobson, 2016 and Gao *et al.*, 2012). The immature stages of *T. tabaci* prefer to live in the central leaves of the plant and reduce their photosynthetic ability. Onion thrips has a wide host range that is reported to feed on more than 300 plants (Guillén *et al.*, 2014 ; Hussain *et al.*, 1997; Hodges *et al.*, 2009 and Kaur *et al.*, 2017). For example, in Hawaii, 66 plants from 25 families were found to be attacked by onion thrips (Jones *et al.*, 2005; Khaliq *et al.*, 2016 and Kudom *et al.*, 2015). It has been found that the vegetables such as cabbage, cantaloupe, carrot, cauliflower, asparagus, bean, beet, celery, cowpea, cucumber, garlic, kale, leek, mustard, parsley, pea, pepper, squash, sweet potato, tomato, turnip, pigeon pea, potato, pumpkin and spinach more attacked by thrips (Kay and Herron, 2010 ; Khan *et al.*, 2017 and Loomans, 2003). Under the field conditions, thrips cause the most damage to the onion, followed by edible-podded pea and cabbage (Khaliq *et al.*, 2014; Kadri and Goud, 2006; Lopez *et al.*, 2008 and Maliniak *et al.*, 2012).

Vegetables such as cucumber and tomato are grown in the greenhouse, onion thrips can sometimes cause serious damage. Field crops, especially cotton, oats, alfalfa, sugar beets, soybeans, tobacco, and wheat may also be affected by

onion thrips. Ornamental crops like carnation and rose may be supported, especially when planted under greenhouse conditions (Maniania *et al.*, 2003; Mautino *et al.*, 2012; Nikolova and Georgieva, 2014 and Mandi and Senapati, 2009). Leaves of onion are curled, wrinkled and dried after being infected with onion thrips. This pest is very active at flowering time which adversely affects seed yield and viability (Sonderholm, 2010; Pourian *et al.*, 2009 and Sedaratian *et al.*, 2010). Nutrition of *T. tabaci* destroys the epidermal cells of the onion causing the leaf whitening due to sucking of the sub epidermal cell contents by adults and larvae (Sharma, 2014 and Shelton *et al.*, 2009) . In general, onion thrips feeds most when the onion is young, and when the bulbs are rapidly enlarging (Sonderholm, 2010 ; Srivastava *et al.*, 2014 ; Shelton *et al.*, 2008; Zezlina and Blazic, 2003 and Sadozai *et al.*, 2009). Falling water from damaged leaf surfaces can cause stress and reduce plant growth and accelerate leaf aging, both of which may shorten the period of bulbs enlargement (Toda and Murai, 2007 and Ullah *et al.*, 2010). In New York, a 30-50% decrease in bulb yield (Smaller bulbs sizes) may occur due to severe thrips damage. Thrips may also feed onion bulbs after harvesting and storage, and this can cause scarring, which may affect the appearance and quality of the bulbs (Ananthakrishnan, 1993; Bielza *et al.*, 2009 and Gandhale *et al.*, 1984) .

The current experiment was conducted to study the population of *T. tabaci* in the Agriculture Faculty of Kabul University and, in the Agriculture Faculty of Nangarhar University to find out the efficacy of various chemical insecticides for the management of *T. tabaci* that will result in the increasing onion yield.

Materials and methods

1. Experimental sites:

An onion variety “White Ghorbandi” was obtained from the research farm of agriculture faculties of Kabul and Nangarhar Universities and planted on May 31, 2019, at the research farm of Agriculture Faculty of Kabul and on January 8, 2019 at Nangarhar University at latitude 34.5281296 and 34.4264717 and longitude 69.1723328 and 70.4515305, in the northern hemisphere, respectively. The

experiment was designed in a Complete Randomized Block Design (CRBD) with seven treatments and five replications. The total number of plots was 35 and each plot size was 2 × 2.5 m. The distance between plant-plant and row-row was kept 35 cm and 50 cm, respectively. The main irrigation channel of 1.0 m, Sub-irrigation channel of 1.0 m, and width of bund 0.5 m were kept. The total length of the experimental area was 39 m² with the gross cultivated area of 378 m².

2. Fertilizers and insecticides:

The insecticides were purchased from the local markets and applied to the experimental area at the recommended rate. The crops were carefully observed at the weekly intervals to monitor the number of thrips and insecticides were applied when the population reached the economic threshold level (ETL) (39.6 thrips /plant). The insecticide application rate was as follows: Carbamate (Carbaryl 950 g/hectare), organophosphorus OP (Chlorpyrifos 900 ml/hectare), synthetic pyrethroids (Lambda-cyhalothrin 2.5% EC 900 ml, cypermethrin EC10% 900 ml/hectare), neonicotinoid (Acetamiprid 20% SL 950g/hectare) and antibiotic group (Emamectin benzoate 1.9% EC 900 ml/ hectare). Only water was applied as a control treatment. Insecticides were applied with a knapsack sprayer three times during the growing season within 38 day intervals (From 29 February to 5 April in Nangarhar province and 18 July to 25 August in Kabul province). The rate of DAP and Urea was used as 80 kg/ha and 120 kg/ha, respectively.

3. Determining the thrips population:

The number of thrips was counted three times before the spraying. After the application of insecticides, the number of thrips was recorded at 1, 3, and 7-days interval. Before using insecticides, the number of onion thrips was recorded at regular intervals by selecting five onion plants from each sampling unit. The post spray data were recorded at 1, 3, and 7 days post-application.

4. Yield assessment:

At the end of the growth period and complete drying of the onion leaves, the performance of all cultured treatments was

examined separately. Onion tubers were mechanically harvested, and the total product weight was calculated per hectare.

5. Data analysis:

The mean data from 5 replications were analyzed with one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) using Statistical Analysis Software (SAS) (SAS Institute, 2002) and the means were compared with the least significant difference (LSD) for significant differences between the variables. The bio-efficacy percentage was calculated by using the method reported previously by Shiberu and Negeri (2012).

$$\text{Efficacy (\%)} = \frac{\text{Pre spray count} - \text{Post spray count}}{\text{Pre-spray count}} \times 100$$

$$\text{Reduction efficacy \%} = \frac{\text{Control count} - \text{Post spray count}}{\text{Control count}} \times 100$$

Results and discussion

1. Determining the thrips population:

Thrips populations were recorded before and after the insecticide application in both experimental areas. The analyses of variance indicated that there were no significant differences between treatments before application of insecticides in both sites (Kabul and Nangarhar) ($F_{6,055}=0.073$; $P < 0.001$ and $F_{6,06}= 0.085$; $P < 0.001$) respectively. However, the significant difference was observed after three times application of insecticides i.e. after 24h of recording showed that treatment was applied insecticide significantly reduced ($F_{6,105.73}= 0.0001$; $P < 0.001$ and $F_{6,112.32}= 0.0001$; $P < 0.001$), in comparison to the control, so after 3- days of recoding the population of onion thrips significantly ($F_{6,162.32} = 0.0001$ $P < 0.001$ and $F_{6,98.93} = 0.0003$ $P < 0.001$) higher in control plot and finally, after 7-days of recording indicated that the plots which applied insecticides the population of onion thrips significantly ($F_{6,22.4} = 0.004$; $P < 0.001$ and $F_{6, 67.43} = 0.0001$; $P < 0.001$) lower than control plot. (Figure 1 A and B).

The same trend in the effectiveness of insecticides was observed at both sites (Kabul and Nangarhar). The lowest density of thrips after application of insecticides was recorded in acetamiprid SL, followed by chlorpyrifos SL and carbaryl WP while the high density was recorded in emamectin benzoate followed by EC, lambda-cyhalothrin EC, and cypermethrin EC. Result of the

Tukey's test indicated that the density of thrips was much lower at 3-days post-treatment in compared to 24 hrs. and 7 days. Data on the number of thrips per plant showed that percentage and reduction percentage was significantly higher in plots treated with acetamiprid SL, chlorpyrifos SL and carbaryl WP than plots treated with cypermethrin EC, lambda-cyhalothrin EC and emamectin benzoate in both sites after

application of insecticides at 24hrs, 3-days and 7-days. (Tables 1 and 2).

2. Yield assessment:

More number of dead thrips and increasing yield were observed in plots treated with acetamiprid SL followed by chlorpyrifos SL, and carbaryl WP

and in the same way the lowest dead onion thrips and decreasing yield were found in plots treated with emamectin benzoate among all insecticides (Table 1).

Table (1): The percentage mortality of onion thrips after spraying and weight yield per plot and total yield per hectare in two locations (Kabul and Nangarhar provinces).

Treatments	Times of data recorded			Yield/plot (Kg)	Yield/hectare (Ton)
	24-hours	3-days	7-days		
Kabul province					
Acetamiprid SL	77.8 ± 2.5 ^a	84.4 ± 4.3 ^a	51.4 ± 3.2 ^a	8.10 ± 0.8 ^a	16.20 ± 0.7 ^a
Chlorpyrifos SL	77.3 ± 3.4 ^a	84.0 ± 4.0 ^a	52.2 ± 0.9 ^a	7.83 ± 0.4 ^b	15.66 ± 0.5 ^b
Carbaryl WP	73.3 ± 1.3 ^a	80.9 ± 6.7 ^a	48.9 ± 2.1 ^a	7.84 ± 0.6 ^b	15.68 ± 0.9 ^b
Cypermethrin EC	58.3 ± 5.1 ^b	60.6 ± 4.3 ^b	30.7 ± 4.3 ^b	7.13 ± 1 ^c	14.26 ± 0.6 ^c
Lambda-cyhalothrin EC	56.5 ± 0.7 ^b	59.3 ± 4.2 ^b	28.4 ± 2.1 ^b	6.93 ± 0.9 ^c	13.86 ± 1.1 ^c
Emamectin benzoate EC	48.0 ± 5.8 ^c	52.2 ± 8.9 ^c	25.4 ± 1.1 ^c	6.63 ± 0.6 ^d	13.26 ± 0.8 ^d
Control	-1.8 ± 0.4 ^d	-9.8 ± 1.1 ^d	-28.2 ± 2.2 ^d	6.13 ± 0.3 ^e	12.26 ± 0.4 ^e
LSD	10.321	9.120	17.59	0.244	0.642
CV	10.99	9.24	19.7	1.90	2.05
F	77.56	110.81	12.49	82.10	97.13
P	0.0001	0.0001	0.0005	0.0001	0.0001
Nangarhar province					
Acetamiprid SL	76.7 ± 1.5 ^a	86.9 ± 1.3 ^a	58.7 ± 0.7 ^a	7.20 ± 0.5 ^a	14.40 ± 0.5 ^a
Chlorpyrifos SL	75.3 ± 2.4 ^a	84.8 ± 3.1 ^a	56.9 ± 0.5 ^a	6.93 ± 0.7 ^b	13.86 ± 0.4 ^b
Carbaryl WP	74.5 ± 1.3 ^a	83.3 ± 2.4 ^a	56.3 ± 1.1 ^a	6.94 ± 0.4 ^b	13.88 ± 0.4 ^b
Cypermethrin EC	57.3 ± 3.1 ^b	61.6 ± 1.3 ^b	34.7 ± 1.7 ^b	6.35 ± 1.2 ^b	12.70 ± 0.9 ^b
Lambda-cyhalothrin EC	52.5 ± 0.7 ^c	58.6 ± 1.2 ^{bc}	32.9 ± 2.7 ^{bc}	6.57 ± 0.7 ^b	13.14 ± 0.6 ^b
Emamectin benzoate EC	50.3 ± 2.2 ^c	52.7 ± 3.9 ^c	28.4 ± 1.6 ^c	5.69 ± 0.6 ^c	11.38 ± 0.7 ^c
Control	-3.5 ± 0.8 ^d	-9.8 ± 1.3 ^d	-28.2 ± 1.2 ^d	5.13 ± 0.6 ^d	10.26 ± 0.5 ^d
LSD	9.761	10.120	15.123	1.142	0.642
CV	8.09	13.290	13.321	7.564	2.05
F	85.59	120.81	11.97	69.10	97.13
P	0.0001	0.0001	0.0006	0.0001	0.0001

Different lowercase case letters indicate that there is significant difference between treatments after insecticides applied in both sites according to Tukey LSD.

Table (2) : Mean reduction percentage of onion thrips population in Kabul and Nangarhar provinces.

Treatments	Times of data recoded in Kabul province			Times of data recorded in Nangarhar province		
	24-hrs.	3-days	7-days	24-hours	3-days	7-days
Acetamiprid SL	88.3 ± 2.5 ^a	91.1 ± 4.1 ^a	71.8 ± 3.2 ^a	89.3 ± 1.3 ^a	93.1 ± 4.1 ^a	74.2 ± 1.7 ^a
Chlorpyrifos SL	87.6 ± 1.2 ^a	90.7 ± 1.3 ^a	71.6 ± 4.9 ^a	87.4 ± 2.6 ^a	91.2 ± 1.3 ^a	72.9 ± 5.2 ^a
Carbaryl WP	84.0 ± 2.8 ^a	89.2 ± 1.8 ^a	68.6 ± 5.1 ^{ab}	85.5 ± 3.1 ^a	90.4 ± 1.8 ^a	68.6 ± 2.8 ^{ab}
Cypermethrin EC	54.3 ± 5.3 ^b	59.6 ± 4.5 ^b	48.9 ± 3.6 ^c	52.8 ± 2.2 ^b	59.6 ± 4.5 ^b	48.9 ± 3.6 ^b
Lambda-cyhalothrin EC	53.0 ± 3.1 ^b	57.9 ± 1 ^b	46.5 ± 4.2 ^b	51.3 ± 2.3 ^b	58.9 ± 1 ^b	41.9 ± 2.9 ^c
Emamectin benzoate EC	51.1 ± 8.5 ^b	54.2 ± 7.9 ^b	42.4 ± 3.7 ^c	48.1 ± 3.7 ^b	53.2 ± 7.9 ^b	41.4 ± 3.3 ^c
LSD	8.5512	7.6941	14.30	12.7812	9.6341	8.390
CV	8.72	7.08	18.68	9.790	10.78	15.645
F	108.74	162.75	14.61	143.789	173.796	140.619
P	0.0001	0.0001	0.0004	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001

The different lowercase letters indicate that there is a significant difference between the treatments after insecticides utilized on both sites according to Tukey LSD.

Chemical insecticide application against onion thrips population is generally one of the prevalent methods because of their rapid effect on the pest population. The result of the preliminary assessment of the study areas showed that the onion thrips infestation was high and specifically; the damage was increased on the crop in Nangarhar province of Afghanistan during the late February to April and in Kabul province during the mid-July to August 2019. Culture practices, including intercropping of several crops such as chili, cotton, tomato, and okra are a more important components of eco-friendly management of many economic pests, especially onion thrips and reported that intercropping can successfully reduce the damage of onion thrips (Kay and Herron , 2010) .

It has been reported that carbosulfan, cypermethrin EC deltamethrin+ triazophos, bifenthrin, and dimethoate reduced the *T. tabaci* population for more than 2 weeks and the

effect of imidacloprid was better than cyhalothrin (Ashghar *et al.*, 2018) . Majority of the farmers extensively applying synthetic pyrethroides and contact insecticides and also synthetic insecticides for the management of the pest. Therefore, repeated use of the same group of chemicals is not a desirable practice as this could lead to undesirable resistance problems. After three years of research on onion variety NHRDF Red -2, the result indicated that chlorantraniliprole 0.4% @ 10kg/ha and subsequently sequential sprays of carbosulfan @ 0.2%, fipronil @ 0.1%, spinosad @ 0.03% and profenofos @ 0.1% at ten days interval is very effective for controlling of thrips and increasing the yield of onion seed with highest cost benefit ratio (1:4:19) at Nashik, Maharashtra (Pathak *et al.* , 2018). El-Wakeil *et al.* (2010), applied imidacloprid and thiamethoxam against the sucking insect including whitefly, thrips, and cotton aphid, and reported that imidacloprid reduced the pest number better than

thiamethoxam. Ullah *et al.* (2010), also applied thiodan[®], confidor[®], tracer[®], megamos[®], and actara[®] for the management of onion thrips on crops and except for actara[®], the remaining insecticides were successful in reducing the population of onion thrips. Sadozai *et al.* (2009) found that after application of karate[®], thiodan[®], confidor[®], curacron[®], and crown[®] for the control of onion thrips, they showed a significant reduction of thrips with the highest reduction rate by thiodan[®] and followed by curacron[®] and karate[®].

Zežlina and Blazic (2003), applied several insecticides for the management of *T. tabaci* and indicated that malathion, methomyl and phenthoate can control onion thrips at 14 days intervals. It demonstrated that the pesticide residue lasted for 14 days, which confirm the finding of studies, also different insecticides were utilized in different agro-ecological regions and utilized some chemical insecticide on onion thrips and indicated the residues could last for a period of one week or so. Since all the insecticides applied lost their effect after 15 days, it is assumed that pre harvest period is supposed to be somewhat longer than twenty days. Therefore, instrumental residual analysis studied is needed for the definite and safe pre-harvest period.

Hodge *et al.*, 2009, applied various insecticides for the management of onion thrips and reported that methamidophos had the best effect and followed by dicotrophus and endosulfan, while the lowest efficacy was recorded in cypermethrin and monocrotophos. Mandi and Senapati (2009), applied different insecticides for the management of onion thrips and reported that acetamiprid and thiamethoxam had the highest mortality rate of 93.3% and 89.9%, respectively. Mallik *et al.* (2003) reported 42.2%, 17.2% and 6.8% thrips mortality with extracts of milkweed, datura, and bitter apple, respectively.

Similarly, Kadri and Goud (2006) recorded significant reductions in onion thrips with neem extracts. Like this efficacy of neem extract against thrips were reported by Mishra *et al.* (2007) and cited by Khaliq *et al.*, 2016. Shelton *et al.*, 2008, applied

acetamiprid, dimethoate, spinosad, imidacloprid, and lambda-cyhalothrin against thrips on cabbage and showed that except lambda-cyhalothrin, the others had good effect on thrips. (Kudom *et al.*, 2015), used acetamiprid, imidacloprid and emamectin benzoate against onion thrips and reported that these insecticides significantly reduced the thrips population. In this study, we examined the effect of six chemical insecticides as mentioned above that are among the different chemical classes. The results showed that acetamiprid SL had a higher efficacy followed by chlorpyrifos SL and carbaryl WP, while emamectin benzoate EC had the lower efficacy (Tables 1 and 2). The results of our present research are in agreement with the results of previously conducted studies particularly with (Kudom *et al.*, 2015; Hodges *et al.*, 2009 and Ashghar *et al.*, 2018).

The findings of this research indicated that acetamiprid SL, chlorpyrifos SL and carbaryl WP presented the best result in compared to other chemical insecticides against *T. tabaci*. It resulted in the lower population of thrips/plant and highest reduction percentage in all data recording intervals among the applied insecticides. Therefore, it can be concluded that acetamiprid SL, chlorpyrifos SL and carbaryl WP can be safely used in favorable times for the management of thrips population.

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References

- Ananthakrishnan, T. N. (1993): Bionomics of thrips. Annual Review of Entomology, 38: 67-77. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.ent.38.1.71>.
- Ashghar, M.; Baig M. M. Q.; Afzal, M. and Faisal, N. (2018): Evaluation of different insecticides for the management of onion thrips (*Thrips tabaci* Lindeman, 1889) (Thysanoptera, Thripidae) on onion (*Allium cepa* L.) crops.

- Polish Journal of Entomology, 87: 165–176.
<https://doi.org/10.2478/pjen-2018-0012>.
- Azazy, A. M.; Abdelall, M. F. M.; El-Sappagh, I. A. and Khalil, A. E. H. (2018):** Biological control of the onion thrips, *Thrips tabaci* Lindeman (Thysanoptera: Thripidae), in open fields using Egyptian entomopathogenic nematode isolates. Egyptian Journal of Biological Pest Control, 28:
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s41938-017-0025-9>.
- Badillo-Vargas, I. E.; Rotenberg, D.; Schneewis, B. A. and Whitfield, A. E. (2015):** RNA interference tools for the western flower thrips, *Frankliniella occidentalis*. Journal of Insect Physiology, 76: 36-46.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jinsphys.2015.03.009>.
- Bielza, P.; Fernández, E.; Grávalos, C., and Abellán, J. (2009):** Carbamates synergize the toxicity of acrinathrin in resistant western flower thrips (Thysanoptera: Thripidae). Journal of Economic Entomology, 102: 393–397.
<https://doi.org/10.1603/029.102.0151>.
- Broughton, S., Learmonth, S., Hargreaves, J. and Nimmo, P. (2011):** Further development of integrated pest management strategies to control thrips in pome and stonefruit in WA and QLD. Published by Horticulture Australia.
- Brunner, P. C.; Chatzivassiliou, E. K.; Katis, N. I., and Frey, J. E.(2004):** Host-associated genetic differentiation in *Thrips tabaci* (Insecta; Thysanoptera), as determined from mtDNA sequence data. Heredity, 93: 364–370.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/sj.hdy.6800512>.
- Cannon, R. J. C.; Matthews, L. and Collins, D. W. A. (2007):** review of the pest status and control options for *Thrips palmi*. Crop Protection, 26: 1089-1098.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cropro.2006.10.023>.
- De Brujin, P. J. A.; Egas, M.; Janssen, A. and Sabelis, M. W. (2006):** Pheromone-induced priming of a defensive response in western flower thrips. Journal of Chemical Ecology, 32: 1599-1603.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10886-006-9092-1>.
- Demirozer, O.; Tyler-Julian, K.; Funderburk, J.; Leppla, N. and Reitz, S. (2012):** *Frankliniella occidentalis* (Pergande) integrated pest management programs for fruiting vegetables in Florida. Pest Management Science, 12: 1537-1545.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/ps.3389>.
- Din, N.; Ashraf, M. and Hussain, S. (2016):** Effect of different non-chemical and chemical measures against onion thrips. Journal of Entomology and Zoology Study, 4:10–12.
- Duchovskiene, L. (2006):** The abundance and population dynamics of onion thrips (*Thrips tabaci* Lind.) in leek under field conditions. Agronomy Research (Tartu), 4, 163–166.
- El-Naggar, J. B. and Zidan, N, E. H. A.(2013):** Field evaluation of imidacloprid and thiamethoxam against sucking insects and their side effects on soil fauna. Journal of Plant Protect Research , 53: 375–387.
<https://doi.org/10.2478/jppr-2013-0056>.
- El-Wakeil, N. E.; Volkmar, C. and Sallam, A. A. (2010):** Jasmonic acid induces resistance to economically important insect pests in winter wheat. Pest Management Science, <https://doi.org/10.1002/ps.1906>.
- Fernandes, F. L.; De Sena and Fernandes, M. E. (2015):** Flight movement and spatial distribution of immunomarked thrips in onion, potato, and tomato. Pesquisa Agropecuaria Brasileira, 50: 399–406.
<https://doi.org/10.1590/S0100-204X2015000500007>.

- Gandhale, D. N.; Paattil, A. S.; Swate, B. G., and Naik, L. M. (1984) :** Evaluation of certain insecticides for control of onion thrips in maharashtra. *Journal of Maharashtra Agriculture University*, 9: 104-105. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jipm/pmv1006>.
- Gao, Y.; Lei, Z. and Reitz, S. R. (2012):** Western flower thrips resistance to insecticides: Detection, mechanisms and management strategies. *Pest Management Science*, 61: 179-185. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ps.3305>.
- Gholami, Z.; Sadeghi, A.; Sheikhi Garjan, A.; Nazemi Rafi, J. and Gholami, F. (2015):** Susceptibility of western flower thrips *Frankliniella occidentalis* (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) to some synthetic and botanical insecticides under laboratory conditions. *Journal Crop Protection*, 4: 627–632.
- Gill, H. K.; Garg, H.; Gill, A. K.; Gillett-Kaufman, J. L. a and Nault, B. A. (2015):** Onion thrips (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) biology, ecology, and management in onion production systems. *Journal of Integrated Pest Management*, 6; 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jipm/pmv006>.
- Guillén, J.; Navarro, M. and Bielza, P. (2014):** Cross-resistance and baseline susceptibility of spirotetramat in *Frankliniella occidentalis* (Thysanoptera: Thripidae). *Journal of Economic Entomology*, 107: 1239–1244. <https://doi.org/10.1603/ec13397>.
- Hodges, A.; Ludwig, S.; Osborne, L. and Edwards, G. B. (2009):** Pest thrips of the United States: Field Identification Guide, pp 143.
- Hussain, T. M.; Iqbal, M.; Ullah, F. and Anwar, M. (1997):** Population trend, varietal preference and chemical control of garlic thrips (*Thrips tabaci* L.). *Sarhad Journal of Agriculture*, 13: 175-180. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jipm/pmv006>.
- Jacobson, A. L.; Nault, B. A.; Vargo, E. L. and Kennedy, G. G. (2016):** Restricted gene flow among lineages of thrips tabaci supports genetic divergence among cryptic species groups. *PLoS ONE*, 11:1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0163882>.
- Jones, T.; Scott-Dupree, C.; Harris, R.; Shipp, L. and Harris, B. (2005) :** The efficacy of spinosad against the western flower thrips, *Frankliniella occidentalis*, and its impact on associated biological control agents on greenhouse cucumbers in southern Ontario. *Pest Management Science*, 61: 179–185. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ps.939>.
- Kadri, S. and Goud, B. (2006):** Efficacy of newer molecules of insecticides and botanicals against onion thrips, *Thrips tabaci* (Lindeman), (Thysanoptera: Thripidae). *Karnataka Journal of Agriculture Sconce*, 19;539-943.
- Kaur, S.; Kular, J. S. and Chandi, R. S. (2017):** Effect of temperature on growth and development of *Thrips tabaci* Lindeman in BT cotton. *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences*, 6:2553–2560. <https://doi.org/10.20546/ijcmas.2017.605.287>.
- Kay, I. R. and Herron, G. A. (2010):** Evaluation of existing and new insecticides including spirotetramat and pyridalyl to control *Frankliniella occidentalis* (Pergande) (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) on peppers in Queensland. *Australian Journal of Entomology*, 49: 175–181. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1440-6055.2010.00751.x>.
- Khaliq, A.; Afzal, M.; Khan, A. A.; Raza, A. M.; Kamran, M.; Tahir, H. M.; Aqeel, M. A. and Ullah, M. I. (2016):** Management of *Thrips tabaci* (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) through agronomic practices in

- Onion field plots. Pakistan Journal of Zoology, 48: 1675–1680.
- Khalique, A.; Khan, A. A.; Afzal, M.; Tahir, H. M.; Raza, A. M. and Khan, A. M. (2014)** ; Field evaluation of selected botanicals and commercial synthetic insecticides against *Thrips tabaci* Lindeman (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) populations and predators in onion field plots. Crop Protection, 62:10–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cropro.2014.03.019>.
- Khan, A. B.; Panhwar, W. A.; Mehmood, S. A.; Gilal, A. and Ahmed, S. (2017)**: Population of *Thrips tabaci* Lindeman , 1889 in onion crop from district Mansehra , Khyber. Journal of Entomology and Zoology Studies, 5: 502–505.
- Kudom, A. A.; Mensah, B. A.; Froeschl, G.; Rinder, H. and Boakye, D. (2015)**: DDT and pyrethroid resistance status and laboratory evaluation of bio-efficacy of long lasting insecticide treated nets against *Culex quinquefasciatus* and *Culex decens* in Ghana. Acta Tropica, 150:122–130. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actatropica.2015.07.009>.
- Loomans, A. J. M. (2003)**: Parasitoids as biological control agents of thrips pests (Unpublished master's thesis) Wageningen University, pp. 208.
- Lopez, J. D.; Fritz, B.K.; Lathheef, M. A.; Lan, Y.; Martin, D. E. and Hoffmann, W. C. (2008)**: Arthropod management: Evaluation of toxicity of selected insecticides against thrips on cotton in laboratory bioassays. Journal of Cotton Science, 12: 188–194.
- Malik, M.F.; Nawaz, M. and Hafeez, Z. (2003)**: Inter and intra row spacing effects on thrips (*Thrips* spp.) population in onion (*Allium cepa*). Asian J. Plant Sci., 2(9): 713-715.
- Maliniak, D.; Peterson, S. and Tierney, M. J. (2012)**: Trips Around the World: Teaching, Research, and Policy Views of International Relations Faculty in 20 Countries. Årsbok Göteborgs Tandläkare-Sällskap, 7–24. <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/21638869>.
- Mandi, N. and Senapati, A. K. (2009)**: Integration of chemical botanical and microbial insecticides for control of thrips, *Scirtothrips dorsalis* hood infesting chili. Journal of Plant Protection Science, 1: 92-95.
- Maniania, N. K.; Sithanatham, S.; Ekesi, S.; Ampong-Nyarko, K.; Baumgärtner, J.,; Löhr, B. and Matoka, C. M. A. (2003)**: field trial of the entomogenous fungus *Metarhizium anisopliae* for control of onion thrips, *Thrips tabaci*. Crop Protection, 22: 553–559. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0261-2194\(02\)00221-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0261-2194(02)00221-1).
- Mautino, G. C.; Bosco, L. and Tavella, L. (2012)**: Integrated management of *Thrips tabaci* (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) on onion in north-western Italy: Basic approaches for supervised control. Pest Management Science,; 68, 185–193. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ps.2243>.
- Minoia, G.; Mumtaz, W., and Pain, A. (2015)**: Peeling the onion: Social regulation of the onion market, Nangarhar, Afghanistan. Economic and Political Weekly, 50: 79–86.
- Mishra, D. K.; Pathak, G. ; Tailor, R. S. and Deshwal, A. (2007)**: On-farm trial: an approach for management of thrips in onion. Indian Res. J. Ext. Ed., 7: 66 – 67.
- Nikolova, I. and Georgieva, N. (2014)**: Effect of botanical insecticides neemazal-t/s and pyrethrum applied alone and in combination with different organic products on *Thrips tabaci* population density. Acta Entomologica Eerbica, 19:1–11.

- <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18141>.
- Nault, B. A. and Shelton, A. M. (2010):** Impact of insecticide efficacy on developing action thresholds for pest management: a case study of onion thrips (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) on onion. *Journal of Economic Entomology*, 103: 1315–1326.
<https://doi.org/10.1603/ec10096>.
- Pathak, M. K.; Pandey, M. K.; Gupta, R. C. and Gupta, P. K. (2018) :** Evaluation of different insecticides against onion thrips in onion seed production. *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences*, 7: 4204–4207.
<https://doi.org/10.20546/ijcmas.2018.707.491>
- Pourian, H. R.; Mirab-Balou, M.; Alizadeh, M. and Orosz, S. (2009):** Study on biology of onion thrips, *Thrips tabaci* lindeman (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) on cucumber (Var. Sultan) in laboratory conditions. *Journal of Plant Protection Research*, 49: 390–394.
<https://doi.org/10.2478/v10045-009-0061-x>.
- Sadozai, A.; Zeb, Q.; Iqbal, T.; Anwar, S.; Badshah, H.; Ali, A.; Ahmad, M. and Tahir, M. (2009):** Testing the efficacy of different insecticides against onion thrips in tarnab, Peshawar. *Sarhad Journal of Agriculture*, 25: 2007–2010.
- SAS Institute (2002):** Proc User's Manual, Version 9. 1th ed. SAS Institute, Cary, N. C., Scholthof, K. B. G. The disease triangle: pathogens, the environment and society. *Natural reviews, Microbiology*, (2007), 5: 152-156.
- Sedaratian, A.; Fathipour, Y.; Talebi, A. A., and Farahani, S. (2010):** Population density and spatial distribution pattern of *Thrips tabaci* (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) on different soybean varieties. *Journal of Agricultural Science and Technology*, 12: 275–288.
- Shang, L. G.; Xyong-Reitz, S.; Nauen, R.; Lei, Z.; Ren, L. S. H. and Gao, Y. (2016):** Field resistance to spinosad in western flower thrips *Frankliniella occidentalis* (Thysanoptera: Thripidae). *Journal of Integrative Agriculture*, 15: 2803–2817.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S2095-3119\(16\)61478-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2095-3119(16)61478-8)
- Sharma, D. A. (2014):** Nutritional benefits of onion. *Market Survey*, 27–30.
https://doi.org/10.1007/0-387-26691-7_12.
- Shelton, A. M.; Nault, B. A.; Plate, J., and Zhao, J. Z. (2009):** Regional and temporal variation in susceptibility to λ -cyhalothrin in onion thrips, *Thrips tabaci* (thysanoptera: thripidae), in onion fields in New York. *Journal of Economic Entomology*, 96: 1843–1848.
<https://doi.org/10.1603/0022-0493-96.6.1843>.
- Shelton, A. M.; Plate, J. and Chen, M. (2008):** Advances in control of onion thrips (Thysanoptera; Thripidae) in cabbage. *Journal of Economic Entomology*, 101: 438–343.
- Shiberu, T. and Negeri, S. (2012):** Evaluation of some botanicals and entomopathogenic fungi for the control of onion thrips (*Thrips tabaci* l.) In west Showa, Ethiopia. *Journal of Plant Pathology & Microbiology*, 4: 1–7.
<https://doi.org/10.4172/2157-7471.1000161>
- Sonderholm, J. (2010):** Intellectual property rights and the trips agreement : An overview of ethical problems and some proposed solutions. *WTO Policy Research Working Paper*, 5228: 48.
<https://doi.org/10.1596/1813-9450-5228>.
- Srivastava, M.; Funderburk, J.; Olson, S.; Demirozer. O. and Reitz, S. (2014):** Impacts on natural enemies and competitor thrips of insecticides against the western flower thrips (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) in fruiting vegetables.

- Florida Entomologist, 97: 337–348.
<https://doi.org/10.1653/024.097.0201>.
- Toda, S., and Murai, T. (2007):** Phylogenetic analysis based on mitochondrial COI gene sequences in *Thrips tabaci* Lindeman (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) in relation to reproductive forms and geographic distribution. Applied Entomology and Zoology, 42: 309–316.
<https://doi.org/10.1303/aez.2007.309>.
- Ullah, F.; Maraj-ul-Mulk, F. A.; Saeed, M. Q. and Sattar, S. (2010)** :Population dynamics and chemical control of onion thrips (*Thrips tabaci*, Lindemann). Pakistan Journal of Zoology, 42: 401–406.
- Zezlina, I. and Blazic, M. (2003):** Testing the efficacy of different insecticides to control onion thrips (*Thrips tabaci* Lindeman, Thysanoptera, Thripidae) in onion crops. Communications in Agricultural and Applied Biological Sciences, 68:287–290.

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Impact of some plant oils and hexaflumuron against of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae) and *Tetranychus urticae* (Acari: Tetranychidae) on cotton plants

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Abstract:

The cotton mealybug *Phenacoccus solenopsis* Tinsley (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae) and the two spotted spider mite, *Tetranychus urticae* Koch (Acari: Tetranychidae) were predicted to become two of the most damage cotton pests within the next few years and polyphagous and live to gather. Field trials were carried out during 2020 and 2021 seasons at, Sakha Agricultural Research Station, Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate to the efficacy of garlic, moringa and jojoba essential oil and hexaflumuron (Scorch) (IGR) were tested against their toxicity to the immature stages and adult for both pests as well as biochemical studies. Plant essential oil and insecticide are commonly used to control *P. solenopsis* and *T. urticae* after 3, 7, 10 and 13 days post treatment, the average percentage of reduction will be calculated. The findings showed that the average % of reduction of the mealybug was 50.49, 38.44, 23.65 and 22.29 % by hexaflumuron, garlic, jojoba and moringa in the first season, respectively. While the second season was 51.98, 42.13, 27.24 and 24.76 with *P. solenopsis*, respectively. Thus, the trials indicated that the reduction % of *T. urticae* were 53.40, 39.44, 24.86 and 24.65 in the first season and 59.22, 50.13, 23.01 and 22.86 in the second season as well, respectively. The impacts of hexaflumuron, garlic, moringa and jojoba on trehalase, chitinase and protease activities were tested against the 3rd instars nymphs of the mealybug and all stages of the mite. The difference in trehalase and protease activities were insignificant between garlic and control after 3 days, but decreased significantly after 10 days of treatment for both pests, while hexaflumuron increase significantly between moringa, jojoba and control after 7 and 10 days after treatment. After 3 and 7 days of treatment, the difference in chitinase activity was significant between garlic and control. The data in the first season and the second season showed that, hexaflumuron was the most effective compound in reducing the population density of motile stages of *T. urticae* followed by garlic oil, whereas moringa oil and jojoba oil were the least effective compounds in reducing the population density of motile stages of *T. urticae* in the field. The pests, four toxic materials, garlic, moringa, jojoba and hexaflumuron in all experiments can be useful for developing safe elements for an integrated pest management strategy.

Introduction

The cotton mealybug, *Phenacoccus solenopsis* Tinsley (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae) and the two spotted spider mite, *Tetranychus urticae* Koch (Acari: Tetranychidae) are considered the most recent invasive sap suckling pests in Egypt and many parts of the world attacking the cotton plantations and many other agricultural crops of economic importance (Fuchs *et al.*, 1991 and Ibrahim *et al.*, 2015) as well as the cotton is considered of the most preferred hosts of the mealybug and mite. Causes direct damages by sucking the cell sap and becoming stunted, weak and fruit a few small bolls resulting in severe economic yield losses (Dhawan *et al.*, 2007).

P. solenopsis infestation on many other field crops could be effective, control using plant extract, mineral oils and insecticides (Suresh *et al.*, 2010; Kumar *et al.*, 2012 and El-Zahi *et al.*, 2016). The mealybug feeds on all the green parts of the infested plants which become stunted and it is predicted to become one of the most dangerous economic pests during the next years in Egypt where the agroecosystem is close adequate to its development and spread (El-Zahi and Farag, 2017). The use of essential oil and plant extract in pest control could be an effective alternative compared to pesticides. In Egypt, toxicity of chlorpyrifos, biochemical, IGR and Jojoba oil against 2nd and 4th instar of *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisduval) (Lepidoptera ; Noctuidae) and their effect on some biological characters as well as fecundity were studied on 4th instar larvae (Gaaboub *et al.*, 2012). Dimetry *et al.* (2017) tested moringa trees that decreased the weight gain significantly in the treated larvae of *S. littoralis* in comparison with the control. The cotton mealybug and the two spotted spider mite are a polyphagous pest,

feeding on a wide variety of plants. The host range of this mealybug includes okra, eggplant, and cotton (El-Fakharany, 2020 and El-Zahi and Farag, 2017).

P. solenopsis infestations on different hosts could be effectively controlled using synthetic insecticides, plant extracts, mineral oils, and biological control agents (El-Zahi *et al.*, 2016). Today, among the first observations carried out in this field, two were particularly focused on the effect of essential oils on insect pests. Essential oils are presently regarded as a new class of ecological products for controlling insect pests. The diversification of the approaches inherent in IPM is necessary for better environmental protection, the chemical complexity of essential oils, several mechanisms being contingent on the phytochemical pattern of the oils and the sensitivity of the insect species could be involved. Jojoba oil is suggested as a safe product with a potential for use as a biocide in IPM especially in urban countries where the use of chemical insecticides is discouraged (Abdel-Razik and Mahmoud, 2017). Spider mites feed by inserting their needle-like piercing-sucking mouthparts inside the plant tissue and they prefer to feed on the lower leaf surface (Attia *et al.*, 2013). Natural plant extracts are causing damage of economic importance in agriculture. Plant essential oils have more toxic effects on pests through contact, ingestion and fumigation; so, plant essential oils or their constituents have significant behavioral effects on spider mites, especially as *T. urticae* (Akhtar *et al.*, 2010).

The aim of the present work is to study the efficacy of garlic, moringa and jojoba essential oil and hexaflumuron (Scorch) (IGR) against the immature stages and adults for *P.*

solenopsis and *T. urticae* as well as biochemical studies.

Materials and methods

1. Plant oils and insecticidal:

Commercial formulations of hexaflumuron (Scorch 10 % EC) (IGR), (Syngenta Agrosiencs, Swizerland) and three plant oils, garlic (*Allium sativum* L.), moringa (*Moringa oleifera*) and jojoba (*Simmondsia chinensis*) produced by Egyptian Natural Oil Co. used at the rate of 1.5 liter/F. They were dissolved in water containing 1% Triton, were tested for their toxicity to *P. solenopsis* and *T. urticae* under field conditions.

2. Field evaluation of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* and *Tetranychus urticae*:

The field experiment was conducted during the summer of 2020 and 2021 to evaluate the efficacy of one insecticide and three plant oils against *P. solenopsis* and *T. urticae* on the previously mentioned cotton plant variety at the farm of Sakha Agricultural Research Station, Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate, Egypt. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with five treatments. Each treatment contained three replications in an area of approximately 1500 m². Five plots were allocated randomly to each treatment. During the two seasons, these experiments did receive plant oil and insecticide treatments, the spraying was done 8-11 am. A knapsack sprayer provided with one nozzle delivering 1.5 letters/feddan was used to plant oils and hexaflumuron (Scorch 10% EC by rate 200 cm/ Fedden. The micron Ulva (ULVAT), Nozzle: Red nozzle to treatment Ec. According to the method described by Ahmad *et al.* (2011). Ten apical twigs of the same age from the cotton plants were randomly selected and labeled appropriately for further observation from each replicate to count all stages of *P. solenopsis*.

Treatments were imposed when an enough mealybug population and mite were observed in the experimental block. Samples of 10 cotton leaves were randomly collected from each plot before and after treatment of the two spotted spider mites. Observations were recorded a day before spray and 3, 7, 10 and 13 days after spray. The percentage reduction of infestation was calculated for each treatment, according to Handerson and Tilton (1955) and Duncan (1955) multiple range tests at the 5% level was used for statistical analysis of significant differences among treatment.

$$\% \text{redaction} = \left\{ 1 - \frac{\text{NCBS/NCASXNTAS/NTBS}}{\text{NCBS/NCASXNTAS/NTBS}} \right\} \times 100$$

NCBS= No. in cont. before spraying

NCAS= No. in cont. after spraying

NTAS= No. in treat. after spraying

NTBS= No. in treat. before spraying

3. Biochemical studies:

All the biochemical analysis was carried out in the Faculty of Agriculture, Kafr El-Sheikh University. Observations were recorded enzyme activities after spray on three, seven, and ten days. Total body tissue samples were collected from individuals treated is fed on treating leaves. Pests bodies treated or untreated were homogenized in distilled water (One gm. insect bodies/5ml) using a chilled glass teflon tissue grinder for 3 min. Homogenates were centrifuged at 8000 r.p.m. for 15 min at -2°C in a refrigerated centrifuge. The supernatant used was stored at -5°C until the use (Max-2 week) for determination of some enzyme activities included trehalas, chitinase, and protease (Figure 1).

4. Statistical analysis:

The collected data were subjected to one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), and the means separated using Duncan's (1955) Multiple Range Test at P < 0.05 using SAS program (SAS, 1995).

Figure (1): Preparation of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* and *Tetranychus urticae* for enzymes analysis.

Results and discussion

1. Impact of some plant oils and hexaflumuron on *Phenacoccus solenopsis* and *Tetranychus urticae* under field conditions:

The first incidence of *P. solenopsis* and *T. urticae* was recorded in June, the highest population density was noticed in September. Also, in both seasons the infestation started when the cotton plants aged were three months. The effect of garlic, moringa, jojoba oils and hexaflumuron were tested under field conditions against all immature stages and adults of the mealybug infesting cotton plants during

2020 and 2021 by using ULVA+ spraying equipment after 3, 7, 10 and 13 days post treatment (Table 1). Results showed that there is no mortality in the check (Untreated from all experiment day). Results indicated that the average numbers percentage of *P. solenopsis* started at least after treatment and the population decreased gradually and its least number, were 91.47, 78.37, 60.93 and 53.93 numbers with hexaflumuron after 3, 7, 10 and 13 days post treatment, respectively. While in case of garlic showed the average numbers percentage value (102.36, 98.16, 81.47 and 71.28 numbers after 3, 7, 10 and 13

days post treatment, respectively). While jojoba and moringa were less toxic, recording 178.63, 191.38, 146.79 and 134.52 numbers with Jojoba and 166.52, 175.42, 143.38 and 211.73 numbers on moringa after 3, 7, 10 and 13 days, respectively in the first season. However, in the second season (2021), the data cleared that hexaflumuron proved to be the most effective against the mealybug, while garlic and jojoba showed effectiveness among them, indicating that the numbers % of *P. solenopsis* on cotton plants were 87.63, 75.45, 52.85 and 48.55 numbers in hexaflumuron after 3, 7, 10 and 13 days, respectively compared to the control. Whereas jojoba recorded the least mean numbers 167.58, 184.58, 130.45 and 123.63 numbers after 3, 7, 10 and 13 days post treatment, respectively. The results are shown in Table (2) indicated that hexaflumuron and garlic caused the highest reduction in mealybug (50.49 and 38.44 %, respectively) followed by jojoba and moringa (23.65 and 22.29% respectively), in the first season. While hexaflumuron and garlic in the second season (2021) had a similar effect on mealybug (51.98 and 42.13% reduction, respectively), followed by jojoba and moringa (27.24 and 24.76%, respectively).

The present results are in parallel with El-Zahi and Farag (2017) and Sahito *et al.* (2011) who observed the highest infestation of *P. solenopsis* on cotton during September and October. Soltan (2020) cleared that the mortality percentages of nymph instars of grasshoppers were jojoba 96%, moringa 65% and cascade 87% after 12 days post treatment, while Abd El-Rahman (2003) indicated that jojoba caused 83.8 and 90.8% mortality against *Liriomyz atrifolii*. (Burgess) (Diptera: Agromyzidae) larvae at 0.5 and 1% respectively. The present results in this concern, agreed with

Gaaboub *et al.* (2012) who observed the toxicity of IGR (Lufenuron) and jojoba oil against 2nd and 4th of instar larvae *S. littoralis* and their effect on some biological characters and fecundity. jojoba, moringa and cascade against nymph instars of the grasshoppers, after 2, 4, 6, 8, 10 and 12 days post treatment in the field.

Salem *et al.* (2003) revealed that jojoba oil formulation was the potent agent against both whitefly and leafhopper species where the LC₅₀ was 5.4% for *Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) and 6.4% for *Empoasca decipiens* Paoli (Hemiptera - Cicadellidae), respectively. Abdel-Razik and Mahmoud (2017) showed that 2nd or 4th instar larvae of cotton leafworm, *S. littoralis* exposed to jojoba extract for 24 hrs were greatly suffered from toxic effects which give good evidence for using jojoba as an element for the integrated management of insects. The highest mortality percentage (100%) of *Schistocerca gregaria* nymphs was calculated at 10% jojoba oil (Halawa *et al.*, 2007). Buprofezine was the least toxic one with LC₅₀ value of 121.79 and 146.14 mg AI L-1 on eggplant and okra. In an attempt to control this pest, buprofezin, was tested for its influence against *P. solenopsis* on eggplant and okra under field conditions (El-Fakharany, 2020). Rizvi *et al.* (2015) found that spirotetramat proved significantly superior in controlling *P. solenopsis*. El-Zahi *et al.* (2016) found that imidacloprid and thiamethoxam showed the highest efficacy against *P. solenopsis* recording 89.2 and 84.6% reduction of the insect population while emamectin benzoate failed to exhibit sufficient *P. solenopsis* control. Unfortunately, recent studies reported that *P. solenopsis* has developed resistance to spirotetramat (Ejaz and Ali Shad, 2017 and Rezk *et al.*, 2019).

The data in the first season presented in Tables (3 and 4) had a similar effect on mite and showed that hexaflumuron was the most effective compound in reducing the population density of motile stages of mite, *T. urticae* (82.47, 67.55, 52.34 and 45.66 numbers after 3, 7, 10 and 13 days, respectively) with 53.40% reduction followed by garlic oil (90.53, 87.54, 73.33 and 66.23 numbers after 3, 7, 10 and 13 days, respectively) with a percentage reduction of 39.44%. Whereas moringa oil and jojoba oil were the least effective compounds in reducing the population density of motile stages of *T. urticae* (24.86% and 24.65%, respectively). But in the second season hexaflumuron was the most effective compound in reducing

the population density of motile stages of mite, *T. urticae* (73.56, 62.66, 47.23 and 39.54 numbers after 3, 7, 10 and 13 days post treatment, respectively) with 59.22% of the reductions, followed by garlic oil was (50.13%). Whereas moringa oil and jojoba oil were the least effective compounds in reducing the population density of motile stages of *T. urticae* (23.01 and 22.86 %, respectively). In general, in all treatments the most effective compounds in reducing the population density. Based on these reductions, all compounds were effective in reducing the population density of motile stages of mite *T. urticae*.

Table (1): The tested compounds effect *Phenacoccus solenopsis* on cotton plants in field condition.

Compounds	No. of <i>Phenacoccus solenopsis</i> per-treatment	No. of <i>Phenacoccus solenopsis</i> post-treatment			
		3 rd day	7 th day	10 th day	13 th day
Season 2020					
Hexaflumuron	188.43	91.47	78.37	60.93	53.93
Garlic oil	186.61	102.36	98.16	81.47	71.28
Moringa oil	211.73	166.52	175.42	143.38	211.73
Jojoba oil	231.36	178.63	191.38	146.79	134.52
Control	262.73	177.91	185.48	216.72	258.81
Season 2021					
Hexaflumuron	185.77	87.63	75.45	52.85	48.55
Garlic oil	192.23	92.64	91.65	78.74	76.57
Moringa oil	201.84	153.53	170.73	132.13	120.64
Jojoba oil	220.54	167.58	184.58	130.45	123.63
Control	265.92	173.57	182.63	225.65	248.74

Table (2): The reductions effect of tested compounds on motile stages of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* on cotton plant in field condition.

Compounds	% reduction				General mean
	3 rd day	7 th day	10 th day	13 th day	
Season 2020					
Hexaflumuron	28.64	41.36	60.87	71.09	50.49
Garlic oil	19.36	25.83	47.17	61.42	38.44
Moringa oil	15.61	16.81	18.06	38.71	22.29
Jojoba oil	13.49	16.63	23.22	41.27	23.65
Season 2021					
Hexaflumuron	27.82	42.73	66.71	72.29	51.98
Garlic oil	26.26	32.77	52.07	57.77	42.13
Moringa oil	16.37	19.26	23.40	36.64	24.76
Jojoba oil	16.25	18.00	30.79	40.57	27.24

Table (3): The tested compounds effect on motile stages of *Tetranychus urticae* on cotton plants in field condition.

Compounds	No. of <i>Tetranychus urticae</i> per-treatment	No. of <i>Tetranychus urticae</i> post-treatment			
		3 rd day	7 th day	10 th day	13 th day
Season 2020					
Hexaflumuron	172.76	82.47	67.55	52.34	45.66
Garlic oil	168.44	90.53	87.54	73.33	66.23
moringa oil	198.56	152.45	166.13	130.16	106.28
Jojoba oil	201.73	162.53	178.46	137.34	112.37
Control	256.77	180.33	182.27	212.53	246.76
Season 2021					
Hexaflumuron	178.54	73.56	62.66	47.23	39.54
Garlic oil	180.75	84.57	76.42	63.53	53.43
moringa oil	192.59	142.53	153.88	112.45	98.62
Jojoba oil	206.44	151.63	166.42	122.66	104.88
Control	260.64	175.44	178.73	197.49	242.79

Table (4): The reductions effect of tested compounds on motile stages of *Tetranychus urticae* on cotton plant in field condition.

Compounds	% reduction				General mean
	3 rd day	7 th day	10 th day	13 th day	
Season 2020					
Hexaflumuron	32.21	45.25	63.64	72.51	53.40
Garlic oil	23.68	27.24	47.75	59.10	39.44
Moringa oil	7.48	17.13	21.33	53.52	24.86
Jojoba oil	14.40	23.85	18.30	42.06	24.65
Season 2021					
Hexaflumuron	41.49	50.86	68.25	76.30	59.22
Garlic oil	33.56	40.80	57.82	68.37	50.13
Moringa oil	5.08	11.86	29.93	45.20	23.01
Jojoba oil	4.29	12.85	28.69	45.63	22.86

Asmae *et al.* (2019) investigate the toxicity of the essential oils of *Salvia officinal* and *Eucalyptus globulus* against the adults of two spotted spider mites, *T. urticae*. The results showed that the two oils increase spider mite mortality in adults. Gaber and Nasr (2020) investigated the effects of neem essential oil and aqueous neem extract on female adult *T. urticae*. The results showed that neem essential oil was more effective than aqueous neem extract.

2. Biochemical studies:

The data in Tables (5 and 6) showed that, the effect of garlic, moringa, jojoba and hexaflumuron on trehalase, chitinase and protease activities of the cotton mealybug and mite. Jojoba highly significant increased trehalase activity after 3, 7

and 10 days compared to control. The trehalase activity difference was significant increased with garlic after 7 and 10 days and was insignificant after 3 days, while causing highly significant increased after 3 days with hexaflumuron and significant after 7 and 10 days from treatment compared to control of *P. solenopsis* and *T. urticae*.

On the other hand, garlic showed highly, significant increases in chitinase activity after 3 days, but was significant after 7 and 10 days compared with control with both pests moringa illustrated that insignificant after 3, 7 and 10 days compared with control. Jojoba increased the chitinase activity significantly after 3, 7 and 10 days compared with control of *P. solenopsis* and *T. urticae*.

Data presented showed the hexaflumuron increase highly significant on chitinase activity after 3, 7 and 10 days after treatment compared with control on both pests and while garlic showed the insignificant difference in activity in protease after 3 days but highly significant increased after 7 and 10 days compared with control. Moringa significant difference in activity in protease after 3 and 7 days.

Also, jojoba induced a highly significant increase compared with control after 7 and 10 days. While hexaflumuron increased protease activity highly significantly after 3 days from treatment compared with control all this data on *P. solenopsis*. But with *T. urticae*. was significant compared with control.

Table (5): The effect of the plant oils and hexaflumuron on enzymes activity of *Phenacoccus solenopsis*.

Enzymes	Days after Treatment	Plant oils			Hexaflumuron	Control	LCD
		Garl	Moringa	Jojoba			
Trehalase Mgmol /min. /mg protein	3	395 ^c	426 ^b	582 ^a	551 ^a	370 ^c	63.27
	7	401 ^c	415 ^b	435 ^a	418 ^b	294 ^d	66.21
	10	345 ^c	340 ^b	407 ^a	315 ^c	282 ^d	73.44
Chitinase Mgmol /min. /mg protein	3	510 ^a	400 ^c	483 ^b	525 ^a	420 ^c	42.33
	7	410 ^c	381 ^d	815 ^b	1128 ^a	311 ^d	512.11
	10	346 ^c	281 ^d	933 ^b	1677 ^a	291 ^c	589.11
Protease Mgmol /min. /mg protein	3	4.41 ^c	5.21 ^b	6.11 ^a	6.32 ^a	4.21 ^c	3.89
	7	15.32 ^a	10.23 ^b	15.82 ^a	10.30 ^b	5.52 ^c	4.11
	10	17.65 ^a	14.11 ^c	18.31 ^b	13.84 ^c	8.24 ^d	5.57

Table (6): The effect of the plant oils and hexaflumuron on enzymes activity of *Tetranychus urticae*

Enzymes	Days after treatment	Plant oils			Hexaflumuron	Control	LCD
		Gar	Moringa	Jojoba			
Trehalase Mgmol /min. /mg protein	3	289 ^c	376 ^b	423 ^a	405 ^a	366 ^c	58.50
	7	316 ^c	366 ^b	377 ^a	366 ^b	285 ^d	61.25
	10	233 ^c	235 ^c	357 ^a	272 ^b	273 ^b	67.55
Chitinase Mgmol min. /mg protein	3	457 ^a	312 ^c	338 ^c	390 ^b	416 ^a	37.47
	7	355 ^c	268 ^d	634 ^b	917 ^a	318 ^d	358.32
	10	235 ^c	164 ^d	748 ^b	1240 ^a	288 ^c	527.16
Protease Mgmol /min./mg protein	3	3.55 ^c	3.80	4.88 ^a	5.35 ^a	4.33 ^b	2.73
	7	10.24 ^a	6.94 ^c	8.45 ^c	9.55 ^b	5.49 ^d	3.81
	10	13.84 ^a	10.54 ^c	13.35 ^b	13.14 ^a	9.12 ^d	4.63

These results agree with Soltan (2020) found that no significant difference activity between moringa and control after 2 days, the difference in chitinase and protease in activity was insignificant between moringa and control after 2 and 4 days. The difference in protease activity was insignificant between moringa and control after 2 days while causing an increase significant between jojoba and control after 4 and 6 days after treatment. Soltan (2014) observed that the difference trehalase activity of desert locust was insignificant between garlic and control after 2 days while increased significantly after 4 and 6 days post treatment. The molting fluid contains protease and chitinase, enzymes that digest the main constitution of the old end cuticle (Reynolds and Samuels, 1996). Accordingly, mortality percentage and changes in enzymes activities of the insects were greatly affected. Thus, it could be concluded that garlic oil, moringa, jojoba and hexaflumuron could be used as an effective natural product to be included in the integrated pest management program of the cotton mealybug in the field, Tanani *et al.* (2012) found that the treatment of *Schistocerca gregaria* (Forsk.) (Orthoptera: Acrididae) by tebufenozide caused a significant increase in trehalase activity after 4 days from treatment.

References

Abd El-Rahman S. F. (2003): Damage assessment of certain insects attacking faba bean in the field and store. M. Sc. Thesis, Fac. of Agric., Cairo University .

Abdel-Razik, M. and Mahmoud, S. A. (2017): Toxicological and biochemical effects of jojoba, *Simmondsia chinensis* extract on cotton leaf worm, *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisd.). J.

Plant Prot. and Pathol., Mansoura Univ., 8 (6): 233-239.

Ahmad, F.; Akram, W.; Sajjad, A. and Imran, A. (2011): Management practices against cotton mealybug, *Phenacoccus solenopsis* Tinsley (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae). Int. J. Agric. and Biol., 13 (4): 547– 552.

Akhtar, Y.; Yu, Y.; Isman, M.B. and Plettner, E. (2010): Dialkoxybenzene and dialkoxyallylbenzene feeding and oviposition deterrents against the cabbage looper, *Trichoplusia ni*: potential insect behavior control agents. Journal of Agricultural Food and Chemistry, 58(8): 4983-4991.

Asmae, B. A.; Zantar, S.; Eamranll, A. (2019): Chemical composition and potential acaricide of salvia officinalis and *Eucalyptus globulus* on *Tetranychus urticae* Koch (Acarina:Tetranychidae). J. of App.Chem.and Env.Prot., 4(1): 1-15.

Attia, S.; Grissa, K.L. ; Longnay, G.; Bitume, E. and Hance *et al.* (2013): A review of the major biological approaches to control the worldwide pest *Tetranychus urticae* (Acari : Tetranychidae) with special reference to natural pesticides. J. Pest Sci., 86: 261 - 386. DOI: 10.1007/s 10340-013-0503-0.

Dhawan, A. K.; Singh, K. ; Saini, S.; Mohindru, B.; Kaur, A.; Singh, G. and Singh, S. (2007): Incidence and damage potential of mealybug *Phenacoccus solenopsis* Tinsley on cotton in Punjab. Indian Journal of Entomology, 43: 166-172.

Dimetry, N. Z.; Metwally, H. M.; Abdou. W. L. and Abdel-Hakim, E. A. (2017): Acceptability and anti-feedant

- effect of the drumstick *Moringa oleifera* leaves towards the cotton leaf worm *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisd) under laboratory conditions. Res. J. Pharm. Biol. Chem. Sci., 1006-1014.
- Duncan, D.B. (1955):** Multiple range and multiple F- test. Biometrics, 11:1-42.
- Ejaz, M. and Ali Shad, S. (2017):** Spirotetramat resistance selected in the *Phenacoccus solenopsis* (Homoptera: Pseudococcidae): cross-resistance patterns, stability, and fitness costs analysis. Journal Economic Entomology, 110 (3):1226–1234.
- El-Fakharany, S. K. M. (2020):** Cotton mealybug *Phenacoccus solenopsis* (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae) population density in eggplant and okra plantations and effect of some insecticides. Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst. 3 (1): 377 – 388.
- El-Zahi, E. S. and Farag, A. A. (2017):** Population dynamic of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* Tinsley on cotton plants and its susceptibility to some insecticides in relation to the exposure method. Alexandria Science Exchange Journal, 38(2):231-237.
- El-Zahi, E.S.; Aref, S. A. and Korish, S.K.M. (2016):** The cotton mealybug, *Phenacoccus solenopsis* Tinsley (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae) as a new menace to cotton in Egypt and its chemical control. J. Plant Prot. Res., 56 (2): 111-115.
- Fuchs, T. W.; Stewart, J. W.; Minzenmayer, R. and Rose, M. (1991):** First record of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* Tinsley in cultivated cotton in the United States. Southwestern Entomologist, 16 (3): 215-221.
- Gaaboub, I. A.; Halawa, S. and Rabiha, A. (2012):** Toxicity and biological effects of some insecticides, IGRs and Jojoba oil on cotton leaf worm, *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisd.). J. Appl. Sci. Res., 8(10): 5161-5168.
- Gaber, W. M. and Nasr, H. M. (2020):** Comparison Between the Effect of Neem Oil and Neem Aqueous Extract on *Tetranychus urticae* Koch (Acari: Tetranychidae). Egypt. Acad. J. Biolog. Sci., 12(2): 19-23.
- Halawa, S. M.; Kamel, A. M. and Abd El-Hamid, S. R. (2007):** Chemical constituents of jojoba oil and insecticidal activity against *Schistocerca gregaria* and biochemical effects on albino rates. J. Egypt. Soc. Toxicol., 36: 77-87.
- Handerson, C. F. and Tilton, E. W. (1955):** Test with acaricides against the brown wheat mite. J. Econ. Entomol., (48):157-161
- Ibrahim, S. S; Moharum, F A. and Abd El-Chany, N. M. A. (2015):** The cotton mealybug, *Phenacoccus solenopsis* Tinsley (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae) as a new insect pest on tomato plant in Egypt. Journal of Plant Protection Research, 25(1):48-51.
- Kumar, R.; Nitharwal, M.; Chauhan, R.; Pal, V. and Kranthi, K. R. (2012):** Evolution of ecofriendly control methods for management of mealybug *Phenacoccus solenopsis* Tinsley in cotton. Journal of Entomology, 9(1):32-40.

- Reynolds, S. E. and Samuels, R. I. (1996):** Physiology and biochemistry of insect moulting fluid. Adv. Ins. Physiol., 26:157-163.
- Rezk, M.; Hassan, A. T.; El-Deeb, M.F.; Shaarawy, N. and Dewar, Y. (2019):** The impact of insecticides on the cotton mealybug, *Phenacoccus solenopsis* (Tinsley): Efficacy on potato, a new record of host plant in Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res., 59 (1): 50–59.
- Rizvi, S. A. H.; Ikhlaq, M. N.; Jaffar, S. and Hussain, S. (2015):** Efficacy of some selected synthetic chemical insecticides and bio-pesticides against cotton mealybug, *Phenacoccus solenopsis* Tinsley (Sternorrhyncha: Pseudococcidae) under agro ecological conditions of Peshawar, Pakistan. Journal of Entomology and Zoology Studies, 3 (6): 223–231.
- Sahito, H. A.; Abro, G. H.; Mahmoud, R. and Malik, A. Q. (2011):** survey of mealybug, *Phenacoccus solenopsis* Tinsley and effect of bio-ecological factors on its population in different ecological zones of Sindh. Pakistan journal of Agriculture, 27(1):51-65.
- Salem, H. E. M.; Omar, R. E. M.; El-Sisi, A. G. and Mokhtar, A. M. (2003):** Field and laboratory use of environmentally safe chemicals against whitefly *Bemisia tabaci* (Gennandius) and leafhopper *Empoasca discipiens* (Paoli): Annals Agric. Sci., Moshtohor, 41 (4): 1737-1741.
- SAS. (1995):** Statistical analysis system stat user's guide, release 6.03. ed., SAS Institute Inc., Cary, Nc. USA, pp. 125-154.
- Soltan, E. (2014):** Separate and joint action of neem and cascade on the desert locust *Schistocerca gregaria* Forskal. Ph. D. Thesis, Inst Afr. Res. Stud., Cairo University .
- Soltan, E. (2020):** Effect of jojoba and moringa essential oils and cascade on grasshoppers in the field. Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst., 3 (1): 486-492
- Suresh, S.; Jothimani, R.; Sivasubramanian, P.; Karuppuchamy, P.; Samiyappan, R. and Jonathan, E. I. (2010):** Invasive mealybugs of Tamil Nadu and their management. Kamataka Journal of Agricultural Sciences, 23(1):6-9.
- Tanani, M. A.; Ghoneim, K. S. and Hamadah, Kh. Sh. (2012):** Comparative effects of certain IGRs on the carbohydrates of haemolymph and fat body of the desert locust, *Schistocerca gregaria*(Orthoptera: Acrididae). Flor. Entomol., 95(4):928-935.

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Antimicrobial activity of bee (Hymenoptera: Apidae) venom against pathogens of human and honey bee colonies

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strains and human .

Abstract:

Experiments were conducted in the Research Complex of Agriculture Faculty (Microbiology Research Laboratory), Cairo University-Giza, Egypt in 2019 season, to study the antimicrobial activity of a mix of bee venom collected from two hybrid, Carniolian bees *Apis mellifera carnica* and Italian bees *Apis mellifera ligustica* (Hymenoptera: Apidae) at different concentrations using a well diffusion assay against different bacterial and fungi strains which causes diseases of honey bee colony and human. Also, Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of bee venom against fungal disease "Stone brood" caused by *Aspergillus flavus* NRR1 1957 affect honey bees colony. Data indicate the antimicrobial activity of the collected bee venom against different microorganisms that infect both human and honey bee colonies. The present study showed that antifungal effect has a dry bee venom against "Stone brood" caused by *Aspergillus flavus* that affect honey bee colonies. Moreover, the experiment detected the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of the collected bee venom against fungus *Aspergillus flavus*. Moreover, the bee venom concentration at (40 and 80 mg/ml) showed an incomplete reduction of *Aspergillus flavus* growth rate while bee venom concentration at (≥ 320 mg/ml) recorded has the highest reduction rate. Thus, the highest concentration of bee venom showed the highest antifungal and antibacterial activity. Furthermore, the bacterial and antifungal activity of bee venom on different bacterial and fungi strains affecting humans were investigated too in the current study. Concentrations of bee venom were chosen according to previous MIC experiments studied in the current work (320 μ g/ml). Bee venom showed a broad antibacterial activity against different G+ve bacterial strains of (*Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 6538P, *Staphylococcus aureus* MRSA ATCC 43300, *Bacillus Cereus* ATCC 33018), and G-ve bacteria (*Salmonella typhimureum* ATCC 14028). In addition, it showed antifungal activity against (*Candida albicans* ATCC 10231 and *Aspergillus niger* NRRL 326) indicating bee venom had broad spectrum activity against a different variety of microorganisms. Finally, bee venom is an important economical product of honey bees colonies in the medical field and plant disease control. Therefore, the light should be shed on bee venom productivity and industry.

Introduction

The products of the honey bee *Apis mellifera* L. (*Hymenoptera: Apidae*) are of great concern in (Apitherapy) fields of medicine and pharmaceutical industry nowadays and many researches proved the importance of honey bee and honey bee products. These products such as honey, royal jelly, wax, venom, pollen and propolis are very important due to their nutritive value or important pharmacological activities, which influence different biological and medical aspects of human health. Successful treatments of the central and peripheral nervous system, such as back pain, limb pain, neuralgia, neuritis, articulates polyneuritis and ear inflammation (Munstedt and Bogdanov, 2009). According to Dong *et al.* (2007), the venom also contains mineral substances, volatile-organic acid, formic acid and some antibiotics. Venom is one of the products of honey bee which is an important component in the pharmaceutical industry of use of naturally available substances medicines. Bee venom has interesting pharmacological properties and is used in the treatment of various health condition such as rheumatism (Kim *et al.*, 2003).

Bee venom therapy is a part of apitherapy that utilizes bee venom in the treatment of health conditions. Apitherapy is the use of bee products, such as: honey bee, pollen grain, propolis, royal jelly, and wax and bee venom. It has been used since ancient times and in this modern age as an alternative therapy to treat several diseases like multiple sclerosis, Lyme disease, and chronic fatigue syndrome. Bee venom has a rich source of enzymes, peptides and biogenic amines and contains at least 18 active components (El-Bassiouny, 2007).

Pheromones secretion is considered as one of the main stimuli

for inducing an aggressive attitude amongst defending worker bees (Gary, 1974), also the use of the bee venom for medical purposes is known to be a very old practice, especially for rheumatism and thirties. Hypocrites (400 B.C.) have mentioned about bee sting therapy used for arthritis. Nowadays bee venom (Epitoxen) is used for the treatment of naturopaths. It's also used in immunotherapy as a means for decreasing the sensitivity of allergic reactions in individuals who are hypersensitivity to bee stings.

Attention has been made to bee venom collection in abundance from two hybrid from honey bee colonies. In this working bee venom collecting device (VC-4FK) was used under local conditions of North Sinai in Egyptian apiaries ,to determine some factors affecting the bee venom collection from two hybrid honey bee colonies such as: Study the effect of bee venom collection from two hybrid against fungal diseases that affect honey bees colony. Stone brood caused by *Aspergillus flavus* (NRRL 1957) and different strains of fungal and bacterial microorganisms affecting human been.

Materials and methods

Experiments were conducted in the research complex of Agriculture Faculty (Microbiology Research Laboratory), Cairo University-Giza, Egypt in 2019 season, to detect the antimicrobial activity of a mix of bee venom collected from two hybrid, Carniolian bees *Apis mellifera carnica* and Italian bees *Apis mellifera ligustica* (*Hymenoptera: Apidae*) against different bacterial and fungi strains that causes diseases of honey bee colony and human been.

Venom preparation:

Bee venom was dissolved in sterile water as it must be freshly prepared to avoid protein denaturation. This experiment included:

1. Effect of bee venom against fungal diseases "Stone brood" that affect honey bees colony:

The current experiment was carried out at Microbiology Research Lab, (Faculty of Agriculture Laboratory), Cairo University and it is considered as the principle experiment in the present study where it detecting both minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of antifungal activity of bee venom against fungal diseases that affect honey bees colony such as: stone brood caused by *A. flavus*.

Briefly, the method follows well diffusion assay, where the well which is used in the experiment was 8mm and saturated with 100µl of bee venom at different concentrations (40, 80, 160, 320 mg/ml). *A. flavus* NRRI 1957, which was obtained from (Biofertilizers Unit "Cairo Mircen", was inoculated in Sabaroud Dextrose Agar (TSB, Oxoid, Basingstoke, UK) at 25 °C for 24-48hr. The MIC was defined as the lowest concentration of each bee venom sample at which visible inhibition of bacterial growth was induced and the diameter of each inhibition zone was measured by a regular ruler and presented in cm.

2. Antimicrobial and antifungal activity of bee venom on different bacterial and fungi strains affecting human been:

The current experiment was carried out at Microbiology Research Lab, Faculty of Agriculture Laboratory, Cairo University. Each bacterial strain of *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC 6538P), *S. aureus* MRSA (ATCC 43300), *Salmonella typhimureum* (ATCC 14028) were grown overnight in Mueller-Hinton Agar medium (TSB, Oxoid, Basingstoke, UK) at 37°C/24-48 hr., while *Bacillus Cereus* (ATCC 33018) was incubated at 300c/24-48 hr. The *Candida albicans* (ATCC 10231) and *Aspergillus niger* (NRRL 326) were

inoculated in Sabaroud Dextrose Agar at 250c/24-48 hr. The method follows well diffusion assay, where the well which is used in the experiment was 8mm and saturated with 100µl of bee venom sample at 320 mg/ml concentration. Concentrations of bee venom chosen according to previous MIC experiment studied in the current work (320 µg/ml). The inhibition zone of bacterial growth was observed, and the diameter of each inhibition zone was measured by a regular ruler and presented in cm.

Results and discussion

Effect of the collected bee venom on different microorganism:

The experiment detected the antimicrobial activity of the collected bee venom from the two bee hybrids against different microorganism of bacterial and fungi strains that affect diseases of both honey bee colony and human been to evaluate the effect of different concentrations of bee venom on their growth.

1. Effect of bee venom against fungal diseases affect honey bee colony "Stone brood" caused by *Aspergillus flavus*:

Data in Table (1) and Figures (1 and 2) showed minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of collecting bee venom against fungus *A. flavus* as well as its antifungal activity against stone brood caused by *A. flavus* NRRL 1957 that affect honey bees' colony. The results showed that the collected bee venom at high concentrations (≥ 320 µg/ml) recorded the highest reduction rate against fungal cells of Stone brood caused by *A. flavus* NRRL 1957. On the other hand, the low bee venom concentration (40 and 80 µg/ml) showed the lowest inhibition of *A. flavus* NRRL1957 growth rate. Thus, indicated that the higher concentration of bee venom recorded the highest antifungal activity.

Table(1):The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of tested honey bee venom against honey bee’s colony fungal disease " Stone brood" caused by *Aspergillus flavus* NRRI 1957.

Disease affects honey bee colony	Microbial Type	Causative Microorganism	Bee venom (MIC)		Medium	Incubation Conditions
			Conc. (mg/ml)	Inhibition Zone (cm)		
stone brood	Fungi	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i> (nrri 1957)	40	9	Sabaroud Dextrose Agar	25 o C /24 - 48h.
			80	13		
			160	20		
			320	25		

The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of tested honey bee venom against honey bee’s colony fungal diseases " Stone brood" caused by *Aspergillus flavus* NRRI 1957

Figure (1): The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of tested honey bee venom against honey bees colony fungal diseases "Stone brood" caused by *Aspergillus flavus* NRRI 1957.

Figure (2): Show effect of bee venom against fungal diseases "Stone brood" caused by *Aspergillus flavus* (MIC).

2. Antimicrobial activity of bee venom against different bacterial and fungi strains affecting human been:

Results in Table (2) and Figures (3 and 4) showed the antimicrobial activity of bee venom against different bacterial and fungi strains affecting humans been using the highest

concentrations of bee venom (320 µg/ml) chosen according to previous MIC experiment studied in the current work. In the current study, bee venom showed a broad antibacterial activity against different G+ve bacterial strains of (*Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 6538P, *S. aureus* MRSA ATCC 43300, *Bacillus Cereus* ATCC 33018), and G-

ve bacteria (*S. typhimureum* ATCC 14028). In addition, it showed antifungal activity against (*Candida albicans* ATCC 10231 and *A. niger*

NRRL 326) indicating bee venom broad spectrum activity against different variety of microorganisms.

Table (2): Effect of antimicrobial activity of bee venom Extracted from Italian hybrid on different bacterial and fungi strains affecting human been.

Different Pathogenic Microorganisms Name	Microbial Type	Bee venom Extracted		Medium	Incubation Conditions
		Concentration (mg/ml)	Inhibition Zone(cm)		
Staphylococcus aureus (ATCC 6538P)+	Bacteria	320	15	Mueller - Hinton Agar	37 o C /24 - 48 hrs.
Staphylococcus aureus MRSA+ (ATCC 43300)	Bacteria	320	17	Mueller - Hinton Agar	37 o C /24 - 48 hrs.
Bacillus Cereus+ (ATCC 33018)	Bacteria	320	20	Mueller - Hinton Agar	37 o C /24 - 48 hrs..
Salmonella - typhimureum (ATCC 14028)	Bacteria	320	23	Mueller - Hinton Agar	30 o C /24 - 48 hrs.
Candida albicans (ATCC 10231)	Fungi	320	25	Sabaroud Dextrose Agar	25 o C /24 - 48 hrs.
Aspergillus niger (nrrI 326)	Fungi	320	20	Sabaroud Dextrose Agar	25 o C /24 - 48 hrs.

Figure (3): Effect of antimicrobial and antifungal activity of bee venom on different bacterial and fungi strains affecting human.

Figure (4): Antibacterial and antifungal activity of bee venom on different bacterial and fungi strains affecting human been such as:

A.B.V against *Staphylococcus aureus* MRSA (ATCC 43300).

B. B.V against *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC 6538P).

C.B.V against *Salmonella typhimureum* (ATCC 14028).

D.B.V against *Bacillus Cereus* (ATCC 33018).

E.B.V against *Candida albicans* (ATCC 10231).

References

Beven, L. and Wroblewski, H. (1997):

Effect of natural amphipathic peptides on viability, membrane potential, cell shape and motility of mollicutes. *Res. Micro.*,148(2) 163-175.

Dong , Ju Son; Jae, Woong Lee; Young, Hee Lee; Ho, Sueb Song; Chong Kil Lee and Jin, Tae Hong (2007):Therapeutic application of anti – arthritis, painreleasing, and anti- cancer effect of bee venom and its constituent compounds. *Pharmacology &Therapeutics*, 115 (2):246-270.

El-Bahnasy, S.A. (2017): Studies on collection of bee venom from different strains and its effect on the activity of hive with

referring to its antimicrobial activity M.Sc. Thesis, Fac. Environ. Agric. Sci., EL-Arish, University.

El-Bassiouny, A. M. (2007): Monitoring the reproductive individual in the oriental hornet *Vespa orientalis*. *Arab Univ. J. Sci.*, 15 (2): 459-511.

Fennell, J.F.; Shipman, W.H. and Cole, L.J. (1968): Antibacterial action of melittin, a polypeptide from bee venom. *Proc. Soc. Exp. Biol. Med.*,127(3):707-710.

Gary, N.E. (1974): Pheromones that effect the behavior and physiology of honey bees, pheromones, Ed. M.C. Birch. Amsterolam: N. Holland, 200-201.

- Han, S.M.; K.G. Lee; Park, K.Y. and Pak, S.C. (2013):** Antimicrobial activity of honey bee venom against select infectious fish pathogens. North American Journal of Aquaculture, 75(3): 445-448.
- Hegazi , A.G.; Abdou, A.M. and Abd Allah, F. (2014):** Evaluation of the antibacterial activity of bee venom from different sources. World Applied Sciences Journal, 30(3): 266-270.
- Hegazi, A. G.; El-Feel, M. A.; Abdel-Rahman, E.H. and Al-Fattah, M. A. A. (2015):** Antibacterial activity of bee venom collected from *Apis mellifera* Carniolan pure and hybrid races by two collection methods. Int .J. of Current Microbiology and Applied Sci., 4(4): 141-149.
- Hegazi, A. G.; Moharram, N. Z.; Abd-Allah, F. A.; Nour, M. S. and Khair, A.M. (2002):** Antibacterial activity of different Egyptian honeys in relation to some bee products. Egyptian J. of Veterinary Science, 36 (3): 1-42.
- Inoue, H.; Nakajima, T. and Okada, I. (1987):** The venomous components of the worker and queen honey bees during their nutrition and the seasonal generation. Japanese of Sanitary- Zoology, 38: 211-217.
- Kim, H.W.; Kwon, Y.B.; Ham, T.B.; Roh, D.H.; Yoon, S.Y. and Lee, H.J. (2003):** Acupoint stimulation using bee venom attenuates formalin-induced pain behavior and spinal cord fos expression. J .Vet. Med. Sci., 65(3):349-355.
- Kondo, E. and Kanai, K. (1986):** Bactericidal activity of the membrane fraction isolated from phagocytes of mice and its stimulation by melittin. Japan, J. Med. Sci. Biol., 39(1):9-20.
- Kwon, Y.B.; Lee, H.J. ; Han, H.J.; Mar, W.C. ; Kang, S.K. ; Yoon, O.B.; Beitz, A.J. and Lee, J.H.(2002):** Antinociceptive and anti-inflammatory effects on rheumatoid arthritis in rats. Life Sci., 71 (2): 191-204.
- Marz, R.; Mollay, G.; Krell, R. and Zelger, J. (1981):** Queen bee venom contains much less phospholipase than worker bee venom . Insect Biochem., I I : 685-690.
- Matsuzaki, K. (1997):** Molecular action mechanisms and membrane recognition of membrane-acting antimicrobial peptides, Yakugaku Zasshi, 117(5): 253-264.
- Metwaly , A.A. (2016):** Studies on honey bee venom. Ph.D. Thesis, Fac Environ. Agric. Sci., Cairo, Al-Azhar University.
- Mohamed, W. F.(2017):** Studies on honeybee venom production and its antimicrobial activity M.Sc. Thesis, Fac. Environ. Agric. Sci., EL-Arish, University.
- Monk, J. D.; Beuchat, L. R. and Hathcox, A. K. (1996):** Inhibitory effects of sucrose monolaurate, alone and in combination with organic acids, on *Listeria monocytogenes* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. J. Appl. Bacteriol., 81: 7-18.
- Munstedt, K. and Bogdanov, S. (2009):** Bee product and their potential use in modern medicine. J. of Api. Product and Api. Medical Sci.,1(3):57-63.
- Nour, M.E.; Zakaria, M.E. and Abdel-Wahab , T.E. (2004):** Electrophoretic studies on venom properties of the honey

- bee (*Apis mellifera* L.). Bull. Ent. Soc. Egypt, 81: 43-46.
- Omar, M.O.M. (1994):** Some factors affecting bee venom extraction from honeybee colonies, Assiut J. Agric. Sci., 25: 139-148.
- Oren, Z. and Shai, Y. (1997):** Selective lysis of bacteria but not mammalian cells by diatereomers of melittin : Structure-Function study. Biochemistry, Feb., 36 (7) : 1826-1835.
- Ortel, S. and Markwardt, F. (1955):** Studies on the antibacterial properties of bee venom. Pharmazie, 10(12): 743-746.
- Park, S.; Park, B.; Yun, S.; Kang, H.; So, B. and Yun, S. (2013):** Antimicrobial activities of honey bee venom against pathogens isolated from clinical bovine mastitis in Korea Planta Med., 79 – PL 16.
- Perumal, S. R. P.; Gopalakrishnakone, M. M.; Thwin, T. K.; Chow, H.; Bow, E. H.; Yap, T. W. and Thong, J. (2007):** Antibacterial activity of snake, scorpion and bee venoms: a comparison with purified venom phospholipase A2 enzymes. J. Appl. Microbiol., 102(3):650-659.
- Robinson, A. and Otis, W. (1996):** Bee venom: Concern about variability, Am. Bee J., 136(8): 584-588.
- Stocker, J.F. and Traynor, J.R. (1986):** The action of various venoms on Escherichia coli. J. Appl. Bacteriol., 61 (5): 383-388.
- Subbalakshmi , C.; Nagaraj, R. and Sitaram, N. (1990):** Biological activities of C-terminal 15-residue synthetic fragment of melittin: design of an analog with improved antibacterial activity .FEBS Lette., 448(1) : 62-66.

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Effect of some plant extracts in controlling the two-spotted spider mite *Tetranychus urticae*
(Acari: Tetranychidae)

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Abstract:

Laboratorial experiments are carried out to determine the effects of local plant extracts *Mentha piperita*, *Ricinus communis* and *Punica granatum* (At the rate of 10%) extraction from Water, ethanol and methanol on *Tetranychus urticae* Koch (Acari: Tetranychidae) at 25±5°C; 60±5% RH. The obtained results showed that the treatments of *M. piperita* extraction by methanol (PM), ethanol (PE) and water (PW) have reduction percentage values, 91.71, 91.13 and 89.14 %, respectively, followed by treatment by *P. granatum* extraction have reduction percentage values, 90.98, 90.02 and 88.02%, respectively, and finally treatment by *R. communis* extraction have reduction percentage values , 88.77, 88.22 and 88.43 %, respectively. Extraction of *M. piperita*, *R. communis* and *P. granatum* by methanol was more effective than water or ethanol on *T. urticae*. Therefore, it could be concluded that the tested treatments exhibited the potential acaricidal effect ($P \leq 0.05$) on the population numbers of *T. urticae* compared to the control.

Introduction

The two-spotted spider mite *Tetranychus urticae* Koch (Acari: Tetranychidae) is one of the most common and harmful pests in vegetable production areas. Although more and more farmers consider biological control as a valid option to keep spider mites below economic damage thresholds, control of *T. urticae* is still mainly based on the application of acaricides (Çağatay *et al.*, 2018). *T. urticae* is notorious for its ability to develop acaricide resistance very quickly (Van Leeuwen *et al.*, 2010 and Van Leeuwen and Dermauw, 2016). Its short life cycle, high reproduction and

fecundity all contribute to resistance development. Resistance has often been reported to evolve only a few years after the introduction of a new acaricide (Van Leeuwen *et al.*, 2009 and 2010). Another reason for fast resistance development is the polyphagous nature of the species, *T. urticae* is encountered on many crops, resulting in high acaricide exposure. In addition, the evolution to polyphagy might have equipped spider mites with a unique detoxification toolkit (Dermauw *et al.*, 2013), although other factors in resistance development might prevail in the broader context of arthropod pests (Dermauw *et al.*, 2018).

As an alternative to synthetic acaricidal agents, essential oils from plants constitute excellent candidates for pest control involving various modes of action that offer less mammalian toxicity and low persistence in the environment. Volatility is one of the most important characteristics of essential oils, enabling their use as fumigating agents for the control of pests under greenhouse conditions (Aslan *et al.*, 2004). Essential oils are complex mixtures comprised of monoterpenes, sesquiterpenes and phenylpropanoids, which are chemical classes of substances known for their acaricidal properties (Araújo *et al.*, 2012; Moraes *et al.*, 2012 and Ribeiro *et al.*, 2016). One of the advantages of using essential oils in the formulation of a plant-based acaricidal agent is the fact that possible resistance in the target pest generally takes a much longer time to develop for a mixture of natural active compounds compared to any single component (Koul *et al.*, 2008).

Mentha piperita is a well-known genus belonging to family *Lamiaceae* shows a reputed medicinal and aromatic value. That genus includes about 30 species that grow in the temperate regions of Eurasia, Australia and South Africa (Dorman *et al.*, 2003).

Table (1): Plant extracts used in the present study

English Name	Scientific Name	Family	Part used	active constituent
Peppermint	<i>Mentha piperita</i>	Lamiaceae	Leaves	Menthol
Pomegranate	<i>Punica granatum</i>	Lythraceae	Peel	Ellagic acid
Castor	<i>Ricinus communis</i>	Euphorbiaceae	Leaves	Ricin

2. Extraction procedures:

2.1. Extraction by water:

Peppermint and castor leaves and peels of pomegranate (Table 1) were dried and grinded. 200 gm. powder of each were dissolved in 1000 ml of boiled water, mixed and covered to prevent evaporation of the volatile oils. Incubated for 24h at RT (room temperature). Occasional shaking of

Pomegranate fruit has been used in China, India, Japan, and the Mediterranean basin as a medicine to cure a variety of diseases. Recently, the traditional usage was corroborated by scientific data indicating that pomegranates are a good source of antimicrobial, anticancer, and antidiabetic compounds (Seeram *et al.*, 2006). Moreover, different pomegranate accessions contain different amounts of bioactive compounds such as punicalagin, punicalin, galagic acid, and ellagic acid (Tzulker *et al.*, 2007). However, the effect of plant-based castor leaves on *T. urticae* has not been studied till date.

The aim of this study is to evaluate the toxic effects and repellence of *M. piperita* and *Punica granatum* and *Ricinus communis* extracts by organic solvents against *T. urticae* under laboratory condition.

Materials and methods

1. Plant extracts:

Leaves of peppermint (*M. piperita*) and castor (*R. communis*) as well as peels of pomegranate (*P. granatum*) against the two-spotted spider mite *T. urticae*. (Table 1)

mixture was carried out to get maximum extraction, then it was blended for 15 min. in a laboratory blender. The mixture was filtered to eliminate the wastes. The crude extracts were weighed and kept in refrigerator. Series of dilutions were prepared using distilled water to make required concentrations (Berktaş and Cam, 2020).

2.2. Extraction by the organic solvent:

2.2.1. Methanol:

Peppermint and castor leaves and peels of pomegranate (Table, 1) were dried and grinded. 200 gm. powder of each were dissolved in methanol (MeoH) (1 gm: 7 ml methanol: 3ml Water) for 24/hrs., and then blended for 15 min. The mixtures were set aside for 3 days at RT. with shaking each day and then filtrated. The mixtures were transferred to round bottles in a rotary evaporator adjusted at 60°C until dryness. The mixtures were evaporated. The crude extracts were weighed and kept in refrigerator. Series of dilutions were prepared using distilled water to make required concentrations (Ahmed *et al.* , 2021 and Pramila *et al.*, 2012).

2.2.2. Ethanol

Peppermint and castor leaves and peels of pomegranate (Table, 1) were dried and grinded. 200 gm. powder of each were dissolved in ethanol (1 gm: 7 ml ethanol: 3ml Water) for 24/h, and then blended for 15 min. The mixtures were set aside for 3 days at RT. with shaking each day and then filtrated. The mixtures were evaporated. The crude extracts were weighed and kept in refrigerator. Series of dilutions were prepared using distilled water to make required concentrations (Vasavada and Inampudi, 2020).

3. Rearing technique of mites:

A pure culture of *T. urticae* was reared at (25±5°C) in the Pharmaceutics laboratory, Pharmaceutics Department, Faculty of Pharmacy, The British University in Egypt. *T. urticae* was hosted on the lower surface of mulberry leaves (*Morus nigra* L.) which placed on filter paper in Petri-dishes (20 cm in diameter) padded with moist cotton. The cotton pads were moistened daily to avoid disc dryness, and to prevent mite escape. The damaged infested leaves were placed on new ones to

maintain mites feeding which assure its proliferation and transformation. Females were collected, then each female was cultured in Petri-dishes provided with surplus of *T. urticae* to get small colonies which used for further tests.

4. Effect of extracts on different developmental stages of *Tetranychus urticae*:

To test the susceptibility of *T. urticae* to different groups of extracts, mulberry leaves were placed in Petri dishes (15 cm in diameter) padded with moist cotton which represented five replicates for each treatment. To study the effect of the extracts on *T. urticae*, five gravid females for 24 h. At the end of this time the spider mites were removed, and the number of eggs was adjusted to 50 by destroying, removing or adding eggs using a fine brush. All discs except controls were treated with extracts by spraying. The treated discs were kept at RT. The number of adult females and the deposited eggs were counted daily.

5. Treatments:

5.1. 10% peppermint extract water (PW) on 55 *T. urticae*; **5.2.** 10% peppermint extract ethenol (PE) on 55 *T. urticae*; **5.3.** 10% peppermint extract methanol (PM) on 55 *T. urticae*; **5.4.** 10% pomegranate extract water (PeW) on 55 *T. urticae*; **5.5.** 10% pomegranate extract ethanol (PeE) on 55 *T. urticae*; **5.6.** 10% pomegranate extract methanol (PeM) on 55 *T. urticae*; **5.7.** 10% castor extract water (CW) on 55 *T. urticae*; **5.8.** 10% pomegranate extract ethanol (CE) on 55 *T. urticae*; **5.9.** 10% pomegranate extract methanol (CM) on 55 *T. urticae* and **5.10.** Control without any plant extract.

The reduction percentages of *T. urticae* average number were calculated according to the equation of Henderson and Tilton (1955).

$$\text{Reduction} = 1 - \frac{\text{Treatment after x control before}}{\text{Teaiment before x control after}} \times 100$$

6. Statistical analysis:

One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and mean comparison using Fisher's least significant difference (LSD) were conducted for the number of spider mite, using the software packages SPSS 16.0.0 (USA) for windows. Significance level was $P \leq 0.05$.

Results and discussion

The extract of peppermint (Menthol), pomegranate (Ellagic Acid) and castor (Ricin) were used to evaluate toxic effect on *T. urticae* population. Figure (1) shows the relation between time (Days) and the mean average numbers of *T. urticae* (Individual) for the previously mentioned 9 treatments and the control. Also, Table (1) shows the results of the average number of *T. urticae* population and their reduction percentage for all treatments. The experimental results showed that the spider mite population and their reduction percentage showed no significant difference between different extract treatments (LSD; $P = 0.895$). However, there was significant difference of the spider mite population in the control treatment. (LSD; $P < 0.004$).

Control: Number of spider mites increased, and this increase continued till reached its peak (about 228 individual/Petri Dish) on day 15. After that, the population of spider mite started to decrease sharply due to the damage of leaves caused by the spider mite population, the population extinction on day 19 (Figure 1 and Table 2).

In all treatments the average of spider mite populations (Eggs, adults and total of spider mite; Figure 1) declined immediately after spraying the plant extracts.

- **Peppermint 10% water (PW):** Number of spider mites in this treatment decreased gradually compared to the control directly after spraying and reached zero on the 7th day

(Figure 1). The obtained reduction percentage of spider mite population under this treatment was 91.13% (Table 2).

Peppermint 10% ethanol (PE): Similarly, number of spider mites decreased gradually compared to the control directly after spraying and reached zero on the 7th day (Figure 1). The obtained reduction percentage of spider mite population under this treatment was 89.14% (Table 2).

Peppermint 10% methanol (PM): Likewise, number of spider mites decreased gradually compared to the control directly after spraying and reached zero on the 6th day (Figure 1). The obtained reduction percentage of spider mite population under this treatment was 91.71% (Table 2).

- **Also, Pomegranate 10% water (PeW):** Number of spider mites decreased gradually compared to the control directly after spraying and reached zero on the 9th day. (Figure 1). The obtained reduction percentage of spider mite population under this treatment was 88.02% (Table 2).

Pomegranate 10% ethanol (PeE): Similarly, number of spider mites decreased gradually compared to the control directly after spraying and reached zero on the 9th day (Figure 1). The obtained reduction percentage of spider mite population under this treatment was 90.02% (Table 2).

Pomegranate 10% methanol (PeM): The same number of spider mites decreased gradually compared to the control directly after spraying and reached zero on the 9th day (Figure 1). The obtained reduction percentage of spider mite population under this treatment was 90.98% (Table 2).

- **Finally, Castor 10% water (CW):** Number of spider mites decreased gradually compared to the control directly after spraying and reached zero on the 9th day (Figure 1). The obtained reduction percentage of spider mite

population under this treatment was 88.43% (Table 2). **Castor 10% ethanol (CE):** Number of spider mites decreased gradually compared to the control directly after spraying and reached zero on the 8th day (Figure 1). The obtained reduction percentage of spider mite population under this treatment was 88.22% (Table 2).

Castor 10% methanol (CM): Number of spider mites decreased gradually compared to the control directly after spraying and reached zero on the 10th day (Figure 1). The obtained reduction percentage of spider mite population under this treatment was 88.77% (Table 2).

Figure (1) : The average numbers of *Tetranychus urticae* reduction by peppermint, pomegranate and castor extractions by methanol, ethanol and water as well as the control treatment.

Table (2): The average numbers of *T. urticae* and their corresponding reduction percentage (%) by peppermint, pomegranate and castor extraction by methanol, ethanol and water as well as the control treatment.

Treatments	Average \pm SE	Max.	Reduction %
Peppermint 10% water (PW)	10.73 \pm 4.83 _{ab}	55.00	91.13 % _A
Peppermint 10% ethanol (PE)	12.73 \pm 4.98 _{ab}	55.00	89.14 % _A
Peppermint 10% methanol (PM)	10.20 \pm 4.78 _a	55.00	91.71 % _A
Pomegranate 10% water (PeW)	13.93 \pm 5.02 _{ab}	55.00	88.02 % _A
Pomegranate 10% ethanol (PeE)	11.73 \pm 5.06 _{ab}	55.00	90.02 % _A
Pomegranate 10% methanol (PeM)	11.00 \pm 4.71 _{ab}	55.00	90.98 % _A
Castor 10% water (CW)	13.53 \pm 4.95 _{ab}	55.00	88.43 % _A
Castor 10% ethanol (CE)	13.73 \pm 5.00 _{ab}	55.00	88.22% _A
Castor 10% methanol (CM)	13.27 \pm 4.83 _{ab}	55.00	88.77% _A
Control	145.53 \pm 13.85 _c	228.00	-

Means followed by different subscript letters within columns are significantly different from each other ($P < 0.05$) LSD test.

The previous results show that all treatments have close reduction percentage values. The menthol (Methanol) treatment has the highest reduction percentage value (91.71%), while, ellagic acid (Water) treatment has the lowest reduction percentage value (88.02%). The curve of menthol treatments (Methanol, ethanol and water) reached zero on (6th day, 7th day and 7th day, respectively). The curve of ellagic acid treatment (Methanol, ethanol and water) reached zero on (8th day, 8th day and 9th day, respectively). The curve of ricin (Methanol, ethanol and water) reached zero on (10th day, 8th day and 9th day, respectively; Figure 1).

There are several studies in different countries to assess the effect and potential of plant extraction for controlling the pest without the use of pesticides without economic damage to the crop (e.g. Kotb, 2003; ElMougy and Alhabeab, 2009; Hussein *et al.*, 2013

and Abdallah *et al.*, 2015). Successful biocontrol can be obtained in many cases (e.g., Brødsgaard and Enkegaard, 1997; Messelink *et al.*, 2005 and 2006). Our result is closely and agree with Gorski and Piatek (2008); El-Zemity *et al.* (2009) and Abdallah *et al.* (2015) who recorded that the peppermint oil was the best extract to control of *T. urticae* with 92.70% reduction. The three essential oils that extracted by (Methanol, ethanol and water) have high efficiency in eliminating *T. urticae*. Menthol extraction by methanol better than extraction by water or ethanol in reduction percentage. Also, ellagic acid extraction by methanol better than extraction by ethanol or water in reduction percentage. Finally, the Ricin extraction by methanol better than extraction by ethanol or water in reduction percentage.

Reference

- Abdallah, A.A.; Abbassy, M.R.A. and Salem, A.A. (2015):** Efficacy of two essential oil extracts and predatory mite *Phytoseiulus persimilis* in suppressing the population of the two spotted spider mite, *Tetranychus urticae* Koch. J. Plant Prot. and Path., Mansoura Univ., 6 (7):1123-1133.
- Ahmed, K.; Tariq, I. and Mudassir, S. U. S. M. (2021):** 11. Green synthesis of cobalt nanoparticles by using methanol extract of plant leaf as reducing agent. Pure and Applied Biology (PAB), 5(3): 453-457.
- Araújo, M.J.C.; da Camara, C.A.G.; Born, F.S.; Moraes, M.M. and Badji, C.A. (2012):** Acaricidal activity and repellency of essential oil from *Piper aduncum* and its components against *T. urticae*. Exp Appl Acarol, 57:139–155.
- Aslan, İ.; Ozbek, H.; Çalmaşur, O. and Şahin, F. (2004):** Toxicity of essential oil vapours to two greenhouse pests, *T. urticae* Koch and *Bemisia tabaci* Genn. Indian Crop Prod., 19:167–173.
- Berktaş, S. and Cam, M. (2020):** Peppermint leaves hydrodistillation by-products: Bioactive properties and incorporation into ice cream formulations. Journal of Food Science and Technology, 1-12.
- Brødsgaard, H.F. and Enkegaard, A. (1997):** Interactions among polyphagous anthocorid bugs used for thrips control and other beneficials in multi-species biological pest management systems. In: Pandalai SG, editor. Research Signpost, Trivandrum. Rec. Res. Develo. Entomol., 153-160.
- Çağatay, N.S.; Menault, P.; Riga, M.; Vontas, J. and Ay, R. (2018):** Identification and characterization of abamectin resistance in *T. urticae* Koch populations from greenhouses in Turkey. Crop Prot., 112:112–117.
- Dermauw, W.; Pym, A.; Bass, C.; Van Leeuwen, T. and Feyereisen, R. (2018):** Does host plant adaptation lead to pesticide resistance in generalist herbivores? Curr Opin. Insect Sci., 26:25–33.
- Dermauw, W.; Wybouw, N.; Rombauts, S.; Menten, B.; Vontas, J.; Grbic, M.; Clark, R.M.; Feyereisen, R. and Van Leeuwen, T. (2013):** A link between host plant adaptation and pesticide resistance in the polyphagous spider mite *T. urticae*. Proc. Nat. Acad Sci. USA, 110: 113–122.
- Dorman, H.J.M.; Kosar, K.; Kahlos, Y.H. and Hiltunen, R. (2003):** Anti-oxidant prosperities and composition of aqueous extracts from *Mentha* species, hybrids, varieties and cultivars. J. Agric. Food chem., 51: 4563- 4569.
- ElMougy, N. S. and Alhabeab, R. S. (2009):** Inhibitory effects of powdered caraway and peppermint extracts on pea root rot under greenhouse conditions. J. plant protect. Res., 49 (1): 93-96.
- El-Zemity, S.R.; Rezk, H.A.; Zaitoon, A.A. (2009):** Acaricidal potential of some essential oils and their monoterpenoids against the Two-spotted spider mite *Tetranychus urticae* Koch. Naturwissen schaften, 100(6): 541-549.
- Gorski, R. and Piatek, H. (2008):** Efficacy of natural essential oils in the control of two-spotted

- spider mite (*Tetranychus urticae* Koch) occurring on dwarf bean. [Polish] Progress in Plant Protection, 48(4):1347-1350.
- Henderson, C.F. and Tilton, E.W. (1955).** Tests with acaricides against the brown wheat mite. J. Econ. Entomol., 48(2): 157-161.
- Hussein, H.; Reda, A.S. and Momen, F.M. (2013):** Repellent, antifeedent and toxic effects of three essential oils on the two spotted spider mite, *Tetranychus urticae* Koch (Acari: Tetranychidae). Acta Phytopathologica et Entomologica Hungarica, 48 (1): 177-186.
- Kotb, M.S.A. (2003):** Toxicity and biological effects of some plant extraction on phytophagous and predaceous mites. M Sc. Plant protection Dept., Fac. Agric., El-Fayoum, Cairo University.
- Koul, O.; Walia, S. and Dhaliwal, G.S. (2008):** Essential oils as green pesticides: potential and constraints. Biopesticide Int., 4:63–84.
- Messelink, G.J.; van Steenpaal, S.E.F. and Ramakers. M.J. (2006):** Evaluation of phytoseiid predators for control of western flower thrips on greenhouse cucumber. Biocontrol, 51(5): 753- 768.
- Messelink, G.J.; van Steenpaal, S.E.F. and van Wensveen, W. (2005):** *Typhlodromips swirskii* (Athias-Henriot) (Acari: Phytoseiidae): a new predator for thrips control in greenhouse cucumber. IOBC/wprs Bulletin, 28(1): 183-186.
- Moraes, M.M.D.; da Camara, C.A.G.; Santos, M.L.D. and Fagg, C.W. (2012):** Essential oil composition of *Eugenia langsdorfi* O. Berg.: relationships between some terpenoids and toxicity against *T. urticae*. J. Braz. Chem. Soc. 23:1647–1656.
- Pramila, D. M.; Xavier, R.; Marimuthu, K.; Kathiresan, S.; Khoo, M. L.; Senthilkumar, M. and Sreeramanan, S. (2012):** Phytochemical analysis and antimicrobial potential of methanolic leaf extract of peppermint (*Mentha piperita*: Lamiaceae). J. Med. Plants Res., 6(2):331-335.
- Ribeiro, N.; Camara, C. and Ramos, C. (2016):** Toxicity of essential oils of *Piper marginatum* Jacq. Against *T. urticae* Koch and *Neoseiulus californicus* (McGregor). Chilean JAR., 76:71–76.
- Seeram, N.P.; Schulman, R.N. and Heber, D., (2006):** Pomegranates: ancient roots to modern medicine. CRC Press Taylor & Francis Group, Boca Raton, FL, pp.244.
- Tzulker, R.; Glazer, I.; Bar-Ilan, I.; Holland, D.; Aviram, M. and Amir, R. (2007):** Antioxidant activity, polyphenol content and related compounds in different fruit juices and homogenates prepared from 29 different pomegranate accessions. J. Agric. Food Chem., 55: 9559–9570.
- Van Leeuwen, T. and Dermauw, W. (2016):** The molecular evolution of xenobiotic metabolism and resistance in chelicerate mites. Annu. Rev. Entomol., 61:475–498.
- Van Leeuwen, T.; Vontas, J.; Tsagkarakou, A.; Dermauw, W. and Tirry, L. (2010):** Acaricide resistance mechanisms in the two-spotted spider mite *T. urticae* and other

- important Acari: a review. Insect Bio Chem. Mol. Biol., 40 (8):563–572.
- Van Leeuwen, T.; Vontas, J.; Tsagkarakou, A.; Tsagkarakou, A. and Tirry, L. (2009):** Mechanisms of acaricide resistance in the two spotted spider mite *T. urticae*. In: Ishaaya I, Horowitz AR (eds) Biorational control of arthropod pests. Springer, Amsterdam, pp. 347–393.
- Vasavada, H. and Inampudi, S. (2020):** Anti-bacterial activity of peppermint (*Mentha piperita*) extracts against standard microorganisms, Mukta Shabd Journal, 9 (7): 108-194.

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Pheromone technology applications in the cotton fields in Egypt, with special references

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Abstract:

Only 20 years altered the discovery and identification of the first insect pheromone, Bombykol, the silk worm *Bombyx mori* sex – pheromone by Adolf Friedrich Johann Butenandt in 1959 (The Noble Prize in Chemistry 1939, discovery of human female sex – hormones, estrone and other primary female sex hormones, received in 1949) after the discovery of the insecticidal efficacy of DDT , the first chemical insecticide in 1939 by Paul Hermann Muller in 1939 (Noble Prize in medicine 1948). Pheromone technology could be used in many different tactics throughout the integrated pest management (IPM) strategy for the monitoring and control actions of the insect pest complex in the cotton fields. This article emphasizes on the pheromone technology tactics, applications, advantages and benefits in the modern cotton industry.

Introduction

Insecticides are used in agriculture, medicine, industry and the household. The use of insecticides is believed to be one of the major factors behind the increase in agricultural productivity in the 20th century. Nearly all insecticides have the potential to significantly alter ecosystems; many are

toxic to humans; and others are concentrated in the food chain. Although the first chemical insecticide (DDT) was discovered its biological activity (Insecticidal activity) in 1939, the first pheromone was (Bombykol) was characterized in 1959, it's only 20 years that altered the pheromones use after the insecticides use.

1. DDT Discovery (Figure 1) :

Figure (1) : DDT chemistry

DDT the first of the chlorinated organic insecticides (Figure 1) , was originally prepared in 1873, but it was

not until 1939 that Paul Muller of Geigy Pharmaceutical in Switzerland discovered the effectiveness of DDT as

an insecticide he was awarded the Nobel Prize in medicine and physiology in 1948 for this discover. The use of DDT increased enormously on a worldwide basis after World War II, primarily because of its effectiveness against the mosquito that spreads malaria and lice that carry typhus. The World Health Organization estimates that during the period of its use approximately 25 million lives were saved. DDT seemed to be the ideal insecticide, it is cheap and of relatively low toxicity to mammals (Oral LD50 is 300 to 500 mg/kg). However, problems related to extensive use of DDT began to appear in the late 1940s. Many species of insects developed resistance to DDT, and DDT was also discovered to have a high toxicity toward fish. The chemical stability of DDT and its fat solubility compounded the problem. DDT is not metabolized very rapidly by animals; instead, it is deposited and stored in the fatty tissues. The biological half-life of DDT is about eight years; that is, it takes about eight years for an animal to metabolize half of the amount it assimilates. If ingestion continues at a steady rate, DDT builds up within the animal over time.

1.1. Insecticide problems :

The heavy use of insecticides almost causes one or more of these problems:

- 1.1.1.** It acts as environmental pollutants.
- 1.1.2.** It has many risks to human health.
- 1.1.3.** It has many side effects on beneficial insects especially natural enemies.
- 1.1.4.** It causes the outbreak of secondary pests.
- 1.1.5.** It causes the problems of what so-called "Insecticide resistance".
- 1.1.6.** It has a side effects on the treated crops and causes what so-called "Phytotoxicity".
- 1.1.7.** It affects the soil fertility.

1.2. Costs of Insecticide problems :

Although, the above mentioned pesticide problems, we have to pay a huge amount of money to overcome some of its side effects. The return on pesticide-intensive agricultural practices has proved unrealized, considering billions of dollars in secondary or externalized costs — from \$2.2 billion in annual pesticide poisonings, water treatment and pollination, according to two Iowa State University economists, to \$10 billion, according to the research of Cornell University professor David Pimentel.

2. Integrated Pest management (IPM) :

2.1. IPM definitions:

2.1.1. "Integrated pest management, or IPM is a systematic approach to crop protection that uses increased information and improved decision-making paradigms to reduce purchased inputs and improve economic, social, and environmental conditions on the farm and in society. Moreover, the concept emphasizes the integration of pest suppression technologies that include biological, chemical, legal, and cultural controls" (Allen and Rajotte, 1990).

2.1.2. "Integrated pest management (IPM) is a pest management strategy that focuses on long-term prevention or suppression of pest problems with minimum impact on human health, the environment, and non-target organisms". "Preferred pest management techniques include encouraging naturally occurring biological control, using alternate plant species or varieties that resist pests, selecting pesticides with lower toxicity to humans or nontarget organisms; adoption of cultivating pruning, fertilizing, or irrigation practices that reduce pest problems; or changing the habitat to make it incompatible with pest development. Broad spectrum

pesticides are used as a last resort when careful monitoring indicates they are needed according to pre-established guidelines" (Flint *et al.*, 1991).

2.1.3. "IPM is a system approach based on science and proven crop production and resource conservation practices. It uses all suitable techniques, such as natural enemies, pest resistant plants, cultural management, and pesticides in a total crop production system to anticipate and prevent pests from reaching damaging level " (Bruhn *et al.*, 1992).

2.1.4. "Integrated Pest Management is the coordinated use of pest and environmental information along with available pest control methods, including cultural, biological, genetic and chemical methods, to prevent unacceptable levels of pest damage by the most economical means, and with the least possible hazard to people, property, and the environment"(Sorensen, 1993 a and 1994a).

2.1.5. "IPM is an ecologically-based pest control strategy which is part of the overall crop production system. 'Integrated' because all appropriate methods from multiple scientific disciplines are combined into a systematic approach for optimizing pest control. 'Management' implies acceptance of pests as inevitable components, at some population level of agricultural system" (Zalom *et al.*, 1992; Gianessi, 1993 ; Saarenmma, 1992; Sorensen, 1993a and Vandeman, 1994).

2.1.6. "Integrated Pest Management, or IPM, involves the carefully managed use of an array of pest control tactics - including biological, cultural, and chemical methods - to achieve the best results with the least disruption of the environment" (EPA, 1993 and AMACSA, 1993).

2.1.7. "Integrated Pest Management (IPM)- A combination of pest control methods (biological, chemical, and

cultivation) that, if used in the proper order and at the proper times, keep the size of a pest population low enough that it does not cause substantial economic loss"(Raven *et al.*, 1993).

2.1.8. "IPM is a management approach that encourages natural control of pest populations by anticipating pest problems and preventing pests from reaching economically damaging levels. All appropriate techniques are used such as enhancing natural enemies, planting pest-resistant crops, adapting cultural management, and using pesticides judiciously" (USDA-ARS, 1993 and Vandeman *et al.*, 1994).

2.1.9. "Management activities that are carried out by farmers that result in potential pest populations being maintained below densities at which they become pests, without endangering the productivity and profitability of the farming system as a whole, the health of the family and its livestock, and the quality of the adjacent and downstream environments"(Wightman, 1993).

2.1.10. "Integrated Pest Management is the judicious use and integration of various pest control tactics in the context of the associated environment of the pest in ways that complement and facilitate the biological and other natural controls of pests to meet economic, public health, and environmental goals"(Cate and Hinkle, 1994 and Wightman, 1993).

2.1.11. "Integrated Pest Management is the use of a variety of pest control methods designed to protect public health and the environment, and to produce high quality crops and other commodities with the most judicious use of pesticides" (CES-UC, 1994).

2.1.12. European Plant Protection Organization has defined integrated Control as "the use of all economically, ecologically and toxicologically justifiable means to keep pests below the economic threshold, with the

emphasis on the deliberate use of natural forms of control and preventive measures" (Dehne and Schonbeck, 1994).

2.1.13. "An effective and environmentally sensitive approach to pest management that relies on a combination of common-sense practices. IPM programs use current, comprehensive information on the life cycles of pests and their interactions with the environment. This information, in combination with available pest control methods, is used to manage pest damage by the most economical means, and with the least possible hazard to people, property, and the environment. IPM take advantage of all pest management options possible, including, but not limited to the judicious use of pesticides" (Leslie, 1994).

2.1.14. "Integrated pest management is a sustainable approach to managing pests by combining biological, physical, and chemical tools in a way that minimizes economic, health, and environmental risks" (NCIPM, 1994; ATTRA, 1995; NFIPME, 1994 and Vandeman *et al.*, 1994).

2.1.15. "Integrated Pest Management (IPM) is an approach to making pest control decisions with increased information and the use of multiple tactics to manage pest populations in an economically efficient and ecologically sound manner" (Norton and Mullen, 1994).

2.1.16. "IPM, in its simplest form, is a control strategy in which a variety of biological, chemical, and cultural control practices are combined to give stable long-term pest control." (Ramalho, 1994).

2.1.17. "IPM is a system that controls pests and contributes to long-term sustainability by combining judicious use of biological, cultural, physical and chemical control tools in a way that minimizes the risks of pesticides to

human health and the environment" (Sorensen *et al.*, 1994).

2.1.18. "Integrated pest management is a pest management system that in the socioeconomic context of farming systems, the associated environment and the population dynamics of the pest species, utilizes all suitable techniques in as compatible manner as possible and maintains the pest population levels below those causing economic injury" (Dent, 1995). This definition was modified from Smith and Reynolds (1966).

2.1.19. " 'Integrated Pest Management' means the selection, integration, and implementation of multiple pest control techniques based on predicted economic, ecological, and sociological consequences, making maximum use of naturally occurring pest controls, such as weather, disease agents, and parasitoids, using various biological, physiological, chemical, and habitat modification methods of control, and using artificial control only as required to keep particular pests from surpassing intolerable population levels predetermined from an accurate assessment of the pest damage potential and the ecological, sociological, and economic cost of other control measures (Florida Statutes 1995, Chapt. 482).

2.1.20. "Integrated pest management (IPM) is the judicious use and integration of various pest control tactics in the context of the associated environment of the pest in a way that compliment and facilitate the biological and other natural controls of pests to meet economic, public health, and environmental goals. Whenever possible, IPM uses scouting, pest trapping, pest resistant plant varieties, sanitation, various cultural control methods, physical and mechanical controls, biological controls, and precise timing and application of any needed pesticides" (Adams, 1996).

2.1.21. "Integrated Pest Management (IPM) is a sustainable approach to managing crop pests. IPM combines the use of biological, cultural, physical and chemical tactics in a way that minimizes economic, health, and environmental risks" (FCES, 1996).

2.1.22. "Real IPM: 'A crop protection system which is based on rational and unbiased information leading to a balance of non-chemical and chemical components moving pesticide use levels away from their present political optimum to a social optimum defined in the context of welfare economics'" (Waibel and Zadoks, 1996).

2.1.23. "The management of pests by integrating host resistance, cultural, biological and chemical controls in a manner that minimizes economic, health and environmental risks" (CPM, 1997).

2.1.24. " 'Integrated pest management' means a coordinated decision-making and action process that uses the most appropriate pest control methods and strategy in an environmentally and economically sound manner to meet agency pest management objectives. The elements of integrated pest management include: (a) Preventing pest problems; (b) Monitoring for the presence of pests and pest damage; (c) Establishing the density of pest population, which may be set at zero, that can be tolerated or corrected with a damage level sufficient to warrant treatment of the problem based on health, public safety, economic or aesthetic threshold; (d) Treating pest problems to reduce population below those levels established by damage thresholds using strategies that may include biological, cultural, mechanical and chemical control methods and that shall consider human health, ecological impact, feasibility and cost effectiveness; and (e) Evaluating the effects and efficacy of pest treatments"

(Oregon Statutes (ORS 262.1), Chapter 943) and McCoy, 1992).

2.1.25. "The management of pests by integrating host resistance, cultural, biological and chemical controls in a manner that minimizes economic, health and environmental risks" (CPM, 1997).

2.1.26. "Integrated Pest Management (IPM) for agriculture is the application of an interconnected set of principles and methods to problems caused by insects, diseases, weeds and other agricultural pests. IPM includes pest prevention techniques, pest monitoring methods, biological control, pest-resistant plants varieties, pest attractants and repellents, biopesticides, and synthetic organic pesticides. It also involves the use of weather data to predict the onset of pest attack, and cultural practices such as rotation, mulching, raised planting beds, narrow plant rows, and interseeding" (Tette, 1997) .

2.1.27. "Integrated Pest Management (IPM) is an ecosystem-based strategy that focuses on long-term prevention of pests or their damage through a combination of techniques such as biological control, habitat manipulation, modification of cultural practices, and use of resistance varieties. Pesticides are used only after monitoring indicates they are needed according to established guidelines, and treatments are made with the goal of removing only target organism. Pest control materials are selected and applied in a manner that minimizes risks to human health, beneficial and nontarget organisms, and the environment (UCS-IPM, 1997).

2.1.28. "IPM is a decision support system for the selection and use of pest control tactics, singly or harmoniously coordinated into a management strategy, based on cost/benefit analyses that take into account the interests of

and impacts on producers, society, and the environment" (Kogan, 1998).

2.2. IPM (History, Principles and Processes):

2.2.1. History :

Shortly after 1812, when synthetic insecticides became widely available, entomologists in California developed the concept of "supervised insect control. Around the same time, some entomologists in the cotton belt region of the United States were advocating a similar approach. Under this scheme, insect control was "supervised" by qualified entomologists, and insecticide applications were based on conclusions reached from periodic monitoring of pest and natural-enemy populations. This was viewed as an alternative to calendar-based insecticide programs. Supervised control was based on a sound knowledge of the ecology and analysis of projected trends in pest and natural-enemy populations.

Supervised control formed much of the conceptual basis for the "integrated control" that University of California entomologists articulated in the 1950s. Integrated control sought to identify the best mix of chemical and biological controls for a given insect pest. Chemical insecticides were to be used in manner least disruptive to biological control. The term "integrated" was thus synonymous with "compatible." Chemical controls were to be applied only after regular monitoring indicated that a pest population had reached a level (The economic threshold) that required treatment to prevent the population from reaching a level (The economic injury level) at which economic losses would exceed the cost of the artificial control measures.

IPM extended the concept of integrated control to all classes of pests and was expanded to include tactics other than just chemical and biological

controls. Artificial controls such as pesticides were to be applied as in integrated control, but these now had to be compatible with control tactics for all classes of pests. Other tactics, such as host-plant resistance and cultural manipulations, became part of the IPM arsenal. IPM added the multidisciplinary element, involving entomologists, plant pathologists, nematologists, and weed scientists.

In the United States, IPM was formulated into national policy in February 1972 when President Richard Nixon directed federal agencies to take steps to advance the concept and application of IPM in all relevant sectors. In 1979, President Jimmy Carter established an interagency IPM Coordinating Committee to ensure development and implementation of IPM practices.

2.2.2. Principles :

An American IPM system is designed around six basic components:

2.2.2.1. Acceptable pest levels:

The emphasis is on control, not eradication. IPM holds that wiping out an entire pest population is often impossible, and the attempt can be expensive and environmentally unsafe. IPM programs first work to establish acceptable pest levels, called action thresholds, and apply controls if those thresholds are crossed. These thresholds are pest and site specific, meaning that it may be acceptable at one site to have a weed such as white clover, but at another site it may not be acceptable. By allowing a pest population to survive at a reasonable threshold, selection pressure is reduced. This stops the pest gaining resistance to chemicals produced by the plant or applied to the crops. If many of the pests are killed then any that have resistance to the chemical will form the genetic basis of the future, more resistant, population. By not killing all the pests there are some un-resistant pests left

that will dilute any resistant genes that appear.

2.2.2.2. Preventive cultural practices:

Selecting varieties best for local growing conditions, and maintaining healthy crops, is the first line of defense, together with plant quarantine and 'cultural techniques' such as crop sanitation (e.g. Removal of diseased plants to prevent spread of infection).

2.2.2.3. Monitoring:

Regular observation is the cornerstone of IPM. Observation is broken into two steps, first; inspection and second; identification. Visual inspection, insect and spore traps, and other measurement methods and monitoring tools are used to monitor pest levels. Accurate pest identification is critical to a successful IPM program. Record-keeping is essential, as is a thorough knowledge of the behavior and reproductive cycles of target pests. Since insects are cold-blooded, their physical development is dependent on the temperature of their environment. Many insects have had their development cycles modeled in terms of degree days. Monitor the degree days of an environment to determine when is the optimal time for a specific insect's outbreak.

2.2.2.4. Mechanical controls:

Should a pest reach an unacceptable level, mechanical methods are the first options to consider. They include simple hand-picking, erecting insect barriers, using traps, vacuuming, and tillage to disrupt breeding.

2.2.2.5. Biological controls:

Natural biological processes and materials can provide control, with minimal environmental impact, and often at low cost. The main focus here is on promoting beneficial insects that eat target pests. Biological insecticides, derived from naturally occurring microorganisms (e.g.: *Bt*, entomopathogenic fungi and

entomopathogenic nematodes), also fit in this category.

2.2.2.6. Responsible pesticide use:

Synthetic pesticides are generally only used as required and often only at specific times in a pest's life cycle. Many of the newer pesticide groups are derived from plants or naturally occurring substances (e.g.: Nicotine, pyrethrum and insect juvenile hormone analogues), but the toxophore or active component may be altered to provide increased biological activity or stability. Further 'Biology-based' or 'ecological' techniques are under evaluation. An IPM regime can be quite simple or sophisticated. Historically, the focus of IPM programs was on agricultural insect pests. Although originally developed for agricultural pest management, IPM programs are now developed to encompass diseases, weeds, and other pests that interfere with the management objectives of sites such as residential and commercial structures, lawn and turf areas, and home and community gardens.

2.2.3. Processes :

IPM is applicable to all types of agriculture and sites such as residential and commercial structures, lawn and turf areas, and home and community gardens. Reliance on knowledge, experience, observation, and integration of multiple techniques makes IPM a perfect fit for organic farming (Sans artificial pesticide application). For large-scale, chemical-based farms (conventional), IPM can reduce human and environmental exposure to hazardous chemicals, and potentially lower overall costs of pesticide application material and labor.

2.2.3.1. Proper identification of pest -

What is it? Cases of mistaken identity may result in ineffective actions. If plant damage is due to over-watering, it could be mistaken for fungal infection, since many fungal and viral infections arise under moist conditions. This could

lead to spray costs, but the plant would be no better off.

2.2.3.2. Learn pest and host life cycle and biology. At the time you see a pest, it may be too late to do much about it except maybe spray with a pesticide. Often, there is another stage of the life cycle that is susceptible to preventative actions. For example, weeds reproducing from last year's seed can be prevented with mulches and pre-emergent herbicide. Also, learning what a pest needs to survive allows you to remove these.

2.2.3.3. Monitor or sample environment for pest population - How many are here? Preventative actions must be taken at the correct time if they are to be effective. For this reason, once the pest is correctly identified, monitoring must begin before it becomes a problem. For example, in school cafeterias where roaches may be expected to appear, sticky traps are set out before school starts. Traps are checked at regular intervals so populations can be monitored and controlled before they get out of hand. Some factors to consider and monitor include: Is the pest present/absent? What is the distribution - all over or only in certain spots? Is the pest population increasing, decreasing or remaining constant? This is done through crop scouting. Monitoring should also include the status of the water source being used for irrigation. Water is a breeding house for water borne diseases, and invertebrates, which could potentially contaminate or spread pests, directly onto crops.

2.2.3.4. Establish action threshold (Economic, health or aesthetic) - How many are too many? In some cases, there is a standardized number of pests that can be tolerated. Soybeans are quite tolerant of defoliation, so if there are a few caterpillars in the field and their population is not increasing dramatically, there is not necessarily any action necessary. Conversely, there

is a point at which action must be taken to control cost. For the farmer, that point is the one at which the cost of damage by the pest is more than the cost of control. This is an economic threshold. Tolerance of pests varies also by whether or not they are a health hazard (Low tolerance) or merely a cosmetic damage (High tolerance in a non-commercial situation). Different sites may also have varying requirements based on specific areas. White clover may be perfectly acceptable on the sides of a tee box on a golf course, but unacceptable in the fairway where it could cause confusion in the field of play.

2.2.3.5. Use resources to keep up to date on IPM developments. Researchers are always discovering new techniques, and ways to improve old techniques. Keeping up to date gives you the best options available to when using IPM.

2.2.3.6. Choose an appropriate combination of management tactics. For any pest situation, there will be several options to consider. Options include mechanical or physical control, cultural controls, biological controls and chemical controls. Mechanical or physical controls include picking pests off plants or using netting or other material to exclude pests such as birds from grapes or rodents from structures. Cultural controls include keeping an area free of conducive conditions by removing or storing waste properly, removing diseased areas of plants properly, late water floods, sanding, and the use of disease-resistant varieties. Biological controls are numerous. They include: conservation of natural predators or augmentation of natural predators, Sterile Insect Technique (SIT).

Augmentative control includes the introduction of naturally occurring predators at either an inundative or inoculative level. An inundative release would be one that seeks to inundate a

site with a pest's predator to impact the pest population. An inoculative release would be a smaller number of pest predators to supplement the natural population and provide ongoing control.^[13] The SIT is an Area-Wide IPM that introduces sterile male pests into the pest population to act as birth control. The biological controls mentioned above should only be used in extreme cases, because in the introduction of new species, or supplementation of naturally occurring species can have detrimental effect to the ecosystem. Biological controls can be used to stop invasive species or pests, or they can be they route by which new pests are introduced. Chemical controls would include horticultural oils or the application of pesticides, such as: insecticides and herbicides. A Green Pest Management IPM program would use pesticides derived from plants, such as botanicals, or other naturally occurring materials. When using any type of chemical control make sure that your pesticide applicator certification is up to day, and that your equipment is well maintained to ensure proper application.

2.2.3.7. Evaluate results - How did it work? Evaluation is often one of the most important steps. This is the process to review an IPM program and the results it generated. Asking the following questions is useful: Did actions have the desired effect? Was the pest prevented or managed to farmer satisfaction? Was the method itself satisfactory? Were there any unintended side effects? What can be done in the future for this pest situation? Understanding the effectiveness of the IPM program allows the site manager to make modifications to the IPM plan prior to pests reaching the action threshold and requiring action again.

2.3. IPM applications in Egypt :

2.3.1. In Egypt, insect pests attack reduced yield and quality of cotton, and

oil content in the seeds. The cotton leaf worm (*Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisduval)), the cotton pink bollworm (*Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) and spiny bollworm (*Earias insulana* (Boisduval)) (Lepidoptera, Noctuidae) cause the greatest damage in nearly one million feddans cultivated annually. This study describes an improvement in insect control practices directed against feeding insects (i.e., *S.littoralis*, *P. gossypiella* and *E. insulana*) by integration of insect monitoring, biological control, cultural, behavioral and genetic approaches that can serve as a base for the formulation of biologically- based new approach of integrated management of cotton key pests. Field studies were conducted during 2004 and 2005 cotton seasons at Minia Governorate, middle Egypt, with an experimental area of about 150 feddans of cotton (Giza 80). Five control measures were evaluated: (a) Prediction models based on the Pheromone trap catches; (b) Bio insecticides such Agreen (contains *Bacillus thuringiensis agypti*) and Spinosad; (c) Insect Growth Regulators (Consult: Anti molting compound produced by Dow Agrosience; Cascade: Anti molting compound produced by American Cyanamid; Mimic Molting accelerating compound produced by Rhorm and Haas; (d) Plant growth regulators and Defoliant (Pex: Cotton leaf defoliant and Cytokin: Growth promoting and fruiting hormone compound produced by Rhorm and Haas); (e) Augmentation of *Trichogramma* sp. Various combinations of the tested components were formulated and applied in commercial cotton fields in two successive seasons. Percent of infestations, cotton yield and population density of both natural enemies and sucking pests were used as criteria for evaluation of the various measures. Results showed that: Agreen,

trichograma, cascade, consult, mimic, spinosad and conventional insecticides gave reduction in infestation of the three tested pests by 34-75%, 22.1%, 37.7- 75.3%, 33.9- 71.4%, 38.8-74.5%, 67-77.1% and 63.4%, respectively (Amin and Gergis , 2006).

2.3.2. Cotton is the most important crop in Egypt as well as in other countries in the world. Pink bollworm; *P. gossypiella* and spiny bollworm; *E. insulana* are considered the main pests infesting cotton plants. These pests attack the fruit parts of the cotton plants such as buds, flowers and green bolls. This investigation is intended to control bollworms by using sex attractant pheromones with the following objectives in mind: protection of the ecosystem from insecticidal pollution, reducing the insecticides dosages, delaying the emergence of resistance in the pest to the insecticide and to keep the natural enemies which represent the most important factor in the integrated pest management to maintain their role in controlling many pests. The methods of pheromone application used included: a) Pheromone baited traps for the timing of the application (Besides the green boll inspection). This procedure was effective in reducing the infestation rates caused by bollworms from 7% to be less than 2%; b) Mass trapping was effective in reducing the infestation levels with bollworms due to the disturbance in the sex ratio. This method could be utilized at low infestation rates rather than at high infestation levels; c) Attractant and kill technique was implemented to attract the male moths by the pheromone in order to be killed by the insecticide substance in the mixture of pheromone and insecticide. This method reduced significantly the rates of infestation as well as insecticides used in comparison to using insecticides alone for bollworms control (Khider , 2007).

2.3.3. Pink bollworm, *Pictinophora gossypiella* (Sound.) is the most important pest infesting cotton plants and causing considerable loss of cotton yield in Egypt. The extensive use of insecticides for the pest control had created several problems, such as polluting the environment, development of resistance and disturbance of normal balance between the pests and their natural enemies. The objective of this study was to evaluate some elements of integrated pest management for pink bollworm control. Insects control by the mating disruption technique is achieved by the wide spread application of synthetic pheromone formulation over the crop. The insects are then unable to locate their mates when using their own pheromone and mating activity is therefore reduced. The aim of this work was to protect green bolls from the pest damage. Results revealed that when the application of pheromone is integrated with insecticidal treatments had a highly significant reduction on the green bolls infestation with pink bollworm as compared with using insecticides alone, where the reduction in infestation was around 37%. It was noticed that the predators number in the pheromone treated area was two fold of that in the insecticides treated area. The enzymes activity in the larvae collected from the insecticides treated area was much higher than that in the pheromone treated area because of selection for resistance in the pest due to the extensive use of insecticides. Infestation rates caused by the pest and the insecticides used were higher in the late planting as compared with early planting (Khider , 2007).

3. Bombykol Discovery and the beginning of the pheromone Era (1959):

Bombykol is a pheromone released (Figure 2) by the female silkworm moth to attract mates.

Discovered by Adolf Butenandt in 1959, it was the first pheromone to be characterized chemically. Minute quantities of this pheromone can be used per acre of land to confuse male insects about the location of their female partners, it can thus serve as a lure in traps to effectively remove insects without spraying crops with large amounts of chemicals. Butenandt named the substance after the moth's Latin name *Bombyx mori*.

Figure (2): Bombykol chemistry

3.1. Pheromones :

A pheromone (from Greek phero "to bear" + hormone from Greek

- "impetus") is a secreted or excreted chemical factor that triggers a social response in members of the same species. Pheromones are chemicals capable of acting outside the body of the secreting individual to impact the behavior of the receiving individual. There are alarm pheromones, food trail pheromones, sex pheromones, and many others that affect behavior or physiology. Their use among insects has been particularly well documented. In addition, some vertebrates and plants communicate by using pheromones. The term "Pheromone" was introduced by Peter Karlson and Martin Lüscher in 1959, based on the Greek word pherein (To transport) and hormone (To stimulate). They are also sometimes classified as ecto-hormones. German Biochemist Adolf Butenandt characterized the first such chemical, Bombykol (A chemically well-characterized pheromone released by the female silkworm to attract mates) (Table 1).

Table (1): Pheromone time line .

Pheromone Time line (1870 - 1990)	
1870	In the 1870s, New York entomologist Joseph A. Lintner suggests the chemical scents emitted by insects could be used to control insect pests.
1870	In the 1870s, French naturalist Jean-Henri Fabre notices a female peacock moth is able to attract 150 male peacock moths from miles away.
1957	German biologist Dietrich Schneider develops the electroantennogram (EAG), a method for using the antenna of a moth to detect pheromones electrically.
1959	German chemist Adolf Butenandt isolates and characterizes the first insect pheromone, that of the domestic silkworm moth.
1959	German biochemist Peter Karlson and Swiss entomologist Martin Lüscher coin the term "pheromone" to describe a compound an animal gives off that triggers a specific behavioral or developmental reaction in a member of the same species.
1960	U.S. Department of Agriculture chemist Morton Beroza reports his idea of using sex pheromones to disrupt insect mating.
1960	In the 1960s, pheromone researchers begin to use gas chromatography, mass spectrometry, and nuclear magnetic resonance to identify insect pheromones.
1961	Colin G. Butler identifies the pheromone of the honey bee, the first pheromone that regulates the development of an insect.
1966	Chemist Robert Silverstein and entomologist David Wood demonstrate that all three components of the bark beetle's pheromone blend are required to attract the beetles—a phenomenon known as synergism.
1967	Entomologist Harry Shorey shows that pheromones can be used to disrupt the mating of cabbage looper moths in the field.
1970	In the 1970s, British biologist John Kennedy develops the wind tunnel assay.
1970	In the 1970s, farmers begin to use pheromones for monitoring insect pests in order to reduce insecticide use.
1971	Wendell Roelofs uses EAG as an analytical tool to identify the codling moth pheromone.
1978	First pheromone is registered in the United States for commercial use in mating disruption—against the pink bollworm on cotton.
1980	Pheromones are used in more than a million traps to capture more than four billion beetles, curbing an epidemic of bark beetles in the forests of Norway and Sweden.
1990	In the 1990s, pheromones used for mating disruption effectively help curb insect damage in stone-pitted fruit orchards, and tomato, rice, cotton, and grape fields.

3.2. Pheromones applications:

The concept of IPM is based on the recognition that no single approach to pest control offers a universal solution, and that the best crop protection can be provided by a fusion of various tactics and practices based on sound ecological principles. Pheromones are a commonly used component of many insect IPM programs.

The existence of pheromones has been known for centuries, apparently originating in observations of mass bee stinging in response to a chemical released by the sting of a single bee. The first isolation and identification of an insect pheromone (Silkworm moth) occurred in 1959 by German scientists. Since then, hundreds, perhaps thousands of insect pheromones have been identified by increasingly sophisticated equipment. Today we have a much clearer view of the limitations and possibilities associated with insect pheromones in IPM programs. The two primary uses of insect pheromones are for detection and monitoring of populations and for mating disruption. These uses take advantage of sex pheromones on which a vast majority of insect pests rely to mediate reproduction.

3.2.1. Uses of pheromones in Integrated Pest Management (IPM) :

3.2.1.1. Detection and Monitoring.

The principle use of insect sex pheromones is to attract insects to traps for detection and determination of temporal distribution. In most instances, it is the males who are responders to female-produced sex pheromones. Trap baits, therefore, are designed to closely reproduce the ratio of chemical components and emission rate of calling females. Ideally, a trap bait should uniformly dissipate its pheromone content over time and not permanently retain or degrade the pheromone in the process. Trap baits of

many designs have been tested over the years, but the hollow polyvinyl plastic fiber (Emit from open ends), closed hollow fiber and bag (Emit through walls) and laminated plastic flake (Emit through walls and exposed edges) are commonly used today. Trap design is also critical to effective use of traps for monitoring insect populations. Traps vary in design and size dependent on the behavior of the target insects. Consistent trapping protocols are essential for population evaluations, spray thresholds, and year to year comparisons. The information from trap catches can be very useful for decision making on insecticide applications or other control measures. For example, trap catches may indicate a loss of effect of pheromone on mating disruption and the need to reapply a pheromone treatment. Careful monitoring and experience in interpreting collected data are important for success. Traps may also be placed with the objective of destroying males for population control.

Male annihilation is trapping carried to a seemingly logical conclusion. Place enough traps, catch enough males, and leave the females of the species without mates. This approach has been used against pink bollworms in an isolated area of Arizona with low numbers of overwintering moths. A rate of 5 traps per acre was used and the traps were composed of Styrofoam cups containing oil to provide larger capacity for dead moths. These traps were placed on row centers to avoid the cultivator and never serviced again. The grower community paid for this program for a few years, but results were difficult to prove because a control area was not available. Calculations by Dr. Edward Knipling (USDA retired) indicated that almost all (95%+) male pink bollworms would have to be destroyed before they could mate in order to exert significant

population control. Any untrapped males simply mate more frequently. Mating disruption does not depend on traps for control, although traps are frequently used to monitor the extent of mating disruption in the population. Failure to trap males is taken as an indication that males are unable to find females which may or may not be true. Thus, trap data must always be related to actual levels of crop infestation.

3.2.1.2. Mating Disruption. With the commercial availability of insect sex pheromones for several agricultural pests in the 1970's, scientists and entrepreneurs turned their attention to mating disruption as a "Biorational" approach to insect control. In theory, mating disruption may be accomplished in two principle ways: false trail following or confusion (Figure 3) . False trail following results from placing many more point sources of pheromone (Hollow fibers, flakes or other point sources) per acre than the anticipated numbers of females in the crop. The odds of males finding females at the end of the pheromone trail must be greatly reduced. Emission of pheromone is relatively low from each source such that a downwind trail is created and not lost in a background of released pheromone. Males following these trails are thought to spend their mating energies in pursuit of artificial pheromone sources. Pink bollworm males were early observed trying to mate with hollow fiber pheromone sources in treated fields. Thereafter, commercial pink bollworm pheromone products were applied in stickem containing small amounts of a contact insecticide. The resulting attract-and-kill formulations (Another form of male annihilation) were viewed as a subversion of the pheromone by purists, but in practice the damage was limited to the target species. However, the effectiveness of the added insecticide is largely unknown under field conditions.

Growers endorsed the idea that a dead male is better than a confused one. A further combination of pheromones and insecticides is occasionally encountered. Dual applications of pheromone and full strength insecticides (Either separately or in tank mixes) are applied with the idea of increasing insect flight activity and thus increasing the chance of insecticide exposure. Full strength applications of pheromone are generally used for this method. The greater the amount of pheromone applied and the greater the release rate, the more likely males are to be confused in the fog of ambient pheromone.

Male confusion is thought to be the result of ambient pheromone concentrations sufficient to hide the trails of calling females (Large doses from diffuse sources such as microcapsules or larger doses of pheromone in point source dispensers such as tie-on polyethylene ropes). Added to the effect, or indeed the effect, is the adaptation of antennal receptor sites and/or habituation of the insect's central nervous system. Specific receptor sites on the antennae respond to only the pheromone molecules (Individual component molecules appear to have individual receptor sites on antennae). When a receptor site is continually activated by high ambient concentrations of pheromones, the resulting electrical signal diminishes (Measured by an electroantennogram). The receptor site becomes unresponsive and the insect becomes navigationally blind. When the insect's central nervous system is inundated with signals from the receptor sites it becomes habituated: no longer able to provide the directed behavior. All of the above are, to some degree, based on known neurophysiology, but exactly what proportion of each occurs in a given situation can only be guessed. The net result of confusion is that the male is

unable to orient to any pheromone source and follow the upwind trail to a mate. For a current summary of theory and application of pheromones for control of lepidopterous pests. Present commercial formulations of pheromones for both trap baits and mating disruption mimic the natural chemical blends of females as clearly as possible. Most insect sex pheromones are multicomponent with precise ratios of components which may be expensive

to manufacture. Thus, insect sex pheromones and products containing pheromones, are commercially available primarily for insects of economic importance. Fortunately, there is hardly an insect species of agricultural importance, among the Lepidoptera at least, for which there are not some pheromone products available.

Figure (3) : Pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* and twist-on spiral mating disrupting pheromone dispenser.

3.3. History of gossypure applications :

1.3.1. In USA :

Conventional insecticides have not provided a long-term solution to the pink bollworm problem (Henneberry, 1986). Considerable amounts of basic biological and ecological information have been accumulated and applied in developing PBW control programs. No single control method is completely satisfactory. The possibility of combining a number of methods into a single control system appears to be the most promising approach (Henneberry *et al.*, 1980).

Efforts to control the pink bollworm *P. gossypiella*, by mating disruption began with the sex attractant "hexalure" in the early 1970's (Figure 4) . The discovery of the pink bollworm sex pheromone in 1973 led to the first successful commercial formulation in 1978 (See review by Baker *et al.*

(1991). The pheromone, a two component mixture of Z, Z- and Z, E-7,11- hexadecadienyl acetate (Called gossypure in commercial products) (Figure 5) , has appeared in a variety of aerially applied formulations including hollow fibers, flakes, microcapsules, and in hand-applied twist-tie ropes and twist-on spirals. Original applications utilized 0.75 to 1.5 g AI/acre in several thousand point sources and were applied several times during early to mid-season while recent hand-applied formulations utilized ca. 30 g AI/acre and were applied once. These are known as false-trail following and confusion methods, respectively. All formulations are to be applied at first flower bud ("Pin-square" or about 8 true leaf stage cotton) which is the earliest fruiting form in which the pink bollworm can reproduce. Applications at first flower bud are made against the

lowest seasonal (Over-wintered) populations, an aid to efficacy.

Figure (4) : Hexalure chemistry .

IUPAC:	1:1 mixture of (7Z,11E)- and (7Z,11Z)-hexadeca-7,11-dien-1-yl acetate
	Or
	1:1 mixture of (Z,E)- and (Z,Z)-hexadeca-7,11-dien-1-yl acetate
CAS:	(7Z)-7,11-hexadecadienyl acetate
Reg. No.:	50933-33-0
Formula:	C ₁₈ H ₃₂ O ₂

Figure (5) : Gossyplure chemistry.

Commercial use of pheromone in IPM programs for control of the pink bollworm is widely used in Arizona. The current and perhaps most

successful demonstration of the value of this approach is the Parker, AZ, program on ca. 25,000 acres of cotton along the Colorado river in the

northwest corner of the state. Deemed to be a somewhat isolated area of the northern extreme of pink bollworm overwintering, the area growers have supported a systematic approach fashioned after the successful boll weevil eradication program. The area-wide program has used selected commercial formulations (including dual applications with insecticide) to reduce pink bollworm populations each year during the past 5 seasons. The results have been so satisfactory that very little control for pink bollworm is presently needed in the program areas. Systematic IPM programs using pheromone to control pink bollworm are also in use in India and Pakistan but attain the greatest acreage in Egypt. Pheromone treatments totaling a hundred thousand acres, or more were used in Egypt during the 1995 season. Published reports indicate the program of several years is expanding and has produced control of pink bollworm comparable to conventional insecticides. The use of pheromone in Egypt is under state control and is applied to selected large areas of cotton. An overall view of cotton pest management is provided by Luttrell *et al.* (1994).

3.3.1.1. Mating disruption with PBW sex pheromone (Gossyplure):

Behavioral insect control by mating disruption with sex pheromone was suggested by Knipling and McGuire (1966). Hummel *et al.* (1973) identified a mixture of the Z,Z- and Z,E-isomers of 7,11-hexadecadienyl acetate as the pink bollworm sex pheromone and proposed the name "Gossyplure." Shorey *et al.* (1976) initiated studies to evaluate the mating disruption method, in which the atmosphere of the cotton field was permeated with gossyplure, for PBW control. Albany International Co., Needham, Massachusetts, developed NoMate-PBW®, a slow release

formulation of gossyplure and hexane contained in 1.5 cm lengths of about 200 I.D. hollow fibers, sealed near one end (Brooks and Kitterman, 1977). The results of extensive testing in Arizona and southern California indicated substantial reduction in boll infestations and in the need for chemical insecticides for PBW in the NoMate-PBW treated fields (Doane and Brooks, 1980).

Area wide applications with PBW pheromone in the Imperial Valley of California resulted in curtailing insecticide use and significant yield increases (Staten *et al.*, 1983). Additional evaluations of the effectiveness of control of PBW using pheromones in commercial cotton conditions were made in 1981 and in 1982. The gossyplure combination used in these studies included the addition of 0.004 kg of permethrin or fenvalerate (AI) per hectare to the polybutene sticker, Bio-Tac, used to adhere fibers to leaves (NoMate-PBW Attact'n Kill). The addition of this small amount of insecticide was shown to enhance the effectiveness of the pheromone by killing male moths that encountered the fiber (Staten and Conlee, U.S. Patent No. 4671010). The small amount of insecticide, in sources that were attractive only to the pink bollworm and widely scattered (one per 2 m²) through the top of the cotton canopy, did not appear to be a threat to insect predators.

Hercon Group of Herculite Products, Inc., New York, developed Disrupt®, a slow release system for gossyplure, consisting of three-layer plastic dispensers (0.05 cm²) with gossyplure concentrated in the center reservoir and the outer layers regulating the release of the pheromone. The results of field tests of this product in Arizona indicated substantial reduction in boll infestations (Henneberry *et al.*, 1981). Shin-Etsu Chemical Co., Ltd, Tokyo, Japan, developed the PB-

Rope®, a high-rate, slow release system consisting of a wire-based, sealed polyethylene tube (8") filled with gossypure. Extensive field trials conducted in the Imperial Valley of California and the Mexicali Valley of Mexico indicated a substantial reduction in boll infestations and insecticide applications in the PB-Rope treated fields, compared with that in conventional insecticide-treated fields (Staten *et al.*, 1987). Community-wide application of the PB-Rope in the Coachella Valley of California, at the pinhead square growth stage, provided a highly effective level of control of PBW for approximately sixty days, and insecticide usage was drastically reduced or even eliminated in some fields (Staten *et al.*, 1988). Area wide, timely application of commercial formulations of gossypure in the Parker Valley of Arizona, demonstrated the feasibility of suppressing PBW infestations to a near zero level in four years, and conceptualized the prospect of eradication (El-Lissy *et al.*, 1993; Staten *et al.*, 1995; Antilla *et al.*, 1996 and Grefenstette *et al.*, 2009).

3.3.1.2. Combining gossypure and insecticides :

Gossypure, the pink bollworm sex pheromone, has been used commercially since 1977 to suppress pest populations by disrupting mating in cotton crops. Two slow-release systems for gossypure are commercially available: No- Mate PBW fibers and Disrupt flakes, suspended in the sticker Bio-Tac or Phero-Tac, respectively, and applied aerially with special equipment. The addition of small amounts of pyrethroid insecticide to the sticker has been suggested to kill male pink bollworm moths attracted to and contacting the pheromone-sticker combination (Point source). To determine the effectiveness of such treatments, we conducted tests in cooperation with growers and pest

control advisors in southeastern California's Palo Verde Valley. Catches of male pink bollworm moths (*P. gossypiella*) in gossypure baited traps, rosetted blooms and boll infestations, and numbers of beneficial predators were compared in fields treated with: (a) Disrupt with and without the pyrethroid insecticide permethrin in Phero-Tac; (b) NoMate PBW with and without permethrin in Bio-Tac; and (c) Insecticides only (Trichlorfon). Some decisions to treat or not to treat were made jointly by the chemical representatives, grower, and pest control advisors. Others were made routinely by grower's pest control advisor. This is a report of the 1982 studies (Beasley and Henneberry, 1984).

3.3.2. In Egypt:

In 1999, in the Governorate of Fayum, Egypt, an organically managed area of 66 ha (33 ha of cotton) was subjected to pheromone mating disruption (MD) in order to control *P. gossypiella* (PBW). Tripherone-PecGos dispensers (Trifolio-M Comp., Lahnu, Germany), evaporating 0.7 mg pheromone per day, were applied, at a density of 300 dispensers per hectare, in mid-June when the first bolls were forming. In a neighboring area of conventional agriculture, no PBW-MD was used. Instead, two insecticides were sprayed in the cotton fields: Profenophos in early July, and Esfenvalerate in early August. Two cotton fields (0.5–1 ha each) were studied in each area. Boll infestation by PBW was low in the area with mating disruption, and significantly higher in the conventionally managed cotton, prior to insecticide use (June) and in August 1999. *Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) *Aphis gossypii* (Glover) (Hemiptera: Aphididae) and *Empoasca lybica* (de Bergevin) (Hemiptera:Cicadellidae) infested

conventional cotton in significantly higher numbers than organic cotton. Spiders proved to be more common in organically grown cotton (With PBW-MD) than in conventionally managed cotton (With mineral fertilizers and insecticides). The reasons of these differences are discussed. In 1998, the cotton yield had shown no differences between organically and conventionally managed farms (both used insufficient PBW-MD). However, in 1999, the yield from the organically grown cotton (With MD) was significantly (52%) more than that from conventionally managed cotton (With insecticides). In this study, PBW-MD proved to be superior to insecticides in several aspects (Boguslawski and Basedow, 2001).

3.3.2.1. Different Pheromone tactics applied in Egypt:

Pheromones strategy differs completely in its tactics than the insecticide strategy (Because of their different aims and targets). In Egypt, pheromone strategy was used widely with many different tactics as an important part of the IPM program conducted then. Some of these tactics are:-

3.3.2.1.1. Pheromone traps for monitoring and detection technique :

3.3.2.1.1.1. The use of pheromone traps, of different types and shapes, for monitoring insect pest field population density and dynamics over place (Village, district, Governorate, region, countrywide), (Campion *et al.*, 1978; Campion *et al.*, 1980; Doane and Brooks, 1980; El-Sayed *et al.*, 1984; El-Deeb *et al.*, 1987; Albeltagy *et al.*, 1991a; Hosny *et al.*, 1991; Khider *et al.*, 1991 and Albeltagy, 2012 a).

3.3.2.1.1.2. The use of pheromone traps, of different types and shapes, for monitoring insect pest field population density and dynamics over time (day, week, month, season, year), (Albeltagy *et al.*, 1993a).

3.3.2.1.1.3. The use of pheromone traps, especially delta traps, as a control indicator to differentiate between

different kinds of control actions as a mean of IPM (Albeltagy *et al.*,1996a).

3.3.2.1.1.4. The use of pheromone traps, especially delta traps, as a control trigger for insect pest control decision for different kinds of control actions as a mean of IPM, (Albeltagy, 1999).

3.3.2.1.1.5. The use of pheromone traps, especially delta traps , to evaluate the pheromone release rates and its corresponding effect on crop infestations (Albeltagy *et al.*, 1993 c).

3.3.2.1.1.6. The use of pheromone traps, especially delta traps, to indicate the relationship between trap catches and crop infestation (Albeltagy *et al.*, 1995 a).

3.3.2.1.1.7. The use of pheromone traps, especially delta traps, to build up computer simulation models for different insect pest control strategies and tactics (Albeltagy *et al.*, 1995b).

3.3.2.1.2. Pheromone traps for mass trapping technique :

3.3.2.1.2.1.The use of many different pheromone trap types (delta, funnel and / or water) as a mass trapping technique against many different insect pest field strains (Campion and Nesbitt, 1981; Crithley and El-Deeb, 1981; Albeltagy *et al.*, 1991b and Hamid and Albeltagy, 1995; Khider, 1997 and Albeltagy 2012a).

3.3.2.1.3. Pheromone disruption technique:

3.3.2.1.3.1. Pink bollworm (PBW) rope gossyplure (The sex pheromone of PBW) formulation was used against pink bollworm on large scale applications (thousands of acres) in cotton fields for many years (Albeltagy, 1993 and Albeltagy *et al.*, 1993 b).

3.3.2.1.3.2. The use of pheromone disruption technique as a part of IPM program against cotton insect complex pests (Albeltagy *et al.*, 1993d).

3.3.2.1.3.3. The use of pheromone disruption technique as a part of IPM program to enhance the role of

biological control agents in cotton fields.

3.3.2.1.3.4. The use of different pheromone confusion techniques, disruption – lure and kill, in different formulation types (Dispensers, rubbers and microencapsulated) (Brooks *et al.*, 1979; Kydonieus and Beroza, 1981; Hall *et al.*, 1982; Campion, 1983; Critchley *et al.*, 1983; Critchley *et al.*, 1985, Khider *et al.*, 1986; Gadallah *et al.*, 1990; Abdo *et al.*, 1991 ; Moawad *et al.*, 1991 ; Albeltagy and Haroun, 1996 and Albeltagy, 2012a).

3.3.2.1.4. Attracticide resistance monitoring technique(ARMT) :

3.3.2.1.4.1. The use of pheromone traps in the attracticide resistance monitoring technique as a simple, easy , effective, accurate, and quick tool for monitoring and detecting insecticide resistance in insect pest field populations (Tables 2 and 3) (Albeltagy *et al.*, 1996 b ; Albeltagy *et al.*, 2000 ; Khider *et al.*, 2002; Albeltagy *et al.*, 2010 and Albeltagy, 2012b)

Table (2): Pheromone treated area in Egypt.

#	Year	Cotton area	Pheromone area	%
		(Feddan)	(Feddan)	
1	1982	1,065,841.00	500.00	0.05
2	1983	998,277.00	1,250.00	0.13
3	1984	983,560.00	13,000.00	1.32
4	1985	1,081,009.00	37,000.00	3.42
5	1986	1,054,860.00	61,000.00	5.78
6	1987	969,793.00	6,000.00	0.62
7	1988	1,013,960.00	30,000.00	2.96
8	1989	1,005,533.00	40,000.00	3.98
9	1990	993,047.00	0.00	0.00
10	1991	851,283.00	7,500.00	0.88
11	1992	840,296.00	40,000.00	4.76
12	1993	884,310.00	100,000.00	11.31
13	1994	721,443.00	360,000.00	49.90
14	1995	710,207.00	500,000.00	70.40
15	1996	920,911.00	550,000.00	59.72
16	1997	859,255.00	590,000.00	68.66

Table (3) : Gossypure formulations used in disruption technique in Egypt.

Campany	Product	Formulation	Concentration	Application rte	a.i. (gm)
			a.i.(gm)/L. or Kgm	/ feddan	/ Feddan
ICI	Pectone	Microencapsulated	20	200 ml	4
Sandoz	Nomate	Hollow Fiber	76	15 gm	1.14
Bassif	Hircon	Micro flakes	28	60 gm	1.68
Feromone	Stirrup	Concentrated liquid	6.32 gm	240 ml	1.52
Somotomo	Pb-Rope	Long tube	1 = 144 mgm	150 tube	21.6
Ecogen	Nomate	Gelatin Ring	1 = 155 mgm	200 ring	31
Agrisence	Sellibete	Rubber ring	1 = 254 mgm	104 ring	26.4
Feromone	Lastfight	Poly- metric Paste	1 = 73 mgm	300 drop	22

4. Advantages of pheromone applications :

- 4.1. Decreases number of insecticide applications.
- 4.2. Rationalizes insecticides usages.
- 4.3. Keeps the susceptibility of insect pest field populations.
- 4.4. Keeps the efficiency of insecticides.
- 4.5. Increases pollinators.
- 4.6. Increases crop productions.
- 4.7. Decreases environmental pollutions.
- 4.8. Enhances biological control agents.
- 4.9. Increases honey- bee populations and honey productions.
- 4.10. Increases farmer benefits.

5. Recommendations :

We must expand in using pheromone technology tactics for insect pest management (IPM) in different agricultural crops (Especially cotton) and horticultures, and also against medical and livestock insect pests as mentioned previously to obtain these results :-

- 5.1. To overcome the above mentioned pesticide problems.
- 5.2. To gain the advantages of pheromone technology use.
- 5.3. For farmers to gain good profits of their cultivations, instead of their annual losses .

References

- Abdo, M.Z.; Awad, H.A.; Albeltagy, A.M.; Mourad, A.K. and Mesbah, H.A. (1991):** The efficiency of four new pheromone formulations in reducing the population density of the pink bollworm in El-Bohira Governorate. *Egypt. J. Appl. Sci.*, 6 (12): 37-47.
- Adams, R. G. (1996):** Introduction to Integrated Pest Management. pp. 1-7. In *Northeast Sweet Corn Production and Integrated Pest management manual*, [R.

A. Adams and J. C. Clark (eds.)], Cooperative Extension System, University of Connecticut, pp.120.

- Albeltagy, A.M (1999):** Plant and insect triggers for sequential use of gossypure and insecticides for pink bollworm control actions . *Egypt J. Agric. Res.*, 77(4) : 1633 - 1643 .

- Albeltagy, A.M. (1990) :** Integrated pest management (IPM) of bollworms as a means for pesticides rationalization and increasing cotton production. *Symposium of IPM and Pesticides Rationalization and Environmental protection*, 7-8 Nov. , Fac. Of Agric., Alex. Univ., Egypt., 56 - 59.

- Albeltagy, A.M. (2012a) :** Pheromone traps for the assessment of insecticides efficiency and monitoring insecticides resistance in insect field strains . *Proc. of Minia Int. Conf. for Aric. and Irrig. In the Nile Basin Countries*, 26th – 29th March 2012, El-Minia, Egypt, 213 - 222 .

- Albeltagy, A.M. (2012b):** Semiochemicals : The Future Of Pest Management . *Proc. Of Minia Int. Conf. for Aric. And Irrig. In the Nile Basin Countries*, 26th – 29th March 2012, El-Minia, Egypt, 257 - 270.

- Albeltagy, A.M. (1993):** Pheromone application for pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders), control reduces number of insecticide applications. *Abstract, Entomol. Soc. of Amer. (ESA), Annual Meeting*, 12-16 Dec., Indianapolis, IN., USA.

- Albeltagy, A.M. ; Radwan, H. S. ; El-Bermawy, Z. A. ; Nassar, M. E.; Yousef, A. G. and**

- Shekeban, M.M. (2000)** : Attracticide resistance monitoring technique for assaying insecticide resistance in pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) field populations. Egypt. J. Agric. Res., 79(3) : 949 - 962 .
- Albeltagy, A.M. and Haroun, N.S. (1996)**: A new technique for pink bollworm suppression: "Sirene" attract and kill technique. Alex. Sci. Exch., 17 (4): 343-350.
- Albeltagy, A.M.; El-Deeb, A.S. and Barania, H.A. (1996a)**: Bollworm infestation indicator for comparing the efficiency of different control tactics. Alex. J. Agric. Res., 41 (3): 85-92.
- Albeltagy, A.M.; El-Mourshedy, M.M. and Mourad, A.K. (1996b)**: Pheromone traps for monitoring insecticide tolerance in three different lepidopterous insects, as an effective tool for insecticide resistance management. Egypt. J. Agric. Res., 74 (1): 29-37.
- Albeltagy, A.M.; El-Mourshedy, M.M.; El-Deeb. A.S. and Mourad, A.K. (1993a)**: The role of light and sex-pheromone traps in monitoring the populations of certain lepidopterous cotton insects. Egypt. J. Appl. Sci., 8 (4): 287-302.
- Albeltagy, A.M.; El-Tabakh, S.S.; Mourad, M.A.; Shawir, M.S. and Moawad, G.M. (1993b)**: Effect of pheromone and conventional insecticides on cotton bollworms infestation, plant and yield properties. Egypt. J. Biol. Pest Control, 3 (1): 1-12.
- Albeltagy, A.M.; Hamid, A.M. and Moawad, G.M. (1995b)**: Different models of pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) trap catches and boll infestation under different conditions. Egypt. J. Agric. Res., 73 (4): 1019-1034.
- Albeltagy, A.M.; Hamid, A.M. and Salem, A.A. (1995a)**: Efficacy of nine different control techniques (pheromone and/or insecticides) on pink bollworm trap catches and boll infestation. Proc. of 1st Int. Conf. of Pest Control, Mansoura, Egypt, 3-5 Sept., 197-204.
- Albeltagy, A.M.; Salem, R.M.; El-Hamaky, M.A.; Abu-Aiana, R. and Omar, M.E. (1993d)**: Cotton aphid, Jassid and whitefly population dynamics under pheromone and insecticide applications against pink bollworm. J. Biol. Pest Control, 33 (1): 63-70.
- Albeltagy, A.M.; Shaker, N. ; Taman, F.A. and El-Khishen, S.A. (1991b)**: The efficiency of funnel and delta pheromone traps for bollworms. Proc. of the 4th Arab Congress of Plant Prot., Cairo, 1-5 Dec., Pesticides and Toxicology, 111: 485-489.
- Albeltagy, A.M.; Shaker, N.; Taman, F.A. and El-Khishen, S.A. (1991a)**: The influence of pheromone traps on the infestation percentages and population density of bollworms in Alexandria and Al-Behera Governorates. Proc. of the 4th Arab Congress of Plant Prot., Cairo, 1-5 Dec., Pesticides and Toxicology, 111: 485-489.
- Albeltagy, A.M.; Shawir, M.S.; Mourad, M.A. and Moawad, G.M. (1993c)**: Preliminary evaluation of pheromone release in relation to pink

- bollworm infestation in cotton fields. Egypt. J. Biol. Pest Control, 3 (1): 13-19.
- Albeltagy, A.M.I.; Shekeban, M. M.K. ; Abo El-Amayem, M.M.; Kassem, S. M. I. ; Mancee, A.H. and El-Arami, S.A. (2010):** Monitoring for pyrethroid resistance in pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) field strains . Pest Management Newsletter , 19(2) : 46-52 .
- Allen, W.A. and Rajotte, E.G. (1990):** The changing role of extension entomology in the IPM era. Annual Review of Entomology, 35:379-397.
- AMACSA (American Medical Association Council on Scientific Affairs) (1993):** Diet and cancer: where do matters stand?. Archives of Internal Medicine, 153: 50-56.
- Amin, A.A. and Gergis, M.F. (2006):** Integrated management strategies for control of cotton key pests in Middle Egypt. Agronomy Research 4(Special issue), 121–128.
- Anonymous (2006) :** Integrated Pest Management. Ninth Arab Congress of Plant Protection, 19-23 November 2006, Damascus, Syria, E-189 – E-197.
- Anonymous (2012) :** Wikipedia: IPM.
- Anonymous ,** Beyond Discovery, The National Academies - National academy of Sciences. <http://www.beyonddiscovery.org/content/view.txt.asp?a=2702#Timeline>
- Anonymous, DDT @ 3DChem.com - Banned Insecticide.** (www.3dchem.com/molecules.asp?ID=90) .
- Anonymous, Wikipedia, Bombykol .** <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bombykol>
- Anonymous, Wikipedia, Pheromones.** <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pheromone>
- Antilla, L.; Whitlow, M.; Staten, R. T.; El-Lissy, O. and Myers. F. (1996):** An integrated approach to areawide pink bollworm management in Arizona. Proc. Beltwide Cotton Production and Research Conf., National Cotton Council of America, pp. 1083-1085.
- ATTRA (Appropriate Technology Transfer for Rural Area) (1995):** Integrated pest management information package. National Center for Appropriate Technology. Fayetteville, Arkansas, pp. 21.
- Baker, T. C.; Staten, R. T. and Flint, H. M. (1991):** Use of pink bollworm pheromone in the southwestern United States. pp. 417-436. In Behavior Modifying Chemicals for Insect Management. Ridgeway, R. L.; Silverstein, R. M. and Inscoe, M. N. [eds.]. Marcel Dekker, New York, NY.
- Beasley, C.A. and Henneberry, T.J. (1984):** Combining gossypure and insecticides in pink bollworm control. California Agriculture, July-August : 22 - 23
- Boguslawski , C.V. and Basedow, T. (2001):** Studies in cotton fields in Egypt on the effects of pheromone mating disruption on *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) (Lep., Gelechiidae), on the occurrence of other arthropods, and on yields . Journal of Applied Entomology, 125(6): 327-331.
- Brooks, T. W. and Kitterman, R. L. (1977):** Gossypure H. F. - pink bollworm population suppression with male sex attractant pheromone released

- from hollow fibers, 1976 experiments. Proc. 1977 Beltwide Cotton Production-Mechanization Conf. National Cotton Council of America, pp. 79-82.
- Bruhn, C.; Peterson, S. and Sakovich, N. (1992):** Consumer response to information on integrated pest management. J. Food Safety, 12: 315-326.
- Campion, D. G.; Hunter- Jones, P.; McVeigh, L. J.; Hall, D.R.; Lester, R. and Nesbitt, B.F. (1980) :** Modification of the attractiveness of the primary pheromone components of the Egyptian cotton leafworm, *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisd.) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae), by secondary pheromone components and related chemicals. Bull. Ent. Res., 70: 417 - 434.
- Campion, D.G. (1983):** Pheromone for the control of insect pests in Mediterranean countries. Crop Protection, 2 :3-16 .
- Campion, D.G. and Nesbitt, F. (1981) :** Recent advances in the use of pheromone in developing countries with particular reference to mass - trapping the control of Egyptian cotton leafworm, *Spodoptera littoralis* and mating disruption for the control of pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* .In Les M'ediaterus chimiques Agissant Sur Le Comportement des, Institute National de la Recherche Agronomique, Paris, pp. 335 – 342.
- Campion, D.G.; Lester, R. and Nesbitt, B.F. (1978) :** Controlled release of pheromones. Pestic. Sci., 9: 434 - 440.
- Cate, J. R. and Hinkle, M. K. (1994):** Integrated Pest Management: the path of a paradigm. The National Audubon Society Special Report, pp. 43.
- Cooperative Extension System, University of Connecticut (1994):** Integrated pest management programs. Univ. Connecticut, pp. 22
- CPM (Crop Protection Manager) (1997):** In: Insect Management- Insecticides Do Have a Role in IPM. pp. 21-22.
- Critchley, B.R. and El – Deeb, Y.A. (1981) :** An improved pheromone trap for mass trapping of cotton moths in Egypt. Appropriate Technology for Egyptian Agriculture, 4: 6-10.
- Critchley, B.R.; Campion, D.G.; McVeigh, L.J.; McVeigh, E.M.; Cavangh, G.G.; Hosny, M.M.; El-Sayed, A.N.; Khider, A.A. and Naguib, M. (1985) :** Control of pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) (Lepidoptera : Gelechiidae) , in Egypt by mating disruption using hollow fiber, laminate - flakes and microencapsulated formulations of synthetic pheromone. Bull. Ent. Res., 75: 329- 345.
- Critchley, B.R.; Campion. D.G.; McVeigh, L.J.; Hunter-Jones, P.; Hall, D.R.; Cork, A.; Nesbitt, B.F.; Marss, D.J.; Justum, A.R.; Hosny, M.M. and El-Sayed, A. N. (1983) :** Control of pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae), in Egypt by mating disruption using an aerially applied microencapsulated pheromone

- formulation. Bull. Ent. Res.,73: 289 - 299.
- Dehne, H.W. and Schonbeck, F. (1994):** Crop Protection- past and present. pp. 45-71. In Crop Production and Crop Protection, Oerke, E-C. H-W. Dehne, F. Schonbeck and A. Weber (eds.), Elsevier, Amsterdam, Netherlands, pp. 808.
- Dent, D. R. (1995):** Integrated pest management. Chapman & Hall, London, pp. 356.
- Doane, C. C., and Brooks. T. W. (1980):** Research and development of pheromone for insect control with emphasis on the pink bollworm, pp. 285-303. In Mitchell, E. (edit.), management of insect pests with semiochemicals. Plenum Press, New York and London. p. 514
- El-Deeb, M.A.; Hegab, A.H. ; Mohamed, Z.A. and Khider, A.A. (1987) :** Population dynamics and testis development of male bollworm moths captured in sex pheromone traps sited in cotton fields at Sharrkia Governorate. Egypt Bull. Ent. Soc. Econ. Ser.,16: 181 - 190 .
- El-Lissy, O.; Staten, R.T. and Antilla, L. (1993):** Control of pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) in Parker Valley, Arizona, by mating disruption using commercial formulations of gossyplure. Proceedings of the International Cotton Pest Work Committee, California Department of Food and Agriculture, Sacramento, CA., pp.114-117
- EPA (Environmental Protection Agency) (1993):** EPA for Your Information. Prevention, Pesticides and Toxic Substances (H7506C). 2 pp.
- FCES (Florida Cooperative Extension Service) (1996):** (The Institute of Food and Agricultural Sciences, University of Florida). Fall 1996. p. 2. IPM Florida.
- FCES (Florida Cooperative Extension Service) (1996):** (The Institute of Food and Agricultural Sciences, University of Florida). Winter 1996. p. 2. IPM Florida.
- Feldman, J. (2012) :** Organic pesticide a better option. ajc (The Atlanta J. Constitution.) : 1-2 .
- Flint , H. M. and Doane, C. C. (2009) :** Understanding semiochemicals with emphasis on insect sex pheromones in integrated pest management programs, radcliffe's IPM TextBook, <http://ipmworld.umn.edu/chapters/flint.htm>.
- Flint, M. L.; Daar, S. and Molinar, R. (1991):** Establishing integrated pest management policies and programs: A guide for public agencies. Univ. Calif. IPM Publication, pp.9-12.
- Gadallah, A.I.; Khider, A.A.; Ali, M.A. M. and Morsey, M.A. (1990) :** New approach for the Control of pink bollworm, , *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). J. Pest Control and Environ. Sci., 2: 189 -199.
- Gianessi, L. (1993):** The Quixotic Quest for Chemical-free Farming. Issues in Science and Technology, 10: 29-36.
- Grefenstette, B. ; El-Lissy, O.; and Staten, R. T. (2009):** Pink bollworm Eradication Plan In The U.S. PBW Eradication Plan in the U.S. (2-25-09) : 1-9. http://www.aphis.usda.gov/plant_health/plant_pest_info/cotton

- _pests/downloads/pbw-erad-plan2-09.pdf
- Hall, D.R. ; Nesbitt, B.F.; Mars, G.J.; Green, A. st. J. ; Campion, D.G.; and Critchley, B.R. (1982) :** Development of microencapsulated pheromone formulations. In insect Pheromone Technology : (Eds .), Chemistry and Applications, B. A. Leonhardt and M. Berosa, (Eds.) , American Chemical Society, Symposium Series No., 190, Washington, DC, August 1981, pp. 131 - 143 .
- Henneberry, T. J. (1986):** Pink bollworm management in cotton in the southwestern United States. U.S. Dep. Agric. Agric. Res. Serv. ARS-51.
- Henneberry, T. J.; Bariola, L. A. and Kittock, D. L. (1980):** Integrating methods for control of the pink bollworm and other cotton insects in the southwestern United States. USDA, Tech. Bull. No. 1610. pp. 45.
- Henneberry, T. J.; Gillespie, J. M. and Bariola, L. A. (1981):** Gossypure in laminated plastic formulations for mating disruption and pink bollworm control. J. Econ. Entomol., 74:376-380.
- Hosny, M.M.; Khider, A.A. and Abdeen, S. A. O. (1991) :** sex pheromone and population dynamics of the spiny bollworm, *Earias insulana* (Boisd.). Zagazig J. Agric. Res., 18 (5) : 1599 - 1603 .
- Hummel, H. E.; Gaston, L. K.; Shorey, H. H.; Kaae, R. S.; Byrne, K. J. and Silverstein, R. M. (1973):** Clarification of the chemical status of the pink bollworm sex pheromone. Science, 181:873-875.
- Khider, A.A. (1997) :** Effect of mass trapping of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) on the green boll infestation rates caused by pink bollworm. (Unpublished data).
- Khider, A.A. (2007) :** Scientific Programs And Strategic Applications In Integrated Cotton Pest Management. (Arabic Text Book), pp. 366.
- Khider, A.A.; Abd El-Karim, H. E. ; Abo El-Ghar, E.G.; Matar, A.M. and Abd El- Halim, A. (2002) :** Development of discriminating monitoring techniques for moths insecticide resistance in *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) (Lepidoptera : Gelechiidae) in cotton . 2nd Int. Conf. Plant protect. Res. Inst., Cairo, Egypt, 21 - 24 Dec., pp. 472 - 476.
- Khider, A.A.; Abdeen, S.A.O. and Ahmed, N.M. (1986) :** Effect of pheromones as a new approach on increasing honey production. Zagazig J. Agric. Res., 64() : 169 - 182 .
- Khider, A.A.; Abdo, M.Z. ; Kostandy, S.N. and El-Feel, E. A. (1991) :** Seasonal population dynamics of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) as monitored by gossypure traps. Egypt J. Agric. Res., 69 (1) : 83 - 87 .
- Knipling ,E.F., and McGuire Jr, J.U. (1966):** Population models to test theoretical effects of sex attractants used for insect control. Agric. Info. Bull.,308:1-20
- Kogan, M. (1998):** Integrated Pest Management: Historical Perspectives and Contemporary Developments. Annu. Rev. Entomol., 43: 243 - 270.

- Kydonieus, A.F. and Beroza, M. (1981)** : The hercon dispenser formulation and recent test results. In Management of Insect Pest with Semiochemicals : Concept and Practice, Mitchell, E.R. (Ed.), Plenum Press, New York, pp. 435- 445 .
- Leslie, A. R. (1994):** Preface. In Integrated pest management for turf and ornamentals, Leslie, A. R. (ed.). Lewis Publishers, London, pp.660.
- Luttrell, R. G.; Fitt, G. P. ; Ramalho, F. S. and Sugonyaev, E. S. (1994):** Cotton pest management: Part 1. A Worldwide Perspective. Ann. Rev. Entomol., 39: 517-526.
- McCoy, M. (ed.) (1992):** Integrated pest management basic principles fit nursery production. Ornamentals Northwest Seminars & Farwest Show, 36 (8): 120-123.
- Moawad, G.M.; Khider, A.A. ; Zaki, M.; Critchley, B.R.; McVeigh, L.J. and Campion, D.G. (1991) :** Large - scale use of hollow fiber and microencapsulated pink bollworm pheromone formulations integrated with conventional insecticides for the control of the cotton pest complex in Egypt. Tropical Pest Management, 37 (1) : 10- 16.
- Nasr, El-Sayed, A.: Tucker, M.R. and Campion, D.G. (1984) :** Distribution of moths of the Egyptian cotton leafworm, , *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisd.) (Lepidoptera : Noctuidae) in the Nile Delta interpreted from catches in pheromone traps network in relation to meteorological factors. Bull. Ent. Res., 74: 487 - 494 .
- NCIPM (National Coalition on Integrated Pest Management) (1994):** Toward a goal of 75 percent cropland under IPM by 2000. Jan. Austin, TX.
- NFIPME (National Foundation for Integrated Pest Management Education) (1994):** Integrated pest management. IPM Monitor. Austin, TX, Winter.
- NFIPME (National Foundation for Integrated Pest Management Education) (1994):** IPM: The Essence. IPM Monitor. Austin, TX, Summer.
- Norton, W. G. and Mullen, J. (1994):** Economic Evaluation of integrated pest management programs: a literature review. Virginia Cooperative Extension Publ. 448-120, Virginia State Univ. Petersburg, VA., and Virginia Polytech. Instt. & State University, Blacksburg, VA., pp. 112.
- Ramalho, F.S. (1994):** Cotton pest management. Annu. Rev. Entomol., 39: 563-578.
- Raven, P.H.; Berg, L.R. and Johnson, G.B. (1993):** Environment. Saunders College Publishing, N.Y. pp. 569.
- Saarenmma, H. (1992):** Integrated pest management in forests and information technology. J. Appl. Entomol., 114: 321-332.
- Shorey, H. H.; Gaston, L. K. and Kaae, R. S. (1976):** Air-permeation with gossypure for control of the pink bollworm. In Pest Management with Insect Sex Attractants. Beroza, M. (ed.) ACS Symposium Series 23, American Chemical Society, Washington, DC, pp. 67-74.
- Smith, R. F. and Reynolds, H. T. (1966):** Principles, definitions and scope of integrated pest control. Proc. FAO Symposium

- on Integrated Pest Control, 1: 11-17.
- Sorensen, A. A. (1993a):** Integrated pest management: future farming tasks lessons from the past. Food Insight, May/June .
- Sorensen, A. A. (1993b):** Integrated pest management- finding a new direction. Cereal Food World, 38: 187-196.
- Sorensen, A. A. (1994a):** IPM in partnership with nature. Center for Agriculture in the Environment, American Farmland Trust, DeKalb, Illinois, pp. 2
- Sorensen, A. A. (1994b):** Proceedings of the National Integrated Pest Management Forum. American Farmland Trust, pp. 86.
- Staten R. T.; Finnel, C. and Jensen, L. (1983):** Monitoring of the Imperial Valley pheromone program. Imperial County Agricultural Commissioner's Office, pp.14
- Staten, R. T.; Antilla, L. and Walters, M. (1995):** Pink bollworm management: prospects for the future. Proc. Beltwide Cotton Production and Research Conf., National Cotton Council of America, pp. 153-156.
- Staten, R. T.; Flint, H. M.; Weddle, R. C.; Quintero, E.; Zariti, R. E.; Finnel, C. M.; Hernandez, M. and Yamamoto, A. (1987):** Pink bollworm (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae): Large scale field tests with a high rate gossypure formulation. J. Econ. Entomol., 80: 1267-1271.
- Staten, R. T.; Miller, E.; Grunnet, M. and Andress, E. (1988):** The use of pheromones for pink bollworm management in western cotton. Proc. Beltwide Cotton Production and Research Conf., National Cotton Council of America, pp. 206-209.
- Tette, J. P. (1997):** New York State Integrated Pest Management Program, New York State Department of Agriculture and Markets, Cornell University and Cornell Cooperative Extension., pp. 60.
- UCS-IPM (1997):** [University of California State-wide Integrated Pest Management Project, 1997. Annual Report, University of California State-wide Integrated Pest Management Project, California, pp .77.
- USDA-ARS (United State Department of Agriculture) , Agricultural Research Service) (1993):** USDA programs related to integrated pest management. USDA Program Aid 1506.
- Vandeman, A.; Fernandez-Cornejo, J. ; Jans, S. and Lin, B. (1994):** Adoption of integrated pest management in U. S. Agriculture. Agri. Information Bull. 707. USDA, pp. 28.
- Vandeman, A.; Fernandez-Cornejo, J.; Jans, S. and Lin, B. (1994):** Adoption of integrated pest management in U. S. Agriculture. Agri. Information Bull. 707. USDA, pp. 28.
- Waibel, H. and Zadoks, J. C. (1996):** Institutional Constraints to IPM. XIIIth International Plant Protection Congress (IPPC), The Hague, July 2-7, Pesticide Policy Project, Publ. Series. No. 3. Institute of Hortic. Economics, Hannover, Germany. pp.63)
- Wightman, J. A. (1993):** Towards the rational management of the insect pests of tropical legumes crops in Asia: review and remedy. pp. 233-256. In Crop

protection and sustainable agriculture. CIBA Foundation Symposium pp. 177- 285.

Zalom, F. G.; Ford, R. E. ; Frisbie, R. E. ; Edwards, C. R. and Telle, J. P. (1992): Integrated pest management: addressing the economic and environmental issues of contemporary agriculture. In Food, crop pests, and the environment: the need

and potential for biologically intensive integrated pest management, Zalom, F. G. and Fry, W. E. (eds.), APS Press, St. Paul, MN.

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Economic outcome of producing royal jelly from two honeybee hybrids rearing colony under queen right and queen less conditions through two different grafting type of larvae genotype

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Abstract:

Honeybee royal jelly is one of the most important products in the honeybee industry, it is produced from the hypopharyngeal and mandibular glands of 6-12 days old workers. it's a white creamy substance containing mainly proteins, sugars, and lipids. Also, it has many benefits for humans such as stimulating the immune system, strengthening the body and it's a good assistant cure for many diseases such as leukemia, cancer, high blood pressure, high cholesterol, and infertility in males and females. This investigation aimed to study the economic feasibility of producing royal jelly from two honeybee hybrids under queen right and queen less conditions through the different grafting larvae genotype at two years .The queen rearing colonies were provided: either queen less or queen right of the Italian or Craniolan honeybee hybrids using an inverted L- queen excluder. During the spring season (April and May) - summer season (July and August) and late summer season (August to September) for two successive years 2020 and 2021. The queen right condition produced royal jelly less than the queen less. The value of royal jelly production was recorded during the spring season while The lowest value of royal jelly production was recorded at the Late summer season. The queen less condition, the Craniolan grafting larvae and spring season can use for the best quantity of produce royal jelly.

Introduction

Royal jelly is one of the most importance products in honeybee industrial, it produced from hypopharyngeal and mandibular glands of 6-12 days old workers, (Deseyn and Billen, 2005). It's a white creamy substance contains mainly of proteins, sugars, and lipids (Schmidt, 1997). Also it has many benefits for humans such as stimulate the immune system, strengthens the body and it's a good assistant cure for many diseases such as leukemia, cancer, high blood pressure,

high cholesterol, and infertility in males and females (Krell, 1996 and Sahinler, 2000).

The quantity of royal jelly per cup varies depending on the time it remains in the colony. Chang (1977) obtained more royal jelly when collecting 72 hours after 12-14 hour-old larvae transference than in collects done 48 hours after larvae transference. The quantity of royal jelly per cup varies depending on the time it remains in the colony. Toledo (1997) observed that Carniolan had higher larvae acceptance

and higher royal jelly production than Africanized queens descending from: queens inseminated by Italian males; Africanized queens with Italian males; Italian queens inseminated by Italian males and Italian queens with Africanized males.

Different factors may interfere in royal jelly production: genetics; colonies internal population conditions; food flow; queen's egg-laying; and external environment related to weather conditions and food availability (Nogueira-Couto, 1992 and 1996; Toledo, 1997 and Azevedo-Benitez *et al.* 1998). Thus, it is important to study the influence of these factors on royal jelly production, and honeybee's regional adaptability. Royal jelly is being produced as a result of grafting process and the acceptance of grafted queen cups is being affected by type of nutrition and queen cups introduced to the bees (Mohanny, 2010 and Zeedan, 2002).

Royal jelly contains remarkable amounts of proteins, lipids, glucides, vitamins, hormones, enzymes, and mineral substances (Howe *et al.*, 1985). The composition of elements in the royal jelly are water (50% to 60%), proteins (18%), carbohydrates (15%), lipids (3% to 6%), mineral salts (1.5%), and vitamins (Trace amount) (Nagai and Inoue, 2004).

There are several factors affecting royal jelly production, the most important of them are the age of transferred larvae (Sahinler and Kaftanođlu, 1997), feeding (Fuhai *et al.*, 1993), number of transferred queen cell cups (Van-Toor and Littlejohn, 1994), harvesting interval (Fiahinler and Fiahinler, 2002), whether, the colony is queen less or queen right (Van-Toor and Littlejohn, 1994) and bee race (Shibi *et al.*,1993).

This investigation aimed to study the economic outcome of producing royal jelly from two honeybee hybrids

under queen right and queen less conditions through the different grafting larvae genotype at two years.

Materials and methods

The experiments were conducted under the conditions of Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate (With the facility of the Sakha Agricultural Research Station) during years 2020 and 2021. The hive approximately equal of strength and number of combs. The queen rearing colonies were provided: Either queen less or queen right of the Italian or Craniolan honeybee hybrids using an inverted L- queen excluder.

Procedures:

During the spring season (April and May) - summer season (July and August) and late summer season (August to September) for two successive years 2020 and 2021.

The bee colonies under the study are as follows:

1. Choose the parent colony of the Italian and Craniolan honeybee hybrids, an empty worker brood frame was but between the brood frames to force the queen to lay eggs and follow until the hatching is completed three days later. The fourth day is the first larval age (larvae of one day) which takes the shape of the crescent.

2. Processing of grafting frames with three strips arranged in three different locations (Upper, middle, lower) each frame carrying 45 plastic cups. The rearing frame is then exposed to the rearing colony two hours before the grafting.

3. Colonies without queens (Queen less):

The queens were removed, and the colonies became without queens (queen less). The strength of the colonies were Eight combs covered with bees divided into five sealed brood combs plus three honey and pollen combs + plastic feed.

4. Colonies with queens (Queen right):

Inverted L-shaped excluder was used. Each colony has 11 combs covered with bees divided as follows: two sealed brood combs + one honey and pollen comb) under the Queen's reservation + a vertical queen excluder + four sealed and open brood combs, the open combs close to the sealed (Two sealed brood) + two honey and pollen combs) in addition to plastic feed. The rearing process in the honey box.

Twelve honey bee colonies were used in the experiment of the Italian and Craniolan honeybee hybrid distributed as follows:

Six replicates of the Italian honey bee hybrid was divided to three replicates without queen and three replicates with queens. Also, Six replicates of the Craniolan honey bee hybrid were divided to three replicates without a queen and three replicates with queens.

The queens of the rearing colonies were removed 48 hours before inserted the grafting from either for queen less or queen right colonies. The method of Doolittle was applied 1909 - wet method of grafting (1 gram of royal jelly: 1 cm distilled water) (1909)

Procedures:

1. Exposing the grafting frames that carry the plastic cups to the breeding colony for two hours before the grafting. Provide nutrition to the rearing colony

2. Rearing was carried out in the brood chamber for the queen less. In the case of the queen right, rearing was carried out in honey supers under the inverted L-shaped excluder

3. Grafting the one day larvae were transferred into the plastic cups by the grafting needle and then the rearing frame that carried three wooden bars placed between the sealed brood combs in both queen less and queen right chamber.

4. The nutrition

Sugar solution with concentrate of 1kg sugar: 1.5 water. Each colony fed on half a liter of the solution.

5. On the same date of grafting, after 72 hours the rearing frames were raised from the rearing colonies and removing the larvae from the plastic cups by a plastic needle, then collecting the royal jelly with a wooden spoon, and collecting the royal jelly according to the successful royal cups. The royal jelly containers were weighed empty and filled then numbered with a code number, the capacity of each container was five grams. Each queen cell was weighed (1-5 cups or less). The number of cups is divided by the number of cups to find the average per cup. The royal jelly was saved in the fridge.

The grafting process is repeated every three days to bring new crews in the royal cups. During the experiment, five grafting process were taken for all seasons and also in all experiments for 2020 and 2021 years.

Results and discussion

Data in Table (1) indicated the royal jelly quantity means (gm/colony/year) produced from Craniolan hybrid rearing colony under queen right and queen less of grafted Italian and Craniolan genotype larvae during different seasons in year 2015. At the spring season the Italian grafting larvae in the queen right produced 21.32 gm less than the queen less which produced 24.32 gm. As the Craniolan grafting larvae in the queen right produced 23.83 gm less than the queen less which produced 26.17 gm.

At the summer season, the Craniolan grafting larvae in the queen right produced 19.97 gm less than the queen less which produced 21.89 gm. Moreover, the Italian grafting larvae in the queen right produced 15.99 gm less than the queen less which produced 22.46 gm.

At the late summer season, the Italian grafting larvae in the queen right produced 13.00 gm less than the queen lees which produced 13.85 gm. However, the Carniolan grafting larvae

in the queen right produced 15.55 gm less than the queen lees which produced 16.36 gm.

Table (1):Royal jelly quantity means (gm/ colony/year) produced from Carniolan hybrids rearing colony under queen right and queen-less of grafted Italian and Carniolan genotype larvae during different seasons in year 2020.

Rearing colony	Grafting Larvae genotype	Seasons						Mean /Colony /Year	
		Spring		Summer		Late Summer		Queen right	Queen less
		Queen right	Queen less	Queen right	Queen less	Queen right	Queen less		
Carniolan	Italian	21.32	24.32	15.99	22.46	13.00	13.85	50.31	60.63
Hybrid	Carniolan	23.83	26.17	19.97	21.89	15.55	16.36	59.35	64.42
Means		22.6	25.3	17.98	22.2	14.3	15.1	54.85	62.5

Data in Table (2) indicated the royal jelly quantity means (gm/ colony/year) produced from Italian hybrid rearing colony under queen right and queen-less of grafted Italian and Carniolan genotype larvae during different seasons in year 2016. At the spring season the Italian grafting larvae in the queen right produced 29.00 gm less than the queen lees which produced 31.10 gm. As the Carniolan grafting larvae in the queen right produced 27.04 gm more than the queen lees which produced 23.90 gm.

At the summer season, the Italian grafting larvae in the queen right produced 22.76 gm less than the queen lees which produced 27.50 gm. As the Carniolan grafting larvae in the queen right produced 20.32 gm less than the queen lees which produced 21.28 gm. At the late summer season, the Italian grafting larvae in the queen right produced 16.93 gm less than the queen lees which produced 17.79 gm. As the Carniolan grafting larvae in the queen right produced 13.31 gm less than the queen lees which produced 14.70 gm.

Table (2): royal jelly quantity means (gm/ colony) produced from Italian hybrids rearing colony under queen right and queen-less of grafted Italian and Carniolan genotype larvae during different seasons in year 2021.

Rearing colony	Grafting Larvae genotype	Seasons						Mean /Colony /Year	
		Spring		Summer		Late Summer		Queen right	Queen less
		Queen right	Queen less	Queen right	Queen less	Queen right	Queen less		
Italian	Italian	29.00	31.10	22.76	27.50	16.93	17.79	68.69	76.39
Hybrid	Carniolan	27.04	23.90	20.32	21.28	13.31	14.70	60.67	59.9
Means		28.02	27.5	21.55	24.4	15.12	16.25	64.68	68.15

Data in Table (3) indicated the royal jelly quantity means (gm/ colony/year) produced from Italian hybrid rearing colony under queen right and queen-less of grafted Italian and Carniolan genotype larvae during different seasons in year 2016. At the spring season the Italian grafting larvae in the queen right produced 27.66 gm more than the queen lees which produced 26.69 gm. As the Carniolan grafting larvae in the queen

right produced 24.88 gm less than the queen lees which produced 25.00 gm. At the summer season, the Italian grafting larvae in the queen right produced 22.34 gm more than the queen lees which produced 19.65 gm.

As the Carniolan grafting larvae in the queen right produced 22.91 gm more than the queen lees which produced 20.62 gm. At the late summer season, the Italian grafting larvae in the queen right produced 15.00 gm more

than the queen lees which produced 14.03 gm. As the Craniolan grafting larvae in the queen right produced

12.34 gm less than the queen lees which produced 12.99 gm.

Table (3): Royal jelly quantity means (gm/ colony) produced from Italian hybrid rearing colony under queen right and queen-less of grafted Italian and Carniolan genotype larvae during different seasons in year 2020.

Rearing colony hybrid	Grafting larvae genotype	Seasons						Mean /Colony /Year	
		Spring		Summer		Late Summer			
		Queen right	Queen less	Queen right	Queen less	Queen right	Queen less	Queen right	Queen less
Italian Hybrid	Italian	27.66	26.69	22.34	19.65	15.00	14.03	65.00	60.37
	Carniolan	24.88	25.00	22.91	20.62	12.34	12.99	60.13	58.1
Means		26.3	25.8	22.6	20.10	13.67	13.51	62.6	59.23

Data in Table (4) indicated the royal jelly quantity means (gm/ colony) produced from Italian hybrid rearing colony under queen right and queen-less of grafted Italian and Carniolan genotype larvae during different seasons in year 2016. At the spring season the Italian grafting larvae in the queen right produced 23.49 gm more than the queen lees which produced 22.41 gm. As the Craniolan grafting larvae in the queen right produced 24.28 gm less than the queen lees which produced 23.89 gm.

At the summer season, the Italian grafting larvae in the queen right produced 22.54 gm more than the queen lees which produced 15.34 gm. As the Craniolan grafting larvae in the queen right produced 19.57 gm more than the queen lees which produced 18.02 gm. At the late summer season, the Italian grafting larvae in the queen right produced 11.82 gm less than the queen lees which produced 12.30 gm. As the Craniolan grafting larvae in the queen right produced 14.00 gm less than the queen lees which produced 13.23 gm.

Table (4) royal jelly quantity means produced from Italian and Carniolan hybrids rearing colony under queen right and queen-less of grafted Italian and Craniolan genotype larvae during different seasons in year 2021.

Rearing colony hybrid	Grafting larvae genotype	Seasons						Mean /Colony /Year	
		Spring		Summer		Late Summer			
		Queen right	Queen less	Queen right	Queen less	Queen right	Queen less	Queen right	Queen less
Carniolan Hybrid	Italian	23.49	22.41	22.54	15.34	11.82	12.30	57.85	50.1
	Carniolan	24.28	23.89	19.57	18.02	14.00	13.23	57.85	55.14
Means		23.9	23.15	21.1	16.68	12.91	12.8	57.85	52.62

From the obtained results it could be suggested that, under the Craniolan rearing colony in year 2020 the queen right condition produced royal jelly less than the queen less. Whoever the Craniolan grafting larvae produced royal jelly more than the Italian one. The highest value of royal jelly production was recorded at the spring season while The lowest value of royal jelly production was recorded at the Late summer season. under the

Italian rearing colony in year 2021. As the queen less condition produced royal jelly more than the queen right. Whoever the Italian grafting larvae produced royal jelly more than the Craniolan one. The highest value of royal jelly production was recorded at the spring season while The lowest value of royal jelly production was recorded at the Late summer season. under the Craniolan rearing colony in year 2020 the queen right condition

produced royal jelly more than the queen less. Whoever the Italian grafting larvae produced royal jelly more than the Carniolan one. The highest value of royal jelly production was recorded at the spring season while The lowest value of royal jelly production was recorded at the late summer season.

Under the Italian rearing colony in year 2021 the queen right condition produced royal jelly more than the queen less. Whoever the Carniolan grafting larvae produced royal jelly more than the Italian one. The highest value of royal jelly production was recorded at the spring season while The lowest value of royal jelly production was recorded at the Late summer season this may be due to the differences between season in weather conditions and the differences between hybrids.

From the obtained result the following conclusion can be drawing. The queen less condition, the Carniolan grafting larvae and spring season can use for the best quantity of produce royal jelly. Many authors discussed these points . Descendants from highly royal jelly productive colonies had a higher acceptance of transferred larvae and also deposited more royal jelly per cup (Azevedo, 1996). Toledo (1997) observed that Carniolan had higher larvae acceptance and higher royal jelly production than Africanized queens descending from: queens inseminated by Italian males; Africanized queens with Italian males; Italian queens inseminated by Italian males and Italian queens with Africanized males. Different factors may interfere in royal jelly production: genetics; colonies internal population conditions; food flow; queen's egg-laying; and external environment related to weather conditions and food availability (Nogueira-Couto, 1992 and 1996; Toledo, 1997 and Azevedo-Benitez *et al.*, 1998). The average acceptance rates throughout the season were 88.2% and

72.1% in queen less and queen right cell builders, respectively (Sahinler and Kaftanođlu, 1997). Kaftanođlu and Kumova (1990) reported that, the average acceptance rates for queen less cell builders were 87.1%, 75.9% and 77.59%, respectively. Royal jelly production in April was 9.2% greater than that in May, 17.7% greater than that in June, 41.9% greater than that in July, 65.1% greater than that in August and 103% greater than that in September. These results showed that royal jelly production decreased significantly over time. This was due to the shortage of fresh pollen during summer and weakness of the queen less cell builders due to ageing. Öztürk (1997) reported that the average royal jelly yield for queen less cell builders was 0.180 g and 0.303 g, respectively.

The acceptance rates in the Carniolan bee genotype were 7.9% and 16.7% more than in the Muđla and Caucasian genotypes, respectively. Similarly, royal jelly yield in the Carniolan bee genotype was 14.46% and 86% more than that in the Muđla and Caucasian genotypes, respectively. The honeybee colonies can maintain their life even in adverse weather conditions. They are active during the whole year, but the degrees of these activities differ from time to time, from period to period and from season to another. These differences are due to the variation in the environmental conditions, which includes both weather factors and sources of nectar and Pollen, which considered the main food for these colonies. The brood rearing activity of honeybee colonies depends upon many factors, among them temperature and the collection of pollen and nectar, on one side and the colony population (Farrar, 1944; Larie and Brand, 1958; Townsend and Smith, 1969 and Keith, 1975) in the other. Mohanna (1969) reported that, the breeder colony had a limited capacity to

rear queens, and the obtained number of successful queen cells differed from one month to another. The number of sealed queen cells differed from 10 cells in March to 25 sealed queen cells in July. The highest percentage of a successful queen cell (Average 71.8%) was obtained in July. The lowest average percentage occurred during March average (45.80%). During May, the average percentage of successful queen cells was 60%, but was only 47% in September.

Eweis (1974) found that the largest amount of royal jelly production for younger worker colonies was obtained during the spring (11.82 and 8.84 g), the late summer (14.23 and 10.95 g) and early summer (11.28 and 7.8 g) through 1970 and 1971, respectively. The lowest amount for the old worker bees (4.8 and 2.47 g) queen less normal colonies (4.59 and 3.56 g) and small worker age colonies (7.83 and 3.77 g) were showed during the autumn season in 1970 and 1971. Mouatadid (1978) reported that the queens reared during the honey flow (June-July) were significantly heavier (196,0 mg) than those reared at other times (159.5 mg). Nasr (1979) found that the mean weights of newly emerged queens during spring, summer and autumn seasons were 196.6 mg, 185.6 mg and 177.9 mg, respectively.

Krol (1985) found that during the first 6 days of queen larval development, differences were observed between Causasian, Camiolan, Italian and north European honey bee races. Carnelians built the largest and heaviest queen cells and put most royal jelly in each cell. The best time of the year for queen production was at the end of May and in early August. In all the races, the amount of royal jelly in the cell was maximal one at the fourth day of larval development.

El-Sarrag (1993) found that queens were successfully reared in

February (92%) from grafted larvae and during March – June (82%). The least favorable periods (48%) were in August – September, 28% in December – January. He added that the mortality of embryos was significantly correlated with temperature and with pollen collection. The most suitable seasons for rearing queens could be descending ordered as follows: spring, summer and late summer. Ismail (2001) found that queen rearing began when the brood nest was congested and nectar and pollen were abundant, obtained. March was the maximum month for queen cups production. El-Wassef (2002) indicated that the mean number produced queen cups were higher in spring – 1998 (16.77/col.) and winter (5.741/col.) than in summer (2.89/col.) and autumn (0.2/col.) in the indoor colonies in closed area. While, in the second experimental period (1999-2000) the mean number of produced queen cups were higher in winter (3.71/col.) and summer (3.481/col.) than in spring (3/col.) and autumn (0.29/col.) under the same condition. The fed colonies were active in building more queen cups than unfed ones and higher building queen cups in March.

Shoreit *et al* (2002) found that the maximum total of queen cells and queen cups was found during February – April period or swarming period. Minimum construction of queen cells and cups was observed during November and December. No constructed queen cells were observed during June, October and November, while queen cups can be observed every month maximum population of adult bees was found during the period from July till September. Maximum stored pollen or bee bread was observed inside colonies during August – October period, while minimum stored pollen was noticed during December, November and May.

Zeedan (2002) showed that the highest number of building queen cups was during March (24.6 queen cups/colony) while the lowest number was during December (0.9 queen cups /colony). The building queen's cups could be arranged in descending order as follows: during spring (38.4%) followed by summer (26.4%) winter (20.1%) and autumn (15.1%) seasons. He added that there were significant differences in the mean of accepted larvae between both spring (84.2%) and summer (82.3%) from one side and both autumn (73.4%) and winter (71.1%) from the other one, and he also, added that the heaviest queens were produced during summer (178.7mg/queen). This value was significantly higher than during the other seasons which were 175.6, 171.8 and 168.2 mg/ queen in spring, autumn and winter, respectively. Abd Al-Fattah *et al.* (2003) under the environmental conditions of North Sinai region determined that the highest rate of acceptance (82.8%) occurred during summer. Significant difference was found between summer and other seasons. The lowest significant percentage appeared in winter (36.1%) while moderate results for the acceptance larvae were noticed during spring (70.0%) and autumn (72.8%) seasons with insignificant differences between them.

References

- Abd Al-Fattah, M.A.; El-Basiony M.N. and Mahfouz H.M. (2003):** Some environmental factors affecting the quantity of artificially reared queens (*Apis mellifera* L.) in North Sinai region. Egypt. L. Agric. Sci. Mansoura Univ., 28(8): 6407-6417.
- Azevedo, A. L. G. (1996):** Estudos de parâmetros relacionados com a produção de geléia real em colméias de *Apis mellifera* mais e menos produtivas. Dissertação (Mestrado em Zootecnia) - Faculdade de Ciências Agrárias e Veterinárias - Universidade Estadual Paulista, Jaboticabal, Brasil.
- Azevedo-Benitez, A. L. G.; Pereira, F. M. and Nogueira-Couto, R. H. (1998):** Seleção bidirecional para a produção de geléia real em colméias de *Apis mellifera*. Trabalho apresentado no 3. Encontro Sobre Abelhas. Faculdade de Filosofia, Ciências e Letras de Ribeirão Preto - USP, Ribeirão Preto, Brasil.
- Chang, S. Y. (1977):** Effects of size and type of queen cup on the production of royal jelly and acceptance by nurse bees. Thesis (Master Science), National Chang Hsing University, Taichung, Taiwan.
- Deseyn, J. and Billen, J. (2005):** age dependent morphology and ultra-structure of the hypopharyngeal gland of *Apis mellifera* workers (*hymenoptera, Apiadae*). Apidologie, 36: 49-57.
- El-Sarrag, M.S. (1993):** Studies on some factors affecting rearing of honeybee queen (*Apis mellifera* L.) under Riyadh conditions. Agric. Res. Center college of Agric., Kin Saud Univ., 41: 30.
- El-Wassef, R. A. (2002):** Ecological and physiological studies on honeybee colonies under different environmental conditions. M. Sc. Thesis. Fac. Of Agric, Cairo University.
- Eweis, M. A. (1974):** Some factors affecting royal jelly production and the effect of methods of storing unit's quality Ph. D. Fac. Agric. Cairo. University.
- Farrar, G. L. (1944):** Protective management of honeybee

- colonies in the Northern states (Circular 702, U.S.D.A).
- Fiahinler, N. and Fiahinler, S. (2002):** Effects of The Number of Queen Cells and Harvesting Interval On the Acceptance Rates of the Larvae, Royal Jelly Quality and Quantity. *Journal of Animal and Veterinary Advances*, (1) 3: 120-122.
- Fuhai, L.; Shibi, C.; Shengming, H. and Fuxiu, L. (1993):** The Study on Pollen Substitutes of Honeybees. *Honeybee, Royal jelly, Environment*, Edited Dept. of Beekeeping Technology, Bee Inst. CAAS, Beijing, China, 22-40.
- Howe, S. E.; Dimick, P. S. and Benton, A. W. J. (1985):** Composition of freshly harvested and commercial royal jelly. *Apic. Res.*, 24: 52-61.
- Ismail, A. A. (2001):** Effect of some natural substances on the activity and some products of honeybee. M. Sc. Thesis, fac. Agric. Mansoura University.
- Kaftanođlu, O. and Kumova, U. (1990):** Çukurova Bölgesi Kofllularında Anaar› (*Apis mellifera* L.) Yetifltirme Mevsiminin Anaar› Kalitesine Olan Etkileri. *Dođa Veteriner ve Hayvanc›lık Dergisi*, 16: 569-577.
- Keith, D. M. (1975):** Pollen supplements :1- Relationships between supplements. Pollen and Brood rearing. *Amer. Bee J.*, 115(1) : 14-15.
- Krell, R. (1996):** Value-added products from beekeeping. (FAO agricultural services food and agriculture organization of the United Nations. Bulletin, No. 124, Rome.
- Krol, A. (1985):** Provision of royal Jelly during the development of queen larvae of four honey bee races and the amount of wax in the queen cells. *Pszczelniczezeszyty Naukowe*, 29: 57-71.
- Larie, O. and Brand, E. J. (1958):** A method for mass production of queen. XVII Int. Bee keep. Conger.A.A.422,1958.
- Mohanna, N.M.F. (1969):** The effect of some ecological factors in honeybee queen rearing mating and fecundity. M.Sc. thesis. Fac. Agric., Alexandria University.
- Mohanny, K. M. (2010):** new treatments for increasing and improving the production of the honeybee colonies. *Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt*, 87: 201-210.
- Mouatadid, S.M. (1978):** Research on the biology of the queen honeybee memorie present pour L'obtenion du DEA. UnivesitePartis-Saud, France pp. 87 (A.A. 1288/81).
- Nagai, T. and Inoue R. (2004):** Preparation and the functional properties of water extract and alkaline extract of royal jelly. *Food. Chem.*, 84: 181-186.
- Nasr, M.E. (1979):** Studies on some factors affecting the mating of honeybee queens *Apis mellifera* L. (Hymenoptera: Apidae) under Shambat conditions. M.Sc. Thesis Fac. Of Agric. Cairo University.
- Nogueira-Couto, R. H. (1992):** Alguns fatores que afetam a produçao de geléia real em colméias de *Apis mellifera*. Trabalho apresentado no Encontro Brasileiro Sobre Biologia de Abelhas Outros Insetos Sociais. Universidade Estadual Paulista, São Paulo, Brasil.
- Nogueira-Couto, R. H. (1996):** Uso dr atrativos e repelents como reguladores da

- Öztürk, C. (1997):** (*Apis mellifera* L.) Kolonilerine Uygulanacak Farklı Besleme ve Yetiştirme Yöntemlerinin Arı Sütü Verimine Olan Etkilerinin Araştırılması. Yüksek Lisans tezi, Çukurova Üniversitesi, Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü Zootekni Anabilim Dalı, Adana.
Polinização: Simpósio Estadual de Apicultura do Paraná, XI, Pato Branco (PR), pp. 61-65.
- Sahinler, N. (2000):** Arı urunleri yapisi ve insan sagligi acisindan onemi. (Mustafa Kemal Univ.). Ziraat Fak. Derg., 5: 139-148.
- Sahinler, N. and Kaftanoğlu, O. (1997):** Effects of Feeding Age of the Larvae and Queenlessness on the Production of Royal Jelly. Bee Products Properties, Applications and Apitherapy. Plenum Press. New York and London, 173-178.
- Schmidt, J. O. (1997):** Bee products chemical composition and application. Bee products properties, applications and apitherapy. (Plenum Press. New York and London, 15-26.
- Shibi, C.; Shengming, H.; Fuhai, L. and Puxiu, L. (1993):** Studies on the Relationship Between the Bee Races and the Yield of Royal Jelly. Honeybee, Royal jelly, Environment, Edited Dept. of Beekeeping Technology, Bee Inst. CAAS, Beijing, China, 40-53.
- Shoreit, M. N.; Hussen, M. H.; Omar, M. O. M. and Abdel-Rahman, M. F. (2002):** Brood rearing of the honeybee colony individuals and their activities in Assiut region. Egypt J. of Agric. Res., 80 (1): 83-103
- Toledo, V. A. A. (1997):** Estudo comparativo de parâmetros biológicos e de produção de cera e geléia real em colônias de abelhas *Apis mellifera* africanizadas, cárnicas, italianas e seus híbridos. Jaboticabal UNESP, Tese (Doutorado) - Faculdade de Ciências Agrárias e Veterinárias - Universidade Estadual Paulista, Jaboticabal, Brasil.
- Townsend, G. F. and Smith, M.V. (1969):** Pollen storage for bee feeding. Amer. bee J., 109(1):14-15.
- Van-Toor, R.F. and Littlejohn, R.P. (1994):** Evaluation of hive management techniques in production of royal jelly by honey bees (*Apis mellifera*) in New Zealand. Journal of Apicultural Research, 33 (3): 160-166.
- Zeedan, E.W.M. (2002):** Studies on certain factors affecting the production and quality of queen honeybee (*Apis mellifera* L.) in Giza Region M.Sc. Thesis, Fac. Agric. Cairo University .

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The effect of some insecticide and insect growth regulator on cotton leaf worm
Spodoptera littoralis (Lepidoptera, Noctuidae) under laboratory condition

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Abstract:

The effect of amidochlorochloride, lambda and biflorate (IGR) against 2nd and 4th instars of the laboratory strain of *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisduval). (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) was calculated under laboratory conditions. Amidochlorochloride was the most toxic compound against the 2nd and 4th larval instars of *S. littoralis*. All the treated larvae were biologically affected by the three tested compounds. The result was varied according to the larval instars and tested compounds. Therefore, the treated larvae were resulted in decreased pupation and adult emergence percentages, even so it reaches to 0% in the 2nd instar treated with amidochlorochloride had the strongest effect in this respect. The treatment of 2nd instar with the three compounds induced the highest increase in larval mortality, least pupation percentage and also least adult emergence percentages. Hence, the larval treatment of 2nd and 4th instars with amidochlorochloride, lambda and biflorate gave the shortest period of adult longevity, as compared to control. The larval treatment of 2nd and 4th instars with the three tested compounds increased the adult emergence, the treatment of 2nd and 4th instars with amidochlorochloride, lambda and biflorate (IGR) had the strongest effect in this respect than control.

Introduction

The cotton leaf worm *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisduval). (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) considered as one of the most serious and destructive pests not only for cotton plant, but also for other vegetable and field crops in Egypt. This insect has a complete developmental stage this mean that has four stages

(Adults, egg, larval stage and pupal stage), after coupling male with the female, the female moth lays prominent masses of egg (20 to 1000 eggs) on the underside of the cotton leaf which far about 50 cm above the ground (El-Saadany and Abdel Fattah, 1976).

Such larval stage is the longest and most destructive

stage in terms of physical damage to plant tissues. As the insect develops, it completes six instars. The first three instars feed mainly on the lower surface of the cotton leaves, whereas later instars feed on both surfaces. The third and fourth instars remain on a plant but do not feed during daylight.

Later instars migrate off the plant and rest in the soil during the day and return to the plant at night. When the temperature increases, the young larvae hide under the leaves and the older ones move to the soil (Gawaad and El-Gayar, 1974 and Abdel-Megeed and Iss Hak, 1975).

In the pupal stage the insects remain at 3-5 cm depth below the soil surface. Pupa creates "a clay cell" or cocoon in which it usually pupates within five to six hours. Emergence of moths occurs at night, and they have a lifespan of five to ten days. Adults fly at night, mostly between the hours of 8 pm and midnight. About half of females will lay their eggs before sunrise of the same night of mating. The adult moth is very active, agile and becomes capable of longer flights (Salama and Shoukry, 1972).

The aim of the present work is to study the effect of amidochlorochloride, lambda and biflorate (IGR) against the 2nd and 4th instars of the laboratory strain of *S. littoralis* was calculated under laboratory conditions.

Materials and methods

1. Maintenance of insect culture:

The culture of *S. littoralis* is used in this study originated from eggs obtained by a susceptible strain established in Cotton Leaf Worm Department, Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center , Giza, Egypt. This strain was reared in the laboratory under constant laboratory conditions of 25 ± 2 °C and 65 ± 5 % R.H. according to El-Defrawi *et al.* (1964).

Egg masses were kept in petri dishes, 2 egg masses in each dish, until hatching. The hatched larvae were transferred to glass jars (2 liter capacity) covered with muslin cloth secured with rubber bands larvae were provided daily with fresh Castor leaves (*Ricinus communis*).

The larvae develop reaching for the 6th instar, pre-pupae were allowed to pupate in glass jars containing 2 inch layer of dry saw dust, the resulting pupae were then placed on filter paper discs in uncovered petri- dishes, which were kept I 1 cubic foot wire screen cages.

The resulting moths were fed on 20% sugar solution and allowed to lay their eggs on fresh *Nerium oleander* leaves as a physical surface for moths mating, ovipositor and resting egg- masses were collected after 2 days and transferred to petri- dishes for another generation.

The effect of these treatments was studied on 2nd and 4th instar larvae of cotton leave worm.

2. The tested compound:

2.1. Amidochlorochloride 35%

2.2. Lambda:

CASName: (R)-cyano(3-phenoxyphenyl)methyl(1S,3S)-rel-3-[(1Z)-2-chloro-3,3,3-trifluoro-1-propenyl]-2,2-dimeth

Molecular

Formula: C₂₃H₁₉ClF₃NO₃

2.3. Biflorate (IGR) 25% WB

By a concentration 0.25, 0.50 and 1.00% for each treatment three replicate for these treatments each have 20 larvae in addition to untreated check control (Treated with fresh water).

3. The following procedures were applied:

3.1. For each concentration of any tested treatment, three replicates, of 20 2nd and 4th instar larvae, placed in a jar for rearing to feed on the castor bean leaves treated with the different concentrations of Treatments.

3.2. Mortality rates were recorded every 2 days. Larvae that survived after treatment were transferred to other jars containing untreated castor bean leaves.

3.3. Before exposing the larvae to treated food, they were starved for 4 hours in order to obtain rapid simultaneous ingestion of the contaminated food.

3.4. Control test was conducted by dipping clean castor bean leaves in

$$\text{Percentage of Pupation} = \frac{\text{No. of formed pupae}}{\text{Initial No. of 2}^{\text{nd}} \text{ or 4}^{\text{th}} \text{ instar larvae}} \times 100$$

$$\text{Percentage of moth emergency} = \frac{\text{No. of formed moth}}{\text{Initial No. of 2}^{\text{nd}} \text{ or 4}^{\text{th}} \text{ instar larvae}} \times 100$$

Antifeedent, effect of different treatments against 2nd and 4th instars larvae was determined by introducing accurately the weight of the bean leaves treated with concentration mentioned before compared with un-treated

$$\text{Percentage of Antifeedent} = \frac{C_c - C_t}{C_c} \times 100$$

Where: C_c = Consumed amount in un-treated.

C_t = Consumed amount in treated.

Results and discussion

Data in Table (1) showed the effect of three compounds (Two insecticides, amidochlorochloride, lambda and biflorate (IGR) with serial concentrations (0.25, 0.50 and 1 %) on the 2nd instar larvae of cotton leafworm

water, left to dry and then offered to the experimental larvae.

3.5. The experiments were carried out under laboratory conditions of 25 ± 2°C and 65 ± 5 % RH.

3.6. The castor-bean leaves were dipped for one minute in each of the used concentrations, and then treated leaves were left for air dryness and offered to the tested larvae.

4. Studying effects on different developmental stages:

For studying the latent effect, other samples were taken each 2 days and introduced to the rest a live larva until pupation stage. Mortality count was recorded each 2 days then mortality percentages were calculated, developmental effect against both pupae and moth emergency was studied by recording total numbers of formed pupae and moth emergency for each treatment then calculating their percentages by method publishing by El-Sisi and Farrag (1989) as the following:

which fed with un-treated bean leaves. After 48 hrs. of feeding, the rest leaves were weighted in each replicate, then consumed amount of leaves were calculated and antifeedent effect were calculated as Waldbauer (1968) equation:

under laboratory conditions. In addition to the developmental effect in pupation and moth emergency.

The obtained results showed for all compounds used that there was a regular direct relationship for each concentration between the percentage

of mortality and the increase in the period of treatment. Amidochlorochloride on using 0.25 % showed 25.00, 45.00, 62.00, 86.00 and 90.00 % mortality after 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 days from treatment, respectively, and on using 1 % of amidochlorochloride, the mortality percentage changed from 48.00, 64.00, 90, 99.00 and 100 % after the same periods of treatment.

Furthermore for all tested concentrations for each compound after the same period of treatment, there was also a regular direct relationship between the increase in concentration and the percentage of mortality, lambda after 2 days from treatment, the mortality percentage changed from 15.00, 24.0, to 40.00 % and after 4 days from treatment, it changed from 39.00, 57.00 to 65.00 % and after 8 days, it changed from 85.00, 92.00 to 95.00 % for the three concentrations used respectively. For the developmental effect, the three compounds showed fluctuations in both percentage of pupation and the percentage of moth emergency, the variation was not only between the three compounds but also between the used concentrations of the same compound, the percentage of pupation in the case of biflorate changed from 55.00 to 60.00 and returned back to 58.00 %. The same result was noticed with the percentage of moth emergency for the same compound as it changed from 54.00 to

59.00 and returned back to 55.00 %. The direct proportionation between concentration and percentage of mortality agreed with El-Khayat *et al.* (2012), reported that the second instar larvae reflected higher level of susceptibility towards all the tested insecticides that included Insect growth regulators (Nomolt 15% Mimic 24% an Runner 24%); Bio-insecticides, Tracer , XDE and Dipel 2x ;and Organophosphorus (Chlorpyrifos) than fourth one.

Also, Haggag (2013) found that Bt-formulations named Dipel DF, Dipel 2X and Delfin tested against 2nd and 4th instars larvae of *S. littoralis* were highly killed at the initial time, followed by agry, protecto and agerin formulations, respectively, who reported that, the increase either in the concentration of insecticides or the period of treatment resulted in an increase in the percentage of mortality. While the fluctuations in the percentage of pupation and the percentage of moth emergency may be explained on the basis of population individuals tolerance, any population consisting of individuals varies intolerance, sensitive individuals will die directly while tolerant individuals will remain whatever the concentration used or the period of treatment (Mohamed and El-Kady, 2010).

Table (1): Effect of amidochlorochloride, lambda and biflorate on 2nd instar larvae of *Spodoptera littoralis* under laboratory conditions.

Compounds	Concentration (%)	Mortality % after days					Developmental effect	
		2	4	6	8	10	% pupation	% moth emergency
Amidochlorochloride	0.25	25.0	45.0	62.0	86.0	90.0	5.0	1.00
	0.50	30.0	56.0	88.0	95.0	100.0	00.0	00.0
	1.00	48.0	64.0	90.0	99.0	100.0	00.0	00.0
Lambda	0.25	15.0	39.0	50.0	85.0	97.0	00.0	00.0
	0.50	24.0	57.0	89.0	92.0	100.0	00.0	00.0
	1.00	40.0	65.0	89.0	95.0	100.0	00.0	00.0
Biflorate	0.25	10.0	19.0	23.0	32.0	40.6	55.0	54.0
	0.50	18.0	24.0	29.0	37.0	39.0	60.0	59.0
	1.00	20.0	25.0	33.0	39.0	42.0	58.0	55.0

Also, Haggag (2013) found that Bt-formulations named Dipel DF, Dipel 2X and Delfin tested against 2nd and 4th instars larvae of *S. littoralis* were highly killed at the initial time, followed by agry, protecto and agerin formulations, respectively, who reported that, the increase either in the concentration of insecticides or the period of treatment resulted in an increase in the percentage of mortality. While the fluctuations in the percentage of pupation and the percentage of moth emergency may be explained on the basis of population individuals tolerance, any population consisting of individuals varies intolerance, sensitive individuals will die directly while tolerant individuals will remain whatever the concentration used or the period of treatment (Mohamed and El-Kady, 2010).

The data showed the effect of the three previously mentioned compounds with the same concentrations on the 4th instar larvae under laboratory conditions, relatively the results found were as in the case of

the 2nd instar larvae, direct proportionation between the percentage of mortality and the period of treatment for each concentration, in addition to the increase in the percentage of mortality with the increase in concentration for the same period of treatment. Furthermore, the developmental effect for pupation and moth emergency showed the same fluctuations as in the case of the 2nd instar larvae, the results that may be attributed also to population tolerance (Mohamed and El-Kady, 2010).

Data presented in Table (2) showed the antifeedant effect of the three used compounds with the same concentrations on both 2nd and 4th instar larvae under laboratory conditions. For all used compounds and for both stages, an inverse proportionation was obtained between the increase in concentration and the antifeedant effect. Amidochlorochloride showed 90.00, 70.00 and 60.00 % antifeedant effect on using 0.25, 0.50 and 1.00 % respectively.

Table (2): Antifeedant effect of both 2nd and 4th instar larvae of *Spodoptera littoralis*.

Compounds	Concentration (%)	2 nd instar larvae		4 th instar larvae	
		Consumed %	Antifeedant %	Consumed %	Antifeedant %
Amidochlorochloride	0.25	3.0	97.0	10.0	90.0
	0.50	15.0	85.0	30.0	70.0
	1.00	25.0	75.0	40.0	60.0
Lambida	0.25	10.0	90.0	5.0	95.0
	0.50	18.0	82.0	15.0	85.0
	1.00	30.0	70.0	20.0	80.0
Biflorate	0.25	3.0	97.0	3.0	97.0
	0.50	5.0	95.0	5.0	95.0
	1.00	10.0	90.0	4.0	96.0
Control		95.6	4.4	100	0.0

The results could be explained on the basis of leaf composition and the increase in insecticide concentration, the leaf consists of wax and fat, organic materials that facilitate penetration of the insecticide, as its concentration increased inside the leaf. The softness of the leaf may be affected and as a result the insect may refuse to feed on it

(Mesbah *et al.*, 2000 and El-Naggar, 2009) indicated farming practices that cause nutrition in balance can lower pest resistance. Meyer (2000) proposed that soil nutrient availability not only affects the amount of damage that plants receive from herbivores but also the ability of plants to recover from herbivores. Ramesh *et al.* (2005)

conducted that organic crops have been shown to be more tolerant as well as resistant to insect attacks. Saad and Nabil (2012) were studied the effects of some foliar fertilizers on the biology of silkworm, *Bombyx mori* L. In this study, the authors investigated the possibilities of using four compounds as foliar fertilizers to determine the new beneficial effects on larval and pupal mortality and larval, pupal weights, finally, the effect of these compounds on some biological aspects of cotton leaf worm, *S. littoralis*.

1. Larval and pupal duration:

Data presented in Tables (3 and 4) indicated that the 2nd and 4th larval instars of *S. littoralis* fed on castor oil leaves treated with amidochlorochloride, lambida and biflorate compounds induced a highly significant ($p < 0.01$) increase of the larval duration. The effect was more pronounced with the larval treatment of 2nd larval instar with the three tested compounds, it averaged 18.9+1.0, 17.8+ 3.1 and 18.0+ 2.5 days, respectively, as compared with 14.3+ 1.0 days of control. While the 4th instar larvae fed on lambida, gave the highest significant ($p < 0.01$) increase in the larval duration to average 16.5+ 1.3 days, as compared to 14.3+ 1.3 days of control. Whereas, the treatment of 4th instar with both amidochlorochloride and biflorate compounds caused equal significant increase in the larval duration to average 12.8+1.1 and 14.9+1.4days, respectively, as compared to that of control (13.2days) (Table 5). Treatment of the 2nd and 4th instar larvae of *S. littoralis* with the three compounds showed highly significant ($p < 0.01$) increase in the pupal duration. The effect was more noticeable with the treatment of 2nd instar with the three compounds of control. Whereas, the 4th instar treated with the three compounds gave

significant ($p < 0.01$) increase in the pupal duration.

Lambida treatment caused a higher prolongation to pupal duration averaged 19.0 days, as compared to 14.4 days of control. While, the larval treatment of 4th instar with amidochlorochloride compounds increased the pupal duration to an average 30.6 and decreased in the biflorate 20.2.1days, respectively, as compared to that of control (14.4 days). These results are similar to that obtained by Abd El-Kader *et al.* (1995) who reported that larval and pupal durations of *S. littoralis* were increased due to feeding on IGRS, atabron and alsystin and their combinations. On the contrary, Ahmed (2004) mentioned that the larval period was elongated, and the pupal period shorted for the new hatched larvae of pink and spiny bollworms (Laboratory strain) treated with the higher concentrations of Spinosad when compared with untreated larvae.

2. Pupation and adult emergence:

Data represented in Tables (3 and 4) demonstrated that the treatment of the 2nd and 4th instars larvae of *S. littoralis* with the three tested compounds amidochlorochloride, lambida and biflorate compounds caused a highly significant ($p < 0.01$) reduction of the pupation percentages, as compared to that of control. The 2nd larval instars treated with the lambida resulted non pupation percentage, reduction in amidochlorochloride compound the pupation ranged 15.5% for the second instar larvae while had equal higher effect 65.0 in biflorate compound, as compared to that of the check (93.0%). Also, the treatment of the 4th instar with lambida, compounds highly significant decreased in the pupation ranged 25%, while its moderate in both , amidochlorochloride, and biflorate

compounds 57.0 and 67.0%, respectively, as compared to control.

Also, the emergence of adults in the susceptible strain was highly affected by all treatments compared to that in the control. Hence, Aly *et al.* (2011) recorded that the pupation percentage and total adult emergence of

1st and 2nd instar larvae of *Sesamia cretica* (Lederer) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) treated with *B. thuringiensis* at the LC₅₀ concentrates were was (47 and 92 %), (94 and 100%) and (18 and 84 %), (100 and 100%) for treated and untreated, respectively.

Table (3): Effect of amidochlorochloride, lambda and biflorate on 4th instar larvae of *Spodoptera littoralis* under laboratory conditions.

Compounds	Concentration (%)	Mortality % after days					Developmental effect	
		2	4	6	8	10	% pupation	% moth emergency
Amidochlorochloride	0.25	15.0	33.0	50.0	68.0	70.0	20.0	10.0
	0.50	20.0	40.0	70.0	85.0	90.0	5.0	3.0
	1.00	33.0	55.0	77.0	88.0	100.0	00.0	00.0
Lambida	0.25	10.0	28.0	44.0	55.0	67.0	30.0	18.0
	0.50	18.0	38.0	66.0	81.0	86.0	10.0	7.0
	1.00	30.0	44.0	71.0	84.0	90.0	7.0	4.0
Biflorate	0.25	4.0	7.0	13.0	20.0	28.0	70.0	70.0
	0.50	8.0	12.0	20.0	25.0	29.0	71.0	7.0
	1.00	10.0	20.0	28.0	33.0	44.0	65.0	60.0
Control		0.0	0.0	1.0	3.0	0.6	93	91.4

Table (4): Effect of amidochlorochloride, lambda and biflorate on 2nd instar larvae of *Spodoptera littoralis* under laboratory conditions.

Treatment	Larval Duration (days) ± SD	Pupation%	Pupal duration (days) ± SD	% Adult emergence ±S.D
Amido chlorochloride	18.9±1.0**	15.5	30.6±2.7**	11.1± 1.6**
Lambida	17.8±3.1**	non	-----	-----
Biflorate	18±2.5**	65.0	20.2±1.4**	7.9 ±1.1*
Control	14.3 ± 1.0	93.0	14.4±0.8	9.0 ±1.4
F value	202.9	97.00	582.8	559.9
P value	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.0004
L.S.D.at.05	0.7	10.2	0.7	4.5
L.S.D.at.01	0.9	18.00	0.9	8.2

Table (5): Biological activity of Amidochlorochloride, lambda and biflorate against the 4th instar larvae of *Spodoptera littoralis*.

Treatment	Larval Duration (days) ± SD	Pupation%	Pupal duration (days) ± SD	% Adult emergence ±S.D
Amido-chlorochloride	12.8 ± 1.1**	25.0±12**	20.8 ±2.8**	15.0±1.3**
Lambida	16.5±1.3**	17±7.1**	19.0±4.5**	33.3 ± 1.1
Biflorate	14.9±1.4. **	67±2.3**	17.5±4.1**	82 ±25**
Control	13.2 ± 1.6	93.0	14.3 ±1.1	97.0
F value	18.7	382.8	294.3	92.7
P value	0.001	0.01	0.0001	0.01
L.S.D.at.05	0.7	8.4	0.9	5
L.S.D.at.01	0.9	15.4	1.2	9.1

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References

- Abd El-Kader, M. M.; Shaaban, M. N.; Abd El Rahman, H. A.; Moustafa, O. K. and Radwan, E. M. (1995):** Effect of insect growth inhibitors, insecticides and their combinations on some biological aspects of *Spodoptera littoralis*. Egypt J. Agric. Res., 73 (3): 677-684.
- Abdel-Megeed, M.I. and Iss Hak, R.R. (1975):** Field observations on the vertical distribution of the cotton leafworm, *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisd.) on cotton plants. Zeitschrift fur Angewandte Entomologie, 78(1): 59-62.
- Ahmed, E. M. (2004):** New approaches for control of cotton bollworms. D.ph thesis, Faculty of Agric. Cairo University.
- Aly, M. Z. Y. ; Soliman, M. M. M. ; Mohamed, E. E.E. ; Dahi, H. F. and Salem, S. A. R. (2011):** Assessments the toxic effects of entomopathogenic bacterium, *Bacillus thuringiensis* subsp. kurstaki, and methomyl insecticide on larval instars of the greater sugarcane borer; *Sesamia cretica* (Lederer). Egypt. Acad. J. biolog. Sci., 3 (1): 1- 9.
- El-Defrawi, M. ; Tappozada, A.; Mansour, N. and Zeid, M. (1964):** Toxicological studies on the Egyptian cotton leafworm, *Prodenia littoralis*. I. Susceptability of different instar to insecticides. J. Econ. Entomol. 57 (4): 591- 594.
- El-Khayat, E. F.; Desuky, W. M. H. ; Azab, M. M. and Kherd, M. M.A. (2012):** Toxic impact of some insect growth regulators and biocides in relative to chlorpyrifos to cotton leafworm, *Spodoptera littoralis*. Egypt. J. Agric. Res., 90 (1):55-65.
- El-Naggar, A. Z. (2009):** Efficacy of some foliar fertilizers and alternative chemicals on the spiny bollworm, *Erias insulana* (Boisd.) larvae (Lepidoptera : Noctuidae) and their side effect on protease activity. J. Entomol., 9 (6): 375- 381.
- El-Saadany, G. and Abdel Fattah, M. I. (1976):** Contributions to the ecology of cotton-pests in Egypt: I. Studies on the egg-laying preferences of the cotton leaf worm moth, *Spodoptera littoralis* Boisd. (Noctuidae). Journal of Applied Entomology, 80(1-4): 31-35.
- El-Sisi, A. G. and Farrag, R. M. (1989):** Formulation and biological effects of copper carbonate against the Egyptian cotton leave worm, *Spodoptera littoralis*. Agric. Res. Rev., 67 (1) :29- 35.
- Haggag, K.H.E. (2013):** Changes in protein profile of cotton leaf worm, *Spodoptera littoralis*, induced by Bt formulations stored at cold and hot storage conditions. Nat. Sci., 11(7):77-85.
- Gawaad, A. A. A. and El-Gayar, F. H. (1974):** Habits and behaviour of *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisd.) (Lep., Noctuidae) and their importance for control measures. Z. Ang. Ent., 75: 295-300.
- Mesbah, H. A.; Ibrahim, M. M.; Tayeb, E. H.; El-Naggar, A. Z. and, El-Nimr, H. M. (2000):**

- Plant health anew approach for the attainment of tolerant plants to pests infestation: Effect of fertilization and application of nutritive elements on the infestation of cotton with bollworm, *Adv. Agric. Res.*, 5: 1437- 1445.
- Meyer, G. A. (2000):** Interactive effects of soil fertility and herbivory on *Brassica nigra*. *Oikos*, 88 (2): 433-441.
- Mohamed, A. I. and El-Kady, M. A. (2010):** Effect of wetting agents on some biological activity of alum soluble powder formulations against *Aphis craccivora* . *Egypt . Acad. J. Biolog. Sci.*, 3 (1):89-93.
- Ramesh, P. ; Singh, M. and Subba Rao, A. (2005):** Organic farming: Its relevance to the Indian context . *Current Science*, 88 (4): 561-568.
- Saad, M. S. I. and Nabil, H. A. (2012):** Effects of some foliar fertilizations on some biological aspects of mulberry silkworm, *Bombyx mori* L. *Egypt J. Agric. Res.*, 90 (2): 547-558.
- Salama, H. S. and Shoukry, A. (1972):** Flight range of the moth of the cotton leafworm *Spodoptera littoralis*. *Zeitschrift fuer Angewandte Entomologie*, 71(2):181-184.
- Waldbauer, G. P. (1968):** The consumption and utilization of food by insect. *Adu. Insect. Physiol.*, 5229- 5238.

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Predacious mites as a tool to manage spider mites *Tetranychus* spp. population on cotton cultivars

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Abstract:

A Field experiment was carried out to evaluate the role of predacious mites, which are associated with *Tetranychus* spp. infestation on their population of cotton. The susceptibility of three cotton cultivars (Mc Nair 220, Okra leaf and Giza 70) to the infestation by *Tetranychus* spp. was evaluated. The existence of three predatory mites of *Tetranychus* spp.; *Amphyseius gossipi* (El-Badry) (Acari: Phytoseiidae) , *Agistemus exertus* (Gonazlez) (Acari: Stigmaeidae) and *Tydeus californicus* (Banks) (Acari: Tydeidae) was also, estimated on cotton cultivars. The population dynamics of *Tetranychus* spp. and their associated predacious mites were studied along two successive cotton seasons on the three cotton cultivars. The average number of spider mites, abundant density (Expressed as the square root of the observed number +1), on each cultivar declared significant differences between all tested cultivars. The upland Mc Nair 220 cultivar was more susceptible to *Tetranychus* spp. infestation with a mean of abundant density 6.42 and 6.05 and 6.02 mites/ 10 leaves while the Egyptian cultivar Giza 70 was tolerant (3.78 and 3.69 mites/10 leaves) along with the first and the second seasons, respectively. In addition, data showed the existence of the three predator mites on all cotton cultivars during both seasons. The highest abundant density was recorded for *T. californicus* followed by *A. exertus* and *A. gossipi*. Moreover, the population of *Tetranychus* spp. started to increase in June and reached its peak in September when it started to decline till October. The same trend was observed among the three spider predator mites, but they started to increase in July and reached their peaks in the first week of October. These results might be useful to determine the appropriate time to apply the other technique of control for integrated pest management of the two spotted spider mites, *Tetranychus urtica* Koch and *T. cinnabarinus* (Boisduval) (Acari: Tetranychidae) .

Introduction

Egyptian cotton is well ranked as the first of its kind globally due to its long stable and spinning quality. Cotton seed also produces a good oil quality. Unfortunately, Cotton functions as a sink crop for phytophagous pests because of its long season and its common host for pests found on adjacent short-season crops, including soybeans and corn (Barros *et al.*, 2010). This instance pests pressure results in a large number of insecticide applications. The cultivated cotton is liable to be attacked by serious pests among which is the piercing-sucking pests. Phytophagous mite represents particular importance in our modern agriculture. Scarcely can we find an agriculture crop without mite population. *Tetranychus* spp. [*Tetranychus urticae* Koch and *Tetranychus cinnabarinus* (Boisduval) (Acari: Tetranychidae)] is one of the most severe phytophagous species and it is a significant pest in many cropping systems worldwide (Nauwen *et al.*, 2001), such as field crops, vegetables, fruits and ornamental plants (Dermauw *et al.*, 2012 and Basha *et al.*, 2021). It causes many severe injuries worldwide; such as reducing yield and yield components (Wilson *et al.*, 1991 and Wilson, 1993). The phytoseiidae mites are the vital group among the predatory mites on various crops (El-Badry, 1967 and Croft and McGroarty, 1977). The spider mite is a serious cosmopolitan pest that feeds on more than 1200 host plant species, 150 of them are economically significant (Migeon and Dorkeld, 2011; Azadi-Goort *et al.*, 2019 and Najafabadi *et al.*, 2019). *Amphyseius gossipi* (El-Badry) (Acari: Phytoseiidae) is the key predator for managing spider mites (Specht, 1968) in particular the two-spotted spider mites. It reproduces more quickly than the two-spotted spider mite, and feeds on all of their stages.

Stigmateid mites are found in several fields, forests, and cash crops they can predate on a wide variety of harmful soft bodies and slow-moving insects and mites (Wilson, 1993). The most important predators of family Stigmatidae include genera *Agistemus* that predate on spider mite (Croft, 1994) of these genera, *Agistemus exertus* (Gonazlez), *Agistemus buntex* Chaudhri, *Agistemus pallinii* Matioli are widely diverse species (Khan *et al.*, 2010 and Fouly *et al.*, 2011).

Tydeus californicus (Banks) (Acari: Tydeidae) is considered a scavenger mite (Gerson, 1968). Reports showed that some tydeid species prey on tetranychid eggs, eriophyids (Laing and Knop, 1983). Several tydeids can act as alternative prey of phytoseiids (Knop and Hoy, 1983 and Camporese and Duso, 1995) and their presence could contribute towards maintaining phytoseiid population levels when spider mite population is low.

Spider mites' control in cotton is mainly reliance on the use of chemical pesticides. These pesticides destruction of predacious mite is partially responsible for spider mites increasing population (Dittrich, 1988). As a consequence of public awareness of environmental hazards due to pesticide application, several alternative ways were developed to refine the overall integrated pest control strategy such as; host plant resistance to pests, and pest population monitoring. Biological control, evaluation economic thresholds, pesticide selectivity, minimized pesticide application rates, and application timing are commonly employ tactics (Flint and Bosch, 1981).

In the case of the cotton crop, breeders, especially in the United States of America and Egypt, have produced several cultivars and genotypes that differ in their ability to tolerate pest infestation. The property of plant resistance to insect, usually attributed to

morphological as well as biochemical factors (Amr, 1993). Several investigators have found that cotton cultivars that are tolerant pest infestation differ from susceptible ones in their content of a group of chemicals known collectively as allelochemicals (Kogan, 1986) and reduction in nutrients level (Penny *et al.*, 1967).

T. urticae developed resistance expeditiously as a consequence of short life cycle, heavy progeny and arrhenotokous parthenogenesis. Thus, it could be labeled as one of the most resistant species that its control became challenging in several parts globally (Van Leeuwen *et al.*, 2010). The development of resistance in spider mites *Tetranychus* spp. has highlighted the need for an integrated pest management strategy. Studies of spider mites predators species that can be utilized for biological control of the *T. urtica* in Egypt are inadequate (Ibrahim, 2017 and El-Erksousy *et al.*, 2016). Pest management adopts specific tactics such as; host plant susceptibility and biological control.

Therefore, the current work aimed to utilize predator mites and plant resistance tactics for integrated pest management of *Tetranychus* spp., through monitoring the population dynamics of the spider mite and their predacious mites.

Materials and methods

1. Cotton cultivars:

Two types of cotton species were selected for the study; the upland glanded species *Gossypium hirsutum*, (A medium stable) represented by Mc Nair 220 and Okra leaf cultivars and the Egyptian glanded *Gossypium barbadense*, an extra stable species demonstrated by Giza 70 one. The three cotton cultivars were obtained from the Agronomy Department, Alexandria University.

2. Field trials:

The experiment was carried out at the Experimental Station, Alexandria university at Abies, an area of about 420 m² was divided into four strips (105m²) every strip was divided into four plots each plot (21m²) was divided into four rows surrounded by non-cultivated pelt. The experiment design was Randomized Complete Blocks Design (RCBD). The experimental plot for this study was not sprayed with pesticides. The sampling of cotton leaves was started in May till the early days of November along two successive seasons. The samples were collected in the early morning at about 7 o'clock to ensure mites stability and avoid adverse climatic conditions.

3. Estimation of mite's infestation:

A sample of 10 cotton leaves was randomly collected weakly from the lower, middle and upper leaves of each plot (Petrushov and Belyaeva, 1989). Mobile stages larvae nymphs and adults were recorded weekly on ten leaves as a sub sample. Data of every four successive sub-samples were combined to make a monthly single sample. The family, genus and species levels were identified using the key developed by Krantz (1978) and Zaher (1986). Data of infestation were transformed to $\sqrt{x} + 1$ according to (Snedecor, 1961) the variance was compared using two ways ANOVA with and post hoc Student-Newman-Keuls test (Costat Statistical Software, 1990), <https://www.cohort.com>.

Results and discussion

1. Susceptibility of different cotton cultivars to phytophagous mites *Tetranychus* spp. infestation:

The infestation of *Tetranychus* spp. to the three-cotton cultivar along the two seasons is present in (Figure 1 and Table 1). According to the average number of spider mites (Mobile stages) on each cultivar, the data of first season showed that, the Egyptian cotton cultivars, Giza70 was the most tolerant

cultivar to *Tetranychus* spp. infestation among the tested cotton cultivars. While, Mc Nair 220 cultivar was sensitive to *Tetranychus* spp., infestation. The average number of spider mites showed a significant difference between the sensitive cultivars Mc Nair 220 and Okra leaf (6.42 and 6.11 individuals/10 leaves) on one hand and the tolerant cotton cultivar (Giza70, 3.78 individuals / 10 leaves on the other hand. The data along the second season exhibited the same trend, among the three cotton cultivars, Giza70 was the most tolerant cultivar to *Tetranychus* spp., whereas, the average

number of infestation (3.69 individuals/10 leaves) followed by Okra leaf (5.57 individuals/10 leaves) and finally Mac Nair220 (6.05 individuals/10 leaves). Statistically, there were significant differences between the tested Egyptian cotton cultivar and the two American cultivars which may be due to the variation between cultivars in their morphological characters (Leaf area, or glabrous leaves), allelochemical (Gossypol) and some nutrients (Wilson and Sadras 1998).

Table (1): The accounting of spider mites *Tetranychus* spp. and their associated predators on three cotton cultivars along two successive seasons.

Season	Mite	Cotton Cultivar			LSD (0.05) within row
		Mean number of mites per 10 cotton leaves* ±SE			
		Mac Nair	Okra Leaf	Giza 70	
First	Pest <i>Tetranychus</i> spp.	6.42 ± 1.91	6.11 ± 1.48	3.78 ± 1.92	0.31
	Predator <i>Amblyseius gossipi</i>	1.83 ± 0.42	1.27 ± 0.19	1.42 ± 0.25	0.13
	<i>Agistemus exertus</i>	2.01 ± 0.52	1.68 ± 0.36	1.79 ± 0.05	0.41
	<i>Tydues californicus</i>	2.83 ± 0.76	2.31 ± 0.54	2.94 ± 0.84	0.106
Second	Pest <i>Tetranychus</i> spp.	6.05 ± 2.42	5.57 ± 2.34	3.69 ± 1.52	0.15
	Predator <i>Amblyseius gossipi</i>	2.19 ± 0.47	1.48 ± 0.23	3.69 ± 1.50	0.41
	<i>Agistemus exertus</i>	1.49 ± 0.29	1.30 ± 0.17	1.47 ± 0.56	0.11
	<i>Tydues californicus</i>	2.81 ± 0.88	2.51 ± 0.74	3.63 ± 1.11	0.726

* The mean number of mites (Mobile stages) per 10 cotton leaves expressed as the square root of the obtained number plus one.

Figure (1): Susceptibility of five cotton cultivars to spider mite *Tetranychus* spp. infestation along two successive seasons.

* The mean number of mites/ 10 cotton leaves expressed as the square root of the obtained number plus one

This result was in accordance with the results published by Misra *et al.* (1992). They found that, the population density of *T. cinnabarinus* was in negative relation with the density of leaf hairs.

Miyazaki *et al.* (2017) mentioned that dense leaf hairs and high gossypol content are negatively affecting thrips. Since, thrips were significantly less abundant and caused less damage on diploid cotton genotypes from *Gossypium arboreum* L. than on the standard commercial *Gossypium hirsutum*.

Gentile *et al.* (1969) found that, the resistance of cotton cultivars *Solanum penellii* and *Lycopersicon hirsutum* to *T. cinnabarinus* and *T. urticae* was a consequence of that the mite became entangled in the sticky exudate of the glandular hairs of these species.

Harvey and Martin (1990) reported that, pubescent wheat was more susceptible than the glabrous wheat to the (Wheat crul) dry bulb mite *Eriophyes tulipae* Keifer (Acari : Eriophyidae).

Also, El-Halawany *et al.* (1990) found that, leaves of sultani fig variety were more susceptible to infestation with phytophagous *Tetranychus arabicus* Attiah (Acari: *Tetranychidae*) than the leaves of adsi variety. This might be due to differences in leaf epidermal hairs.

In contrast, several investigators mentioned that the surface hair or trichomes are the first plant organ contacted during the preliminary stages or host plant acceptance. Reed (1974) mentioned that, trichomes also existed on leaves of cotton cultivars that resist to the leafhopper *Empoasca facialis* Jacobi (Hemiptera: Cicadellidae). The current results also indicated significant differences between Mc Nair 220 (Characterized by large leaf area) and Okra leaf (Characterized by small leaf area).

Thus, the leaf area may affect the degree of *Tetranychus* spp. infestation. Gossypol in cotton cultivars had been often correlated with the resistance to insect pests (Sharma and Agarwal, 1984).

Although both cultivars Mc Nair 220 and Giza70 are contain

gossypol, Mc Nair 220 was susceptible to mite infestation while Giza 70 was more tolerant. Abdou (1995) found that, Giza70 had high contents of terpenoids and aldehydes which may explain why this cultivar is spider mite tolerance. Therefore, it could be considered that gossypol is not the sole factor affecting plant resistance to infestation by *Tetranychus* spp.

2. The existence of the associated spider mite predators on the three cotton cultivars along two successive seasons:

The data in (Table 1) showed the existence of three spider mite predators on all cotton cultivars along the two seasons. The results cleared that, the predacious mite *Amplyseius gossipi* El-Badry (Acari: Phytoseiidae) had the lowest average number of mobile stages on okra leaf cultivar (1.27 and 1.48 individuals/10 leaves), within the first and the second seasons, respectively. While, it possessed the highest density on Mac Nair cultivar (1.83 individuals/10 leaves) within the first season and on Giza 70 (3.69 individuals/10 leaves) within the second season.

As regards predatory mite *Agistemus exertus* (Gonzalez) (Acari: Phytoseiidae) the results indicated that, the lowest average number was on (1.68 and 1.30 individuals/10 leaves), within the first and the second seasons, respectively.

Likewise, the highest density was recorded on Mc Nair 220 (2.01 and 1.49) and on Okra leaf (1.68 and 1.30 individuals/10 leaves), within both seasons, respectively. The third predacious mite's data cleared that, predatory mite *Tydues californicus* (Banks) (Acari:Tydeidae), ranging between 2.31 and 2.94 individuals/10 leaves on the okra leaf and Giza 70 cultivar, respectively along with the first season.

Similarly, within the second season the mean abundant *T. californicus* numbers were 2.51 and 3.63 individuals/ 10 leaves on okra leaf and G70 cultivars, respectively. Regarding the three predatory mites' species, the largest population was for *T. californicus* followed by *A. exertus* and *A. gossipi*.

However, there were no significant differences in the abundance density between the three predator mites on all tested cotton cultivars. *T. californicus* has broader diets, feeding on various pest species and pollens (Croft *et al.*, 1998 and Gerson *et al.*, 2003).

Thus, it is considered a scavenger mite (Gerson, 1968), that can thrive by feeding on pollen, and preying on tetranychid eggs and eriophyids (Laing and Knop, 1983). This finding might explain the more significant number of *T. californicus* than *A. exertus* and *A. gossipi*. Several tydeids can act as alternative prey of phytoseiids, and their presence could contribute toward, maintaining phytoseiid population level when spider mite population is low.

The three predators mentioned before were existed all over at the same time. Thus, the combined use of these predators is considered as a control strategy. The current findings coincide with the results published by Vacacela Ajila *et al.* (2019), who stated that the combined use of Neoseius (= *Amblyseiys californicus*) and *Phytoseiulus macropilisis* considered as a control strategy. *P. macropilis* tends to disperse when the density of spider mites is low, *N. californicus* remains behind because it can feed on other food sources and it is more resistant to starvation.

The current results also agreed with Jai-Sun and Soon-Won (1985) 's findings, who stated that, *Amplyseius terminals* was the most effective

biological control agent to the two-spotted spider mite but its density was highly variable with management system from one plot to another, and from year to year.

Fonseca *et al.* (2020) mentioned that the species predator *P. macropilis* and *N. californicus* are used to control the two spotted-spider mite *T. urticae*. The two predators do not avoid plants with other species as they may coexist together with their common prey. This result matches the current study, where the three predators mentioned above existed simultaneously on the same three cotton cultivars.

A.gossypi is a crucial predator for managing spider mites which specialized on two spotted spider mites, fed on all stages of the two spotted spider mite (Specht, 1968). The predation rate of *Amplyseius chiapensis* DeLeon (Acari: Phytoseiidae) was 25.6 protonymph consumed/ leaf/ day in the presence of web by *T. urticae*, while in the absence of web it was slightly higher at 29.5 protonymph consumed/ Female/ day (Do Amaral *et al.*, 2020).

Also, Jai-Sun and Soon Won (1985) found that, *A. terminalis* was an effective biological control agent to the two-spotted spider mite, but its density was highly variable with the management system from one plot to another and from year to year. It seemed to be an effective predator for the phytophagous mite after August.

A relationship could be obtained between the infestation of cotton varieties by *T. urticae* and the presence of the predatory mite *T. californicus*. The current results displayed, that, the susceptible (Mc Nair 220) and

moderately susceptible (Okra leaf) cultivars, had the least abundant density of *T. californicus* while, the tolerant cultivar Giza70 had the highest abundant density of *T. californicus*. Thus, this predator mite may play a role as a biological control agent.

3. The population dynamics of spider mites and their predacious mite on three cotton cultivars:

This part of the research aimed to determine the adjustability of the pesticide application. The data presented in (Figures 2, 3 and 4) show *Tetranychus* spp. and its predators population dynamics on the susceptible cultivar Mac Nair 220; the moderate susceptible okra leaf and the tolerant one Giza 70 cultivars during two successive seasons.

Data of both seasons showed that, on all cultivars the spider mite started to emerge in Jun and increased gradually in numbers to reach its peak during September then starting to decline during October.

The predatory mite *A. gossypi* population size started to increase from July and reached the maximum population before the cotton harvesting. The predatory mite *A. exertus* population also increased from July and reaches their highest density during the first week of October before the cotton was harvested.

Similarly, the numbers of individuals of the predator mite *T. californicus* elevated in July and reaches the high population density in the first days of October.

Figure (2): Population dynamics of spider mites *Tetranychus spp.* and their predacious mites on MC Nair 220 cotton cultivar along two successive seasons.
 * The mean number of mites/ 10 cotton leaves expressed as the square root of the obtained number plus one.

Figure (3): Population dynamics of spider mites *Tetranychus spp.* and their predacious mites on Okra leaf cotton cultivar along two successive seasons.
 * The mean number of mites/ 10 cotton leaves expressed as the square root of the obtained number plus one.

Figure (4): Population dynamics of spider mites *Tetranychus spp.* and their predacious mites on Giza 70 cotton cultivar along two successive seasons.
 * The mean number of mites/ 10 cotton leaves expressed as the square root of the obtained number plus one.

The current results revealed that, the predacious mites were occurred on all tested cotton cultivars. In addition, the population of the predatory mites reached the maximum density before the cotton harvesting. These results agreed with the results obtained by El-Halawany and Abdel-Samad (1990), they found that the annual peak of predaceous mites appeared one month after that of the phytophagous mite *T. arabicus* resulting in a gradual decrease in the later population density. A recent study showed that the density of predators of *T. urticae* was not associated with the pest mite populations during the spring of 2015 and 2016 seasons, which is a result of the low numbers of the recorded predators in the studied area (Abo-Elmaged *et al.*, 2021). As regards of *Tetranychus* spp., the population started to increase in June and reached its peak in the second week of September then it declines till the end of September, these results agree with the results obtained by Petrushov and Belyaeva (1989), they found that the number of *T. urticae* increased intensity from the end of July till the mid-September. Margolies and Kennedy (1985) showed that, *T. urticae* on maize and groundnut outbreak coincided with the crop host's flowering and fruiting season. Shanbaky *et al.* (2016) mentioned that the population of *T. urticae* started to peak up since the fourth week of June when most of the life stages of *T. urticae* were observed on the plant leaves. They also reported that, the abundance of eggs and most movable life stages gradually increased to reach their peaks during September, the peak of *T. urticae* was followed by a decrease of the pest number at the end of the season. Apparently, the *T. urticae* population affect by temperature and humidity as, in current work, the maximum numbers of mites were recorded during the period of moderate

temperature and humidity in Alexandria. Abo-Elmaged *et al.* (2021), found that, the abundance of the two spotted spider mite, *T. urticae* on cucumber in Upper Egypt has fluctuated with a peak during the middle of May when the temperature and relative humidity was moderate.

From the previous data, we can define pesticide application time to be on the second week of September to avoid pesticide application's adverse effect on the three predators. Whereas the three predations mite density was high, and the populations density of *Tetranychus* spp. was approximately low (Abd El-Rahman and Moustafa, 2002).

References

- Abd El-Rahman, S.M. and Moustafa, F.I. (2002):** Field evaluation of some pesticides at recommended and laboratory deduced rates against the spider mite *Tetranychus* spp. and its predatory mites on cotton. The first Conf .of the Agric. Pesticide lab., 3-5 Sep., 797-504.
- Abdou, G. Y. (1995):** Identification and evaluation of certain plant products as potential tools in the control of some insect pests. M.Sc. Thesis. Fac. of Agric, Alex, University.
- Abo-Elmaged, T.M.; Ali, A.W.M.; Abdel-Rahman, M.A. and Abd-Allah, A.H. (2021):** Activity of the two spotted spider mite, *Tetranychus urticae* (Koch) (Acari) infesting cucumber plants in Upper Egypt. International Journal of Tropical Insect Science, 41(1): 463-469.
- Amr, E.M.A. (1993):** Insect infestation of different cotton varieties in Egypt, in relation to their chemical and morphological

- properties. PhD. Thesis Fac. Science, Cairo University.
- Azadi-Goort, A.; Sedaratian-Jahromi, A.; Haghani, M. and Ghane Jahromi, M. (2019):** Biological responses of *Tetranychus urticae* (Acari: Tetranychidae) to different host plants an investigation on bottom-up effects. *Systemic and Applied Acarology*, 24(4): 659-674.
- Barros, E.M.; Torres, J.B.; Ruberson, J.R. and Oliveira, M.D. (2010):** Development of *Spodoptera frugiperda* on different hosts and damage to reproductive structures in cotton. *Entomologia Experimentalis et Applicata*, 137(3):237-245.
- Basha, H.A.; Mostafa, E.M. and Eldeeb, A.M. (2021):** Mite pests and their predators on seven vegetable crops (Arachnida: Acari). *Saudi Journal of Biological Sciences*, 28(6): 3414-3417.
- Camporese, P. and Duso, C. (1995):** Life history and life table parameters of the predatory mite *Typhlodromus fahbii*. *Emt. Exp. Appl.*, 77: 149-157.
- Croft, B.A.; Moneti, L.N. and Pratt, P.D. (1998):** Comparative life history and predation types: are *Neoweius californicus* and *N. fallacis* (Acari: Phytoseiidae) similar type II selective predators of spider mites?. *Environ Entomol*, 24: 531-538. <http://doi.org/10.1093/ee/27.3.531>.
- Croft, B.A. and McGroarty, D.L. (1977):** Role of *Amblyseius fallacis* (Acarina: Phytoseiidae) in Michigan apple orchards, publisher: Michigan State University, Agricultural Experiment.
- Croft, B.A. (1994):** Biological control of apple mites by a phytoseiid mite complex and *Zetzellia mali* (Acari: Stigmaeidae): long-term effects and impact of azinphosmethyl on colonization by *Amblyseius andersoni* (Acari: Phytoseiidae). *Environmental Entomology*, 23(5):1317-1325.
- Dermauw, P. O.; Sbrde Cmerd, D. and Nevri Xerde, E. F. (2012):** Demography and population projection of *Aphis fabae* (Hemiptera: Aphididae): with additional comments on life table research criteria. *J. Econ. Entomol.*, 108(4): 1466-1478.
- Dittrich, V. (1988):** Resistance and hormilgosis as a driving force behind pest outbreak. *Rev. of Appli. Entomol.*, 76(3): 193.
- Do Amaral, F.S.; Cavalcante, A.C. and Lofego, A.C. (2020):** *Amblyseius chiapensis* (Acari: Phytoseiidae) as natural enemy of *Tetranychus urticae* (Acari: Tetranychidae). *Systematic and Applied Acarology*, 25(2): 173-177.
- El-Badry, E.A. (1967):** Five new phytoseiid mites from the U.A.R. with collection notes on three other species (Acari: Phytoseiidae). *Indian J. Ent.*, 29(20): 177-184.
- El-Erksousy, M. H.; Helmy, N.; Abozaed, A. A.; Shanbaky, N. and Ibraheem, M. H. (2016):** Predatory spiders associated with the two spotted spider mite *Tetranychus urticae* on two field crops in Qalubya Governorate, Egypt. *Egyptian Academic Journal of Biological Sciences. A, Entomology*, 9(4): 71-81.
- El-Halawany, M.E. and Abdel-Samad, M.A. (1990):** Population dynamics of the

- spider mite *Tetranychus arabicus* Attiah and its predatory mite *Phytoseius finitimus* Ribaga in a fig orchard. Agricultural Research Review, 68(1):25-29.
- El-Halawany, M.E.; Ibrahim, G.A. and Abdel-Samad, M.A. (1990):** Susceptibility of Sultani and Adsi fig varieties to infestation with *Eriophyes ficus* Cotté and *Tetranychus arabicus* Attiah. Agricultural Research Review, 68(1):31-37.
- Flint, M. L. and Bosch, R. V. D. (1981):** Introduction to integrated pest management. Plenum. Press New York and London: p. 240 .
- Fonseca, M.M.; Pallini, A.; Marques, P.H.; Lima, E. and Janssen, A. (2020):** Compatibility of two predator species for biological control of the two-spotted spider mite. Experimental and Applied Acarology, 80(3): 409-422.
- Fouly, A.H.; Al-Deghairi, M.A. and Abdel Baky, N.F. (2011):** Biological aspects and life tables of *Typhlodromips swirskii* (Acari: Phytoseiidae) fed *Bemisia tabaci* (Hemiptera: Aleyroididae). Journal of Entomology, 8:52–62.
- Gentile, A.G.; Webb, R.E. and Stoner, A.K. (1969):** *Lycopersicon* and *Solanum* spp. resistant to carmine and two spotted spider mite. J. Econ. Entomol., 62:834-836.
- Gerson, U.; Smiley, R.L. and Ochoa, R. (2003):** Mites (Acari) for pest control, London Publishing House, p.540.
- Gerson, U. (1968):** Five Tydeid mites from Israel (Acarima: prosligmata). Israel J. Zool., 17: 191-198.
- Harvey, T.L. and Martin, T.S. (1990):** Effect of wheat bubescence on infestation of wheat curl mite and incidence of wheat streak mosaic. J. Econ. Entomol., 37: 225-227.
- Ibrahim, M. (2017):** Population density of piercing-sucking pests and their associated natural enemies on pepper, *Capsicum annuum* L. plants under greenhouse condition at Ismailia Governorate, Egypt. Journal of Plant Protection and Pathology, 8(9): 451-458.
- Jai-Sun, Hyum and Soon-Won ,Lee (1985):** Studies on the population dynamics of Apple mites and their predacious mites in Apple orchards. Agri. Res. of Sool. Nat, Univ., 10(1): 35-44.
- Khan, B.S.; Bashir, M.H.; Farooq, M. and Khan, N.A. (2010):** A new predatory mite species of the genus *Agistemus* (Stigmaeidae: Acari) from Punjab, Pakistan. Pakistan Entomologist, 32(1):24-28.
- Knop, N. F. and Hoy, M. A. (1983):** Biology Tyeid mites, *Homeopromatus anconeii* (n. comb) Acari: Tydeidae, important in San Joaquin Valley vineyards. Hilgardia, 51(5): 1-30.
- Kogan, M. (1986):** Natural chemicals in plant resistance to insects. Iowa State Journal Research, 60, pp.501-527.
- Krantz, G.W. (1978):** A Manual of Acarology. Oregon State University Book Stores. Inc. Corvallis, 509.
- Laing, J. E. and Knop, N. F. (1983):** Potential use of predacious mites other than phytoseiidae for biological control of orchard pests. In: M.A. hoy, G.L. Cunningham and L. Knutson (eds), Biological control of pests by mites. Publ. univ. calif.,

- Berkeley, California, N. 94720. pp.28-32.
- Margolies, D.C. and Kennedy, G.G. (1985):** Population response of two-spotted spider mite *Tetranychus urticae*, to host phenology in corn and peanut. J. Econ. Entomol., 78(1): 117-120.
- Migeon, A. and Dorkeld, F. (2011):** Spider mites web: a comprehensive database for the Tetranychidae. Available from <http://www.montpellier.inra.fr/CBGP/spmweb> (last accessed the twelfth of January 2019).
- Misra, K. K.; Sarkar, P.K. ; Dos, T.K.; and Smochoudhury, A.K. (1992):** Incidence of *Tetranychus cinnabarinus* Boish (Acari: Tetranychidae) on some selected accessions of brinjal with special reference to the physical basis of resistance. Indian Agriculturist, 34(3): 177-185.
- Miyazaki, J.; Stiller, W.N. and Wilson, L.J. (2017):** Sources of plant resistance to thrips: a potential core component in cotton IPM. Entomologia Experimentalis et Applicata, 162(1):30-40.
- Najafabadi, S. S. M.; Bagheri, A. and Seyahooei, M. A. (2019):** Cucumber cultivar responses to tetranychid mites two-spotted spider mite and strawberry spider mite in greenhouse. Systematic & Applied Acarology, 24(8):1383-1393.
- Nauwen, Q. K. ; Jmyn Wani, V. and Heni Umfd, F. S. (2001):** Life history parameters of *Phytoseius plumifer* (Acari: Phytoseiidae) fed on corn pollen. Acarologia, 53(2): 127-131.
- Penny, L.H.; Scott, G. E. and Dwhrie, W. D. (1967):** Recurrent selection for European corn borer resistance in maize crop. Sci., 7: 407-409.
- Petrushov, A.Z. and Belyaeva, A.V. (1989):** Regularities of distribution of the spider mite. Soviet Agric. Sci., 12: 28-31.
- Reed, W. (1974):** Selection of cotton varieties for resistance to insect. Uganda cotton Grow Review, 51: 106-123.
- Shanbaky, N.M.; Helmy, N.; El-Erksousy, M.H. and Ibraheem, M.H. (2016):** Seasonal dynamics of the two spotted red spider mite, *Tetranychus urticae* Koch on two field crops in Qalubya Governorate, Egypt. Egyptian Academic Journal of Biological Sciences. A, Entomology, 9(1):15-24.
- Sharma, H.C. and Agarwal, R.A. (1984):** Factors importing resistance to stem damage by *Earias vittella* (Lepidoptera: Nuctuidae), in some cotton phenotypes. Protection Ecology, 6: 35-42.
- Snedecor, G.W. (1961):** Statistical methods Now. State College, Ames, U.S.A, pp.1534 .
- Specht, H. B. (1968):** Phytoseiidae (Acarina: Mesostimates) in New Jersey apple orchard environment with descriptions of spermathecae and three new species. Canadian Entomologist ,100: 673-692.
- Vacacela Ajila, H.E.; Colares, F.; Lemos, F.; Marques, P.H.; Franklin, E.C.; Santos do Vale, W.; Oliveira, E.E.; Venzon, M. and Pallini, A. (2019):** Supplementary food for *Neoseiulus californicus* boosts biological control of *Tetranychus urticae* on strawberry. Pest Management Science, 75(7):1986-1992.

- Van Leeuwen, T.; Vontas, J.; Tsagkarakou, A.; Dermauw, W. and Tirry, L. (2010):** Acaricide resistance mechanisms in the two-spotted spider mite *Tetranychus urticae* and other important Acari: A review. Insect biochemistry and molecular biology, 40(8): 563-572.
- Wilson, L.J. (1993):** Spider mites (Acari: Tetranychidae) affect yield and fiber quality of cotton. Journal of Economic Entomology, 86(2):566-585.
- Wilson, L.J. and Sadras, V.O. (1998):** Host plant resistance in cotton to spider mites, in The 10th International Congress of Acarology, ed. by RA Norton and MJ Colloff. CSIRO Publishing, Canberra, pp. 314– 327 .
- Wilson, L.T.; Trichilo, P.J. and Gonzalez, D. (1991):** Spider mite (Acari: Tetranychidae) infestation rate and initiation: effect on cotton yield. Journal of economic entomology, 84(2): 593-600.
- Zaher, M. A. (1986):** Survey and ecological studies on phytophagous, predaceous and soil mites in Egypt, Cairo, Faculty of Agric. Cairo University.

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Efficiency of varied formulations of zinc phosphide (1%) against *Rattus norvegicus* (Rodentia: Muridae) under laboratory and field conditions

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Abstract:

Laboratory and field studies were carried out to show efficiency of varied formulations of zinc phosphide (1%) against *Rattus norvegicus* (Berkenhout) (Rodentia: Muridae). The gained data cleared that the average of daily bait consumption of zinc phosphide and malathion as tracking powder by males of the Norway rat was 4.0 gram and 3.2 gram for females. The data cleared also the same concentration gave 80% kill for males and complete kill of females with average 1.7 day to death for both sexes. The mortality because of 1% zinc phosphide mixed with malathion 1% gave 90% kill of *R. norvegicus* for both sexes. The obtained data cleared that the palatability of zinc phosphide formulations was (17.2% and 19.0%), (18.1% and 17.5%) and (12.0% and 20.3%) for cake, crushed maize and wax block for Norway rat males and female respectively. There were 49 active burrows of *R. norvegicus* were chosen, divided into 12 burrows were treated with cake, 12 treated with crushed maize, 16 treated with tracking powder and 10 treated with wax block, the number reopened burrows were 2, 4, 4 and 4 for the mentioned formulations, respectively. The data showed that zinc phosphide cake was the more effective (83%), and then tracking powder (75%), crushed maize, (66.7%) and the lowest effect was the wax block (50%) on the numbers of *R. norvegicus*. Applied zinc phosphide formulations plus snap traps gave a high control against Norway rats.

Introduction

Until the late 1940s the acute toxicants were the only rodenticides available. They are still widely used today, and users preferred by many users despite their relatively low efficacy. Rodents that succumb to acute toxicants do so quickly, within a few hours usually and having consumed only a small amount of bait. Most uneducated users, incorrectly, interpret the sight of dead rodents soon after placing small amounts of baits, with only low labour inputs, as a proof of cheap and effective control. The effect of zinc phosphide against different species of rodents was studied by several

investigators (Bradfield and Gill, 1984; Abdallah *et al.*, 1991 and Asran, 2001).

Formulation research must be directed to distinguish as far as possible between different mechanisms of availability and activity. If the toxicant is applied directly to the target rodents, it may be possible to reduce its activity and at the same time retard for reduce its loss. As a matter of fact, the modification of the activity by formulation is essentially a matter of altering its availability to the pest. Since the problems of rodents in Egypt are seriously increasing in both agricultural and public health aspects research must be directed to reach a quick and effective way of control.

An attempt is made in this study to formulate baits in the form of zinc phosphide, using local raw materials wherever it is possible, that could be considered as successful methods to ensure the activity of the toxicant.

Materials and methods

1. Tested chemicals materials:

The used Zinc phosphide was brought from Abou Zaalpal Company it has 94% active ingredient. Meanwhile the Malathion powder 1% was provided by Kafer El-Zayat company. The other materials were brought from the market such as, crushed maize ,wheat flour , cotton seed oil and paraffin wax.

2. Tested formulations:

2.1. Zinc phosphide cake (48.5 crushed maize +48.5 flour +2 oil cotton seeds+ 1% zinc phosphide). **2.2.** Zinc phosphide crushed maize as bait (1% zinc phosphide +crushed maize). **2.3.** 1% Zinc phosphide + malathion 1% as tracking powder. **2.4.** Zinc phosphide wax block.

3. Tested animals:

The experimental animals Norway rat, *R. norvegicus* were brought from different fields in Ismailia district, Ismailia Governorate .Rats were individually reared acclimatized under laboratory conditions .Active and healthy rats of both sexes were chosen for each formulation 10 (5 males and 5 females). The rats were weighed to the nearest gram and sex determined. Animals were retained in individual cages, 42, 24, 17 cm small animals or obviously pregnant individuals were omitted from the experiment.

4. The procedure:

For bait tow feeding system were carried to determine the efficiency against the Norway rat, free and obliged feeding test. The choice feeding test was described by Htun and Brooks (1979), two cups were to individually caged animals, and one contains plain bait wheat and the other poison bait. Fifty grams of treated and untreated food was provided daily, for non choice feeding test introduce 50 gram from poisoned bait only (One cup). The bait consumption was calculated to the nearest .01 gram daily .The consumed bait were computed to the body weight of the tested rat. The third group (Control), 5 males and 5 females were caged singly with plain bait

and enough water for the whole period of the experimental. Mortality and the mean death length in day were observed and recorded for 2 weeks. Also, in the case of free choice test the palatability percentages was calculated according to the following equation:

$$\% \text{ Palatability} = \frac{\text{Consumed weight of poison bait}}{\text{Consumed weight of poison bait} + \text{Consumed weight of plain bait}} \times 100$$

Water was available to the tested rat through the experiments. Mortality was observed daily and recorded for three weeks after poisoning. The mean death length in days was calculated. In non choice test, bait consumption was recorded daily and weighed to the nearest 0.01 gram. Another group of 5 rats, 5 mice and 5 meriones of both sexes were caged singly with unpoisoned bait and enough water for the whole period of the experiments.

5. Tracking powder:

Rodents, *R. norvegicus*, *Mus musculus* and *Meriones shawi* placed individually in cages at least 24 hrs before the treatment. The test commenced when the trays of tracking powder (1% zinc phosphide +1% malathion) were placed in the tunnels. Ten mature animals (5 males and 5 females) were used forced to touch tracking powder for 4 days .The consumed powder by each animal was estimated daily. Survived animals were observed for an additional 10 days, mortality percentages and day to death calculated for each treatment.

6. Field trials:

Two traditional areas were chosen at Nafisha village at Ismailia district (Found active burrows of *R. norvegicus*) to apply zinc phosphide formulations, cake, crushed maize, tracking powder and wax block. Twenty traps per one Fadden were put beside every formula of zinc phosphide to calculate the total efficiency for both zinc phosphide formula plus traps. There were 49 active burrows of *R. norvegicus* were chosen, divided into 12 burrows were treated with cake ,12 treated with crushed maize, 16 treated with tracking powder and 10 treated with wax block.

The efficiency calculated as follow:

$$\frac{\text{Closed burrows after treatment}}{\text{Total active burrows before treatment}} \times 100$$

Results and discussion

1. Laboratory trials:

The recorded data in Table (1) showed that the effect of certain concentration of 1% zinc phosphide and malathion 1% as a tracking powder against of *R. norvegicus*. The data cleared that the average of daily bait consumption of zinc phosphide and malathion tracking powder by males of the Norway rat was 4.0 gram and 3.2gram for females. The data cleared also the same concentration gave 80% kill for males and complete kill of females with average 1.7 day to death for both sexes. The compiled results in Table (2) showed that the applied zinc phosphide formulations, crushed maize, wax block, and cake (1% concentration) under two feeding systems, choice and non-choice test against the investigated rodents. The data cleared that *R. norvegicus* males and females consumed in average 3.25 gram, 3.9 gram, 1.9 gram. Under choice test, and 4.24, 4.5 and 2.3 gram under non choice test for the applied formulations cake, crushed maize and wax block respectively (Table 3). The applied, crushed maize gave (100% and 100%) kill and wax block (80% and 80%) kill for both males and females of Norway rat under non choice and choice feeding test. The average time to death was (3.12 day and 2.55 day), (2.5 day and 1.5 day) and (4.12 day and 2.9 day) for cake, crushed maize and wax block against males and females of Norway rat for free and obliged feeding system. The obtained data cleared that the palatability of zinc phosphide formulations was (17.2% and 19.0%), (18.1% and 17.5%) and (12.0% and 20.3%) for cake, crushed maize and wax block for Norway rat males and female respectively. Samol (1972) found that cracked corn was better accepted than a pellet formulation. Asran (1994) found that in his toxicity studies to zinc phosphide (Zn₃P₂) on some Egyptian rodents in both choice and non choice tested animals could be arranged in descending order according to their susceptibility to zinc phosphide at 1% concentration as follows; *M. musculus*

> *A. niloticus* > *R. rattus* > *R. norvegicus*. Abd El-Razek (1997) found that the whole used concentrations of zinc phosphide gave entirely kill for each of male and female of the climb rat for either choice or no-choice feeding test.

2. Field trials:

The recorded data at Table (4) cleared that the applications of the zinc phosphide formulations, cake, crushed maize, tracking powder and wax block at the field inside the burrows of *R. norvegicus* and their efficiency comparing with traps efficiency. There were 49 active burrows of *R. norvegicus* were chosen, divided into 12 burrows were treated with cake, 12 treated with crushed maize, 16 treated with tracking powder and 10 treated with wax block, the number reopened burrow were 2, 4, 4 and 4 for the mentioned formulations respectively. The data showed that zinc phosphide cake was the more effect (83%), and then tracking powder (75%), crushed maize, (66.7%) and the lowest effect was the wax block on the numbers of *R. norvegicus*. The compiled data at Table (4) showed that the efficiency of the snap traps which put after phosphide zinc formulations treatment. It gave 75% efficiency after wax block treatment. Also, the results cleared that the efficiency of traps were 70%, 65% and 65% after zinc phosphide cake, crushed maize and tracking powder treatments. Generally, applied zinc phosphide formulations plus snap traps gave a high control against Norway rats. Ocampo and Lontoc (2006) found that all the rodenticides treated plots had significantly lower rat damage compared with the untreated. There was significant reduction in rat activities based on tracking of feeding census. Khan (2007) found that after 5 applications of the bait, the rodent activity decreased by 90-96%, except for zinc phosphide treatment the rodent activity decreased by 76.04%.

Table (1): Effect of 1% zinc phosphide concentration and malathion 1% as tracking powder on certain rodents under laboratory conditions.

Rodents	Sex	Av. weight		Weight reduction%	Av. Cons. of powder day/individual (gram)			Av. Cons. of powder in gram /Kg. of body eight			Mortality %		Day to death		
		Before	After		Min	Max.	Mean	Min.	Max.	Mean	Min.	Max.	Mean.		
<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	Males	275	246	10.5	1.9	6.1	4.0	13.4	16.4	15.1	80	1.0	2.0	1.5	
	Females	209	194.6	7.0	2.5	3.9	3.2	8.8	24.3	14.8	100	2.0	2.0	2.0	
	Average	242	220.3	8.7	2.2	5.0	3.6	11.1	20.3	14.9	90	1.5	2.0	1.7	
Control	Males	215	215.3	-	2.6	3.9	3.25	-	-	-	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	
	Females	134	134.5	-	3.8	6.5	5.15	-	-	-	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	
Average		174.5	174.9	-	3.2	5.2	4.2	-	-	-	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	

Table (2): Efficiency of certain zinc phosphide formulations (1% concentration) against *Rattus norvegicus* under laboratory conditions (Choice test).

Zinc ph. Form.	Sex	Weight		Weight fluctuation%	Av. cons. of poison bait	Av. cons. of plain bait	Av. cons. of poison bait gr /k gr b w	- Av. cons. of plain bait gr /k gr b w	Palatability%	Mortality%	Time to death		
		Before	after								Min.	Max.	Mean
Cack	Males	214.0	209.3	2.19	3.5	16.8	16.3	78.5	17.2	80	2.0	4.5	3.25
	Females	250.4	240.8	3.8	3.0	12.8	12.0	47.9	19.0	80	2.5	3.5	3.0
	Average	232.2	225.1	3.05	3.25	14.8	14.2	63.2	18.0	80	2.25	4.0	3.12
Crushed maize	Males	300.4	290.5	3.3	4.1	18.5	11.0	61.6	18.1	100	1.5	3.5	2.5
	Females	231.5	221.4	4.4	3.8	17.9	16.4	77.3	17.5	80	1.0	4.0	2.5
	Average	265.9	255.9	3.8	3.9	18.2	13.7	69.5	17.7	90	1.25	3.8	2.5
Wax block	Males	221.8	217.6	2.9	1.5	11.0	6.8	49.6	12.0	80	3.0	5.0	4.0
	Females	207.5	200.4	3.4	2.3	9.0	11.1	43.4	20.3	80	2.5	6.0	4.25
	Average	214.7	209.0	2.6	1.9	10.0	9.0	46.5	15.9	80	2.8	5.5	4.12

Table(3) : Efficiency of certain zinc phosphide formulations (1% concentration) against *Rattus norvegicus* under laboratory conditions (Non choice test).

Zinc ph. Form.	Sex	Weight		Av. cons. of poison bait	Weight fluctuation %	Av. cons. of poison bait gr /k gr b w	Mortality %		Time to death	
		Before	after				Min.	Max.	Mean	
Cack	Males	140.8	134.3	7.5	4.6	53.3	100	1.5	3.0	2.25
	Females	135.0	129.8	6.2	3.9	40.5	80	2.1	3.0	2.55
	Average	137.9	132.05	6.8	4.24	49.3	90	1.8	3.0	2.5
Crushed maize	Males	179.9	173.5	11.2	3.55	62.2	100	1	2	1.5
	Females	199.0	188.4	10.1	5.32	50.7	100	1	2	1.5
	Average	189.4	180.9	10.6	4.5	55.9	100	1	2	1.5
Wax block	Males	223.0	217.6	4.5	2.4	20.2	80	1.5	3.5	2.5
	Females	207.5	203.0	5.2	2.2	20.2	80	2.5	4.0	3.25
	Average	215.2	210.3	4.8	2.3	22.3	80	2.0	3.75	2.9

Table (4) : Efficiency of different formulations of 1% zinc phosphide and traps against certain field rodents in Ismailia Governorate.

Species	Zn. Ph. formulation	Burrows technique		Efficiency% (A)	Total No. of pre applied trap/fed.	Traps		Efficiency% (B)
		No. of active burrows	No of reopened burrow			Av. No. of entrapped rodents/3nights		
<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	Cack	12	2	83	20	14		70
	Crushed maize	12	4	66.7		13		65
	Tracking powder	16	4	75		13		65
	Wax block	9	5	50		15		75

Tracking powder = mixture from 1% Zn ph.+ 1% malathion

References

- Abd El-Razek, E. (1997):** Some ecological and toxicological studies on certain Egyptian rodents, Master of Science in Agricultural (Zoology). Faculty of Agriculture, Al-Azhar University.
- Abdallah, M. D.; Kandil, M. A.; El-Deep, H. I. and Gaber, W. M. (1991):** Laboratory and field studies with zinc phosphide on different rodent species for the Arab Conference of Plant Protection, Cairo Dec., pp. 494-500.
- Asran, A. A. (1994):** Susceptibility and palatability of some Egyptian rodents to zinc phosphide, Agricultural Research Review. Egypt. J. Agric. Res., 72 (1): 141-146.
- Asran, A. A. (2001):** Effect of zinc phosphide and malathion 1% mixture as a tracking powder on some rodents under laboratory conditions. Fayoum J. Agric. Res. and Dev. Vol.15, No. 1, January 2001.
- Bradfield, A.A.G. and Gill, J. E. (1984):** Laboratory trials of five rodenticides for the control of *Mescocricetus auratus* water house. J. Hyg., 93 (2): 398-394.
- Htun, P. and Brooks, J. E. (1979):** Laboratory evaluation of zinc phosphide as rodenticides against *Bandicota bengalensis*. Pans, 25 (3): 246-250.
- Khan, A. A. (2007):** Comparative evaluation of two anticoagulant and two acute rodenticides in sugar cane fields, Sarhad. Journal of Agriculture, 23 (3): 713- 718.
- Ocampo, P. P. and Lontoc, B. M. (2006):** On form pulsed baiting with coumatetralyl for the control of rice field rats. Philippine- Entomologist, 20 (1): 81- 93.
- Samol, H. H. (1972):** Rat damage to sugarcane in Florida. Proc. Int. Soc. Sugar Cane Technol., 14:575- 580.
- Wahab, A. E. S. K.; Asran, A. A. and Keshta, T. M. (1997):** Laboratory trials on effect of the different concentrations of zinc phosphide on the wild and albino house mouse, *Mus musculus* L.. Al -Azhar J. Agric. Res., 25: 261-268.

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- Negotiation research spans many disciplines (Abd-Rabou, 1996).
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Abd-Rabou, S. (1998): The efficacy of indigenous parasitoids in the biological control of *Siphoninus phillyreae* (Homoptera: Aleyrodidae) on pomegranate in Egypt. Pan-Pacific Entomologists, 74 (3): 169-173.

Evans and Abd-Rabou (2005): Two new species and additional records of Egyptian Aphelinidae. Zootaxa, 833:1-7.

Simmons, A. and Abd-Rabou, S. (2006): Whitefly populations in vegetables crops with different fertilizers. 52nd Annual meeting of the South Carolina Entomological Society, Mc Cormick, Sc., October 19-20.

Abd-Rabou, S. and Simmons, A. M. (2012): *Bemisia tabaci* (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) whitefly as a pest in Egypt. Advances In Agricultural Research In Egypt, 10 (1): 1-82.

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